

**Embedding a Culture of
'Internationalisation at Home (IaH)'
Preparing for the Changing Context of
Higher Education in Ireland**

**SE
TU**

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Teicneolaíochta
an Oirdheiscirt

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Technological
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by

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Declaration

I hereby certify that this thesis, which I submit for the award of Doctor of Philosophy, is entirely my own work and has not been taken from the work of others, save to the extent where such work has been cited and acknowledged within the text of my work.

This thesis has been prepared in accordance with the research degree regulations of South East Technological University and has not been submitted, in whole or in part, for any other award at this or any other institution.

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List of Abbreviations

AM	Academic Manager
AS	Academic Staff
BERA	British Educational Research Association
BIPs	Blended Intensive Programmes
BP HEIs	Best Practice Higher Education Institutions
CIF	Communities Integration Fund
CLIL	Content and Language Integrated Learning
COIL	Collaborative Online International Learning
CPD	Continuous Professional Development
CPR	Content, Positioning and Reflection
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
DFHERIS	Department of Further and Higher Education, Research, Innovation and Science
DES	Department of Education and Skills
DoES	Department of Education and Skills
EDI	Equality, Diversity and Inclusion
EAIE	European Association for International Education
ECF	Employment Control Framework
EEA	European Education Area

EHEA	European Higher Education Area
EQUiP	Educational Quality at Universities for Inclusive International Programmes
EUA	European University Alliances
EUI	European Universities Initiative
FG	Focus Groups
GCE	Global Citizenship Education
GEO	Global Engagement Office
GFC	Global Financial Crisis
HE	Higher Education
HEA	Higher Education Authority
HEI	Higher Education Institutions
IAU	International Association of Universities
IaH	Internationalisation at Home
IaH CPR	Internationalisation at Home Content, Positioning and Reflection
IAIE	Irish Association for International Education
ICT	Information Communications Technology
IHES	Internationalisation of Higher Education for Society
IO	International Officer
IoC	Internationalisation of the Curriculum
IoCaH	Internationalising the Curricula at Home

IoHE	Internationalisation of Higher Education
IoTs	Institutes of Technology
IUA	Irish Universities Association
JD-R	Job Demands-Resources
MAW	Mitchell, Agle, and Wood
MES	Minister of Education and Skills
MOOCs	Massive Open Online Courses
NAFSA	North American Association of Foreign Service Administrators
NIF	National Integration Fund
NIRF	National Forum on Research Integrity
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PI	Policy Influencer
PM	Policymaker
QDA	Qualitative Data Analysis
QQI	Quality and Qualifications Ireland
QS	Quacquarelli Symonds
REC	Research Ethics Committees
RTA	Reflexive Thematic Analysis
SATLE	Strategic Alignment of Teaching and Learning Enhancement
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals

SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SM	Senior Manager
SSI	Semi-Structured Interviews
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics
T&L	Teaching and Learning
THEA	Technological Higher Education Association
THE	Times Higher Education
THIAH	The Hague Internationalisation at Home
TRIP	Training and Realising Innovations in Internationalisation at Home Pedagogies
TUD	Technological University Dublin
TUI	Teachers' Union of Ireland
TUs	Technological Universities
TUS	Technological University of the Shannon
UDL	Universal Design for Learning
UK	United Kingdom
UL	University of Limerick
UN	United Nations
VE	Virtual Exchange
VP	Vice President

List of Publicly Funded Irish Higher Education Institutions

ATU	Atlantic Technological University
DCU	Dublin City University
DkIT	Dundalk Institute of Technology
IADT	Dun Laoghaire Institute of Art, Design and Technology
MU	Maynooth University
MTU	Munster Technological University
SETU	South East Technological University
TCD	Trinity College Dublin
TUD	Technological University Dublin
TUS	Technological University of the Shannon: Midlands Midwest
UCC	University College Cork
UCD	University College Dublin
UG	University of Galway
UL	University of Limerick

Dedication

I first offer my sincere gratitude to *God* and the *Universe* for holding me through the unknown, for lighting the way when the path was unclear, opening doors to unexpected opportunities, sending answers in moments of doubt, aligning me with the right people, and anchoring me to my divine purpose. Living in a foreign country, away from my family, there were many moments when it felt dark and overwhelming. In those times of solitude and uncertainty, I was sustained not solely by my own strength but by a force far greater than myself. That strength and divine embrace gave me the courage to carry on. This journey has been more than academic; it has been a spiritual awakening, for which I am eternally grateful.

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Abstract

Title

Embedding a Culture of 'Internationalisation at Home (IaH)' Preparing for the Changing Context of Higher Education in Ireland

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In Irish higher education, only about 4% of learners (students) have historically participated in international mobility experiences like exchanges and Erasmus programs (HEA, 2023). This has created an imbalance, as most learners miss such opportunities. Internationalisation at Home (IaH) seeks to equip all learners with multicultural competencies by providing international and intercultural learning within their home institutions (Beelen and Jones, 2015).

Acknowledgement of IaH's role in promoting 'Global Citizenship' is growing, as seen in the international talent and innovation Strategy, 'Global Citizens 2030' (DFHERIS, 2024). While IaH is recognised as important, the focus has primarily been on increasing revenue through recruitment and learner mobility abroad. Despite its inclusion in strategic plans for many Irish HEIs, IaH remains understudied.

This study conceptualises IaH as a system, identifying opportunities and challenges in cultivating a culture of IaH and providing strategies for embedding such a culture in Irish HEIs. Utilising descriptive qualitative methods grounded in constructivism and interpretivism within a relativist metatheoretical framework, the research reveals that IaH is still developing in many institutions, with traditional universities showing more advanced approaches than technological universities (TUs). There is a shared acknowledgement that internationalisation efforts may not be sufficiently incentivised within Irish HEIs, and the need for a systemic approach was impressed upon if a culture of IaH needs to be cultivated.

This study's theoretical contribution is grounded in applying distinctive theories that can offer a holistic perspective on IaH, embedding it into institutional values, culture, curriculum and campus life through organisational design, curriculum design, and change management theories. Practical contributions involve proposing a working definition and introducing the IaH CPR (Content, Positioning, Reflection) framework to assist Irish HEIs in embedding a culture of IaH. The study also offers progress markers, incentives, and recognition mechanisms for effective implementation.

Ultimately, this research aims to enhance awareness of IaH's potential, nurturing a globally-minded and culturally diverse learning environment in Irish HEIs. It seeks to influence both institutional strategies and national policies on internationalisation, contributing to a more open society as graduates gain intercultural competencies for responsible global citizenship.

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Opening Vignette

In the context of increasingly polarised societies, rising nationalist sentiments, and the challenges posed by climate change and public health crises like COVID-19, this study emphasises the need for nurturing intercultural competence and global citizenship in Irish higher education institutions (HEIs) through 'Internationalisation at Home (IaH).' This study on *'Embedding a culture of internationalisation at home (IaH) in Irish HEIs, preparing for the changing context of higher education in Ireland'* can be seen as an investment in a future characterised by inclusion, peace, justice, and opportunity, as the realities unfolding worldwide are not disconnected from Ireland, which continues to focus on enhancing its reputation as a welcoming nation for international learners, talent, and innovation. As one staff member from a best practice HEI in Europe in this study aptly states, *'We can't opt out... Internationalisation is an inevitable part of our lives.'*

In response to the dynamic challenges surrounding internationalisation in higher education (HE), this study focuses on 'Internationalisation at Home (IaH),' which seeks to provide intercultural and international exposure to learners within domestic learning environments through the curriculum (Beelen and Jones, 2015). The study explores how IaH is interpreted and implemented in Irish higher education institutions (HEIs), examining the opportunities and challenges it presents. Additionally, it aims to offer a guiding framework for embedding a culture of IaH in Irish HEIs, ultimately striving to cultivate intercultural competence and global citizenship among learners and staff. This preparation can enable them to thrive in today's multicultural societies and workplaces while addressing shared local and global challenges.

1.2 Justification for the Study

At the national level, there is a notable lack of research focusing on IaH in Irish HE. As awareness and significance of IaH grow within Irish HEIs, this study seeks to contribute to a knowledge base on IaH by conceptualising 'IaH as a system', proposing strategies that can embed a culture of IaH and create an internationalised learning experience for all learners and staff within the institution, ultimately fostering global citizenship. Furthermore, this study offers an opportunity to engage with some of the assertions presented in the

government's international talent and innovation strategy, Global Citizens 2030 (DFHERIS, 2024), which highlights that

“In line with European trends, European universities have a key role to play in providing internationalisation-at-home experiences and in developing language and international competencies of graduates... In a global environment facing many migration and humanitarian crises, developing our understanding of, and empathy for, global challenges can significantly contribute to social cohesion... Global Citizens 2030 will develop the competencies of Irish-educated learners, researchers and innovators to work in multi-national, multi-cultural and diverse workforces, at home and abroad.”
(Global Citizens 2030, DFHERIS, 2024, p.5)

The national strategy acknowledges the importance of IaH in developing language and intercultural competencies in students, described as 'learners' or 'graduates' throughout the document. However, it also recognises that *'more attention is also needed on internationalisation-at-home opportunities for learners who cannot travel'* (p.18). Importantly, explicitly including IaH as important in the national strategy is a welcome step, contrasting with past iterations. However, the emphasis on IaH is not directly linked with any policy support, and the obscurity around its implementation can pose further challenges. The present study, therefore, aims to bridge this gap through strategies, a working definition and the IaH content, positioning and reflection (IaH CPR) framework that can be useful for Irish HEIs when attempting to embed a culture of IaH in their institutions.

Furthermore, this study engages critically with the government's stance on IaH, which asserts that *'we (DFHERIS) will work closely with Irish HEIs to support the development of innovative internationalisation-at-home experiences for learners that cannot undertake physical travel. We will develop our evidence base to analyse participation patterns across institutions, programmes and learner profiles to identify areas which need particular attention'* (p.20).

In addition to the national strategy, the European Association for International Education (EAIE) also published a spin-off report on Irish HE based on its European Barometer Survey (2024). This provides a snapshot of internationalisation in Irish HE through the responses of forty-eight participants. The participant profile comprised directors and heads of international offices, international officers, and academic staff, mainly from publicly funded institutions in Ireland, which is also the participant group for my study. *Figure 1* below presents one of the key findings from the survey that supports the argument of relevance for this research.

Figure 1: Pressing topics in Internationalisation of Irish HE for the Next 3-5 years (EAIE Barometer Ireland Spin-Off, 2024, p. 28)

Figure 1 above highlights 'strengthening international/intercultural content of the curriculum' (85%) and 'virtual internationalisation activities' (74%), implying IaH as two of the top three topics that may need to be the foci for the next three to five years to achieve the internationalisation goals within Irish HEIs. This finding aligns with the European and global outcomes when understanding the perception and need for IaH, which is elucidated in Chapter 2.

Moreover, at the institutional level, IaH is explicit or alluded to in most of the institutional strategic plans for publicly funded Irish HEIs. When this research began, there was a dearth of studies on IaH in the Irish context. The only literature that existed at the time was uncovering some aspects of IaH, such as Ryan (2020) study, which investigates lecturer's engagement with IoC at TU Dublin, Clarke and Hui Yang (2019) investigating staff perspectives on internationalisation in the Republic of Ireland, Idris, Ion, and Seery (2019) paper on the role of peer learning and presence of international students in an Irish classroom, Dunne (2013) paper exploring motivations for intercultural contact between domestic and international students and O'Reilly, Hickey, and Ryan (2013) work on lecturer's experiences working with international students in a classroom setting. The sparse literature on IaH may stem from a lack of conceptual clarity, as many Irish HEIs are engaged in internationalisation on campus without explicitly identifying it as IaH. Furthermore, the

report by Clarke *et al.* (2018) also suggests that additional efforts may be necessary to advance this area.

During the progress of this study and its dissemination, scholarly interest grew and sparked academic inquiry. This can be visible through recent initiatives such as an Erasmus+ project called the 'training and realising innovations in IaH pedagogies' (TRIP) by a consortium led by the University of Limerick (UL) and the recent compendium that highlights examples of internationalisation of the home curriculum by the Technological University of the Shannon (TUS) (Kelly and O'Donoghue, 2024). Whilst the beginning of the discourse is an indicator of the growing importance of IaH in the Irish context, as is also revealed in the EAIE Barometer Spin-off report for Ireland (2024) and Global Citizens 2030 national strategy (DFHERIS, 2024), there is a gap in implementing and embedding IaH at an institutional level, moving beyond the 'parts' to the 'whole' approach. This gap suggests a need for systems and frameworks suited to holistically support Irish HEIs in embedding a culture of IaH.

1.3 Scope of the Study and Limitations

The research examines the interpretation of IaH within the Irish context, the opportunities and challenges facing Irish HEIs, and suggests strategies for cultivating a culture for IaH. This perspective is gathered from various stakeholders, including learners, academic staff, academic managers, international officers, senior managers, and policymakers/influencers within Irish higher education. This study was conducted in the Republic of Ireland, and the data collection was facilitated online. Furthermore, staff from academic support units at IaH best practice institutions¹ from Europe and the UK were also included as participants in the study.

The sample population for this study comprised thirty-six participants who were recruited from eight institutions/organisations, with six from Ireland and one best practice institution in IaH, each from Europe and the UK. The Irish HEIs included two traditional and two technological universities, selected based on their geographical locations. Each HEI varied in type, size, focus, historical background, and regional influence. The oldest university in the sample was established in the latter half of the nineteenth century, while the most recent institution was formed from a merger into a technological university in 2022. Additionally,

¹ These HEIs were considered 'best practice' because of their advanced nature in implementing and monitoring IaH within their HEIs, evidenced by their innovative approaches, scholarly work, reputation and recognition in the field (Hénard, Diamond and Roseveare, 2012).

one organisation each was chosen for its role in policy-making and influencing role related to the internationalisation of Irish HEIs. The selection of these specific participant groups aimed to gain a comprehensive understanding of IaH from the perspectives of various stakeholders within Irish HE.

Furthermore, the research utilises a qualitative data collection approach grounded in constructivism and interpretivism within a relativist metatheoretical framework. It employs focus groups and semi-structured interviews to elicit rich and in-depth insights. As such, while the aim has been to provide an overarching view of IaH and develop a guiding framework for embedding a culture of IaH, there are, however, a few limitations.

Firstly, this study captures the perspectives of only two publicly funded traditional universities and two technological universities (TUs), which implies that it cannot be considered a representative of the entire Irish HE sector. Additionally, while the best practice HEIs in Europe and the UK provide valuable insights into IaH practices, they cannot be generalised to the specific stakeholders and institutions examined in this study. Their inclusion primarily explores supplementary strategies for implementing IaH in Irish HEIs.

Secondly, data collection from Irish HEIs was conducted online without physical campus visits. Thirdly, there were temporal constraints, as the findings reflect a specific point in time during the full academic year of 2023-24. It is acknowledged that participants' professional, institutional, and external contexts may have evolved since then. Fourthly, the perspectives of individuals who may be indifferent, sceptical, or resistant to IaH could be underrepresented. Finally, the researcher's background, experience, and interpretation inevitably shape the research process. Nonetheless, reflexivity has been employed through journaling and member checking to help reduce potential bias, acknowledging that complete objectivity is neither assumed nor claimed in this qualitative inquiry.

1.4 Researcher's Positionality

My research has been framed from the perspective of someone who has been deeply engaged in internationalisation in higher education in India, drawing on fourteen years of academic and practitioner experience, about half of which has included implementing IaH at an Indian HEI. Alongside this, serving as a General Council Member at the EAIE for four years helped me to build an understanding of the trends and issues influencing European HE. My background and experience have made me acutely aware of my position as a 'practitioner-researcher' (Postholm and Skrøvset, 2013), an 'international learner' from India (Harrison,

2015), a 'woman' (Burkhard, 2021), and an 'outsider' (Hellowell, 2006) within the Irish context.

Living in Ireland for the past four years has allowed me to appreciate the importance of sustaining the friendships and networks I built with European peers. Last year, I had the opportunity to resume my role as a General Council member with the EAIE, which has deepened my exploration of the evolution of the internationalisation of higher education and my research area, IaH. Being 'back to school' and stepping into the shoes of international learners has helped me cultivate empathy, while collaborating with learners from diverse cultures has enhanced my intercultural competence and resilience in adapting to life in a foreign country.

Furthermore, the middle years of my PhD journey aligned with my 'spiritual awakening,' which offered me a reflective lens to view the world more broadly. This perspective enhanced my intuitive engagement with all aspects of my research, particularly in ideas and data interpretation. As I progressed in this research and on my journey of spiritual awakening, I came to realise that idolising best practices in IaH from afar may not yield the best results; no system or institution has perfected it, although some may be more advanced in varying respects. This epiphany altered my initial perception that IaH is novel to Ireland, revealing the vast potential present in untold stories and initiatives.

Irish HEIs exhibit a quiet yet transformative approach to advancing internationalisation. Much like my spiritual awakening in Waterford, I have come to believe that the HEIs involved in my study may require a 'systemic awakening' to consolidate effective practices in IaH, challenge existing ones, create systems and processes that speak to each other and enhance investment in preparing citizens for a multicultural society and world. This transformation must transcend mere diversity, embodying a global mindset that emphasises inclusion, peace, and solutions to shared global challenges. All these experiences and reflections have helped me refine my critical thinking and problem-solving skills, allowing me to step back, reflect, and respond, embracing the 'whole', a philosophy mirrored in this research.

1.5 Contribution to Knowledge

This study's theoretical contribution involves applying a distinctive combination of theories that provide a comprehensive perspective on IaH, which extends beyond curricula to institutional values and campus life. As such, theories related to organisational design, curriculum design, and change management are employed. This framework contributes to addressing the research questions regarding the opportunities and challenges of cultivating a culture of IaH by informing the research design, data collection and analysis for this study.

In organisational design, theories such as *stakeholder identification and salience* (Mitchell *et al.*, 1997) facilitate the identification of stakeholders and their respective salience, namely, power, legitimacy, and urgency in implementing IaH initiatives. Furthermore, the theory of *stakeholder culture* (Jones *et al.*, 2007) highlights the continuum between self-regarding and other-regarding cultures, which can inform the approach of Irish HEIs as they strive to embed IaH. Lastly, the *job demands and resources framework* (Bakker and Demerouti, 2017) sheds light on the motivations, or the lack thereof, among institutional leadership, staff, learners, policymakers, and influencers regarding IaH.

Furthermore, from a curriculum design perspective, the *conceptual framework for an internationalised curriculum* (Leask, 2015) is employed. This framework provides insights into the internationalisation of formal, informal, and hidden curricula, conceptualising 'curriculum as a system' (Leask, 2022). Consequently, it assists in identifying some of the opportunities and challenges facing Irish HEIs in embedding IaH into the curriculum.

Finally, change management theories help suggest strategies to embed a culture of IaH. The *organisational culture transformational framework* (Armenakis *et al.*, 2011) facilitates an assessment of the change readiness and institutionalisation for IaH in Irish HEIs. Additionally, utilising *systems thinking* within a *learning organisation framework* (Senge, 1990) offers a comprehensive approach for effectively integrating and embedding IaH throughout the institution, transitioning from fragmented activities into a cohesive whole.

In addition to this distinctive theoretical pluralism, a working definition for embedding a culture of IaH is proposed in [Chapter 6 \(sub-section 6.4.2\)](#). This definition is anchored in the widely cited definition of IaH (Beelen and Jones, 2015) but expands to encompass a university-wide, systems-based approach, rather than being confined to the curriculum.

Moreover, the practical contributions of this study focus on a pragmatic, evidence-based guiding framework for embedding a culture of IaH within Irish HEIs- the *IaH Content*,

Positioning, and Reflection (IaH CPR) framework, which is built upon existing literature, the theoretical framework, participant accounts, and the researcher's reflections, illustrated in *Figures 28 and 29*. It aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of how IaH can be implemented in practice across faculty, schools, departments and functions within Irish HEIs. To this end, the study also offers progress markers to evaluate the success and impact of IaH initiatives (*Table 12*) and mechanisms to acknowledge and reward staff for engaging in effective practices (*Table 13*). In essence, this research provides targeted recommendations at both the institutional and national levels to assist Irish HEIs in embedding a culture of IaH (*Table 14*).

1.6 Research Aims and Objectives

The extant literature alludes to the growing importance of IaH and the need for guidance to support embedding a culture of IaH to benefit all learners and staff. This study aims to address this gap in the Irish context.

The **primary purpose** of the study is:

- Critique how IaH is interpreted in the Irish context, considering its development globally.
- Draw on findings related to the opportunities and challenges in implementing IaH at Irish HEIs, as presented by the participants in this study.
- Develop a guiding framework that can assist Irish HEIs in embedding a culture of IaH.

In order to achieve the aim of the study, the following **central research questions** have been identified:

1. *What are the opportunities and challenges for developing a culture of IaH in an Irish higher education context?*
2. *What strategies can be developed to embed a culture of IaH in Irish HEIs?*

To this end, the following **research objectives** have been outlined:

- a) Carrying out focus groups with students and individual semi-structured interviews with the academic staff, academic managers, international officers, senior managers, and policymakers/influencers within the Irish higher education sector. The purpose is to

explore, classify, and discuss their experiences and perspectives of IaH and how it could be implemented and embedded.

- b) Analysing national and institutional strategies from the perspective of IaH.
- c) Providing recommendations as to how Irish HEIs can cultivate a culture of IaH within their institutions.
- d) Proposing a guiding framework that assists Irish HEIs in embedding of a culture of IaH.

1.7 Overview of the Thesis Chapters

This sub-section provides a summary of the discourse in each chapter that has shaped the study.

Chapter 2 presents a literature review of IaH from a global perspective, examining the key rationales, enablers, challenges, and suggestions for implementing IaH. Moreover, some existing frameworks were explored, and the development of IaH during COVID-19 has been elucidated.

Chapter 3 shifts focus to Ireland, providing a literature review on the internationalisation of higher education in the country. It explores the developments in internationalisation at the national level, the limited scholarly discourse on IaH, and the increasing prominence of IaH in the strategic plans of Irish HEIs.

Chapter 4 examines the theoretical framework for this study, which conceptualises IaH in the Irish HE context through theories of organisational and curriculum design and change management. In combination, this framework offers a unique yet comprehensive theoretical grounding for the study.

Chapter 5 outlines the research methodology and methodological considerations. Rooted in a constructivist ontological and interpretivist epistemological approach within a relativist metatheoretical framework, this study utilised a descriptive qualitative research design to address its aims and research questions. It adumbrates the theoretical framework's methodological rationale, research design, sample population, and EDI considerations for this study. Furthermore, it describes data collection procedures and justifies the methods suited for this study. The ethical considerations are set forth, and the data analysis techniques are explained. Notably, the researcher reflects on their role in the entire research process. Consequently, the verification strategies elucidated establish the trustworthiness of this

research, and the overall quality is addressed through Tracy's eight "big-tent" criteria for excellent qualitative research (2010) (*Appendix I*).

Chapter 6 presents the findings and discussion from the focus groups and semi-structured interviews. The findings provide strong evidence of the growing importance of IaH in Irish HEIs and fully address this study's research aims and objectives. Additionally, this chapter proposes an evidence-based working definition of IaH (*sub-section 6.4.2*), along with the IaH Content, Positioning, and Reflection (IaH CPR) framework (*Figures 28 and 29*), measures of success (*Table 12*) and possible reward and recognition mechanisms (*Table 13*) which can guide HEIs in their efforts to embed a culture of IaH.

Chapter 7 concludes the study and offers recommendations and implications for policy and practice in IaH (*sub-section 7.4*). Additionally, it outlines the theoretical and practical contributions of this study, discusses its limitations, provides suggestions for future research, and includes the researcher's reflection and reflexivity in the entire research process.

1.8 Conclusion

This chapter presented an overarching view of the study by outlining its context, significance, scope, and limitations. It included a reflexive account of the researcher's positionality and reflexivity in influencing both the study and its outcomes. Additionally, the chapter highlighted the theoretical and practical contributions of the research, addressing its aims and objectives. Finally, it summarised the forthcoming chapters in the thesis. The following chapter introduces the literature review on IaH from a global perspective.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW (GLOBAL CONTEXT)

2.1 Introduction

Throughout history, the international dimension in universities has been fostered through universal knowledge and research, which has facilitated the mobility of students and scholars (De Wit and Deca, 2020; De Wit and Merckx, 2012; Knight, 2004; Altbach, 1998; Kerr, Kerr, Gade, and Kawaoka, 1994). However, in recent years, many higher education institutions have increasingly viewed internationalisation as a means to achieve their economic ambitions (Ibid.). This has resulted in a greater emphasis on recruiting international students and promoting student mobility abroad rather than other objectives, such as improving teaching and learning experiences at the home institution (De Wit, 2022; Knight, 2006). Despite this, many HEIs are rethinking their rationale and approach to internationalisation, engaging in initiatives that promote global citizenship (Gaynor, 2016; Beelen and Jones, 2015; Leask, 2015; Knight, 2012; De Wit, 2010). The growing emphasis on global citizenship can be considered to have led to 'internationalisation at home (IaH)' gaining prominence in many institutions globally, including Ireland (Sierra-Huedo, Bruton and Fernández, 2024; Beelen, 2023; Clarke, Yang, and Harmon, 2018; Harrison, 2016; Beelen and Jones, 2015; Leask, 2015 and Haigh, 2014).

As such, the literature review has been presented in two chapters- the global and the Irish context. The current chapter focuses on the development of IaH globally and has been categorised into eight sub-sections. These include (1) background context of internationalisation of higher education (IoHE) globally, (2) historical context and evolving definitions of internationalisation at home (IaH), (3) rationale for IaH, (4) enablers of IaH, (5) challenges in implementing IaH, (6) overcoming challenges in IaH implementation, (7) existing guiding frameworks, and lastly, (8) IaH in COVID-19 and beyond.

This chapter commences with situating IaH in the broader context of the internationalisation of higher education (IoHE). The attention is drawn to the core theme of this research, 'Internationalisation at Home (IaH),' by focusing on the historical context, evolving definitions, rationale, enablers, challenges, solutions and existing frameworks. The chapter concludes with the development of IaH during the COVID-19 period and its present state.

The sources examined in this review encompass a variety of materials, such as peer-reviewed papers, articles, policy-based papers, case studies, and grey literature pertaining to IaH.

In summary, the literature analysis in this chapter showcases the increasing importance of IaH in many institutions globally. From the literature reviewed, it is evident that IaH has the potential to equip students with international and intercultural skills and competencies, preparing them to become global citizens.

2.2 Internationalisation of Higher Education (IoHE)

In recent years, internationalisation has become one of the core dimensions for many HEIs across the globe (Rumbley, Altbach and Reisberg, 2012, p.3). As institutions strive to internationalise, the concept and practical application of internationalisation have undergone significant changes, from academic cooperation to now a greater emphasis on competitiveness, mobility, curricular relevance and societal impact (De Wit, 2024; Tran, Jung, Unangst and Marshall, 2023; O'Neill, 2019; De Wit, Hunter, Howard and Egron-Polak, 2015; Beelen and Jones, 2015; Leask, 2015 and Rumbley, Altbach and Reisberg, 2012). This section provides an overview of some of the key developments shaping the evolution of IoHE and situating the need for IaH, which is the core theme of the research.

The earliest signs of internationalisation in universities around the world were seen through research, scholar mobility, and the exporting of higher education systems during the 18th and 19th centuries (Deardorff, De Wit, Leask and Charles, 2023; Lee and Stensaker, 2021; De Wit, Hunter, Howard and Egron-Polak, 2015; Hartmann, 2014 and Nelson, 2013). During this period, research was mainly focused on national interests, but there were efforts to share ideas and knowledge through international seminars, conferences, and publications (Ibid). However, only a small number of elite scholars who could afford to travel were able to participate in international scholar mobility (Ibid.).

Interestingly, one of the most prominent internationalisation elements of higher education (HE) during this time was exporting higher education systems (Ibid.). Colonial powers' export of higher education could have had a long-lasting impact on the once-colonised territories, now independent states (De Wit and Merckx, 2023, p.27). For instance, the British and French systems appear to have shaped the HE landscapes of various parts of the world, such as India, Asia, Africa, the Caribbean, and North America. Additionally, the influence of the Spanish and Portuguese systems can be observed in many institutions in Northern, Central, and South America (Robert, Cruz and Herbst 1996).

While countries with a colonial past could have been markedly influenced by the HE systems of their colonial powers, non-colonial countries such as China, Japan, and Thailand can also be considered to have extensively adopted the Western university systems in their efforts to modernise (Ibid.). This adoption may be attributed to Western powers' economic, political, and military pressures on non-colonial countries in the 19th century (Altbach and Selvaratnam, 1989, p.10). For instance, German and American HE systems are visible in many Japanese Universities (Ibid.).

Against this setting, one of the key nations shaping the development of international education, the United States, also mirrored European influences for a very long period. Institutions such as Harvard, Yale, Pennsylvania, Princeton, and Columbia, based on the models of Oxford and Cambridge universities in Britain, are examples of European influences in American HE (Ibid.). Scott (1998) refers to this export of HE systems as the predominant form of internationalisation during this period, which continued into the 20th century and which he referred to as 'academic colonialism' or 'academic imperialism' (p.124). This academic colonialism suggests that colonised countries and their institutions may have adopted not only academic systems and culture but also teaching and learning practices and curricula (Scott, 1998). This can signify the origins of an internationalised curriculum rooted in colonial and Western paradigms (Deardorff *et al.*, 2023).

In addition to academic colonialism, pre and post-World War II periods may have significantly shaped international education. Prior to World War II, there were emerging indications of the growing importance of international cooperation and exchange through the establishment of the Institute of International Education (IIE) in 1919 in the United States, Deutscher Akademischer Austauschdienst (DAAD) in Germany in 1925, and the British Council in the United Kingdom in 1934 (De Wit and Merkx, 2023, p.31). These institutions aimed to facilitate academic cooperation through the mobility of scholars (Ibid.). Establishing these institutions can be a manifestation of the aftermath of World War I for peace and mutual understanding (Ibid.). Early scholars such as Goodwin and Nacht (2009, 1991) suggest that these exchanges may have also influenced curricula as the United States began to recognise the importance of understanding other cultures for peace (Goodwin and Nacht, 1991, p.3). This was reflected in the creation of new institutions focused on international relations, such as the Council on Foreign Relations in the US during this period (Ibid.).

In the years subsequent to the two world wars, much of Europe focused on recovery and reconstruction (De Wit and Merckx, 2023, p.32). At the same time, the United States continued to advance international education in the first decade (Ibid.). During this period, many European academics also migrated to countries such as Australia, Canada, and the United States (p.33). This could have further catalysed the development of internationalisation in HE with the migration of European culture, knowledge, and systems that may have influenced the systems of the universities in these countries (De Wit and Merckx, 2023, p.33).

Across this span, the United States also began to lead the discourse around international education, particularly after establishing the Fulbright Act in 1946, which aimed to facilitate the mobility of scholars and students across borders (Ibid.). The growing mobility may have contributed to increased attention towards teaching and learning practices and curriculum development (Ibid.). Furthermore, to strengthen its international dimension, the United States recognised the potential of third-world colonies as important regions for expanding economic and political power (Ibid.). As a result, they invested development funds in Asia, Latin America and Africa to support teaching, training and curriculum development (Ibid.).

In contrast, many European countries focused on recovery from wars as a top priority for their national governments (Baron, 1993). The subtle signs of international dimension were present in the form of elite degree-seeking students from developing world colonies who pursued their higher education primarily in the United Kingdom, France, and Germany, and, to some extent, in Belgium and the Netherlands (De Wit, 2011; De Wit, 2001; Baron, 1993; Kerr, 1990). This may have been enabled by an open-door policy for foreign students characterised by a 'benevolent laissez-faire' until the late 1970s (Baron, 1993, p.50). Later in the 1980s, this policy was revised to establish reasonable limits for mainly fee-paying international students, particularly in the United Kingdom, a part of the European Union at the time (Ibid.).

Furthermore, as noted by Kerr (1994), the 1980s may have marked a significant period in European history for international education, spurred by changing global dynamics, such as Japan gradually beginning to augment its status as an economic world power, challenging the dominant position of the United States (Ibid.). Concomitantly, key developments in Europe included the establishment of the European Economic Community (EEC) and the introduction of the Erasmus programmes (Ibid.). Scholars such as De Wit and Merckx (2023)

argue that forming the European Community, previously known as the EEC, could have played a crucial role in advancing internationalisation in Europe after World War II (p.42).

Notably, one of the main objectives behind creating the EEC in 1957 was facilitating mobility in vocational education (Teichler, 2009; Neave, 1994). However, in the late 1970s, the EEC began actively promoting and supporting cross-border collaborations, mobility, and recognition of credits between European HEIs (Teichler, 2009; De Wit, 2002; Wachter *et al.*, 1999; European Commission, 1994). The EEC was established to open the European borders between member states, which incidentally created internationalisation opportunities (Ibid). As part of the EEC, the Joint Study Programme (JSP), a pilot initiative, was implemented to encourage cooperation and mobility between EU countries (Ibid.). Interestingly, the JSP funded most of the curricular collaborations and mobility between 1976-86 (Ibid.). However, it was increasingly becoming evident that additional financial support would be necessary to expand mobility opportunities to all of Europe (Teichler, 2009; Opper *et al.*, 1990; Dalichow and Teichler, 1986; Smith, 1979). This could have led to the EEC establishing more programmes to facilitate mobility and cooperation in HE throughout Europe (Ibid.).

The growing support to enhance mobility and cooperation may have set the stage for one of the most significant mobility programmes, ERASMUS, launched in 1987 (Teichler, 2009; Teichler and Maiworm, 1997; Kehm, 1994). The EEC began extending its role and concentrating on international cooperation for curriculum development, university-industry networks, and student mobility (Ibid.). This could have laid the groundwork for a more coordinated approach to internationalisation, uniting most European countries through their member states (Kerr, 1994, p.20).

Remarkably, the launch and implementation of the ERASMUS programme, which stands for 'European Action Scheme for the Mobility of University Students,' in 1987 can be viewed as a significant milestone in developing the international dimension in Europe. This Erasmus programme aimed to enhance the prospects for students to study abroad for a semester or a year as part of their academic programme within the EEC (European Commission, n.d.). Additionally, it sought to foster inter-university cooperation among EU member states (Ibid.).

In addition, the Erasmus programme may have provided some financial support for curricular innovation, staff exchanges and information dissemination between European institutions (Teichler and Maiworm, 1997). Taking its primary goal into account, the Erasmus

programmes aimed at offering mobility opportunities to at least 10% of all the students enrolled in a higher education institution (HEI) in the EEC (Ibid.). To this end, since the adoption of the Erasmus programme, the number of students travelling between EU member states increased significantly from 2,500 in 1986 to 4,000 in 1988-89 and 28,000 in 1989-90 (EAIE, 1990, p.3).

Furthermore, the increasing popularity of the Erasmus programme coincided with the establishment of the European Association for International Education (EAIE) in 1989 with a vision to network, advocate and drive internationalisation in European HE through its annual conferences (De Wit and Merckx, 2023).

Interestingly, the growing popularity of the Erasmus programmes may not have entirely resulted in their achieving the desired outcomes related to mobility. Most European HEIs may not have been able to realise the 10% mobility target established since the programme's inception, as reported by the newly launched EAIE observing trends in the sector (Commission of the European Communities, 1989; EAIE, 1990; Wielemans, 1991; Teichler, 1996). This could be due to various reasons, such as unequal funding distribution to support mobility to EU member states, lack of recognition of academic credentials between universities, inadequate linguistic preparation for travel abroad, and insufficient accommodation to support mobility needs, to mention a few (Ibid.). Moreover, it was increasingly acknowledged that most students were being marginalised due to their limitations constraining them to participate in mobility programmes (EAIE, 1990). This concern could have conceivably scaffolded into the conception and rise of 'internationalisation at home' (IaH) in the later years, as elucidated in *sub-section 2.3*.

These developments occurred amidst the backdrop of globalisation, defined as 'the flow of technology, economy, knowledge, people, values, and ideas across borders' (Knight and De Wit, 1997, p. 6). Although internationalisation and globalisation may have been perceived as interchangeable concepts, globalisation became increasingly prominent since 1992 (Ibid.). According to Altbach, Reisberg, and Rumbley (2019),

"Globalisation is a reality shaped by an increasingly integrated world economy, new information and communications technology, the emergence of an international knowledge network, the role of the English language, and other forces beyond the control of academic institutions [...]. Internationalisation is defined as the variety of policies and programs that universities and governments implement to respond to globalisation."

(Altbach, Reisberg and Rumbley, 2019, p.7)

Interestingly, Marginson (2006) argues that globalisation and internationalisation are associated terms and could have potentially transformed the governance and management of HE. Knight (2008) claims that 'internationalisation is changing the world of higher education, and globalisation is changing the world of internationalisation' (p.1).

The impact of globalisation has the potential to contribute to significant growth in university enrolments worldwide, projected to increase from 250.7 million in 2020 to 594.1 million by 2040, representing an estimated 57% rise (Calderon, 2018, p.24). This trend can also be viewed to have been endorsed by the International Association of Universities (IAU) in their sixth and fifth global surveys, where they deduce that globalisation can be considered one of the most circumstantial factors underpinning IoHE (Marinoni and Cardona, 2024 and Marinoni, 2018). Consequently, universities are becoming more multicultural due to globalisation, and leveraging diversity in a campus environment can contribute to peace, harmony and justice in multicultural societies (Deardorff and Jones, 2012, p.284).

The increasing impact of globalisation has sparked discussions around the rationale for IoHE in most parts of the world. This discourse can be traced to a significant global event in 1994 that may have influenced national policies in the United States, Europe, Canada and Australia (Scherrer, 2005). This event was the signing of the General Agreement on Trade in Services (GATS) by the World Trade Organization (WTO), which identified higher education (HE) as a 'tradable commodity' (Knight, 2006, p.8). Signifying HE this way could have arguably opened opportunities for academic programmes to be offered internationally, which may have led to the perception of international students as 'consumers' and HE as a 'market' (Altbach and Knight, 2007; Van der Wende, 2001). As a result, with GATS, the economic motive could have begun to gain currency in international education (Van der Wende, 2001, p.249).

As a consequence of GATS, many HEIs began to view international student recruitment, student mobility abroad, preparing domestic students for the global job market, and

attracting international talent as key indicators of successful internationalisation (De Wit 2020; O'Neill 2019; De Wit and Hunter 2015; Jiang 2010, and Knight 2006). This shift towards a market-based approach in HE may have influenced national policies in many European countries, including Ireland, to focus on the economic rationale for engaging in internationalisation. In Ireland, GATS was reinforced through the state agency Enterprise Ireland, which recognised HE as a tradeable international service (DoES, 2004).

In the 1990s, significant advancements were made in promoting international cooperation in HE, such as the GATS and the emergence of various associations and organisations besides the EAIE. These included the Canadian Bureau of International Education (CBIE), the National Association of Foreign Student Advisers (NAFSA), the Association of International Education Administrators (AIEA) in the USA, International Education Association of Australia (IEAA), the World Bank, the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), European Universities Association (EUA) and the Journal of Studies in International Education (JSIE) (De Wit, 2013). The gradual development of these organisations could have contributed to more coordinated approaches to internationalisation, particularly in some parts of Europe, which may have resulted in many national governments developing explicit international strategies in HE (De Wit and Merckx, 2023).

Amidst the growing trends of globalisation and internationalisation, the development of international education strategies and enhanced mobility through Erasmus programmes may have prompted many HEIs and governments to prioritise the recognition of academic credentials earned abroad (Huisman, Adelman, Hsieh, Shams and Wilkins, 2012; Kehm, 2010 and De Wit, 2007). As a result, several European HEIs began seeking suitable partner institutions for Erasmus programmes recognising credits, aiming to align the student experience of studying abroad with that of studying at home (Ibid.).

In response to the concerns for recognition of academic credentials, 29 European countries convened in Bologna in 1999 to establish the European Higher Education Area (EHEA) (Huisman, 2014, p.4). The creation of EHEA was intended to enhance the appeal of European HE, increase the mobility and employability of European Citizens, and establish a greater level of comparability and compatibility among HE systems (Ibid.). This could have facilitated the signing of the 'Bologna Accord' in 1999 (Teichler, 2009, p.101), which aimed to create a comparable and standardised framework for qualifications obtained by students

from European HEIs. Ireland was among the 29 countries that signed the accord (Sanders and Dunn, 2010; Teichler, 2009; Trowler, 2004).

The Bologna Accord can be considered a landmark agreement aimed at promoting the internationalisation of European HEIs by facilitating the transfer and recognition of credits earned by students studying at other European institutions across member states (Huisman, Adelman, Hsieh, Shams and Wilkins, 2012; Kehm, 2010 and De Wit, 2007). According to Westerheijden *et al.* (2010), adopting the Bologna Accord may have led to a stable number of EHEA students between 1999 and 2007, while non-EHEA students increased from 1.6 to 2.6%. These developments can signify the growing appeal of Europe as a destination for HE for international students (Ibid.).

Moreover, the Bologna accord may have resulted in improving recognition for credentials earned by the students studying in the Erasmus programmes, mainly through the International Credit Mobility (ICM), which was introduced in 2014 (Crosier and Parveva, 2013; Brookes and Huisman, 2009; Pechar, 2007; De Wit, 2007 and Keeling, 2006). ICM may have enabled students and staff to train, study and teach globally with ease of credit recognition for their experiences within European HEIs (Ibid.). The Bologna process facilitated an internationalised curriculum by promoting the free movement of students, academic culture and systems (De Wit, 2018; Beelen and Jones, 2015; Hunter, 2015; Berndtson, 2015). This could have established the basis for students requiring a curriculum that equips them to tackle societal challenges in local and global contexts (Ibid.).

Notably, an internationalised curriculum appeared capable of developing intercultural competencies, enabling students to adapt and embrace diverse perspectives living and working in multicultural environments (Deardorff and Jones, 2012, p.284). This opportunity to develop intercultural competence catalysed through the Bologna accord may have manifested into other significant dimensions of IoHE, such as 'Internationalisation at Home (IaH)' at the beginning of the 21st century, which is the focus of the current study.

In essence, IoHE can be viewed as primarily developed in the United States, Europe, and Australia in response to globalisation (De Wit and Merckx, 2012, p.57). The emergence of the US as a dominant power after World War II, the recovery of Europe, the implementation of the Bologna process and the Erasmus programmes have all contributed to the growing importance of IoHE in the 21st century (Ibid.). In recent years, the strategic approach to IoHE may have been underpinned by increasing globalisation and deepening of European integration (De Wit and Merckx, 2023, p.44). This can be attributed to several factors, such

as the rise in global student mobility from 2,50,000 in 1965 to 5 million in 2020 (p.45), an increase in cross-border delivery of higher education programmes for many institutions in countries such as the US, UK and Australia; investment in branch campuses abroad by many institutions in Russia, France and Germany; international competitiveness in sourcing highly skilled workforce, particularly with intercultural competencies, and ageing societies competing for international talent such as Japan, North America, Australia and Europe (Ibid.).

The aforementioned evolution of IoHE is reflected in the development of the concept. In the early 1990s, Arum and van de Water defined international education as a set of international activities centred on student mobility at the institutional level (p.202). However, Knight (1994) challenged this definition, arguing that mobility alone did not encompass the full scope of international education.

Knight (1994) proposed a new definition, which emphasised

"The integration of an international and intercultural dimension into the teaching, research and service functions of the institution."
(Knight, 1994, p.7)

A decade later, Knight (2003) expanded the definition to encompass purpose and delivery beyond institutions. It was redefined as

"The process of integrating an international, intercultural or global dimension into the purpose, functions or delivery of post-secondary education."
(Knight, 2003, p.2)

Knight's (2003) definition gained widespread recognition and may have contributed to the transition from 'international education' to 'internationalisation of higher education (IoHE)' (De Wit, 2024, p. 8). However, Hudzik (2011) introduced the concept of 'Comprehensive Internationalisation (CI)' in the United States to provide a more holistic definition. According to Hudzik (2011), CI is

"Commitment, confirmed through action to infuse international and comparative perspectives throughout the teaching, research, and service missions of higher education."
(Hudzik, 2011, p.6)

Whilst different definitions were emerging in process, De Wit, Hunter, Egron-Polak and Howard (2015) aimed to provide a clear direction for the future of internationalisation by redefining IoHE as

"The intentional process of integrating an international, intercultural or global dimension into the purpose, functions and delivery of post-secondary education, in order to enhance the quality of education and research for all students and staff, and to make a meaningful contribution to society."

(De Wit, Hunter, Egron-Polak and Howard, 2015, p.281)

Despite this new, widely cited definition, De Wit and Hunter (2016) suggest that the concept requires further development, asserting that it encompasses various dimensions, components, approaches, and activities (p.53). Stein, Andreotti, Bruce and Suša (2016) add that IoHE is characterised by 'ongoing complexities, tensions, difficulties, and paradoxes' that continue to be a subject of ongoing debate and reflection (p.14). Furthermore, De Wit and Altbach (2021) suggest that changing circumstances require reimagining IoHE. According to De Wit and Altbach (2021),

"Internationalisation is a process in constant evolution, which changes in response to local, national, regional, and global environments. Current global trends appear to be more radical than in the past and require stronger attention and international cooperation than ever; nationalist-populist movements, the need for climate change, and the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic are particularly vital."

(De Wit and Altbach, 2021, p.44)

Nonetheless, De Wit (2023) argues that IoHE is contextually evolving. Rather than focusing on redefining it, institutions may identify the future direction with a clear rationale for engaging in internationalisation (p.10). He concludes

"The end of the current form of internationalisation will need to be the beginning – a beginning with new directions and key themes (...) a shift from short-term neoliberal approaches to long-term societal interests, from international education as a benefit for a small elite towards global learning for all, and from a Western paradigm to a global and equal process."

(De Wit, 2023, p. 206)

Given the emerging understandings and the growing need for a more strategic approach to IoHE, recent events such as the COVID-19 pandemic and intensifying geo-political

conflicts, the emphasis of many HEIs could have been influenced to recognise the significance of other aspects such as internationalisation at home (IaH) that could potentially be a catalyst to promote equity, peace and justice through the development of intercultural competence and global citizenship in HE students, examined in the subsequent sub-section.

2.3 Internationalisation at Home (IaH)

Within the context of the broader field of IoHE, this sub-section describes the historical background and evolution of the concept of IaH, which can be viewed as becoming increasingly significant in many HEIs globally.

2.3.1 Historical Context

Internationalisation at Home (IaH), a notable approach to internationalisation in higher education (IoHE), gained popularity in the 21st century by striving to purposefully integrate international and intercultural dimensions in the formal and informal curriculum for all students within their domestic learning environments (Beelen and Jones, 2015). This can be traced to the low percentage of mobility opportunities (less than 10%) available to students in most European, Australian and American HEIs at the time (Beelen, 2023; Deardorff, De Wit, Leask and Charles, 2023). The 'elitism' associated with mobility experiences and the growing need to prepare citizens to address shared local and global challenges could have contributed to developing IaH in some institutions in Europe, the US, and Australia (Ibid.). Moreover, institutions that engaged in IaH viewed it as a catalyst to foster intercultural competencies essential for functioning within multicultural societies, a consequence of increasing globalisation (Gregersen-Hermans, Jones and Murphy, 2023; Beelen, 2023; Deardorff and Jones, 2022 and Leask, 2015). IaH appeared capable of developing students' awareness of local, national, European, and global contexts and navigating communication in diverse settings (Ibid.).

Furthermore, according to Hunter (2018) and Hunter and Sparnon (2016), for internationalisation to be successful, it must embrace all students and staff, and this process may need to be intentional. Intentionality can involve a carefully planned process that entails thoughtful reflection, decision-making, action, and change across different functions and departments of an institution (Ibid.). One of the effective ways to involve all students and staff in the internationalisation process can be through IaH (Hunter, McAllister-Grande, Proctor and De Wit, 2022).

Interestingly, the concept of 'internationalisation at home (IaH)' can be linked to its emergence at the University of Malmö in Sweden, where Bengt Nilsson first introduced the term in 1999 (Nilsson, 2003, p.31). At the time, the University of Malmö was newly established and did not have an international office or network (Ibid.). However, the region where the university was set up was ethnically diverse, with about 35 % of the population comprising immigrants (Ibid.). The university's Nightingale project helped to nurture a connection between the university and the local community (Sild Lönroth and Nilsson, 2007).

As the institution continued to diversify, it became apparent that more could be done to provide students with opportunities to develop intercultural skills, knowledge, and attitudes within the university that will be useful for them as citizens of the society (Ibid.). Additionally, the limitations of mobility due to various factors, such as awareness, personal circumstances, and funding, were acknowledged (Ibid.). Notwithstanding these limitations, the term 'internationalisation at home (IaH)' was coined as a new approach to internationalisation that had been predominantly mobility-focused (Beelen and Leask, 2012, p.3).

Notably, the concept of Internationalisation at Home (IaH) was initially aimed to equip students who did not travel abroad as part of their studies, also called the 'non-mobile majority,' with intercultural skills (Crowther *et al.*, 2000). Moreover, subsequent research by scholars such as Crawford and Bethell (2012) emphasised the potential benefits of integrating the knowledge and experiences of returning students and staff into programs, which could benefit non-mobile students (Savicki, 2023; Crawford and Bethell, 2012; Teichler and Jahr, 2001). However, Berg and Paige (2009) and Lestinen and Riitaija (2007) suggest that such experience sharing may not naturally take place and can require purposeful intervention (Berg and Paige, 2009; Lestinen and Riitaija, 2007; Mestenhauser, 2007). To this end, Beelen and Jones (2015) argue that IaH has the potential to extend beyond the non-mobile majority and provide an internationalised experience accessible to all students.

Making internationalisation accessible to all students may have catalysed the evolution of internationalisation from an institutional lens through IaH (Ibid.). This may have supported the needs of diverse students at the University of Malmö and in some institutions in other parts of Europe. These included some universities in Denmark, Norway, Finland, the Netherlands, and Belgium, collectively known as 'continental Europe' and the UK (Beelen and Jones, 2015, p.8). The literature suggests that adopting IaH in some of these universities in these countries may have been influenced by their small size, language diversity, and the

widespread use of English as a second language (Beelen and Jones, 2015; OECD, 2009). Consequently, IaH began to be recognised as an approach to internationalisation in many other European institutions (Ibid.).

According to Mestenhauser (2007) and Yang (2002), many universities globally have begun to acknowledge the need to provide their students with an opportunity to develop intercultural competence and global citizenship. IaH can be crucial in achieving these goals (Ibid.). *Global citizenship* entails awareness of oneself, others, and one's surroundings, committing to actions that benefit others across social, political, and environmental dimensions, both locally and globally (Leask, 2015, p.60). Scholars such as Leite (2022), De Wit (2020) and Knight (2003) posit that global citizenship can enable graduates to actively foster peaceful, secure, tolerant, and inclusive societies wherever they go. Meanwhile, *intercultural competence* has the potential to provide students with the skills to adapt to new cultural settings and 'creatively manage the dynamics of cultural differences and unfamiliarity, intergroup posture, and the accompanying stress' (Kim, 2002, p. 377).

However, despite the growing acknowledgement of the importance of IaH, Mestenhauser (2007) sparked a critical discourse about whether IaH is a means to an end or an end itself. Brandenburg and De Wit (2011) argue that IaH can serve as an instrument to achieve the goals of internationalisation, while Beelen, Boddington, Bruns, Glogar and Machado (2013) contend that IaH is a tool that can help students gain international and intercultural knowledge, skills, and attitudes, preparing them as professionals and citizens of the world.

Although IaH can be relevant for all students, Mestenhauser, in his position paper, argues that IaH remains an excellent idea yet to be implemented (Mestenhauser, 2007, p.13). Mestenhauser suggests that a 'systemic' approach may be necessary to implement IaH successfully. This can imply intentionally integrating IaH into the university's structures rather than adopting unfocused or fragmented initiatives or activities disguised as IaH (Ibid.). This view is shared by Beelen and Jones (2018), Beelen and Leask (2012), and Teekens (2007). The systems approach advocated by Mestenhauser is reflected in a more comprehensive approach to internationalisation, as cited by scholars such as Jones (2013) and Hudzik (2011). This perspective remains prevalent today and is relevant to this study, which aims to identify the strategies for systemically embedding a culture of IaH within Irish HEIs. The subsequent sub-section elucidates the evolving understanding of IaH globally.

2.3.2 Evolving Definitions of IaH

Given the historical background, the discussion surrounding internationalisation has evolved from a fragmented initiative focusing on non-mobile students to a more intentional effort to develop international and intercultural skills, knowledge, and attitudes for the benefit of all students through the curriculum. The development and evolution of the concept over the past two decades are illustrated in *Table 1* below.

<i>Table 1: Evolving Definition(s) of 'Internationalisation at Home' (IaH)</i>		
Year	Author	Definition
2000	Crowther, Joris, Otten, Nilsson, Teekens and Wachter	<i>"Any internationally related activity with the exception of outbound student and staff mobility". (p.6)</i>
2003	Paige	<i>"The provision by universities of international and intercultural learning opportunities for those students who for various reasons do not participate in study-abroad programs." (p.52)</i>
2003	Wachter	<i>"IaH is based not only beyond physical mobility but also encompasses teaching and learning in multicultural classrooms." (p.10)</i>
2007	Teekens	<i>"A new paradigm in the discourse on strategic institutional development of the internationalisation of higher education, with a strong emphasis on intercultural learning and teaching for all students, abroad and at home." (p.3)</i>
2011	Beelen and Leask	<i>"A set of instruments and activities 'at home' that focus on developing international and intercultural competencies in all students." (p.5)</i>
2015	Beelen and Jones	<i>"The purposeful integration of international and intercultural dimensions into the formal and informal curriculum for all students within domestic learning environments." (p.69)</i>

As shown in *Table 1*, the original definition of IaH was coined by Crowther *et al.* (2000) as an activity other than international mobility. However, this definition was criticised for its narrow focus. The definition was revised to include international and intercultural learning opportunities (Paige, 2003), teaching and learning in multicultural classrooms (Wächter, 2003), a conceptually coordinated and system-oriented approach for the non-mobile majority (Mestenhauser, 2003) and later, for all students (Teekens, 2007). In the second decade of the 21st century, Beelen and Leask (2011) clarified IaH as a set of instruments and activities for all students. This positioned IaH as complementary to mobility and a means rather than an aim (Ibid.). IaH was not presented as a didactic concept but included didactical elements that

could help students benefit from international and intercultural knowledge and skills (Beelen, 2013).

After IaH's inclusion in the European Commission's (EC) first comprehensive internationalisation strategy, the 'European Higher Education in the World', IaH gained widespread interest from many European institutions (EC, 2013). In response to the increasing interest in this area, Beelen and Jones (2015) revisited the definition of IaH, as illustrated in *Table 1*, emphasising the intentional process of integrating students in a domestic learning environment through formal and informal curricula. A key consideration of this widely cited definition is that the home university and the domestic location can be critical aspects of the curriculum delivery and include all students on the university campus (Beelen and Jones, 2015, p.8).

In their definition, *international* can encompass students and their cultural classifications, while *intercultural* may refer to student experiences (Harrison, 2015, p.414). While international students can bring diversity to the classrooms, they may not necessarily shape the experiences of domestic and international students due to language barriers, stereotypes, cultural differences, and academic backgrounds (Mak, Brown and Wadey, 2014; Jon, 2013; Halualani, 2008). Dinger (2018) suggests that the analogy between international and intercultural experiences may be similar to that of mobile students, where mobility does not necessarily lead to positive outcomes. However, thoughtful planning and interventions can develop intercultural competencies in students at home or abroad (Custer and Tuominen, 2017; Bhat and McMahon, 2016). Deardorff (2009) defines *intercultural competence* as appropriate behaviours and communication in different cultural situations, which includes a range of values, openness, tolerance and inclusivity. Students can develop these skills, knowledge and attitudes through IaH (Ibid.).

Despite the promising nature of IaH, Marginson and Sawir (2011) observe that more needs to be done to realise its full potential. One of the main aims of IaH is fostering intercultural competence, which is increasingly being recognised as a crucial graduate attribute in many universities (Coelen, 2024; Hang and Zhang, 2023; Gregersen-Hermans, 2021; Ji, 2020). This attribute can be developed through IaH, as evidenced by various studies (Ibid.). *Graduate attributes* refer to the 'qualities, skills and understanding a university community agrees its students should acquire during their time with the institution and, consequently, shape their future contributions as professionals and citizens' (Bowden, Hart, King, Trigwell and Watts, 2000, p.1).

In many European HEIs, developing international and intercultural competence as a graduate attribute is still relevant today. This has expanded to discussions around global citizenship encompassing these competencies that can be developed through IaH. Moreover, the discourse surrounding this competency has expanded to include other discussions and themes that are now being explored with great interest. This includes debates on decolonising the curriculum in the global south, particularly in some African institutions focusing on the need for preserving local and indigenous knowledge(s) and challenging the dominant Western paradigms in the curriculum (Marginson and Xu, 2023; Maringe, 2023; Heleta and Chasi, 2022; Marginson, 2020; Harvey and Russel-Mundine, 2018 and Le Grange, 2016). This is due to greater awareness and a growing need for creating an inclusive curriculum that can represent different ways of being and the need for redefining the role of universities as a global good (Ibid.). Other emerging themes, such as equality, diversity, and inclusion and sustainability, have been elucidated in the discussion *Chapter 6*. The ensuing sub-section presents the rationale for higher education institutions (HEIs) engaging in IaH.

2.4 Rationale for IaH

In order to ascertain the rationale for IaH, the literature review has been informed by scholarly research, grey literature around IaH and the latest International Association of Universities (IAU) Global (2024) and European Association for International Education (EAIE) Barometer (2024) surveys that demonstrate the emerging trends driving the international higher education sector. Globally, the International Association of Universities (IAU) releases its international education trend surveys, which have had six iterations to date. The present IAU Global Survey (2024) covered 722 HEIs across 110 countries, with the European region being the most heavily represented (Marinoni and Cardona, 2024, p. 29).

A few days before the IAU survey, one of the leading higher education associations in Europe- the European Association for International Education (EAIE) released its European Higher Education Area (EHEA) wide survey to understand the trends shaping the development of internationalisation in European HEIs. There have been three survey iterations to date. The EAIE Barometer (2024) has been the largest so far, with 2917 respondents from 46 European Higher Education Area (EHEA) countries. Many survey outcomes are relevant to this study and have been captured across various arguments throughout the literature review.

This sub-section outlines several reasons that could have led institutions to increasingly focus on IaH practices in the current landscape. These rationales include the influence of globalisation, the need for the development of intercultural competence and critical thinking skills, the impact on teaching and learning practices, equity considerations in internationalisation experiences, employability prospects for students, and lastly, IaH's contribution to institutional distinctiveness (Beelen, 2023; De Wit *et al.*, 2021, 2020, 2015; Kirk, Newstead, Gann and Rounsaville, 2018; Whitsed & Green, 2016; Leask, 2015, 2012, 2005; De Wit and Leask, 2015; Jones and Killick, 2013; Clifford, 2013; Andrew, 2012; Hudzik and McCarthy, 2012; Hénard, Diamond and Roseveare, 2012; Hudzik, 2011; Clifford and Montgomery, 2011; Guo and Chase, 2011; Svensson and Wihlborg 2010; De Wit, 2010; Leask and Beelen, 2009; Parkes and Griffiths, 2009; Kreber, 2009; Hyland, Trahar, Anderson and Dickens, 2008 and Hellsten, 2007).

2.4.1 Impact of Globalisation

The first rationale is the growing influence of globalisation on internationalisation for higher education (IoHE) (De Wit and Merckx, 2022; Beelen, 2023, 2018, 2015; Leask, 2015). Globalisation has created an opportunity for the free movement of goods, capital, people, cultures and languages across borders (Dewey, 2007; Knight, 2003; Marginson, 1999). Although globalisation has intensified market-based economies, it has also increased diversity (Malek, 2023; McMahon, 2011; and Dogancay-Aktuna, 2005). This diversity is now a defining characteristic of many HEIs globally, including Ireland (DFHERIS, 2024). The growing diversity provides a unique opportunity for students from various cultures to interact and work together harmoniously, enabling them to develop a broad mindset and embrace pluriform perspectives (Zhou, 2022; Ruscio, Korey and Birck, 2015).

Additionally, this diversity is reflected in the societies in which the students live and work, cultivating a preference by employers for students equipped with intercultural competencies and skills to help them tackle shared local and global challenges (Li, and Xue, 2023; Jones, 2017; Temmerman, 2016; Hovland, 2014; European Commission, 2014). As such, IaH has the potential to facilitate the internationalisation of students' experiences and the development of intercultural competencies through the curriculum (Jones, 2017; Killick, 2017; Harrison, 2015; Olson, Evans and Shoenberg, 2007 and Jones and Killick, 2007). This can prepare students as citizens for the challenges of a globalised world and can offer a valuable opportunity for the mutual benefit of both local and international students and staff (Eisenclas and Trevaskes, 2003, p.2). The importance of this stance has been echoed by

several reports and scholars in the field (DFHERIS, 2024; Whitsed, Cassol, Leask, Morosini, Elsner and Nguyen, 2024; Li and Xue, 2023; Beelen, 2023; Malek, 2024; Harrison, 2015; Leask, 2015 and Beelen and Jones, 2015).

The IAU Global Survey (2024) confirms that globalisation is one of the critical drivers for IoHE, which can include IaH, due to increasing diversity and the emphasis on the need to create global citizens (p.197). The survey also found that approximately 87% of institutions globally, consider the growing diversity when developing their internationalisation policy (p.198). This trend is similarly reflected in other surveys, such as the EUA Trends survey (88%) and the EAIE Barometer Survey conducted in 2024 (89%).

2.4.2 Development of Intercultural Competence and Critical Thinking Skills

In addition to the impact of globalisation, the literature also suggests the development of intercultural competencies and critical thinking skills as another important rationale for IaH (UUKi, 2024; Barbosa, Santos and Prado-Meza, 2020; Robson, 2017; Baldassar and McKenzie, 2016 and Rossini, Rincón and Rutkowski, 2015). *Intercultural competencies* refer to the ability to interact meaningfully with people from diverse backgrounds (Deardorff and Jones, 2009, p.15), while *critical thinking* involves independent reflection and logical reasoning (Vandermensbrugge, 2004, p.419).

Many scholars have emphasised the presence of international students in classrooms as a means of nurturing the development of intercultural competencies and critical thinking skills (Ryan, 2020; Weimer, Hoffman and Silvonon, 2019; Guimarães, Mendes, Rodrigues, dos Santos Paiva and Finardi, 2019; Almeida, Robson, Morosini and Baranzeli, 2019; Panajoti, 2019; Nghia, Giang and Quyen, 2019; Harrison, 2016, 2015; Coelen, 2015; Hudzik, 2015; Jones and Killick, 2013; Henard *et al.*, 2012; Clifford and Montgomery, 2011; Hawanini, 2011; Leask, 2011; Eisenchlas, and Trevaskes, 2003; Qiang, 2003; and Dlaska, 2000). Through intentional interventions, domestic and international students can learn to collaborate and adapt to each other's cultures, beliefs, systems, and styles (Ibid.). Such efforts can lay the foundation for 'culture versatility' (Eisenchlas and Trevaskes, 2003, p.2) and 'social integration' of students from diverse backgrounds (Weimer, Hoffman and Silvonon, 2019, p.31), thereby potentially enhancing their skills. While Beelen and Jones (2015) argue that international students may not necessarily be needed to develop intercultural and critical thinking skills, they acknowledge that having them on campus can be advantageous (p.64). However, the process may need to be intentional (Ibid.).

Moreover, Soria and Troisi (2014) make an interesting observation in their study that students' participation in activities such as enrolling in international academic coursework, studying a curriculum with an international dimension, and interacting with international students on campus can lead to the development of intercultural and critical thinking skills, similar to a traditional study abroad experience (p.273). This perspective is further validated by Souto-Otero, Gehlke, Basna, Dóka, Endrodi, Favero, Humburg, Jantoš, Key, Oberheidt and Stiburek (2019) in their Erasmus+ Higher Education Impact Study (EU, 2019), where they acknowledge that students who do not participate in mobility experiences can still benefit from IaH by developing intercultural competencies and critical thinking skills through their domestic curriculum (p.179).

Furthermore, according to the EAIE Barometer (2024), European HEIs increasingly recognise the importance of enhancing intercultural competencies and critical thinking skills by strengthening the international and intercultural content of the curriculum (p.58). The IAU Global Survey (2024), as indicated in *Figure 2* below, also reveals that 78% of the HEIs globally acknowledge that increasing global, international and intercultural knowledge, skills and competencies for students and staff, as well as enhancing the internationalisation of the curriculum at home, as the prime benefits for their institutions engaging in internationalisation (p.64). This trend is also reflected in European HEIs, with 77% considering these benefits significant (Ibid.).

2.4.3 Impact on Teaching and Learning (T&L) Practices

Thirdly, growing diversity in many European HEIs could have positively impacted teaching and learning practices (Weissova, 2021; McCarthy, 2019; Green and Mertova, 2016; Jones and Killick, 2007; Harbon, 2003). This can be attributed to multiple perspectives in the classroom, which can provide opportunities for intercultural encounters and leverage classroom diversity (Ibid.). In order to better optimise the classroom learning experience, academic staff may need to improve their skills in managing multicultural classrooms through continuous professional development (CPD) (Ibid.). The CPD that improves teaching and learning experiences can be one of the key rationales for universities pursuing IaH (Weissova, 2021; Huerta-Jimenez and Sanchez, 2018; Leask, 2015).

Improved teaching and learning practices are also reported as a visible outcome of internationalisation in the IAU 6th Global Survey (2024), showcased in *Figure 3*, presented below. This survey highlighted that improved quality of teaching and learning through internationalisation has consistently been one of the top priorities for most HEIs in almost all iterations.

**Figure 3: Impact of Internationalisation on Teaching and Learning
(IAU 6th Global Survey, 2024, p.66)**

Rank	2 nd Global Survey	3 rd Global Survey	4 th Global Survey	5 th Global Survey	6 th Global Survey
1	More internationally orientated student and staff	Increased international awareness of students	Increased international awareness of/deeper engagement with global issues by students	Enhanced international cooperation and capacity building	Enhanced international cooperation and capacity building
2	Improved academic quality	Strengthened research and knowledge production	Improved quality of teaching and learning	Improved quality of teaching and learning	Increased global, international and intercultural knowledge, skills and competences for both students and staff
3	Strengthened research and knowledge production	Enhanced international cooperation and solidarity	Enhanced international cooperation and capacity building	Several different benefits were identified as third most important	Improved quality of teaching and learning

2.4.4 Equity Considerations in Internationalisation Experiences

Fourthly, equity in internationalisation experiences can be an important consideration for IaH. According to Ferencz, I. and Rumbley (2022), De Wit and Jones (2021) and Almeida *et al.* (2019), IaH appears capable of being equitable as it targets all students in a domestic learning environment (p.201). This perspective is echoed by previous studies conducted by Leask (2016), Hudzik (2015), Harrison (2015), Agnew and Kahn (2014), Denson and Bowman (2013), and Sawir (2013). Notably, offering internationalised experiences at the

home institution can help develop intercultural competencies in students, enhancing their ability to contribute to a globalised world (Ibid.).

The IAU global survey (2024) highlights that equity considerations such as 'limited inclusivity' and 'difficulty to integrate with other institutional priorities such as diversity, equity and inclusion and sustainability' are the top two of the four most significant institutional risks associated with internationalisation, with 57% of the HEIs globally and 39% in Europe reporting this concern (p.67), as illustrated in *Figure 4* below. Additionally, promoting equity is one of the main future concerns for staff working in HE globally (p.227). IaH can be a viable solution to mitigate this risk and offer international and intercultural experiences to a diverse student body.

**Figure 4: Most Significant Potential Risks of Internationalisation
(IAU 6th Global Survey, 2024, p.67)**

2.4.5 Employability Prospects for Students

Fifthly, in terms of employability prospects for students, several studies (UUKi, 2024; Alexiadou, Kefala and Rönnerberg 2023; Heffernan, Morrison, Magne, Payne and Cotton, 2019; Nghia *et al.*, 2019; Watkins and Smith, 2018; Beelen and Jones, 2015; Jones, 2014, 2013; Crossman and Clarke, 2010; Black and Duhon, 2006) suggest internationalised teaching and learning experiences, such as those offered by IaH, can help a range of employability skills. These include soft skills, intercultural competencies, domain-specific knowledge, and transversal skills (EU, 2019, p.86). Transversal skills, as defined by the European Commission (2017), enable complex information management, address global challenges,

involve critical and creative thinking, multidisciplinary teamwork, and effective and inclusive communication. The skills encompass communication, leadership, teamwork, reflexivity, ethical, digital and systems thinking skills (OECD, 2023; UNESCO, n.d.), also known as '21st-century skills' or 'soft skills' (OECD Future of Education and Skills 2030, 2023; WEF Future of Jobs, 2025, 2023, 2020, 2018, 2016; Haug and Jacobs, 2023; Guérin and Beelen, 2022; Wimpenny, Finardi, Orsini-Jones and Jacobs, 2022 and Klein, 2021; Slotte and Stadius, 2019 and Hidden Competences, 2014 EU, 2014). These skills have become increasingly important for many employers due to the fast-paced and ever-changing political, economic, social, environmental, and technological environments surrounding organisations today (Price, 2024; Simões and Sangiamchit, 2023; Watkins and Smith, 2018; Meng, Zhu and Cao, 2017; De Wit and Hunter, 2015).

Leask (2015) posits that Intercultural competence, critical thinking, problem-solving, and transversal skills can be developed through an internationalised curriculum or IaH (p.20). These skills can prepare students for global professions and careers, making them valuable global citizens (Ibid.). The Erasmus Impact Study (European Commission, 2014) reports that approximately 92% of employers seek candidates with transversal skills (p.14). The last available iteration of this study (European Commission, 2019) reveals that 93% of the HEIs agree on the positive impacts of Erasmus strategic partnerships in developing transversal skills through internationalising the curriculum at home (p.178), as depicted in [Figure 5](#) below.

Figure 5: Developing Transversal Skills - Erasmus Impact Study
(European Commission, 2019, p.178)

2.4.6 Contribution to Institutional Distinctiveness

Lastly, the contribution of IaH to the distinctiveness of an HEI can be considerable. While many universities globally prioritise recruiting international students for financial gain, research suggests that IaH could instead be an academic gain as it can offer students an invaluable internationalised learning experience during their journey at the institution (Pawar, 2024; Alexiadou and Rönnerberg, 2023; Cheung, 2022; Manning and Marku, 2021; Wikström-Grotell and Hyde-Clarke, 2019; Slotte and Stadius, 2019; Almeida *et al.*, 2019; Naghdi, and Johnson, 2016; Quintal and Phau, 2014; Jones and Killick, 2013; Jones, 2009). This experience can positively impact student retention, reputation, soft power and alumni engagement, ultimately attracting more students to the institution and generating revenue (Ibid.).

In addition to the positive impact on student retention and revenue, IaH has the potential to enhance research output by facilitating improved international collaborations that enhance their institutional reputation and ranking (Manning and Marku, 2021; Ryan, 2020; Hazelkorn, 2015, 2009; Leask, 2015, 2011; Hudzik, 2015; Svensson & Wihlborg, 2010; Kreber, 2009).

As a result, IaH can be relevant to different stakeholders, including leadership, staff, students, and the institution as a whole, contributing to the distinctiveness of the HEI (Manning and Marku, 2021; Ryan, 2020; Sebea, 2018; Hudzik, 2015).

Upon examining the literature, it becomes evident that institutions pursue IaH for various reasons, with recent surveys highlighting its growing popularity. The following sub-section outlines the factors that can help facilitate the implementation of IaH at the institutional level.

2.5 Enablers of IaH

The preceding sub-section explained the rationale for many HEIs pursuing IaH. This sub-section adumbrates some key enablers facilitating the embedding a culture of IaH globally. These enablers comprise an internationalised curriculum, virtual internationalisation, engaged academic staff and students, institutional commitment and support, and communities of practice.

2.5.1 Internationalisation of the Curriculum (IoC)

One of the critical aspects of IaH can be a curriculum that shapes students' learning experiences in the home institution (Sierra-Huedo, Bruton, and Fernández, 2022; Teekens, 2007; Otten, 2003). This involves both the content and delivery methods used (Ibid.). According to Paige (2005), the curriculum has the potential to provide international and intercultural knowledge and skills. This can be achieved through what is known as an 'internationalised curriculum (IoC),' first defined by Bremer and Van der Wende (1995) as emphasising international content in curricula (p.10).

However, the OECD revised the above definition in 1996 by adding the 'form' of internationalised curricula (p.6), which caused some confusion due to its similarity with Bremer and Van der Wende's (1995) definition. Four years later, Nilsson (2000) defined an internationalised curriculum that may equip 'students with international and intercultural knowledge and abilities to prepare them to perform professionally, socially, and emotionally in an international and multicultural context' (p.22). Leask (2009) expanded on this definition by including a holistic view of teaching and learning practices, assessment, and support services. However, Leask (2015) later refocused the definition of IoC on 'learning outcomes', emphasising the 'global' aspect, which may likely reflect the growing influence of globalisation in higher education.

According to Leask,

"Internationalisation of the Curriculum is the incorporation of international, intercultural and/or global dimensions into the content of the curriculum as well as the learning outcomes, assessment tasks, teaching methods and support services of a program of study"
(Leask, 2015, p.9).

Leask's (2015) definition of IoC gained widespread recognition, particularly in Australia, and is frequently used interchangeably with the IaH definition provided by Beelen and Jones (2015). While the two concepts exhibit similar characteristics, IaH focuses on the domestic curriculum, whereas IoC encompasses both the domestic curriculum and curriculum abroad (Ibid.). Recently, there has been a noticeable trend towards merging the two terms into 'internationalisation of the home curriculum' or 'internationalisation of the curriculum at home (IoCaH)' (Eftekhari, Yousefzadeh and Coelen, 2025; Jones, Reiffenrath, Haug and Louw, 2023 and Trinh, 2019). For this research study, the term 'IaH,' as delineated by Beelen and Jones (2015), has been adopted as a point of departure, given that this study focuses on internationalisation within the domestic learning environment.

When considering IaH from a curriculum standpoint, Leask (2015) distinguishes between three types of curricula: formal, informal and hidden. The *formal curriculum* can refer to the planned schedule and activities students must complete as part of their degree programme, including teaching, learning and assessment (p.7). Conversely, the *informal curriculum* may not be assessed and includes learning from support services and extracurricular activities such as formal mentoring programs, peer-assisted study sessions, volunteering, and social events (Ibid.). Finally, the *hidden curriculum* can be implicit and unintended messages that may be a part of formal and informal curricula (Ibid.). This can include aspects such as textbook selection and whose knowledge is emphasised (Ibid.).

The foundational underpinnings of these concepts can be found in the work of scholars such as Nilsson (2003) and Teekens (2003) and further developed by Leask (2015, 2009). According to Nilsson (2003) and Teekens (2003), the internationalised formal curriculum can promote cognitive and attitudinal growth by encouraging students to engage with diverse perspectives and cultures. By achieving these objectives, students can become more tolerant and accept other cultures and their own (Ibid.). However, Harrison (2015) suggests that cultural diversity may not naturally lead to these outcomes. Instead, intentional efforts

may be necessary to achieve intercultural competencies and an international outlook (Ibid.). De La Garza (2021) also argues that incorporating international perspectives into the formal curriculum can move beyond tokenism and promote a more diverse knowledge base. Sierra-Huedo *et al.* (2022) and McCarthy and Butler (2019) concur that integrating international perspectives into the home curriculum may need to be purposeful and have the potential to foster cultural sensitivity and a commitment to social equity, tolerance, and justice (p.10).

The IAU Global Survey (2024) illustrates several global approaches to implementing IaH through the formal curriculum, as shown in *Figure 6* below.

As depicted in *Figure 6*, there has been a growing trend towards incorporating 'online activities that develop international perspectives of students at home' globally (70%). Additionally, other approaches such as 'integration of international/intercultural dimensions into learning outcomes for courses and programs, leveraging the experience/expertise of international staff to enrich the learning experience, professional development for professors to enhance their ability to integrate international/intercultural dimensions into teaching, community engagement through activities like inviting representatives of local cultural and/or linguistically diverse groups to participate in co-curricular activities or service learning projects focused on working with such groups and integrating the experience/expertise of international students to enrich the learning experience,' were deemed equally significant, garnering around 50% of the responses.

Across Europe, when internationalising the formal curricula, an increasing number of HEIs recognise the value of international staff, with 59% reporting that they leverage their expertise. Additionally, 58% of the respondents emphasised the importance of incorporating international and intercultural elements into learning outcomes. Other important factors include integrating the knowledge and experience of international students, providing professional development for professors, and offering courses in non-local languages, all of which received over 55% agreement from respondents.

While formal curricula are often the focus of literature and surveys, many scholars argue that informal and hidden curricula are also essential components shaping the learning experience of students within an institution (Beelen, 2023; Sierra-Huedo *et al.*, 2022; McCarthy and McCarthy, 2019; Beelen and Jones, 2018, 2015; Yang, 2022 and Leask, 2015, 2009). The informal curriculum can comprise activities that promote the culture, festivals, and cuisine of other nations, global spaces on campus where domestic and international students can interact, peer or buddy programmes, engagement with the local community and organisations, connections with alumni based abroad and visiting campus, organising international conferences or weeks, international campaigns such as human rights, SDGs on campus, and refugee and asylum seekers inclusion through universities of sanctuary initiatives, to name a few (De Wit and Deca, 2020; Universities UK, 2021; Ergin, De Wit and Leask, 2019; Leask, 2015, 2009; Teekens, 2005 and Otten, 2003). These initiatives strive to cultivate a sense of cultural awareness, enhance intercultural competence amongst students and staff, promote internationalisation on campus, and highlight the social responsibility of

universities (Sierra-Heudo, 2022; Romero and Lalueza, 2019; Rubin Oliveira and Wielewicki, 2019; Knight 2008, 2006 and Otten, 2003).

The IAU Global Survey (2024), presented in *Figure 7* below, highlights the growing popularity of IaH through informal curricula. Globally, 'interaction with students in other countries using virtual internationalisation' reigns supreme, with 93% of institutions adopting this approach. Other activities, such as 'events that provide international/intercultural experiences on campus or in the local community,' are equally popular at 93%. In Europe, 64% of HEIs also support this trend. Conversely, 'structured learning programs such as intercultural service-learning projects' are less common across all institutions but still garner support from 66% of respondents. The findings indicate a shift towards virtual internationalisation experiences, which mirrors the top approach to internationalising the formal curriculum.

Lastly, the 'invisible' or 'unwritten' curriculum can impact the international campus experience, according to Kentli (2009, p.83). This can encompass the norms, beliefs, values, intergroup relations, expectations and behaviours that affect the socialisation process embedded within the university's practices, structures, culture and interactions (Yang, 2022; Gregersen-Hermans, 2017; Leask, 2015, 2009). These elements can be tacit, sometimes resulting in unintentional communication between staff and students (Ibid.). The hidden curriculum in practice may include:

"Incidental lessons that are learned about power and authority, what and whose knowledge is valued and what and whose knowledge is not valued, from such things as which textbook and references are used and the way that in-class and out-of-class activities are organised"
(Leask, 2009, p.207)

Other examples such as:

"All international students are required to complete cross-cultural skills training prior to the commencement of classes, but the same is not required of domestic or home students. Is this because domestic students have the required skills? Or perhaps these skills are not important for domestic students because it is up to international students to 'fit in' and make adjustments? Are those the intended messages?"
(Leask, 2022, p.46)

Consequently, the pedagogical approach adopted can significantly impact students' worldviews, with both positive or negative outcomes, intended or otherwise (Ibid.). Furthermore, Gregersen- Hermans (2017) highlights the 'normative character' of the hidden curriculum, which can influence students' implicit learning and development of intercultural competence (p.3). Recognising the existence of the hidden curriculum when practising IaH can help in overcoming biases and create a welcoming environment where diverse students can learn, interact, grow, and develop more purposefully (Below, 2023; Leask, 2022; Reiffenrath and Thielsch, 2022; Pharaoh and Li, 2022; Paduretu, Munteanu and Capraru, 2020 and Hartzell, 2019). *Appendix A* presents some examples of IaH in practice across countries.

2.5.2 Virtual Internationalisation Experiences

Interestingly, there has been a considerable rise in momentum in using digital technologies or virtual mediums to facilitate internationalisation in teaching and learning. Guimarães *et al.* (2019), Weimer *et al.* (2019), Nghia *et al.* (2019), and Almeida *et al.* (2019) have all noted the potential of virtual internationalisation that can be possible through IaH. This interest has been further intensified by recent global events, such as COVID-19, which may have coerced many universities globally to adopt virtual internationalisation initiatives due to travel restrictions (Hackett, Janssen, Beach, Perreault, Beelen and van Tartwijk, 2023; Guimarães and Finardi, 2023; Piplani-Kapur and Kirloskar, 2023; Yeravdekar and Piplani-Kapur, 2022; Rubin, Wimpenny, Portillo, Besana, Haug, Leibowitz, Succi, Szeles and O'Brien, 2022; Ikeda, 2022; Vasquez and Ramos, 2022).

Examples of such initiatives include Virtual Exchanges (VE) and Collaborative Online International Learning (COIL) (Ibid.). While VE can be a broad umbrella term encompassing any online course/internship at home or abroad, COIL enables academic staff from two or more countries to co-design and implement a curriculum through digital platforms, facilitating remote participation by students from diverse locations (Hackett, Dawson, Janssen and van Tartwijk, 2024). The EAIE Barometer Survey (2024) highlights the importance of virtual internationalisation initiatives, demonstrating that 58% of European HEIs view it as increasingly becoming important (p.13), as illustrated in [Figure 8](#) below.

Figure 8: Virtual Internationalisation as a Pressing Priority for European HEIs (EAIE Barometer, 2024, p. 58)

	More attention	Continued level of attention as now	Less attention	Unsure	Does not apply to my institution
Crisis preparedness/management	42%	43%	5%	10%	1%
Data/knowledge security	42%	43%	4%	10%	1%
Digitalisation of administrative tasks	56%	35%	3%	5%	0%
Environmental sustainability and climate action	42%	37%	4%	6%	1%
Inclusion and diversity	50%	42%	3%	5%	0%
International development and capacity building projects	50%	38%	4%	8%	1%
Local/regional community engagement and/or development	38%	46%	5%	10%	2%
Partnerships and networks	50%	46%	2%	2%	0%
Recruiting international talent (students/staff)	52%	33%	7%	6%	2%
Research collaborations and outputs	47%	43%	3%	7%	1%
Strengthening international/intercultural content of the curriculum	65%	29%	3%	3%	0%
Student/staff mobility	51%	45%	2%	2%	0%
Student/staff well-being	57%	38%	2%	3%	0%
Virtual internationalisation activities (COIL, virtual exchange, etc)	58%	28%	6%	7%	1%

2.5.3 Engaged Academic Staff

Secondly, the extant literature indicates that engaging academic staff can play a significant role in facilitating the implementation of IaH (Beelen, 2023; DeWit, 2021; Beelen and Jones, 2018, 2015; Leask, 2015). While traditional views have placed the responsibility of IaH on the international office, many studies suggest that academics are one of the primary drivers of IaH through the formal curricula (Van den Hende, Whitsed and Coelen, 2023, 2022; Beelen, 2023; Renfors, 2021; Leask, 2021, 2015; Annala, Lindén, Mäkinen, and Henriksson, 2021; Ryan, 2020, Broström, Feldmann and Kaulio, 2019, Beelen and Leask, 2009, Beelen, 2007 and Van der Wende, 1997). They further argue that the academic staff have the potential to understand the professional requirements of their disciplines best and respond to the emerging opportunities and challenges presented by globalisation (Ibid.). As Beelen and

Jones (2010) note, 'only academic staff can design curricula to develop interculturally competent graduates for life as global citizens and professionals' (p.4).

When implementing IaH, an engaged academic staff is intended to move beyond international examples in traditional disciplines and teach students to 'engage in interdisciplinary and integrative thinking' (Mestenhauser, 1998, p.23). This can require a comprehensive understanding of each aspect of the curricula, the accumulated whole, and how it enhances international and intercultural dimensions of students' 'knowledge, skills, and attitude' (Beelen and Leask, 2010, p.7). To accomplish this, staff may need to be 'critically self-reflective,' recognising their own biases and those of their traditional disciplines (Ibid.).

Furthermore, Teekens (in Beelen, 2007) suggests that staff may need to possess other competencies, such as the ability to teach in English, which is frequently a second language in most European countries, excluding Ireland and Malta. However, it can be helpful if the staff is conversant with academic traditions across cultures, the expectations of a diverse student body, the awareness that students may not necessarily engage even if they speak the language proficiently, cultural understanding even when engaging virtually, and the professional requirements of their discipline in different countries (Ibid.). Leask (2015, 2009) emphasises that staff can succeed if they become lifelong intercultural learners and possess personal attitudes that make them flexible and approachable to all students.

As a result, an academic staff has the potential to enable IaH more effectively (Ibid.). Beelen (2023); Van den Hende *et al.* (2022); Annala, Lindén, Mäkinen, and Henriksson (2021); Ryan (2020); Beelen and Jones (2018, 2015); Leask (2015, 2009); Agnew (2013); Beelen and Leask (2010) and Clifford (2009) concur that academics have one of the key roles to play in the successful integration of IaH in the formal curricula (Ibid.). The importance of academic staff engagement is also highlighted in the EAIE Barometer (2024), which identifies academics as one of the key drivers of this process (p.46).

2.5.4 Institutional Commitment and Support

Besides the engagement of academic staff in enabling IaH, scholars such as Van den Hende *et al.* (2023, 2022), Ryan (2020), and Oliver and Hyun (2009) underscore the influential role of institutional commitment and support in implementing IaH. This could encompass a well-defined and explicit strategy on IaH in the institutional plan, mechanisms that facilitate various departments within the institution to effectively support implementation through

continuous professional development (CPD), and rewards and recognitions for showcasing best practices (Ibid.).

Bergnut (2007) posits that explicitly emphasising IaH in a university's strategy can enable different departments in the institution to take responsibility for management and governance. This can include the international office, which facilitates integration opportunities for both domestic and international students and staff, as well as student unions, libraries with resources in English, and physical and digital infrastructure that supports and enhances the campus experience for all students to mention a few (Deca and De Wit, 2020). However, according to Sierra-Huedo (2022), the challenges in implementing IaH can be unique to institutions. They may require institutions to develop a shared understanding of IaH and its desired outcomes and establish a dedicated governance and implementation team within the university (p.250).

Furthermore, the creation of language and transversal schools within an institution can catalyse an international and intercultural campus (Teekens, 2007; Leask, 2007; Mestenhauser, 2007, 2003; Paige, 2005; Wachter, 2003 and Crowther *et al.*, 2003, 2000). As Cartwright (2015) highlights, an intercultural campus can foster collaboration and support individuals from diverse backgrounds to achieve their goals harmoniously (p.381). The EAIE Barometer (2024), illustrated in *Figure 9* below, emphasises the importance of a clear strategy and institutional support as the driving forces behind internationalisation in European HEIs.

Moreover, it may be necessary to establish support mechanisms to aid in implementing IaH. These mechanisms could include Continuous Professional Development (CPD), which can equip staff with the skills to manage diverse classrooms and international campus environments (Puck, Kittler and Wright, 2008; Radzevičienė, 2007 Legge, 2005). Beelen (2023); Van den Hende *et al.* (2023, 2022); Jones *et al.* (2022); Bradford, Guzmán, and Trujillo (2017); Leask (2015); Crosling *et al.* (2008); Pausits and Pellet (2007) and Middlehurst (2007) posit that staff may need to develop international and intercultural competencies to support the needs of diverse student populations better. However, this can only be achieved with adequate institutional support through HR policies and funding (Ibid.). The EAIE Barometer (2024) reports that approximately 85% of respondents are interested in CPD to improve their ability to implement IaH more effectively (p.33).

Interestingly, the IAU Global Survey (2024) also supports this, with staff training in international, intercultural, and global competencies being the predominant future priority in internationalisation at most HEIs globally, at 61% (academic and administrative staff), illustrated in *Figure 10*, presented below (p.211). This priority supersedes the need to internationalise and interculturalise the curriculum at home for all students, which is 40%

(p.211). For the European region, no specific priority emerges, as highlighted in both surveys. However, the top three priorities for most European HEIs include 'increasing the number of incoming degree-seeking international students' (37%), 'internationalisation and interculturalisation of the curriculum at home for all students' (35%), and 'academic staff training in international, intercultural and global competencies' (34%) (IAU Global Survey, p.212).

While staff CPD can be viewed as a prime priority, it may be necessary to implement mechanisms that reward and recognise good practices to embed IaH into the institutional culture (Robson, Almeida and Schartner, 2018; Robson, 2015; Haigh, 2014; Jones, 2013;

Beelen and Leask, 2010). However, as Robson *et al.* (2018) note, designing effective reward mechanisms can be challenging in the case of IaH (p.27). This can be due to inadequate metrics to assess performance (Ibid.). In order to be successful, clear metrics need to be embedded in institutional promotion processes and funded through adequate resources (Ibid.). Some examples can include the creation of an 'IoC fund' by Malaspina University-College in Canada, which incentivises staff to incorporate international and intercultural elements in teaching and learning (Jenkins-Deas, 2009, p.119). Ultimately, a clear and explicit institutional strategy on IaH, alongside support mechanisms through CPD and rewarding good IaH practices, can enable the effective implementation of IaH.

2.5.5 Communities of Practice (CoPs)

Fourthly, Van den Hende *et al.* (2023, 2022), Lillis (2015) and Scott (2003) observe that IaH can be facilitated through organisational transformation. One of the approaches for this transformation can be encouraging and sharing good practices (Ibid.). Engaging in cross-disciplinary 'Communities of Practice (CoP)' (Wenger, 1998, p.4) is suggested by Ryan (2020), Kelly and Brennan (2015), Barth and Reickmann (2012) and Beelen and Leask (2010) as a way to embrace transformation and change. CoPs have the potential to foster a collaborative and systematic curriculum change process by involving different stakeholders and acting as a bridge for these stakeholder networks within an HEI (Kezar and Eckel, 2002; Morey, 2000). The CoP can catalyse collaboration between top-down and bottom-up processes, encouraging evolutionary changes in the curricula (Takagi, 2015; Barnett, 2011; Trondal, 2010). This can build a support system for staff, particularly during curriculum and organisational changes, in harmony (Roberts, 2015; Tummons, 2012; Montgomery, 2010; Graven and Lerman, 2003).

Several studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of CoPs in internationalising curricula at home. For instance, in Ireland, Ryan, Faulkner, Dillane, and Flood (2022) investigated the lecturer's engagement with IoC through a CoP at TU Dublin. This may have enabled TU Dublin lecturers to reflect on and tackle challenges while implementing IoC to improve teaching and learning practices (p.894). In Australia, Green and Whitsed (2013) and Leask (2011) established CoPs for the 'Internationalisation of the Curriculum in Action' project with academic staff. This initiative aimed to enhance interdisciplinary understanding while implementing IoC and encouraged participants to reflect on their role as facilitators. The CoPs have since expanded to other disciplines, and experts from these CoPs are mentoring new CoPs in different HEIs in Australia (p.161).

Moreover, with increased accessibility of technology, particularly after the COVID-19 pandemic, there are now several CoPs in action. These include the World Council on Intercultural and Global Competence (ICC Global, n.d.), the European Hub for Virtual Exchange and Collaborative Online International Learning, the International Practitioner Network (Advance HE, n.d.), and the Research with International Students Network (RISE, n.d.) to name a few. As a result, these examples demonstrate how CoP can stimulate awareness about IaH at both academic and institutional-wide levels, scaffolding change in teaching and learning practices (Ryan *et al.*, 2022, p. 882).

2.5.6 Engaged Students

In addition to the CoPs, engaging students in the IaH process can be crucial, and one way to achieve this is through 'co-creating curricula' (Lubicz-Nawrocka, 2020, p.245). Co-creation involves active participation from both students and staff in developing a learning experience (Ibid.). Traditionally, academic staff have taken the lead in curriculum development, but research reveals that involving students can improve teaching and learning practices (Hughes, Michener, Mohamed and McDuff, 2019; Willis and Gregory, 2016; Roberts, 2015; McCulloch, 2009; Kell and Deursen, 2002; Montero-Sieburth, 1992). This approach can sometimes be referred to as 'students as partners' (Healey, Flint, and Harrington, 2016; Levy, Little, and Whelan, 2011) or 'co-producers' (McCulloch, 2009) or 'co-constructors' (Fraser and Bosanquet, 2006).

These terms reflect a shift in ideology from a traditional 'student-faculty relationship' to a more balanced partnership (Hughes, Michener, Mohamed and McDuff, 2019, p.3). Rather than the faculty solely producing knowledge for the students to consume, they work together to construct knowledge (Hughes *et al.*, 2019). This approach is gaining traction in some universities across Australia, Europe, the US and the UK (Hughes, Michener, Mohamed and McDuff, 2019; Willis and Gregory, 2016; Bovill, 2013; McCulloch, 2009).

The literature on co-creating curricula provides some examples of positive outcomes from this initiative. For instance, Mihans II, Long, and Felten (2008) found that involving students in module design and development committees can be effective. Similarly, Rock, Foster and Lamb (2015) revealed that students acting as reviewers of the existing modules can lead to improvements. Other studies suggest that students can act as module designers at the ideation stage (Woolmer, Sneddon, Curry, Hill, Fehertavi, Longbone and Wallace, 2016) or collaborate during module delivery (Bovill, 2019, 2013 and Cook-Sather, Bovill and Felten, 2014). Scholars such as Lubicz- Nawrocka and Bovill (2023), Bovill (2019), Hughes,

Michener, Mohamed and McDuff (2019), Willis and Gregory (2016) and McCulloch (2009) agree that involving students as co-creators in the curriculum change process can make the HE curricula more robust (Ibid.). Co-creating an internationalised curriculum has the potential to include diverse student voices and make HE relevant in international, national and local contexts (Ibid.).

In addition to co-creating curricula, Heffernan, Morrison, Magne, Payne, and Cotton (2019), in their study found that incorporating 'experiential learning' (Kolb, 1984, p.20) can stimulate student engagement by internalising international or multicultural experiences at home (Heffernan, 2019, p.2361). This can be achieved by mixing domestic and international students in group work, tandem learning, or engaging in community work, festivals and events (Heffernan, 2019; Harrison, 2015; Jones, 2014; Wang, Feng, Freeman, Fan and Zhu, 2014; Brown, 2013; Fielden, 2011 and Killick, 2007). The scholars posit that providing explicit instructions to students on contextualising and situating internationalisation in their disciplines can help them better understand its relevance, potentially increase their engagement and build acceptance (Ibid.).

Furthermore, Van Mol and Perez-Encinas (2022) posit that integrating IaH within a formal curriculum can most effectively engage students, circumventing any barriers that may exist to their participation in activities outside of the formal study schedule (p.2523). The scholars also emphasise the importance of considering the social composition of student populations while designing IaH experiences to be more inclusive (p.2525), considering factors such as students' backgrounds, educational aspirations, and future goals (p.2535). However, despite these efforts, Stuber (2011), in (Van Mol and Perez-Encinas, 2022) study, argues that the lack of student interest in IaH should not necessarily be interpreted as a deficiency (Van Mol and Perez-Encinas, 2022, p.2536).

In essence, the literature suggests that an internationalised curriculum, virtual internationalisation, engaged academic staff and students, institutional commitment and support, and communities of practice can be some of the key enablers for implementing IaH in an HEI. However, there are also challenges to implementing IaH, which are presented in the following sub-section.

2.6 Challenges in Implementing IaH

The preceding section highlighted some key enablers for successfully implementing IaH in HEIs, such as an internationalised curriculum, virtual internationalisation, engaged students and staff, institutional commitment and support, and communities of practice. However, many HEIs globally face critical challenges in their efforts to internationalise at home, as evidenced in the extant literature (Gosling and Yang, 2022; Bergman, 2022; Weissova, 2021; Fragouli, 2021; Barbosa, Santos and Prado-Meza, 2020; Kirk, Newstead, Gann and Rounsaville, 2019; Almeida, Robson, Morosini and Baranzeli, 2019; Weimer, Hoffman and Silvonen, 2019; Robson, 2017; De Wit and Leask 2015; Harrison, 2015; Beelen and Leask 2010; Leask, 2009). The challenges include differing conceptual understandings of IaH, institutional commitment and support, varying perspectives among students and staff and the use of English as a lingua franca, most of which also find relevance in an Irish setting, except the use of English language (Beelen, 2023; Weissova, 2021; Kirk, Newstead, Gann and Rounsaville, 2019; Weimer, Hoffman and Silvonen, 2019; Almeida, Robson, Morosini and Baranzeli, 2019; Robson, 2017; Nagarajan and McAllister, 2015; Beelen and Leask, 2010). This sub-section elucidates the challenges of implementing IaH.

2.6.1 Conceptual Understandings

One of the primary challenges in implementing IaH can be the lack of a clear conceptual understanding of the term (Beelen, 2023, 2018, 2015; Kirk *et al.*, 2019; Stohl, 2007; Knight, 2006). According to these scholars, academic staff recognise the importance of embedding IaH into curricula but may struggle to grasp its specific implications for teaching and learning. Some scholars have even conceptualised IaH as an activist network (Rizvi, 2007, p.391) or movement (Brandenburg and De Wit, 2011, p.16), while others have criticised it as a Western construct that fails to fully capture the aims of internationalising the learning experience (Whitsed and Green, 2013 and Brewer and Leask, 2012). Despite its lofty moral principles, many HEIs have yet to fully embrace IaH, leading some scholars to describe it as an underdeveloped concept with great potential (Coelen, 2024; Manning and Marku, 2021; Robson, Almeida, and Schartner, 2018).

This conceptual confusion can be traced back to the early work of scholars such as Crowther *et al.* (2001), who defined IaH as an international activity within a domestic institution and an alternative to physical mobility (p.8), elucidated in *sub-section 2.3*. Although the definitions evolved, IaH is frequently perceived as focusing on activities rather than outcomes, which may partially explain the varied interpretations of its meaning (Beelen, 2023).

Furthermore, studies by Leask (2015, 2010, 2009) and Beelen and Jones (2015) posit that IaH can be implemented through formal and informal curricula. The emphasis on the curriculum in both IaH and a related concept, IoC, may have led to the ambiguity surrounding the understanding of IaH (Zou and Timmermans, 2025; Kirk *et al.*, 2019; Weimer *et al.*, 2019). Zadavec (2025), Beelen (2022), Almeida *et al.* (2019), Beelen and Jones (2018), Leask (2016), and Green and Whitsed (2015) argue that IaH and IoC are not competing concepts and can be utilised interchangeably. More recently, scholars such as Eftekhari, Yousefzadeh and Coelen (2025) have referred to this as the 'internationalisation of the curriculum at home (IoCaH).'

Moreover, Beelen (2023, 2019) observes that some aspects of IaH may have been inadvertently interpreted as representing the entire concept, a phenomenon he terms the 'pars pro toto effect' of IaH (Beelen, 2023, p.104). For example, integrating domestic students with international students on campus is often seen as IaH, but Beelen (2019) argues that IaH can still be implemented without international students (p.41). Ultimately, Beelen (2023) and Robson (2017) concur that the various interpretations of the terminology pose obstacles to implementing IaH and improving the internationalised outcomes of higher education.

2.6.2 Institutional Commitment and Support

Secondly, the successful implementation of IaH can be interrupted by inadequate institutional, financial, and staff development support. Weissova's (2021) study on IaH in Swedish universities identifies financial, human, intellectual and organisational support deficits as the primary challenge in operationalising IaH. This finding is similar to an earlier study on Finnish universities by Weimer *et al.* (2019). Kirk *et al.* (2019) and Egron-Polak and Hudson (2017, 2010) infer that actioning IaH plans can require extensive collaboration between university administration, finance, legal, academic, and non-academic staff and is a time-consuming and costly investment. Kirk *et al.* (2019) and Leask (2011) further argue that IaH is a transformational change at the institutional level, requiring leadership buy-in and the navigation of competing priorities among staff members. To this end, Harrison (2015) and Nagarajan and McAllister (2015) assert that conflicting dynamics between top-down and bottom-up approaches to IaH can be a significant roadblock that can impede its implementation plans.

The IAU Global Survey (2024) sheds light on some of these challenges globally, highlighted in red in *Figure 11* below. For the European region, insufficient institutional support and policies with financial provisions (53%), competing priorities at the institutional level (26%) and lack of or poorly resourced organisational structure/office responsible for internationalisation (13%), absence of a strategy/plan to guide the process and internationalisation not counted for promotion or tenure (7%), and limited institutional leadership/vision (5%) are some of the primary concerns regarding institutional commitment and support impeding internationalisation efforts, which may also be true for IaH (p.78).

2.6.3 Student and Staff Perspectives

The third challenge in implementing IaH can be the lack of student engagement and competing priorities among staff, which may pose challenges when striving to implement IaH (Beelen, 2023, 2018 and 2015). Beelen and Leask (2010) note that academic staff motivation is critical to implementing IaH in most institutions, particularly in Europe. However, staff frequently lack motivation towards IaH as they already consider themselves proactive stakeholders in internationalisation, living in cosmopolitan environments with small distances and affordable travel options (p.10). Furthermore, Muyaka, Wawire and Munene (2020) and Kirk *et al.* (2019) highlight that even if some staff are motivated, they face competing priorities, such as research and administrative responsibilities prioritised by their institution over IaH. Predictably, engaging in IaH can be perceived as an increased workload (Ibid.). This challenge is further exacerbated when domestic students underestimate the value of intercultural competencies in their learning and personal growth trajectory, which IaH seeks to cultivate in them (Hunt and Chalmers, 2021).

As illustrated in *Figure 12* below, a concerning global trend indicates a 42% increase in staff workload (IAU Global Survey, 2024, p.67). This risk is prevalent and reported across all world regions, particularly highlighting a significant risk among European HEIs at 61%. While the increasing workload poses a risk to internationalisation efforts, IaH can further contribute to this risk. Consequently, staff may not necessarily be inclined towards IaH due to the perception of increased workload and the need for training to incorporate international and intercultural perspectives in the curricula.

Figure 12: Most Significant Potential Institutional Risks of Internationalisation (IAU Global Survey, 2024, p.67-69)

Besides challenges perceived by staff, Harrison (2015), Rienties, Alcott and Jindal-Snape (2014), Hou and McDowell (2014), Strauss, U-Mackey and Crothers (2014), Ippolito (2007) and Peacock and Harrison (2008) bring to light that engaging students in IaH can also pose challenges. They assert that many domestic students report discomfort collaborating with international peers due to language barriers, cultural differences, and varying working styles (Ibid.). This discomfort may reinforce the notion that working with international students could adversely impact their academic performance. (Barbosa *et al.*, 2020; Urban and Palmer, 2014; Kimmel and Volet, 2012; Harrison and Peacock, 2009). Moreover, Clifford and Montgomery (2014), Mak, Brown and Wadey (2014), Dunne (2013), Ujitani and Volet (2008), Lee (2006), and Roux (2001) further observe that some domestic students may even avoid academic and social encounters with international students to avoid potential anxiety and embarrassment. Bergman (2022), Cena, Burns, and Wilson (2021); Moore and Hampton (2015); Summers and Volet (2008), Clifford (2009), Leask (2009), and Biggs (2003) concur that these experiences can act as a barrier to fully internationalising the curriculum and implementing IaH.

2.6.4 English Language as the Lingua Franca

Lastly, the perception of English being the primary language for institutional internationalisation efforts can pose a challenge to implementing IaH, particularly in some countries where English is not the first language (Beelen and Leask, 2010). Many staff at European HEIs in countries such as France, Spain, and Portugal, as well as non-European countries such as China, Japan, and Taiwan, may have been reluctant to fully engage with IaH which could be attributed to the prominence of English for internationalising programmes and international students' presence in classrooms (Galloway, Numajiri and Rees, 2020; Le Ha, 2013; Cots, Llorca and Garrett, 2014; Lo, 2009 and Kerklaan, Moreira and Boersma, 2008). Moreover, this perception may lead to unease among academic staff, who might believe that their native language is undervalued (Guo, Guo, Yochim and Liu, 2022; Galloway *et al.*, 2020; Harrison, 2015; Weimer *et al.*, 2019; Kerklaan *et al.*, 2008). This may necessitate additional efforts to develop teaching and learning materials in a foreign language, potentially hindering the progress of IaH implementation plans (Ibid.).

As evident through the literature, conceptual fog, inadequate institutional commitment and support, deficit in student and staff engagement, and the prevalence of the English language as the lingua franca could be some of the key obstacles when implementing IaH. The following sub-section presents possible solutions to these challenges.

2.7 Overcoming Challenges in IaH Implementation

The preceding sub-section presented some of the challenges that HEIs may encounter while striving to implement IaH. These challenges can encompass conceptual confusion, inadequate institutional commitment and support, and a lack of engagement by students and staff regarding IaH and the English language dominance in internationalisation. This sub-section outlines some of the ways to address the challenges associated with IaH implementation (Gosling and Yang, 2022; Sierra-Huedo, Bruton, and Fernández, 2022; Weissova, 2021; Fragouli, 2021; Beelen, 2019; Robson *et al.*, 2017; Leask, 2015; Nagarajan and McAllister, 2015; Marginson, 2014; Friesen, 2013; Beatty, 2013; Mestenhauser, 2011; Leask and Beelen, 2010; Clifford, 2009; Crosling, Edward and Schroder, 2008; Sanderson, 2008; Stohl, 2007; Caruana and Spurling, 2007; Mestenhauser, 2006).

2.7.1 Shared Conceptual Understanding

As described in *sub-section 2.6.1*, several studies have indicated conceptual confusion surrounding the term IaH. Zadravec (2021) and Beelen and Jones (2018) posit that viewing IaH and IoC as interchangeable concepts may mitigate this confusion, given the overlaps in these constructs. Additionally, it may be important to recognise that both IaH and IoC are tools that can enhance students' international and intercultural competencies rather than being goals in themselves (Beelen, 2023, p.105).

Moreover, early studies such as Nagarajan and McAllister (2015) suggest the possibility of a shared understanding of IaH within an HEI that is specific to their context, accompanied by guidance for its systematic integration (p.93). They further advocate for increased investment in evidence-based research to effectively implement and evaluate IaH across diverse disciplines, a point reinforced by Kokkonen, Natri and Moisio (2025), Barbosa, Santos, and Prado-Meza (2020) and Almeida *et al.* (2019). This study aims to bridge this gap within the context of Irish HE.

2.7.2 Institutional Commitment and Support

Addressing the second significant challenge of inadequate institutional commitment and support conducive to IaH, Sierra-Huedo *et al.* (2022), Weissova (2021), Weimer *et al.* (2019), Taylor and Cartwright (2015), Freeman, Treleaven, Simpson Ridings, Ramburuth, Leask, Caulfield and Sykes (2009) suggest that HEIs may need to develop a clear and explicit strategy on IaH and effectively communicate it across the institution. At the departmental level, HEIs

can embed IaH as one of the key metrics in each department's internationalisation plans, reflecting their commitment to this message (Ibid.).

From the academic disciplines perspective, Kokkonen *et al.* (2025), Williams (2022), Sierra-Huedo *et al.* (2022), Beelen (2019), Caruana and Spurling (2007); Gorard, Smith, May, Thomas, Adnett and Slack (2006) argue that clear communication from the leadership and training for staff can be crucial for academic disciplines to recognise that curriculum development and internationalising the curricula are not necessarily distinct processes. Integrating internationalisation into regular curriculum development and reviewing practices can help overcome the perception that such efforts demand extensive additional resources (Beelen, 2019, p. 43).

Albeit not necessarily extensive, additional resources may be needed to advance IaH in HEIs. At a broader level, Williams (2022), Weissova (2021), and Weimer *et al.* (2019) posit that institutional leaders could pursue external funding support to enhance IaH in their HEIs. This approach can provide the necessary financial resources to implement IaH more effectively across all levels of an institution (Ibid.). For instance, these resources could be allocated towards continuous professional development (CPD), which could provide training to staff to develop an internationalised curriculum and teaching and learning experience and establish reward and recognition mechanisms to drive IaH initiatives and acknowledge success (Weissova, Gregersen-Hermans, and Pantelic, 2024; Williams, 2022; Sierra-Huedo *et al.*, 2022; Weissova, 2021; Beelen, 2019 and Weimer *et al.*, 2019; Brewer and Leask, 2012; Sanderson, 2008; Teissier, 2007; Mestenhauser, 1998 and Van der Wende, 1997).

The scholars further add that investing in CPD and recognition programmes for IaH can enhance staff retention rates and improve the management of classroom diversity (Ibid.). By equipping staff to handle multicultural classrooms, it can create a positive impact and foster enriched international learning experiences for students (Weissova, Gregersen-Hermans, and Pantelic, 2024; Beelen, 2019, 2015; Kirk *et al.*, 2019; Leask, 2015, 2011, 2009 Garam, 2012). Besides retention, Fragouli (2021), Weimer *et al.* (2019), Beelen (2019), and Leask (2015) further advocate for incorporating IaH in the quality assurance processes and accreditation standards. This could make engagement in IaH attractive to both institutions and staff, leading to a more comprehensive and dedicated effort towards IaH throughout all levels of the institution (Ibid.).

2.7.3 Student and Staff Engagement

Thirdly, a proactive role played by students and staff in an HEI can address challenges regarding IaH implementation. According to Gosling and Yang (2022), Harrison (2015), Caruana and Spurling (2007), and De Vita and Case (2003), intentional international and intercultural interventions can provide domestic and international students with opportunities to work collaboratively and gain multiple perspectives. Sierra-Huedo *et al.* (2022), Weissova (2021), Fragouli (2021), and Kirk *et al.* (2019) suggest purposeful initiatives such as internationalised learning outcomes, core modules on intercultural competency development, virtual exchanges, and joint programmes with partner institutions, among others can be some of the ways in which domestic and international students can be integrated when striving to implement IaH.

In addition to engaging students, Beelen (2019) and Mestenhauser (2011) advocate for engaging academic staff as principal agents or 'new owners' for IaH (Beelen, 2019, p.29). They contend that the academic staff understand the international competencies required for professional practice in their disciplines (Ibid.). Traditionally, international offices were responsible for internationalisation due to the core emphasis on student mobility (Beelen, 2019, p.35). However, with the increasing focus on internationalisation of the curriculum in many HEIs in Europe, Australia, Canada and the US, academic staff are becoming central to driving internationalisation in universities by incorporating it into the curriculum (Beelen, 2019; Leask, 2015; Friesen, 2013; Hudzik, 2011). Consequently, they can be considered 'new owners' of IaH (Beelen, 2019, p.29).

Furthermore, academic staff are more likely to be invested in IaH efforts when they perceive a strong alignment with the institutional vision, funding sources, CPD opportunities, and systems for reward and recognition (Leask, 2015; Leask and Beelen, 2010; Clifford, 2009; Sanderson, 2008; Stohl, 2007; Van der Wende, 2000). Remarkably, purposefully creating opportunities for students to participate in internationalised initiatives inside and outside the classroom and providing avenues for staff development, reward, and recognition can contribute to heightened engagement among students and staff in IaH (Leask, 2015; Friesen, 2013; Beatty, 2013; Crosling, Edward and Schroder, 2008; Mestenhauser, 2006).

The EAIE Barometer (2024) findings reinforce this view, indicating that the academic staff is one of the key drivers of internationalisation in European HEIs, accounting for 91% of the total respondents in the survey in [Figure 13](#) below.

Figure 13: Influence of Stakeholder Groups in Driving Institutional Internationalisation (EAIE Barometer, 2024, p.56)

	Highly influential	Influential	Somewhat influential	Not at all influential	Unsure
Executive board/team	39%	35%	16%	4%	5%
Academic staff	19%	42%	30%	6%	2%
Administrative staff	11%	32%	36%	18%	3%
Current students	10%	29%	38%	18%	4%
Former students (alumni)	5%	15%	27%	42%	12%
External advisory board	5%	16%	24%	37%	28%
National authorities	20%	38%	26%	8%	9%
European level authorities	17%	36%	26%	9%	12%

2.7.4 Utilising Local Languages

Fourthly, countering the notion of English being the predominant lingua franca for internationalisation, Cunningham, Topping, and Levy (2024); Symeonidis and Impedovo (2023), Altbach and De Wit (2020); Beelen (2019); Beelen (2018), and Beelen and Leask (2010) emphasise that local languages can play a significant role in many European HEIs. While English may help attract and facilitate the integration of international students with domestic students, some European HEIs utilise local or indigenous languages to internationalise their programmes (Ibid.). This can be achieved through multicultural cases, literature spanning different cultural contexts, and guest lectures in the local language from international speakers, to mention a few (Adriansen, Juul-Wiese, Madsen, Saarinen, Spangler and Waters, 2023; Choi, 2021; Nashaat-Sobhy and Sánchez-García, 2020 and Jenkins, 2018).

The scholars further add that some HEIs are beginning to limit the number of English-taught programmes to safeguard their national and local languages (Ibid.). Nonetheless, Guimarães and Finardi (2023), Sercu (2023), Sierra-Heudo (2022), Dafouz and Smit (2021), Ryan (2020) and Jones (2020) argue that the use of English and foreign languages has the potential to amplify the cultivation of intercultural competence, which is one of the key outcomes for IaH. This can be particularly relevant for English-speaking European

countries, such as Ireland. It is, however, worth noting that HEIs prioritising local languages can also successfully implement IaH (Ibid.).

2.7.5 Systemic Approach

Lastly, the implementation of IaH can often be fragmented, even if it is actioned across an institution (Sierra-Huedo, Bruton, and Fernández, 2024; De Wit and Deca, 2020; Teekens, 2007; Bergknut, 2007 and Mestenhauser, 2007, 2003). The scholars contend that a university-wide embedding of IaH can be crucial, as involving every department and engaging all stakeholders as process owners can significantly increase the likelihood of success in preparing graduates as global citizens (Ibid.). Mestenhauser (2011, 2007, 2006) refers to this as a 'systemic approach,' which entails integrating individual parts into a coordinated and balanced whole (Mestenhauser, 2007, p.15). He emphasised that only a systems approach can facilitate large-scale changes in internationalisation (Ibid.).

The remnants of this thought are evident in the work of scholars such as Teekens (2007) and Eisenclas and Trevaskes (2003) and later reiterated by Beelen (2023) and Beelen and Jones (2015). Eisenclas and Trevaskes (2003) suggest that institutions may benefit from examining their academic practices across all programmes while also striving to improve cross-cultural integration among diverse student and local community groups (p.7). Teekens (2007) argues that integrating IaH in an HEI may necessitate institutional change and reform where IaH extends beyond the scope of a single module or programme with an international dimension, evolving into a university-wide initiative involving all members in its implementation process (p.7). In this way, IaH can move beyond 'parts' to a 'whole' approach (Ibid.). Beelen (2023) and Beelen and Doscher (2022) refer to this as the 'pars pro toto' effect of IaH, which can pose as one of the critical challenges in the field. Several other scholars, including Sierra Huedo *et al.* (2024); Beelen (2023); D'Angelo, O'Brien, and Marty (2022); Allen (2021); Beelen and Jones (2018); Leask (2015) and Di Maria (2012), concur with the systemic approach to embedding IaH. This research study seeks to address this gap in the context of Irish HE.

As demonstrated in the literature, implementing agreed-upon terminology, securing institutional commitment and support, actively engaging students and staff, utilising local languages to internationalise curricula, and employing a systemic approach can address some of the challenges related to IaH. The following sub-section will present some frameworks in IaH that are used globally.

2.8 Existing Guiding Frameworks

The extant literature identifies some frameworks that can aid institutions in implementing IaH. Some of these frameworks are outcomes of the Erasmus+ projects, such as the 'Developing Innovative Approaches and Tools for IaH-ATIAH,' 2016-18 (ATIAH, n.d.), as well as insights from research studies such as 'The Hague Internationalisation at Home' (THIAH, 2022, n.d.). This sub-section also highlights other Erasmus+ projects that incorporate various elements of IaH.

The increasing popularity of IaH may have led the European Commission to fund several capacity-building projects that included elements of IaH (Erasmus Charter for Higher Education, 2021-27; 2014-20). These projects comprised initiatives such as 'Developing Innovative Approaches and Tools for IaH-ATIAH' (2016-18), which offered tools to assess and enhance IaH practices in HEIs (ATIAH, n.d.), and 'Systemic University Change Towards Internationalisation- SUCTI' (2016-18), which aimed to equip administrative staff to improve internationalisation practices systemically in European HEIs (SUCTI, n.d.). The success of this project led to an extension that included academic staff through the 'Systemic University Change Towards Internationalisation for Academia-SUCTIA' (2019-22). SUCTIA aimed to enhance academic staff engagement in internationalisation through awareness and training (SUCTIA, n.d.).

Furthermore, other Erasmus+ projects, such as the 'Educational Quality at Universities for Inclusive International Programmes - EQUiIP' (2016-19), addressed various aspects of IaH, comprising training modules that empower staff to manage an international classroom, internationalise course designs and reflect on the role of languages and intercultural dynamics (EQUiIP, n.d.). Recently, the 'Training and Realising Innovations in Internationalisation at Home Pedagogies (TRIP)' project (2022-25) aimed at creating a framework for innovative and quality-assured IaH while linking to broader themes such as the United Nation's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and inclusive internationalisation (TRIP, n.d.).

Notably, many of these Erasmus+ projects involved a consortium of universities focusing on tailored approaches in IaH aligning with their respective institutional contexts. While these projects could have contributed to building the capacity for informing, reviewing, and improving IaH practices, there is limited evidence in the literature to support their long-term impact. This may be attributed to the fact that most Erasmus+ projects are time-bound and are predominantly people-driven rather than institutions. Consequently, there may be a

greater need for funding and resources to facilitate the continuous monitoring of their impact.

Despite the limitations of monitoring the long-term impact of Erasmus+ projects, the ATIAH framework appears more relevant to the current research study. This framework seems to have been utilised by some of the departments/institutions in the UK, Brazil, Portugal, Belgium, Italy, Austria and Ireland (Robson *et al.*, 2022; Weissova, 2021; Lundgren, Castro and Woodin, 2019; Comas-Quinn, Beaven and Sawhill, 2019; PUCRS, n.d.; UCD, n.d.). The ATIAH framework draws on elements from both the framework on Comprehensive Internationalisation (CI) in the US (Hudzik and McCarthy, 2012 and Hudzik, 2011) and a conceptual framework for IoC in Australia (Leask, 2015). Although no direct attribution has been made, the ATIAH framework may have been inspired by the aforementioned frameworks. The CI framework focuses on integrating internationalisation into the core institutional mission (Hudzik, 2015), while the IoC framework emphasises context-specific curriculum design (Leask, 2015).

Interestingly, the ATIAH consortium has developed a toolkit to guide IaH implementation at their respective HEIs. The toolkit comprises three stages: a self-audit tool to examine existing IaH practices, a curricular framework to facilitate internationalisation through the curriculum, and an evidence framework for evidencing and communicating IaH practices (ATIAH, n.d.). The first stage of the 'Self-Audit' involves conducting desk research and focus groups with various stakeholders within the HEI to understand the current status of IaH and its implementation (Ibid.). The second stage of the 'curricular framework' encourages staff at the HEIs to reflect upon, discuss and identify opportunities for internationalisation within the curriculum (Ibid.). This stage also facilitates conversations between staff and leadership regarding the necessary structures and resources to implement IaH effectively (Ibid.). The final stage illustrates an evidence framework that can assist HEIs in reviewing programmes, communicating milestones, and integrating IaH at different levels within their institution (Ibid.).

Although ATIAH aimed at a university-wide approach to implementing IaH (Robson *et al.*, 2022 and Robson *et al.*, 2018), scholars such as Bulnes and De Louw (2022) and Weissova (2021) criticise the framework for overlooking important aspects of IaH, such as the need for guided interventions for internationally mobile students and encouragement of their reflections upon their return from mobility programmes (p.5). They argue that mobile students abroad lack adequate support to enhance intercultural competence (Ibid.). This

could include self-reflection on the mobility experience, which also has the potential to deepen intercultural awareness among non-mobile students, as also highlighted in the work of early scholars such as Berg, Connor-Linton and Paige (2009); Deardorff (2008) and Bennett (2008). Moreover, ATIAH does not explicitly address assessments and learning outcomes from an internationalised curriculum in its curricular framework (Bulnes and De Louw, 2022, p.6).

Importantly, following the culmination of the ATIAH project in 2018, the circumstances shaping trends in IoHE have considerably evolved. For instance, the growing geopolitical uncertainty, global health crisis such as COVID-19, an increasing emphasis on virtual internationalisation, sustainability and equality, diversity and inclusion (EDI), as well as the potential of the European Universities Initiative (EUI), are some of the aspects that have emerged in these years and warrant a framework that sufficiently captures the new reality. This is particularly relevant for this study in the context of Irish HE.

Besides the ATIAH framework, tools such as the 'THIAH' (The Hague Internationalisation at Home Mapping Instrument) developed by staff at the Hague University of Applied Sciences in the Netherlands, have also emerged (Bulnes and De Louw, 2022). THIAH can enable institutions to 'systematically map IaH activities or tools within programmes, both explicitly and implicitly' (NUFFIC, n.d.). The topic guide for the participants for the current study was, in part, informed by the THIAH questionnaire. However, the THIAH questionnaire appears to emphasise the curricular aspects primarily. It may not fully capture the comprehensive institutional approach needed for HEIs to embed a 'culture of IaH,' which presents as one of the aims of this study. Besides ATIAH and THIAH, other resources include the IaH inventory developed by the Dutch Organisation for International Education, NUFFIC (Bulnes and de Louw, 2022), and the Flemish Bologna Experts, which may encompass components of IaH, among others (Depoorter, François, Geens, Joris, Vanbrabant and Verlackt, 2011).

In Ireland, the University College Dublin (UCD) signposts the ATIAH framework on their website. At the same time, the University of Limerick (UL) is the lead of an Erasmus+ consortium for developing the TRIP framework. However, specific information regarding the university-wide implementation of these frameworks remains unavailable. The discussion surrounding these frameworks within the Irish HE context is elucidated in *Chapter 3 (sub-section 3.4)*. Considering the evolving global and national developments in Irish HE, a guiding framework for embedding a culture of IaH could significantly

contribute to developing intercultural competence and global citizenship among learners and staff as the national and institutional importance of IaH continues to grow in Irish HEIs (DFHERIS, 2024).

In summary, this section explored various frameworks that aid in understanding and implementing IaH within a global context. Among these frameworks are the THIAH tool and Erasmus+ projects, such as the ATIAH framework. While these frameworks can offer valuable insights to guide HEIs in their IaH endeavours, the literature alludes to the need for frameworks reflecting the current national and institutional realities facing HE. This consideration may be particularly relevant in the context of Irish HE and is one of the aims of this study. The following sub-section examines the role of IaH in a global pandemic such as COVID-19 and its present state.

2.9 IaH in COVID-19 and Beyond

The preceding sub-section outlined the existing frameworks in IaH, such as the Developing Innovative Approaches and Tools for IaH (ATIAH, n.d.) and the Hague Internationalisation at Home Mapping Instrument (THIAH) (Bulnes and De Louw, 2022). However, the rising global uncertainty and the emergence of health crises such as COVID-19 may have prompted the need for a framework for IaH, taking into account the evolving national and institutional contexts. This sub-section examines the shifting nature of internationalisation in the wake of a global pandemic such as COVID-19 and its connection with the growing significance of IaH in HE.

The COVID-19 outbreak, which began in early 2020, led many HEIs to adopt makeshift arrangements for online/virtual teaching and learning due to lockdowns and travel restrictions that halted air travel and impacted student and staff mobility abroad (Whitsed, Cassol, Leask, Morosini, Elsner and Nguyen, 2024; Beelen, 2023; Li and Xue, 2023; De Wit, Hunter, Egron- Polak, Howard and Coelen, 2023; Raby and Zhang, 2022; Ferencz and Rumbley, 2022; Hammond and Radjai, 2022; Yang, 2022; De Wit and Altbach, 2021; Spurga and Žalėnienė, 2021; Crăciun and Gayardon, 2021 and Yang, 2020). As academics and university leadership in most universities globally grappled with this situation, emerging discourses on what this would look like for IoHE began to take shape (Ibid.).

Notably, leveraging virtual technology for internationalisation initiatives became widespread, leading to IaH taking centre stage in many HEIs globally in this 'new normal' (Ibid.). This trend is evident in the IAU global report, which surveyed respondents from 500 HEIs across

112 countries, revealing a growing emphasis on IaH (Jensen, Marinoni and Van't Land, 2022). The report indicated that 89% of HEIs acknowledged that IaH became a strategic priority during the pandemic, and 92% of the European HEIs recognised the growing importance of IaH within their institutions (p.88).

Although many HEIs have been engaging in IaH prior to the COVID-19 pandemic, largely viewing it as an alternative to physical mobility, the pandemic elevated its importance as an immediate response to continuing internationalisation efforts. This could have resulted from rising discourses surrounding equitable access to internationalisation experiences for all students, the environmental and societal implications of internationalisation activities, the need to prioritise student and staff well-being and to prepare responsible global citizens who can address shared local and global challenges in an increasingly uncertain world (Whitsed *et al.*, 2024; Beelen, 2023; De Wit, Hunter, Egron-Polak, Howard and Coelen, 2023; Yeravdekar and Piplani-Kapur, 2022; Raby and Zhang, 2022; Hammond and Radjai, 2022; Ferencz and Rumbley, 2022; Yang, 2022; Veerasamy and Ammigan, 2022; De Wit and Altbach, 2021; Antonopoulou, 2021; Jones, 2020 and Yang, 2020).

Engaging in IaH during the pandemic necessitated leveraging information and communication technology (ICT) as a prime catalyst to advance IaH initiatives, such as Virtual Exchanges (VE) and Collaborative Online International Learning (COIL), as well as to access support services and manage routine office operations since most of the university activities transitioned online (Haug and Jacobs, 2023; Fløisdorf and Adriansen, 2023; Raby and Zhang, 2022; Hammond and Radjai, 2022; Woicolesco, Morosini and Marcelino, 2022; James, Cobanoglu and Cavusoglu, 2021; Spurga and Žalėnienė, 2021; Crăciun and Gayardon, 2021; Antonopoulou, 2021; Irien, 2021 and De Wit and Altbach, 2020). As such, COIL and/or VE can enable staff across multiple countries to co-design and co-facilitate collaborative classrooms for students from those regions (Hackett, Dawson, Janssen and van Tartwijk, 2024; Rubin, 2017).

However, VE and COIL may have added to the complexity of IaH in many HEIs globally (Beelen, 2023; Yang, 2022; O'Dowd and Beelen, 2021; Van Hove, 2021). While some studies group VE and COIL under 'virtual internationalisation,' these represent a select approach to IaH (IAU, 2022; O'Dowd, 2022; Satar, 2021). Furthermore, Beelen (2023), Yang (2022), O'Dowd and Beelen (2021), and Van Hove (2021) note that many HEIs appear to grapple with the challenge of integrating VE and COIL into the core curricula for all students since the shift to online teaching and learning was sudden (*Ibid.*). Consequently, the rise of virtual

internationalisation could have prompted discussions concerning whether these fragmented initiatives during the pandemic can ultimately be integrated into the core curriculum to be impactful and reach all students (Ibid.).

Nonetheless, as IaH, through virtual internationalisation, gained popularity in many HEIs globally during the pandemic, it brought to light the issue of inequitable access to technology among students, particularly in the developing parts of the world (Li and Xue, 2023; Halder, 2022; Muñiz and Borg, 2022; Ferencz and Rumbley, 2022; Chasi and Quinlan, 2021; James, Cobanoglu and Cavusoglu, 2021; Whatley and Raby 2020 and Rumbley, 2020). At this time, many international students opted to return to their home countries because of the uncertainty imposed by COVID-19 (Ibid.). The inadequate infrastructure to support internet bandwidth in some regions likely revealed inequities in accessing education through ICT, potentially igniting discussions regarding inclusivity in internationalisation experiences (Ibid.). The scholars further argue that implementing IaH could have been a more inclusive and impactful intervention at the home campuses, given the disparities in access to ICT for some students in their home countries (Ibid.).

Furthermore, De Wit, Hunter, Egron-Polak, Howard and Coelen (2023); Beelen (2023); Ferencz and Rumbley (2022) and De Wit and Jones (2022) argue the need for greater emphasis on systematic integration of IaH, particularly through the core curricula rather than leaning predominantly on the sporadic adoption of digital technologies to advance internationalisation efforts. This emphasis may have been exasperated by the pandemic, which highlighted the pressing need to equip students with 21st-century skills, including the ability to communicate effectively across cultures, digital literacy, resilience in the face of uncertainties such as COVID-19, and the capacity to devise solutions to local and global challenges which can be developed through IaH (Simões and Sangiamchit, 2023; Bruhn-Zass, 2022; Satar, 2021; Krasulia and Pistor, 2021 and Sala, Punie, and Garkov, 2020).

Consequently, the COVID-19 pandemic can be viewed as a significant turning point for IaH. The mobility restrictions during the pandemic have arguably led to the prioritisation of IaH in many HEIs globally. Interestingly, according to the EAIE Barometer (2024), 58% of European HEIs now prioritise IaH through virtual internationalisation (p.13). This unprecedented time may have prompted HEIs to reimagine HE in the light of the essential 21st-century skills required to tackle local and global challenges, such as critical thinking, problem-solving, intercultural skills and global citizenship (OECD, 2021; WEF, 2020). Additionally, discussions on virtual internationalisation through VE and COIL (O'Dowd

and Beelen, 2021), equality, diversity, and inclusion (Ferencz and Rumbley, 2022), decolonisation of the curricula (Le Grange, 2020), as well as sustainability and climate action (Huang *et al.*, 2022), have gained considerable traction in many HEIs during this time. These topics are further elucidated in the discussion in *Chapter 6*.

2.10 Conclusion

This chapter reviewed the global literature on internationalisation at home (IaH), which is popularly defined by Beelen and Jones (2015) as the purposeful integration of international and intercultural dimensions into the formal and informal curriculum for all students within domestic learning environments (p.69). The concept of IaH was originally introduced by Nilsson (1999) at Malmö University in Sweden and has since gained significant attention from scholars and practitioners globally. Notably, IaH has become increasingly pertinent after a quarter-century, as demonstrated by recent literature and prominent surveys such as the IAU Global Survey (2024) and the EAIE Barometer (2024) survey, which focused on the European region. The chapter contextualised IaH within the broader context of the internationalisation of higher education (IoHE). It examined IaH's evolution, definitions, key rationales, enablers, challenges, solutions, existing frameworks, and relevance in global events such as the COVID-19 pandemic and the present state.

Some key rationales for IaH that emerged from the literature review indicated the impact of globalisation, development of intercultural competencies and critical thinking skills, impact on teaching and learning practices, equity considerations in internationalisation experiences, employability prospects for students and contribution to institutional distinctiveness. These rationales can be realised through several enablers such as an internationalised curriculum, virtual internationalisation, engagement of students and staff, institutional commitment and support and communities of practice dedicated to IaH. However, facilitating IaH can be challenging due to differing conceptual understandings, inadequate institutional commitment and support, varying student and staff perspectives and the perception of English as the primary language for engaging in internationalisation. To address these challenges, the literature suggested solutions such as establishing a shared understanding of IaH, securing institutional commitment and support, encouraging student and staff engagement, utilising local languages, and adopting a systemic approach to embedding IaH.

Amidst these ongoing developments within this concept, existing frameworks, including the 'Developing Innovative Approaches and Tools for IaH-ATIAH' (ATIAH, n.d.) and the Hague Internationalisation at Home Mapping Instrument (THIAH) (Bulnes and De Louw, 2022) were examined. This examination revealed the need for a comprehensive framework that represents the current realities facing national and institutional contexts in HE, which can be valuable for Irish HE and is further explored in *Chapter 3*. The following *Chapter 3* shifts attention to some of the prominent national and institutional developments in Irish HE, particularly in relation to internationalisation and IaH. It contextualises the need for a holistic approach to embedding a culture of IaH in Irish HE, aligning with the aims of this study.

CHAPTER 3: LITERATURE REVIEW (IRISH CONTEXT)

3.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the main themes that shape the developments in IaH in the present-day Irish higher education (HE) context. It contextualises the research in the broader landscape of Irish HE. Following this, the focus shifts to reviewing IaH in the past Irish HE and international education strategies, scholarly discourse around IaH and the recent international talent and innovation strategy- 'Global Citizens 2030' (DFHERIS, 2024). Furthermore, it explores the connections between IaH and various national strategies and government funding schemes. Finally, IaH is analysed within the institutional strategic plans of publicly funded Irish higher education institutions (HEIs) to interpret recent developments.

The arguments presented demonstrate the need for a scholarly knowledge base and guiding framework to support Irish HEIs in embedding a culture of IaH across their institutions, which grounds the research aims and objectives of this study. For simplicity, this chapter has been categorised into six sub-sections. These include: (1) Irish HE, (2) internationalisation in Irish HE, (3) scholarly discourse on IaH, (4) IaH in Ireland's current international talent and innovation strategy, (5) IaH in other national strategies and funding schemes and lastly, (6) IaH in Irish publicly funded HEIs strategic plans.

3.2 Irish Higher Education

Traditionally, the Irish HE system has mainly been characterised as 'binary,' comprising universities, technological universities (TUs)/institutes of technology (IoTs), other small, affiliated institutions linked to universities and some private providers (Hinfelaar, 2012; Kyvik, 2004; Clancy, 1989). This binary system resembles most European HE systems with clear distinctions between universities and TUs/IoTs (Marginson, 2016; Walsh and Loxley, 2014; Kyvik, 2004). It is worth noting that, in line with some European countries, traditional universities in Ireland have sometimes been perceived as 'elite' institutions, primarily serving a more affluent student demographic (McTaggart, 2024; O'Donoghue, Gleeson and McCormack, 2017; Trow, 1976). These universities typically offered programmes in

disciplines such as arts and humanities, business, law, medicine, teaching, and allied health (McTaggart, 2024; Trow, 1976).

The perception of elitism in Irish traditional universities could be attributed to structural and socio-economic factors, such as the historical marginalisation of certain groups, such as Catholics, from leadership roles in some universities, along with financial constraints faced by student families, geographic barriers limiting rural student enrolment, and academic requirements that may have disproportionately affected students from working-class backgrounds (Ibid.). These aspects could have impacted access and affordability of Irish HE, resulting in only about 15% of Ireland's population pursuing HE in the 1960s (McTaggart, 2024; O'Donoghue, Gleeson and McCormack, 2017; Trow, 2010, 1976).

However, the transition from an elite to a mass HE system began to emerge in the late 1960s in response to the opening of the Irish economy and the rising social demand for HE (Trow, 2010, 2007). One significant factor contributing to this rising demand was the abolition of higher second-level education fees by the then Minister for Education in the Irish government, Donogh O'Malley, in 1967. This policy change likely made education more accessible for students, particularly those with lower socio-economic backgrounds, enabling them to complete second-level education and progress to HE (McWilliams 2025; Nyhan Grey, 2018). Additionally, the need to address the industry skills gap and human resources shortages within the Irish economy may have further facilitated this transition (Walsh, 2014; Trow, 2010, 2007). Consequently, this shift could have led to the establishment of the second tier of the higher educational system through Regional Technical Colleges (RTCs) in the 1970s, which were later rebranded as Institutes of Technology (IoTs) in 1997 (Oireachtas Library and Research Services 2014).

The RTCs/IoTs offered training in disciplines such as craft, engineering, science, technology, tourism, hospitality, and agriculture, to mention a few (McTaggart, 2024). This formation of a binary system through the RTCs/IoTs may have signified the onset of massification in Irish HE, broadening access to third-level education for students from diverse backgrounds and regions (Walsh, 2014; Trow, 2007). Notably, massification was considered attainable when 15-50% of the population within the appropriate age group accessed HE opportunities (Trow, 2007).

Expanding the discourse around widening access to third-level education and bridging industry skilled labour needs, the Irish government in the recent past introduced a new type of HEI known as the 'Technological Universities (TUs)' by passing the Technological Universities Act in 2018 (Stephens and Gallagher, 2022; Houghton, 2020). Consequently, Technological University Dublin (TUD) became the first TU to be established in 2019, and the number of TUs in the country has risen to five following mergers of IoTs (DFHERIS, n.d.). The Irish HE system currently comprises seven traditional universities, five TUs, and two IoTs that are publicly funded (Ibid.). Additionally, eleven affiliate institutions also receive public funding (Ibid.). Importantly, this research focuses on publicly funded traditional and technological universities/IoTs.

Furthermore, McTaggart (2024) argues that the move towards TUs can represent Irish HE gradually approaching a universal education system, with more than 51% of the population, including adults, having had the opportunity to complete post-secondary education (p. 1774). The expansion of the HE system through TUs may stem from the growing national and international demand for higher education, increased diversity within Irish HEIs, and the necessity for qualified and skilled graduates in society, communities, and workplaces (OECD, 2023; OECD, 2017; Harkin and Hazelkorn, 2014; Trow, 2005). As a result, the establishment of IoTs/TUs may contribute, in part, to addressing the rising demand, evidenced by an increase in the number of full-time students in undergraduate programs, which grew from 21,000 in 1967 to 172,830 in 2023-24, alongside additional students pursuing part-time education (HEA, 2024).

Notwithstanding the growing demand for HE and the number of HEIs offering third-level education, internationalisation in Irish HE may be shaped, in part, by the differing historical contexts and focus of traditional and IoTs/TUs, where the TUs appear to encounter additional challenges when responding to institutional and national priorities and internationalisation trends (Ryan, 2020; Finnegan, 2015; Kelly, 2015). For instance, whilst TUs have likely retained the industry focus of the IoTs, there is now a greater emphasis on research linked with industry and work-based teaching and learning (Ibid.).

Furthermore, the IoTs presumably have been predominantly teaching-oriented, with considerable teaching loads each semester ranging from 16-18 per week, as opposed to 8-10 hours per week of teaching load in traditional universities (Houghton, 2020; Boland, 2016). In addition to the IoT teaching load, the research emphasis at the TUs can impose significant demands on academic staff, which can influence their engagement with internationalisation

(Ibid.). Moreover, the TUs appear to be under increasing pressure to compete with traditional universities for research funding and to raise their profile through global rankings (Houghton, 2020).

The heightened pressure on TUs appears to stem from the differing borrowing capacities compared to traditional universities (Griffin and Collins, 2022; Morales, 2021; Houghton, 2020). Both traditional universities and TUs receive public funding through their regulatory body, the Higher Education Authority (HEA). Arguably, the traditional universities benefit from greater financial autonomy, including the right to borrow money from the government for developmental projects, under the Universities Act 1997 (Ibid.). Conversely, the TUs have not yet been afforded the same statutory borrowing rights under the Technological Universities Act of 2018 (Ibid.). This limitation might reflect a cautious approach by the government towards fiscal risk associated with establishing new universities and concerns regarding their financial maturity, as some TUs are still navigating the complexities of post-merger consolidation. Moreover, their classification under general government expenditure could have implications for the national debt if borrowing were permitted (Ibid.).

Whilst the TUs face the aforementioned challenges in contrast to the traditional universities, they share common ground in some aspects of internationalising their institutions, which is the focus of this study. For instance, they concur with the financial rationale as the primary driver for engaging in internationalisation to support an underfunded HE sector (Clarke, Yang and Harmon, 2018). Besides the financial rationale, IoTs/TUs consider 'increasing student mobility, pressure to diversify and institutional rankings,' as opposed to traditional universities considering 'funding incentives and international competition' contributing to their internationalisation efforts (p.22). However, most institutions agree that internationalisation is not sufficiently incentivised in Irish HEIs (p.47).

Although internationalisation does not seem to be adequately incentivised within the HEIs (Clarke *et al.*, 2018), the long-standing reputation and historical precedence of advanced internationalisation in traditional universities could have contributed to their ability to attract a greater number of international students than IoTs/TUs. This is reflected in the HEA (2024) data, which shows that traditional universities currently enrol 24,880 international students across full-time undergraduate and postgraduate programmes, as opposed to 6,090 international students in IoTs/TUs in 2023-24. Factors such as extensive outreach efforts, funding incentives, and the prominence of traditional universities in prestigious league tables, such as Quacquarelli Symonds (QS) and Times Higher Education (THE) global rankings,

likely distinguish them from IoTs/TUs (Hazelkorn, 2024; Clarke, Yang and Harmon, 2018; Hazelkorn, 2015).

Consequently, the financial autonomy alongside the advancement of internationalisation in traditional universities can significantly impact their capacity to contribute more entrepreneurially towards internationalisation efforts, such as IaH and invest in resources that can positively impact the student experience. In contrast, the stricter financial controls for the TUs may present challenges in achieving full engagement in internationalisation and/or IaH, indicating a need for a level playing field between the traditional universities and the TUs. *Appendix B* captures some of the landmark moments in the trajectory of the evolution of Irish HE and the internationalisation of its institutions. The following sub-section will examine internationalisation and the growing importance of IaH in Irish HE.

3.3 Internationalisation in Irish Higher Education

This sub-section reviews the contextual background and previous HE and international education strategies to interpret the development of IaH in the Irish HE sector.

3.3.1 Background Context

Ireland was known as a 'land of saints and scholars' or 'Insula Sanctorum et Doctorum' since medieval times (Healey, 1890), where scholars freely moved between European countries (O'Neill, 2019). This free movement could have been characterised by humanistic ideals that promote collaboration and exchange, which may have influenced some approaches to internationalisation in the current Irish HE context (Ibid.). Whilst the mobility of scholars was not new to the Irish HEIs, internationalisation can be said to have begun to take its definitive shape in the late twentieth century (O'Reilly, 2024; Clarke, Yang and Harmon, 2018; Clarke, 2015; Mernagh, 2010).

Some of the landmark moments illustrating the shift can be Ireland's membership in the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) in 1961, the European Economic Community (EEC) in 1973, its participation in the Erasmus programmes in 1987, signing of the Bologna Accord in 1999 and establishing a national framework for qualifications in 2003 to support mobility abroad at the start of the twenty-first century (Ibid.). These programmes could have strengthened Ireland's reputation with European and international institutions, fostered cooperation, partnership, and exchanges, and concurrently formalised internationalisation in Irish HEIs (Courtois, 2017; Brown and Scott, 2010).

These developments in the internationalisation of Irish HE could be seen in the context of rising globalisation, as discussed in *Chapter 2 (sub-section 2.2)*. This surge in globalisation and the associated opportunities for HE may have prompted the Irish government to publish its inaugural report on the 'Internationalisation of Irish Educational Services' (DES, 2004). The report alluded to a shift in values from cooperation, partnership, and exchange towards the marketisation of HE, which is reflected in its emphasis on the significance of deriving financial benefits from internationalisation activities, which it characterised as 'big business' (DES, 2004, p.5).

Two years later, the OECD published a report underscoring the need to develop an internationalisation strategy for Ireland, echoing recommendations from the DES report. It urged Irish HEIs to actively promote their educational programmes abroad (OECD, 2006). The OECD set a target to double the growth of the international student population in Ireland over the next five years, aiming to inject essential funds into the HE sector (OECD, 2006, p.59). Furthermore, it advocated for implementing the DES report, acknowledging the reluctance among Irish HEIs to embrace the 'big business' approach to HE that leans towards a more market-driven and commercial orientation (Ibid.).

The OECD's endorsement of the DES (2004) report drew criticism from some staff in Irish HEIs, who argued that the report prioritised commercial interests over the traditional academic values of cooperation and exchange (Courtois and O'Keefe, 2015). This divergence of opinions among the OECD, the Irish government, and the Teachers Union of Ireland (TUI), representing academic staff in Irish HEIs, coincided with the onset of the Global Financial Crisis (GFC) in 2008, which severely impacted the Irish economy and plunged the country into recession (O'Neill, 2019; Hazelkorn, Gibson, and Harkin, 2015; Clarke, Kenny & Loxley, 2015; Gaynor, 2009).

Remarkably, the economic rationale for pursuing internationalisation could have been further exacerbated by the financial challenges stemming from the GFC in 2008 (Ibid.). This crisis likely prompted significant funding cuts within the HE sector (Ibid.). As a result, the availability of public funds to HEIs witnessed a notable decline, and recruitment of new staff was halted, leading to a shortage of qualified academic staff in Irish HEIs (Ibid.). Consequently, expenditure on HE experienced considerable reductions, declining by 37% between 2007 and 2014 (Clarke, Kenny & Loxley, 2015; IAU, 2014).

Concomitantly, the funding cuts appear to have contributed to the introduction of an 'employment control framework' (ECF) that restricted full-time staff recruitment in Irish HEIs, which in turn could have deteriorated the student-staff ratios that were recorded at 1:15 in 2008 (O'Reilly, 2024; Clarke, Yang, and Harmon, 2018). In response, the Irish government may have begun to perceive internationalisation as a potential economic opportunity for generating income by recruiting international students, aiming to infuse funds into the Irish HE sector (O'Reilly, 2024; Clarke, Yang, and Harmon, 2018). This context likely played a significant role in shaping a national strategic approach, culminating in the launch of Ireland's first international education strategy, titled 'Investing in Global Relationships – Ireland's International Education Strategy 2010-2015' (MoES, 2010), which is discussed in the subsequent sub-section.

3.3.2 Ireland's Past Higher Education Strategies and IaH

This sub-section describes the development of strategies for higher education (HE) and internationalisation within the Irish HE system. These include 'Investing in Global Relationships – Ireland's International Education Strategy 2010-2015' (MoES, 2010), 'National Strategy for Higher Education to 2030', popularly referred to as the 'Hunt Report' (DES, 2011) and 'Irish Educated, Globally Connected, an international education strategy for Ireland, 2016-2020' (DES, 2016). These strategies can be viewed as incremental towards unpacking the Irish government's primary intentions for engaging in internationalisation. The evolution of the strategies can provide an underpinning for the relevance of IaH in Irish HE, explored in the following sub-sections.

3.3.2.1 First International Education Strategy (2010-2015) and the Hunt Report (2011)

As described in the previous sub-section, the stricter austerity measures introduced in the wake of the GFC could have been one of the factors which led the Irish government to release its first internationalisation strategy, titled 'Investing in Global Relationships – Ireland's International Education Strategy 2010-2015' (MES, 2010). However, the strategy's marked focus on the financial benefits of HE faced considerable criticism from the academic community and scholars (Hazelkorn *et al.*, 2015). A year later, the 'Hunt Report' (DES, 2011) advocated for the marketisation of HE while also asserting the importance of integrating values beyond economic, such as IaH, to ensure the sector's success (DES, 2011, p. 80). It further asserted the importance of creating internationally oriented HEIs, interculturally competent students and promoting partnerships with other countries (p.81).

"At home, internationalisation can contribute to the development of an internationally experienced, inter-culturally adept and skilled population as well as to public and private institutions that are internationally oriented, equipped for such engagement, and attractive to global talent. From a wider perspective, it has a role in contributing to developing knowledge and expertise in partner countries and fostering international development, peace and prosperity."
(DES, 2011, p.81-82)

The need for developing 'internationally experienced, interculturally adept' graduates marks the initial contours of the discourse around IaH in Irish HEIs, even though there was negligible scholarly evidence at the time. Besides IaH, Hunt's report asserted the many benefits of internationalisation beyond revenue generation, and, if implemented, it claimed that it would transform Ireland into a 'leading centre of international education' (p.82). For this to become a reality, the report posited making internationalisation a 'part of a long-term and sustainable process, based on high-quality, holistic and balanced engagement with international partners, requiring a close liaison between the government and Irish HEIs' (p.82).

The differing objectives of the international education strategy (DES, 2010) and the Hunt Report (DES, 2011) could have prompted the creation of an all-in-one education brand that would position and promote Irish HE internationally. The brand 'Education in Ireland', under the auspices of Enterprise Ireland (EI) (formerly known as the 'Irish Trade Board'), was launched in 2011 by the Irish government, mainly to recruit international students into Irish HEIs and promote the English language sector (O'Neill, 2019). Notably, the 'Education in Ireland' brand intended to position Ireland as 'an internationally recognised world leader in delivering high-quality international education' (Irish Government News Service, 2011).

Following the establishment of the 'Education in Ireland' brand and the implementation of an international education strategy, there appeared a notable increase in the enrolment of full-time international students, rising from 10,981 in the 2012-2013 academic year to 35,320 students in 2023-2024, representing a significant growth of over 200% (HEA, 2023, n.d.) to date. Some initiatives that could have contributed to an upsurge of international students choosing Ireland for HE include 'Science without Borders' by the Brazilian government for students to study STEM disciplines (PIE, 2012), 'King Abdullah Scholarship Programme' (IUA, 2013) for students from the Middle East, among other efforts. Scholars such as Gilmartin, Rojas Coppari, and Phelan (2016) suggest that the targeted initiatives through the Education in Ireland brand may have resulted in significant advantages. These can include

tangible benefits, such as economic growth derived from the revenue generated through international student recruitment, as well as intangible benefits, such as enhanced reputation and improved global rankings for Irish HEIs, which were becoming increasingly apparent (p. 10).

Nonetheless, the economic rationale for engaging in internationalisation may reflect a myopic perspective within the Irish government, where pursuing financial objectives precedes the academic goals of HEIs. This perspective can partly account for the initial lack of awareness regarding IaH and its significance for Irish HE, a topic that this study seeks to examine. Importantly, this economic ambition to engage in internationalisation may have expanded its focus to include other dimensions, such as IaH, which began to be more prominently featured in the second international education strategy outlined in the subsequent subsection.

3.3.2.2 Second International Education Strategy (2016-2020) and Indecon Review (2020)

The growing tensions that emerged from underfunding of the HE sector and the strategic push to pursue international students for commercial benefits, as evident in the past international education strategy and the Hunt report, appear to prevail in the second version of Ireland's internationalisation strategy, 'Irish Educated, Globally Connected, an international education strategy for Ireland, 2016-2020' (DES, 2016). This strategy set an ambitious target for international students to represent 15% of the overall student population in Irish HEIs (DES, 2016, p. 31), in line with the government's aim to fulfil the economic objective of engaging in internationalisation.

Despite the renewed emphasis on the economic objective, this strategy appears to subtly extend beyond commercial benefits to include a 'comprehensive approach to education that prepares students, academics and staff to be active and engaged participants in an interconnected global world' (DES, 2016, p.16). The remnants of softer aspects of preparing global citizens can be visible in this second strategy. Notably, this strategy recommended engaging in IaH through internationalising the curricula to improve the quality and experience in teaching and learning (Ibid.). Additionally, it acknowledged the role of IaH in this process; however, there remains a discernible ambiguity regarding its practical implementation within Irish HEIs. It asserts that

"As a strategic priority for the Irish higher education sector, internationalisation will be pursued as an inclusive and holistic strategy for enhancing the quality of the student-learning experience. HEIs should continue to ensure that all graduates are equipped with the skills and attributes required of global citizens by incorporating an international and intercultural dimension into their curricula."
(DES, 2016, p.23)

"Recognising that 'there are tensions surrounding the label "widening participation" in a globally competitive higher education sector, not least reputational risk when trying to recruit international students for prestige', the literature on 'internationalisation at home' calls for synergies between the internationalisation and equality and diversity agendas of institutions to be fostered as the basis for quality enhancement. The approach of our HEIs will continue to support the successful participation of the increasing diversity of students from within Ireland and abroad."
(DES, 2016, p.25)

While the reference to the significance of IaH highlights its increasing relevance, the previously mentioned assertions regarding IaH appear fragmented and lack coherence and contextual clarity. This situation seems to reflect an unfinished discourse transitioning into new themes. Despite acknowledging the importance of IaH, the details surrounding its implementation and progress remain uncertain. This strategy illustrates the gap between policy rhetoric and practice that appear to utilise fads in terminology but are inadequate for pragmatic action on the ground (O'Reilly, 2024; Burke, 2021; Groarke and Durst, 2019).

Moreover, the varying use of terminologies, such as IaH or IoC, in the national strategy may have contributed to some ambiguity in understanding and implementing these concepts within Irish HEIs. Although in the extant literature, IaH and IoC are frequently used interchangeably (Beelen, 2023; de la Garza, 2021; Leask, 2015). However, an internationalised curriculum can be a part, albeit significant, of internationalising a campus. More importantly, embedding a culture of IaH could be embraced as a comprehensive, university-wide strategy encompassing various functions, delivery methods, and services across departments and levels, in addition to curriculum internationalisation efforts.

Following the culmination of the strategic period, the Department of Further and Higher Education, Research, Innovation, and Science (DFHERIS) engaged independent consultants such as Indecon (2020) to review the 2016-20 strategy on internationalisation. However, this review appears to have predominantly been approached from an economic lens. Notably, the findings indicated that the HE sector's target of achieving a 15% representation of full-time international students was nearly met (Indecon, 2020). Consequently, the overall income generated from international student recruitment contributed a total gross value of €2.38

billion to the Irish economy, surpassing the revenue targets set by previous strategies (Indecon, 2020, p.54).

Furthermore, the report estimated that for every €1 of the cost incurred on international students in Ireland, there was a corresponding benefit of €1.67, highlighting the economic value this sector contributes (p.51). While the review assessed quantifiable factors such as the rise in international student enrolment and the resulting revenue, it also noted that the 2016-2020 strategy may have only been partially effective in 'equipping Irish learners with skills and experience to compete internationally' (p.21). This suggests that IaH could have played a role in enhancing the learners' international and intercultural skills and competencies. Moreover, the review emphasised the need to define the broader objectives of the strategy other than economic benefits and measure their successful realisation (Indecon, 2020, p.57), which may encompass IaH.

In essence, the second international education strategy and the review by Indecon may have catalysed the need to examine the broader aspect of internationalisation, which can, in part, be achievable through IaH. The following sub-section investigates the scholarly discourse on IaH that emerged alongside these strategies.

3.4 Scholarly Discourse around IaH

Besides the national strategies, reports and the extensive literature on IaH globally, the literature on IaH is sparse in an Irish context. At the time of the inception of this project in 2021, the only notable studies addressing elements of IaH, although not explicitly labelled as such, were by Clarke and Yang (2021), which explored faculty perspectives on internationalisation in Irish HEIs. Their findings highlighted the instrumentalist objectives of academic staff when engaging in internationalisation at three research-intensive (traditional), publicly funded Irish HEIs, along with a perceived lack of recognition for internationalisation and its connection to career advancement. Furthermore, Ryan's (2020) research examined lecturer engagement with the IoC at Technological University Dublin (TUD), emphasising the importance of implementation as the driving force for internationalising the curriculum, primarily through leadership commitment, staff training, and the establishment of communities of practice (CoPs) in the newly established TU.

Moreover, Clarke and Yang's (2019) paper reflected on strategic approaches to internationalisation and intercultural dialogue from both policy and practice perspectives, advocating for increased resources at local and national levels to support intercultural

dialogue within traditional university curricula. Additionally, Idris *et al.* (2019) investigated the role of peer learning and the presence of international learners in an Irish classroom at a traditional university, revealing the diversity of international students' learning needs and experiences and highlighting the necessity for staff training to enhance these experiences through peer learning initiatives.

Furthermore, O'Connor's (2018) study highlighted the challenges associated with recruiting more international students and their integration within an Irish context, revealing systemic issues that reinforce the homogenisation of international students, as well as social exclusion and racialisation. Additionally, O'Reilly *et al.*'s study (2013) illustrates the experiences of HE professionals and support services working with international students, emphasising the pressing need for staff training to better meet these students' socio-cultural needs. Although these studies focus on some aspects of stakeholder perspectives, strategy and/or curriculum and suggest approaches to improving engagement in internationalisation, the gap in a holistic institutional approach to embedding internationalisation at home for all is imminent.

At the policy level, two years after the release of the second international education strategy by the Irish government in 2016, it is interesting to note that the HEA (2018) published a first-of-its-kind report titled 'the internationalisation of Irish higher education' (Clarke, Yang, and Harmon, 2018) that unpacked multifaceted perspectives of IoHE from the Irish context. It articulated the potential of IaH in equipping students with intercultural competencies and the fragmented efforts made in this direction by Irish HEIs. However, it asserted that more efforts may be needed to develop this area (Clarke *et al.*, 2018, p.67).

Notably, the national discourses on IaH and the dissemination exercises through the present study may contribute to the growing momentum for IaH in Irish HE. Additionally, some Irish HEIs have invested efforts in consolidating resources and guidance on IaH, such as UCD, signposts the Approaches and Tools for IaH (ATIAH, n.d.) on their website. Moreover, UCD's teaching and learning department developed an in-house toolkit to integrate intercultural learning into the curriculum (Quilty and O'Sullivan, 2021). However, specific information regarding implementing these frameworks across all university programmes remains unavailable.

Moreover, UL is working on an Erasmus+ consortium project on 'training and realising innovations in IaH pedagogies (TRIP, n.d.). Some of the recently published outputs from this project include user guides on an institutional inclusive IaH quality assurance framework, a professional development programme for teaching and professional support staff, an

intercultural virtual E-module for students and a best practice guide for inclusive IaH (Ibid.). However, obtaining information about this project required in-depth exploration and seems disconnected from the main university website, indicating the fragmented nature of these initiatives. While this project contributes to the relevance of the present study, it recommends the need for a systematic institutional approach to embedding internationalisation across all programmes and levels beyond isolated instances of good practices, which this study captures from an overarching Irish HE perspective.

Additionally, TUS published a compendium highlighting examples of the internationalisation of the home curriculum at their university (Kelly and O'Donoghue, 2024). Interestingly, this compendium emphasises the importance of IaH in attaining the desired graduate attributes in learners and highlights some of the projects, including the partnerships through the European Universities Initiative (EUI) alliances, as good practice. However, it does not address how these practices form part of the institution-wide approach to IaH. Given this sparse yet developing context of IaH in Irish HEIs, the following sub-section examines the current international education strategy released in 2024 from the prism of IaH.

3.5 IaH in Ireland's Current International Talent and Innovation Strategy (2024-30)

The recently released strategy – 'Global Citizens 2030,' is the newly formed Department of Further and Higher Education, Research, Innovation and Science's first international talent and innovation strategy (DFHERIS, 2024, n.d.) and the third of all international education strategies in Ireland. DFHERIS was established during the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020 with a 'social and economic remit' (DFHERIS, 2024, p.2). This strategy touches on themes beyond the economic ambition of internationalisation, such as developing global perspectives, inclusiveness, and sustainability through internationalisation in Irish HE (Ibid.).

In contrast to the previous strategies, this strategy combines international talent with innovation. The document describes 'international talent' encompassing international students termed 'learners,' researchers, and innovators who can help address societal, social, and climate-related challenges and drive economic development through innovation in Ireland (Ibid.). This strategy release can be considered timely for Irish HE when Ireland celebrates 50 years of membership in the European Union (EU) in 2023 and the upcoming Irish Presidency of the Council of the EU in 2026.

The upcoming Presidency can present a significant platform for Ireland to lead and shape discussions surrounding HE and internationalisation policies at the EU level. By emphasising

the values of equity and inclusivity through IaH, Ireland has the potential to establish itself as a progressive thought leader in this area.

Achieving this vision may require strategic investments in innovative research and developing a robust evidence base regarding various aspects of internationalisation in HE. Additionally, the Presidency provides an opportunity to highlight exceptional research and best practices by facilitating European dialogues on global citizenship and advocating for funding mechanisms that support IaH initiatives at a broader level. Consequently, the lead-up to the Presidency can provide an impetus to the momentum in Irish HEIs towards a systemic embedding of culture for IaH. This endeavour can enable Irish HE to showcase its strengths to Europe and the global community.

This positioning at the European level takes root in the Global Citizen 2030 strategy that intends to position Ireland as a leading knowledge economy within the EU and beyond.

"Ireland globally as a leading knowledge economy with a skills and innovation focus and as a leader in higher education and research, deepening collaboration on an all island and East-West basis within the EU and beyond, attracting talent from around the world to Ireland's international education system and equipping Ireland to compete on the world stage. Ireland's talent and innovation are key to economic prosperity and enhancing diversity, inclusion, and social cohesion."

(DFHERIS, 2024, p.2)

In alignment with its previous iterations, the new strategy has re-emphasised recruiting international talent and preparing learners in Irish HE to compete globally (Ibid.). This is clearly articulated in the statement, 'Ireland seeks to attract talent from around the world to its education and research institutions and to equip Irish-based learners and staff with the skills and experience they need to engage and collaborate internationally' (DFHERIS, 2024, p.31). Despite the renewed focus on recruitment, this strategy can be interpreted as offering a more holistic view of internationalisation than the former releases by highlighting the broader implications of international education in Irish society and economy.

From this study's perspective, the relevance of IaH has been explicitly referenced in various places in the document, as opposed to the past strategies. It asserts that

"In line with European trends, European universities have a key role to play in providing internationalisation-at-home experiences and in developing language and international competencies of graduates. The Further Education and Training (FET) sector is a key enabler for inclusion and cohesion in Ireland's diverse society, building skills, fostering inclusion and facilitating pathways. In a global environment facing many migration and humanitarian crises, developing our understanding of, and empathy for, global challenges can significantly contribute to social cohesion."

(DFHERIS, 2024, p.5)

"Global Citizens 2030 will develop the competencies of Irish-educated learners, researchers and innovators to work in multi-national, multi-cultural and diverse workforces, at home and abroad. It will promote the myriad of opportunities available to learners, staff, researchers and innovators of Irish institutions across a unified tertiary system to develop international competencies in an inclusive way."

(DFHERIS, 2024, p.5)

The intentions outlined in the strategy acknowledge broader aspects of internationalisation that can, in part, be addressed through IaH. These include an inclusive approach to developing intercultural competencies to help Irish learners thrive in multicultural societies and workplaces in Ireland or abroad. The document further elaborates on the critical role of universities, particularly the TUs, as fertile grounds for developing these competencies. It posits that

"The strengths of our university sector, along with the development of Technological Universities and FET Colleges of the Future, also provides excellent opportunities for internationalisation-at-home experiences. We need to build the competencies of our learners, researchers and innovators to succeed on a European and global stage. Working closely with the Department of Education and its strategy 'Languages Connect: Ireland's Strategy for Foreign Languages in Education 2017-2026', DFHERIS will explore the feasibility of developing a Tertiary Foreign Languages Strategy (post-2026) which will align to priority international relationships and promote awareness of the European Union and career opportunities in Europe. Erasmus+ and other mobility programmes provide many opportunities for study abroad, work abroad, green and digital experiences and internationalisation-at-home experiences for students that cannot travel."

(DFHERIS, 2024, p.18)

While the reference to the need for IaH is welcoming, there is a constant juxtaposition of words such as 'internationalisation-at-home' with 'learners that cannot travel' throughout the document, which may warrant further consideration. As evident from the extant literature, IaH seeks to provide an internationalised experience to 'all students' in a domestic environment regardless of their participation in mobility experiences (Beelen, 2023). Although the strategy retains its predominant focus on international student recruitment and

student mobility through Erasmus+, as in its past editions, it argues the need to develop IaH in Irish HEIs. It indicates that

"We will work closely with Irish HEIs to support the development of innovative internationalisation-at-home experiences for learners that cannot undertake physical travel. We will develop our evidence base to analyse participation patterns across institutions, programmes and learner profiles to identify areas which need particular attention. Greater evidence is needed also to match the international competencies of graduates with reference to critical and high-level skills needs, skills shortages and research and innovation intensity targets of the domestic economy."
(DFHERIS, 2024, p.20)

While the government supports Irish HEIs in developing IaH in their context, it recognises the inadequacy of the evidence base in assessing the long-term impact of internationalisation. Moreover, there is an imprecision around the mechanisms for supporting and evaluating the progress of IaH initiatives.

Overall, this new strategy, *Global Citizens 2030*, presents a positive development; however, its effectiveness in bridging the gap between policy rhetoric and actual implementation remains to be demonstrated. This current strategy appears to portray strategic shifts from primarily economic to include the social, cultural, and environmental aspects of engaging in international education. Themes such as 'excellence, equality, diversity, and inclusion; international and multi-cultural competencies; sustainability; international talent; and learners' are now part of the lexicon of the Irish government and can offer an insightful perspective for the present study. However, it is worth noting that specific national funding mechanisms and accountability measures tied to the IaH implementation have not yet been clearly defined.

The following sub-section offers an overview of other national strategies and funding schemes that have the potential to contribute positively to the development of IaH within Irish HEIs.

3.6 IaH in Other National Strategies and Funding Schemes

Whilst IaH appears as one of the important approaches to developing global citizenship in graduates from Irish HEIs, as highlighted in the international talent and innovation strategy—*Global Citizens 2030* (DFHERIS, 2024), there is currently a lack of an explicit policy and/or funding scheme directly aimed at advancing this objective. Nonetheless, a

more thorough analysis of various government strategies and associated funding channels reveals some indirect connections to IaH, as illustrated in *Table 2*.

Table 2: IaH in other National Strategies and Funding Schemes

Strategy	Funding Scheme	Government Agency	Link to IaH
Global Citizenship Education Strategy (2021-25)	Global Citizenship Education (GCE) Grant	Irish Aid – Department of Foreign Affairs and Aid	“Increased interest in GCE across HEIs is reflected in their commitment to advance the SDGs and their identification of global citizenship as a core graduate competency. Initiatives such as the An Taisce supported Green Campus and Universities of Sanctuary, Ireland are further evidence of this. There are many opportunities to engage leadership and management of HEIs, as well as academic staff, to strengthen integration of GCE into all aspects of campus life, from curriculum reform to training of lecturers, to policies and research.” (p. 22)
Migrant Integration Strategy (2017-23)	National Integration Fund Communities Integration Fund	Department of Children, Disability and Equality	‘Intercultural awareness’ and ‘capacity building’ towards integrating migrants and host communities (n.d).
A Strategic Action Plan for Equity of Access, Participation and Success in Higher Education (2022-2028)	National Access Plan	Higher Education Authority	“Fostering equity in the student experience so all students can avail of the opportunities that a full and vibrant student experience offers, including international mobility.” (p.30)
			“The new phase of capital investment calls will encourage collaborative proposals from further and higher education institutions and emphasise universal design principles and fostering inclusion in all its facets.” (p.79)
Ireland’s Strategy for Foreign Languages in Education (2017-2026)	Languages Connect Campaign Funding	Department of Education and Youth	‘The need to raise awareness in society at large of the benefits of varied language capacity for intercultural understanding, for positive citizenship and for job and career opportunities.’ (p.15) to promote their foreign languages courses and increase participation in foreign language learning at third level’ (p. 32).
European Universities Initiative (Alliances)	Erasmus + National Funding Scheme	Department of Further and Higher Education, Research, Innovation and Science European Commission	“EUI membership allows Irish universities to harness the collective potential of their partners in delivering the objectives of Global Citizens 2030 – Ireland’s International Talent and Innovation Strategy. This ensures Ireland is an effective contributor in the delivery of the EU’s long-term joint strategies.” (n.d)
National Forum for the Enhancement of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education	Teaching and Learning Enhancement Projects	Higher Education Authority	Open calls for projects that can be linked to IaH(n.d).
HEA’s Centre of Excellence for Gender Equality	Equality, Diversity and Inclusion Enhancement Fund	Higher Education Authority	Advancing awareness and understanding of intersectionality and multidimensional approaches to equality, diversity and inclusion (n.d).

Table 2 showcases the connections with IaH through other national strategies and funding schemes. For instance, the Global Citizenship Education (GCE) Grant offers funding assistance for training and curriculum development focused on integrating vulnerable communities within Irish society, addressing issues related to refugees and migration, and broadly enhancing '*awareness and understanding of global development issues among the Irish public*' (p.30). Additional funding sources may include the National Integration Fund (NIF) and the Communities Integration Fund (CIF), which focus on themes such as 'intercultural awareness' and 'capacity building' to facilitate the integration of migrants and host communities.

Moreover, some aspects of the HEA's National Access Plan can be viewed as aligned with IaH initiatives, particularly by offering funding support to enhance participation from socio-economically disadvantaged groups. This includes students who are migrants or refugees, those who have gone through the international protection process, students from ethnic minority backgrounds, as well as members of the Irish Traveller and Roma communities, and individuals with disabilities. Irish HEIs have the opportunity to apply for funding through this plan to promote international experiences for these groups.

Furthermore, the Languages Connect Campaign funding aims to promote and enhance learner engagement in foreign languages at Irish HEIs. This initiative seeks to develop language skills that nurture intercultural understanding, encourage responsible citizenship, and improve employability, aligning with some objectives of IaH. The policy and funding schemes include opportunities for Erasmus+ mobility abroad, CPD initiatives, and Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL), among other approaches, to achieve these goals.

Importantly, as part of the European Universities Initiative (EUI), the European University Alliances (EUA) can be a significant enabler for advancing IaH in Irish HEIs (Frame and Curylo, 2024; Gunn, 2020). Supported by the Erasmus+ program, this initiative is further strengthened by contributions from the Irish government's DFHERIS, which provides supplementary funding to encourage efforts the efforts of Irish HEIs engaged in these alliances, potentially encompassing IaH (DFHERIS, 2024). The EUA, conceived under the EUI, is designed to build a European Education Area (EEA) that promotes long-term, strategic, and sustainable cooperation among EU countries. The goals of this initiative include improving the international competitiveness of HEIs in Europe, upholding European values and identity, and enhancing the capacity to address societal challenges

through providing high-quality education and training for all students, staff, and the wider community (European Commission, n.d.).

At present, thirteen publicly funded Irish HEIs are part of the consortia involved in these alliances, which could serve as catalysts to enhance the international competitiveness of Irish HEIs and create greater opportunities for developing IaH. Scholars such as Gunn (2020) suggest that 'EUI has the potential to be a driver of IaH through not just curriculum reform and the promotion of foreign language learning, but through bringing international experiences to the home campus' (p.25).

This perspective is further corroborated by Frame and Curylo (2024), that consider it as a means to 'bring Europe home,' stating that 'the EUI can be seen as an attempt to overcome barriers associated with mobility, encouraging HEIs to go beyond existing forms of cooperation to bring Europe home to the wider higher education community' (p.334). Moreover, various scholars perceive EUI as a means of developing intercultural competence and global citizenship among participating HEIs, which may align with the goals of IaH (Jager, 2025; Kokkinos, Samaras, and Iatrellis, 2024; Ferencz and Rumbley, 2022).

Besides EUI, the funding available through the national EDI fund, HEA's National Teaching and Learning Forum, the Irish University Association (IUA) for universities, the Technological Higher Education Authority (THEA) for technological universities, and Erasmus+ actions can be leveraged to enhance capacity and promote a culture of IaH in Irish HEIs.

While these national policies and funding programs touch upon aspects of IaH, they may not fully encapsulate its scope due to a lack of explicit alignment with IaH. This situation may lead to uncertainty regarding the availability of national support for funding IaH initiatives, as relevant information might not always be readily accessible or clearly understood by university staff. Despite this ambiguity, there is an increasing recognition of the importance of IaH in Irish HEIs, which is reflected in their strategic plans, examined in the subsequent sub-section.

3.7 IaH in Publicly Funded Irish HEIs Strategic Plans

The inclusion of IaH in the current international education (talent and innovation) strategy provides a scaffolding for its development in Irish HEIs through its strategic plans. Whilst the strategic periods for each institution differ and inherently do not correspond with the release of the new strategy, this sub-section presents the current status of IaH in Irish publicly

funded institutions. The fourteen publicly funded institutions comprise seven traditional universities, five technological universities and two institutes of technology (DFHERIS, 2024). *Table 3* below presents the current positioning of IaH in the strategic plans of each publicly funded institution.

Table 3: IaH in Publicly Funded Irish HEIs Strategic Plans

Institution	Type	Strategic Plan	Reference to IaH
University College Dublin (UCD)	Traditional University	Breaking Boundaries UCD Strategy to 2030	"We will deepen our global collaborations to advance the intercultural experience and competencies of UCD students, and to develop their ambition and ability to make a contribution to the world." (p.19)
University College Cork (UCC)	Traditional University	Securing our Future 2023-28	"Internationalise our curriculum and our research through strategic partnerships and mobility." (p.12)
University of Galway (UG)	Traditional University	Of Galway, for the World 2025-30	"Our students engage with global issues as part of an internationally connected academic community, rooted in our vibrant city with its distinctive identity, culture and heritage. They encounter global perspectives and experiences here in Galway and through student mobility programmes abroad, developing capabilities for inter-cultural working and collaboration into the future." (p.25)
Maynooth University (MU)	Traditional University	Excellence, Opportunity and Impact 2023-28	"We will embed international education opportunities for all within our curriculum and our educational offerings, with a particular focus on students for whom international experiences have been difficult to access." (n.d.)
			"Successful internationalisation of our campus requires that we bring a global lens to the full spectrum of education and research activity on our campus. Therefore, we will develop a university-wide, integrated approach to our internationalisation work with initiatives that embed internationalisation across our campus." (n.d.)
University of Limerick (UL)	Traditional University	UL@50 2019-24	"Embedding global perspectives into the curriculum, fostering cross-cultural competencies and growing international partnerships." (p.25)
Trinity College Dublin (TCD)	Traditional University	Community and Connection 2020-25	"At home, we will increase mobility for staff and students at all levels and embed internationalisation deeper in the curriculum and in campus life, ensuring that all our students are better prepared for lives and careers as global citizens." (p.36)
			"Develop teaching and learning initiatives to embed an international perspective into the curriculum for all students and across all disciplines." (p.37)
Dublin City University (DCU)	Traditional University	Transformation for an Unscripted Future 2023-28	No references available

Table 3: IaH in Publicly Funded Irish HEIs Strategic Plans

Institution	Type	Strategic Plan	Reference to IaH
Technological University Dublin (TUD)	Technological University	Creating a better World, together 2024-28	“Our ambition is to enable our students develop awareness and competencies of operating and working in multi-cultural contexts” (p.7)
Munster Technological University (MTU)	Technological University	Our Shared Vision 2022-2027	“MTU will cultivate a ‘global graduate’ mindset with valuable life and employment skills by internationalising the student journey.” (p.33)
			“MTU will have a curriculum based on international best practice” (p.33)
Technological University of the Shannon: Midlands Midwest (TU Shannon)	Technological University	Connecting and Creating 2023-26	No references available
Atlantic technological University (ATU)	Technological University	Shaping the Future Together 2024-28	“Cultivating global engagement and cultural diversity, integrating diverse perspectives into teaching and assessment practices, while preparing students for global citizenship through culturally responsive curriculum and learning environments” (p.2)
South East Technological University (SETU)	Technological University	Connecting for Impact 2023-28	“In support of a globally relevant and internationalised curriculum, extend international mobility options across all programmes and to all students, to include the provision of internationalisation at home opportunities.” (p.45)
			“Develop an Internationalisation at Home Strategy and identify requirements with regard to staff CPD, international events at home (e.g., International Week) and internationalisation at home visibility.” (p.58)
Dundalk Institute of Technology (DkIT)	Institute of Technology	Partnership for Growth 2024-28	“Continue to promote staff and student international collaborations, and develop internationalisation-at-home, in order to foster intercultural competence, develop global perspectives in programmes and increase student participation in Erasmus+” (p.49)
Dun Laoghaire Institute of Art, Design and Technology (IADT)	Institute of Technology	Towards a University for the Creative Industries 2024-28	“We will enhance the internationalisation of our curricula, embracing and recognising other cultures and promoting diversity across all our programmes.” (n.d.)

The institutional strategic plans presented in *Table 3* illustrate the increasing relevance of IaH within the publicly funded Irish HEIs. Interestingly, DCU and TUS do not explicitly reference or allude to IaH in their institutional strategic plans. However, TUS has contributed to the scholarly conversation surrounding IaH by publishing a compendium detailing its practices across various disciplines (Kelly and O'Donoghue, 2024). Ultimately, twelve out of fourteen publicly funded institutions highlight IaH in their plans, establishing its significance of IaH in present-day Irish HEIs.

Moreover, for institutions that have referenced IaH and established key performance indicators, there appears to be a gap between how IaH is perceived and practised in the institutions. The gap could be due to IaH being conceived as discreet actions or initiatives rather than an integrated approach. This could, in part, explain different conceptual understandings of IaH. Additionally, most Irish HEIs consider enhancing classroom diversity by recruiting international students and mobility abroad as key parameters to an internationalised experience, as evident from their plans, which Jones (2017) identifies as a 'misconception' regarding IaH (p. 23).

Additionally, equality, diversity and inclusion (EDI) are imperative in internationalisation for many institutions. This can often be construed as an unintentional consequence where EDI becomes a competing priority with IaH rather than being seen as interdependent. Consequently, this raises the need to investigate the conceptual constructions, opportunities, and challenges associated with developing IaH in Irish HEIs, constituting this study's primary research question. This inquiry also underpins the potential for a guiding framework that can assist in embedding a culture of IaH, thereby presenting the research aims and offering both theoretical and practical contributions through this study, elucidated in *Chapters (4), (6) and (7)*.

3.8 Conclusion

In summary, some of the main themes from the literature review presented in *Chapters (2) and (3)* provide a foundational underpinning for IaH, considering its development globally and the need for a guiding framework for embedding a culture of IaH in Irish HE institutions. The concept appears to be in the advanced stages of development in some HEIs globally. However, it is relatively underexplored in the Irish context. This is demonstrated by the extant literature presented in this chapter, which examined the scholarly discourse, national strategic and policy documents and institutional strategic plans from the prism of IaH.

Furthermore, the dearth of literature on IaH in the Irish HE context and the prevailing focus on achieving financial goals through internationalisation overshadow the academic goals. This situation is exacerbated by decreased funding and the pressure to generate revenue by recruiting international students into Irish HEIs. Notwithstanding the challenges, the iterations in international education and institutional strategies reflect a shift in thinking towards a comprehensive view of internationalisation that situates the growing importance of IaH.

Notably, IaH emerges as a more practical and affordable means for developing graduates with intercultural competencies and global citizenship, including those students who cannot participate in an Erasmus exchange or spend a semester or year abroad for various reasons. Moreover, the increasing global uncertainty and conflicts underscore the importance of providing students with an internationalised curriculum at their home institution that not only aids in developing intercultural competence but can also contribute to ideals of inclusion, peace, justice, and global citizenship.

This study seeks to bridge the existing gap and contribute to developing a comprehensive knowledge base, theory, and practice while offering a guiding framework to assist Irish HEIs intending to embed a culture of IaH. These are the central research questions for this study arising from the reviewed literature. This guiding framework has the potential to fulfil some of the key objectives highlighted in the Global Citizens 2030 national strategy (DFHERIS, 2024), including the enhancement of intercultural competencies and the development of global citizenship among graduates of Irish HEIs. The following chapter outlines the theoretical framework of this study, which can help address the research questions.

CHAPTER 4: THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

4.1 Introduction

The theoretical framework for this study conceptualises IaH in the Irish HE context through theories of organisational and curriculum design and change management. Organisational design can be interpreted through theories such as stakeholder identification and salience (Mitchell, Agle, and Wood, 1997), stakeholder culture (Jones, Felps, and Bigley, 2007), and job demands and resources (Bakker and Demerouti, 2007). For developing a culture of IaH through the curricula, the conceptual framework for an internationalised curriculum by Leask (2015) is considered appropriate. Finally, to embed IaH, theories of change management focusing on organisational culture and systems thinking are deemed suitable. These include the organisational culture transformational framework (Armenakis, Brown, and Mehta, 2011) and the learning organisation through a systems thinking approach (Senge, 1990).

The combination of these theories is unique, influences the study's design, data collection, and analysis stages, and contributes to addressing the central research questions of this study outlined in *Chapter 1 (sub-section 1.6)*. For simplicity, the sub-sections in this chapter are organised into three categories: (1) organisational design theories, (2) curriculum design theory, and lastly, (3) change management theories.

4.2 Theoretical Underpinnings

Leedy and Ormrod (2005) define theories as an 'organised body of concepts and principles that explain a particular phenomenon' (p.4), demonstrating 'how and why something functions the way it does' (Johnson and Christensen, 2007, p. 7). The theoretical plurality, i.e. a combination of theories, can be constructs (concepts) and propositions (relationship between those constructs) that can 'collectively present a logical, systematic and coherent explanation of a phenomenon of interest within some assumptions and boundary conditions' (Wright, 2022, p.6). The theoretical framework can be grounded in literature reviews and the reflected 'views' (Ibid.). Moreover, it can utilise deductive reasoning to generate highly structured ideas (Akpabio, 2015).

In view of the above, the theoretical construct of this chapter comprises theories that can facilitate holistically and systemically embedding a culture of IaH. Moreover, they respond to the central research questions that examine the opportunities and challenges in developing

a culture of IaH in Irish HEIs and ascertain the strategies that can be adopted to embed such a culture. Consistent with the research questions, the theories of organisational and curriculum design and change management were deemed appropriate and are examined in the following sub-sections.

4.2.1 Organisational Design Theories

Organisational design can be considered 'a configuration of the structure, processes and behaviour' (Overholt, 1997, p.22), providing a 'foundation of organisational action' (Miller, Greenwood and Prakash, 2009, p.273). As such, applying theories of organisational design in higher education (HE) settings can be helpful when managing stakeholder relationships, resources, and tasks, aligning with organisational goals and vision (Feeney and Edge, 2015). This approach can contribute to HEIs embracing flexible, open, innovative and agile systems responding to changing internal and external dynamics (Ibid.).

In this study, the organisational design theories can partly aid in addressing the first research question that investigates the opportunities and challenges in developing a culture of IaH in the Irish HE context. In order to address this research question, it is imperative to identify the key stakeholders that partake in and influence the implementation of IaH in an Irish HE setting. Some of these key stakeholders comprise the participants of this study. This subsection explicates the rationale and application of the theories in organisational design such as stakeholder identification and salience (Mitchell, Agle, and Wood, 1997), stakeholder culture (Jones, Felps, and Bigley, 2007), and job demands and resources (Bakker and Demerouti, 2007) recognising key stakeholders and ascertain their engagement that can be necessary to implement and embed a culture of IaH.

4.2.1.1 Stakeholder Identification and Salience (Mitchell, Agle, and Wood, 1997)

Identifying relevant stakeholders and understanding their influence can be helpful in complex HE settings to balance the needs of multiple actors, aligning with organisational vision and ambition. In this regard, the 'stakeholder identification and salience theory' by Mitchell, Agle and Wood (MAW) (1997) can provide a helpful lens in identifying such stakeholders in accordance with what MAW describes as 'power, legitimacy and urgency' who can prioritise, implement and embed a culture for IaH. This theory originated from the limited scholarship on stakeholder relationships during the time and was presented at the 'stakeholder Toronto conferences' in the 1990s (Wood, Mitchell, Agle and Bryan, 2021, p. 198).

As a point of departure, MAW utilise the then-popular definition of a '*stakeholder*' by Freeman (1984), which refers to 'any group or individual who can affect or is affected by the achievement of the organisation's objectives' (p.4). As such, MAW posit a stakeholder identification typology that considers three attributes, namely 'power, legitimacy and urgency' to understand 'who and what really counts' (p. 872). In this context, *power* is the extent to which one can 'gain access to coercive, utilitarian, or normative means to impose its will in the relationship' (p.865), recognising its transitory nature of gaining and losing. *Legitimacy*, on the other hand, is 'individual, organisational and socially accepted structures or behaviours' (p.866). Lastly, *urgency* is understood as the degree of 'time-sensitivity towards attending the claim and criticality, i.e. the importance of the claim or the relationship to the stakeholder' (p.867).

Notably, this theory assumes that managerial perceptions prevail regarding *stakeholder salience*, which indicates 'the degree of importance attached to the stakeholders, as interpreted by the manager when choosing from the competing stakeholder claims' (p.873). MAW assert that a company's management can assess stakeholder salience based on the presence, absence or combination of the three attributes- power, legitimacy and urgency and prioritise those stakeholders that blend all three aspects (p.879). However, the degree of each of these attributes depends on the manager's decision-making (Ibid.). MAW claim their theory can offer a 'more systematic sorting by managers of stakeholder-manager relationships as these relationships attain and relinquish salience in an ongoing business's dynamics' (p.880).

Whilst the MAW theory of stakeholder identification and salience has been widely cited in the last twenty-eight years since its origin, it emanated and was primarily applied in business, corporate strategy and general management settings, with minimal applications in HE such as identifying stakeholders for a university special-purpose identity in Poland (Malwina, 2023) and key collaborators for data literacy in a US HEI (Corrall, 2019). The limited application of this theory in HE could be attributed to some of the critiques of the triad approach of this theory, suggesting it perpetuates 'manager bias' (Currie, Seaton and Wesley, 2009), neglecting 'fringe stakeholders' (Hart and Sharma, 2004), lacking 'moral legitimacy' (Neville, Bell and Whitwell, 2011) and overlooking 'organisational life cycle' (Jawahar and McLaughlin, 2018).

Notwithstanding the aforementioned limitations, the inclination of this theory towards managerial perceptions based on 'power, legitimacy and urgency' can be important in the context of this study, where IaH competes with other incumbent priorities such as

international student recruitment and mobility abroad and more recently, emerging priorities such as EDI and sustainability when internationalising an HEI, highlighted in *Chapter 6*.

The application of this theory is primarily to identify the stakeholders that may need or be impacted by IaH, as well as their positionality and salience towards implementing and embedding IaH, amongst other competing priorities. The MAW theory has enabled the identification of stakeholders, such as students, academic staff, academic managers (head of departments), international officers, and senior managers, such as the Vice President-Global of Irish HEIs, as relevant participants for this study. Besides Irish HEIs, stakeholders such as policymakers and sectoral networks in Irish HE have also been deemed suitable participants. Additionally, staff involved in internationalisation within academic support units at best practice institutions² in Europe and the UK have been considered suitable participants to offer a comparative perspective. Each participant category's varying power, legitimacy, and urgency levels can impact how IaH is understood, implemented and embedded in complex Irish HE settings.

4.2.1.2 Stakeholder Culture (Jones, Felps, and Bigley, 2007)

While the stakeholder identification and salience theory can facilitate identifying key actors for embedding IaH, the 'stakeholder culture theory' (Jones, Felps, and Bigley, 2007) refines the theoretical foundation by focusing on 'organisational values,' which in this study's case can impact internationalisation efforts within Irish HEIs. To this end, Jones, Felps, and Bigley (2007) extend the individual salience of the MAW theory (1997) to an *organisational culture*, which comprises collective beliefs, vision, values, conduct and practices that can influence stakeholder identity and salience (Jones, Felps, and Bigley, 2007, p.151). The theorists provide a continuum of '*stakeholder culture*,' which they define as 'beliefs, values and practices that have evolved for solving stakeholder related problems and otherwise managing relationships with other stakeholders' (p.142).

As such, the stakeholder culture continuum appears to be foregrounded in ethics and value orientations within self-regarding to other-regarding cultures as per their continuum (Ibid.). The continuum demonstrates that managerial perceptions can be influenced in different cultural settings, such as egoistic and instrumentalist self-regarding/interest-based cultures in

² These HEIs were considered 'best practice' because of their advanced nature in implementing and monitoring IaH within their HEIs, evidenced by their innovative approaches, scholarly work, reputation and recognition in the field (Hénard, Diamond and Roseveare, 2012).

organisations may prioritise stakeholder power (p.152). In contrast, moral and altruistic cultures may prioritise stakeholder legitimacy (Ibid.).

Interestingly, the stakeholder culture theory, similar to MAW stakeholder identification and salience (1997) theory, has antecedents in the business context, with some application in HE settings, as evident in the literature. Some studies in HE utilise stakeholder culture theory to create value in transnational HE through stakeholder engagement between an Australian and Chinese university (Bolton and Nie, 2010). Meanwhile, others utilise the theory to assess students' legitimacy in universities in implementing corporate social responsibility (CSR) (Lunenbergh, 2014) or determine the quality of administrative services in a South African institution (Mfecane, Iwu and Mohsam, 2022).

Whilst the stakeholder culture can bring the ethical consideration of managerial decision-making of stakeholder claims at an organisational level, the theory has been criticised for its assumption of homogeneity within stakeholder culture groups that can overlook the diversity of perspectives in multicultural and complex HE environments (Johnson-Cramer, Phillips, Fadlallah, Berman and Elms, 2022; Weitzner and Deutsch, 2019). Moreover, the overemphasis on 'culture' can neglect other influential factors, such as economic, technological, social, regional or political influences, and resultantly, may not fully capture the spectrum of stakeholder salience (Ibid.).

Nonetheless, the stakeholder culture theory can bring a qualitative difference in understanding organisational cultures and their stakeholder influence by including ethical concerns and emotional connections in managerial decision-making (Jones, Felps, and Bigley, 2007, p.153). These can help understand the rationale behind managers prioritising stakeholder relationships in a dynamic environment in which an organisation operates (Ibid.).

In this study, the stakeholder culture theory can signpost collective managerial behaviour and perceptions towards stakeholder prioritisation for IaH. The theory can help interpret the impact of institutional cultures in shaping internationalisation efforts in Irish HEIs. Specifically, HEIs with egoist or self-regarding cultures are more likely to engage with IaH at a superficial level and leverage IaH for marketing efforts rather than focusing on building capacity as a transformational practice. In contrast, HEIs with other-regarding, moralist or altruist cultures will attempt to embed IaH to benefit all students and staff, fostering intercultural competencies and global citizenship.

Specifically, staff with an instrumentalist culture may value investing in IaH if accompanied by incentives, as opposed to the staff in altruist cultures that will champion IaH owing to its value despite the incentives. Similarly, policymakers or influencers in egoist cultures may engage with IaH with a transactional motive to attract more international students for financial gain. However, in instrumentalist cultures, IaH can be recognised as a valuable approach and supported with funding incentives and guidance for implementation. Furthermore, the moralist or altruist cultures can focus on long-term sustainability by prioritising it and embedding it across all levels in an HEI to benefit all students. Ultimately, the salience from an ethical consideration in this theory can influence policy makers/influencers and senior leadership decisions supporting/impeding IaH and engaging with other stakeholder groups, such as staff and students, aligning with the institution's strategic priorities and interests.

4.2.1.3 Job Demands and Resources (Bakker and Demerouti, 2007)

Lastly, in organisational design theories, besides stakeholder dynamics, examining the roles, responsibilities, and motivation impacting the efforts to embed IaH in Irish HEIs is crucial. In this respect, the 'job-demand resources (JD-R)' model (Bakker, Demerouti, and Sanz-Vergel, 2014) appears relevant. In this model, the *job demands* refer to 'physical, social, or organisational aspects of the job that require sustained physical or mental effort and are therefore associated with certain physiological and psychological costs' and *resources* can mean 'physical, psychological, social, or organisational aspects of work that help cope with demands, give meaning and stimulate personal growth, learning, and development' (Bakker and Mostert, 2024; Bakker and Demerouti, 2007).

In view of the above definitions, the job demands can comprise workload, institutional barriers, stress, burnout or resistance to change, and resources can include continuous professional development (CPD), autonomy, incentives or rewards and institutional support, to mention a few. This model explains the correlation between the available job demands and resources with employee well-being and performance through 'burnout and engagement' (Bakker *et al.*, 2014, p. 399). Freudenberger (1974) defines *burnout* as a 'state of mental and physical exhaustion caused by one's professional life that can lead to the extinction of motivation or incentive, especially where one's devotion to a cause or relationship fails to produce the desired results' (p.159). In contrast, Schaufeli, Martinez, Pinto, Salanova, and Bakker (2002) define *work engagement* as a positive, fulfilling, work-related state of mind characterised by high energy, vigour, dedication, and absorption (p. 74).

This model synthesises and builds on the characteristics of some of the previous theories, such as the resource-based view of the firm (Hillman and Keim, 2001), effort–reward imbalance model (Siegrist, 1996), job demands–control model (Karasek, 1979), resource dependence theory (Pfeffer and Salancik, 1978), to name a few. The JD-R theory can scaffold the motivation or lack thereof and stakeholder salience to access resources.

This model, rooted in organisational psychology and behaviour settings in HE, has garnered wide traction. For instance, the model has been utilised to assess student burnout in Hungarian HE (Jagodics and Szabó, 2023); occupational well-being among public university faculty in the Czech Republic (Mudrak, Zabrodska, Kveton, Jelinek, Blatny, Solcova and Machovcova, 2018); burnout and engagement among Australian academics (Boyd, Bakker, Pignata, Winefield, Gillespie and Stough, 2011) and employees working in an institute for higher professional education in the Netherlands (Bakker, Demerouti and Euwema, 2005), to mention a few. More recently, building on the success of the JD-R model, it has been extended to the study demand-resources (SD-R) to include student well-being in higher education (Bakker and Mostert, 2024).

Whilst the JD-R model can help ascertain employee motivation and engagement, Bakker and Demerouti (2017); Bauer, Hämmig, Schaufeli, and Taris (2014); Van den Broeck, De Cuyper, De Witte, and Vansteenkiste (2010) criticise the model arguing that it may skew towards individual experiences in comparison to the collective organisation's vision, values and systems. Moreover, the idealistic assumption of achieving equilibrium between job demands and resources can run the risk of oversimplifying complex HE structures, which may not hold for the dynamic circumstances in which HEIs operate (Ibid.). Notwithstanding the individualistic approach of this model, it has the potential to address individual motivation and engagement that can collectively influence the subcultures and culture of an institution, as evident in the wide applications of this model.

In the context of this study, the JD-R model can provide a lens through which to investigate the enablers and blockers for embedding a culture of IaH. For instance, cultivating a culture of IaH can entail job demands such as designing an internationalised curriculum, managing student and staff diversity, navigating funding constraints and institutional policies alongside competing priorities in teaching, learning, and research. These job demands can increase workload, stress and burnout if not appropriately addressed. The resources, on the other hand, such institutional commitment through policies, funding and reward and recognition systems encouraging IaH efforts, academic autonomy, investment in CPD for staff, training

programmes to develop intercultural competence in students, collaborative networks and alliances can contribute to increased job satisfaction and performance and provide a further impetus for IaH efforts.

Moreover, the extension through SD-R can provide a theoretical underpinning for enhancing student engagement by addressing student workload and incentivising their engagement in IaH efforts through reward and recognition. Undeniably, if the resources outweigh the job or study demands in both JD-R and SD-R, they can contribute more effectively to embedding IaH than vice-versa. Therefore, understanding the relationships between job demands and resources can underpin efforts to sustain IaH practices by mediating individual experiences with institutional structures. Consequently, it can help address the first research question for this study, which is identifying the opportunities and challenges in developing a culture of IaH.

4.2.2 Curriculum Design Theory

The curriculum is the sine quo non in higher education and is largely the central focus for various stakeholders such as educators, policymakers, government, learners and society (Khan and Law, 2015; Alberta Education, 2012). According to Ornstein and Hunkins (2017), *curriculum design* can encompass 'the way we conceptualise the curriculum and arrange its major components such as subject matter content, instructional methods and materials, learner experiences or activities to provide direction and guidance as we develop curriculum' (p. 16). In this respect, a *curriculum design theory* can provide an 'arrangement of ideas explaining how the curriculum works and ways in which we can teach what we think is important' (Kelting-Gibson, 2013, p. 53). This sub-section presents the conceptual framework for an internationalised curriculum (Leask, 2015) as a theoretical construct for curriculum design for this study.

4.2.2.1 Conceptual Framework for an Internationalised Curriculum (Leask, 2015)

As such, organisational design theories can provide an insight into stakeholders' salience, culture, job demands and resources, whereas curriculum design theories, such as the conceptual framework for an internationalised curriculum (Leask, 2015), can offer a pedagogical grounding for embedding IaH through formal and informal curriculum, as elucidated in *Chapter 2 (sub-section 2.5.1)*. This framework emphasises a structured, multi-dimensional view of curriculum, attributing importance to interdisciplinary approaches in design (Leask, 2015, p.2). It comprises internationalising formal, informal and hidden curricula requiring course, programme, and institutional-level changes relevant to emerging

professional practices in disciplines and the institutional, local, regional, national, and international contextual influences facing an HEI (Ibid.).

Furthermore, Leask (2015) asserts that this framework can facilitate the development of academic staff's ability to design a curriculum, such as crafting explicit internationalised learning outcomes and organising teaching and learning in light of emerging and dominant paradigms in and across the disciplines (Ibid.). It has the potential to enhance teaching and learning and enable the development of intercultural and global competencies in students that may be essential to addressing societal and shared global challenges (Zadravec and Kočar, 2024; Beelen, 2019; Beelen and Jones, 2015).

Moreover, in their recent work, Leask (2022) highlights the importance of the framework in contributing to the role of 'curriculum as a system' that may embed internationalisation more systematically by not just focusing on the 'curriculum design, content, pedagogy, learning activities, and assessment, but also how these are affected by much broader issues such as institutional, national, regional, and global contexts' (p.169). The framework by Leask (2015) can provide a holistic view of the curriculum development process when internationalising courses, programmes and disciplines, considering contextual factors. This can lead to systematically cultivating intercultural and global competencies relevant to this study (Leask, 2015, p. 4).

Whilst this framework, which has Australian origins, is of significant importance when approaching an internationalised curriculum from a design and a system point of view, it is important to acknowledge some of its limitations. For instance, some scholars have criticised the framework as an Anglo-centric concept suited to the Western world that does not fully accommodate the realities of indigenous systems in the non-Western parts of the world (Kassaye, 2025; Pap, 2024; Bamberger and Morris, 2024; Eten, 2023). Moreover, Bovill (2015) argues that the framework has given insufficient consideration to conceptualising curriculum and assessments, leveraging staff diversity and the students' role in co-designing the curriculum.

However, despite some limitations, the framework can provide a valuable point of departure in attempting to internationalise curricula at institutions. This is evident in a vast scholarly basis citing the framework's relevance in different contexts. Leask's framework was also utilised in the Irish context, such as examples of different approaches to IoC at TUS (Kelly and O'Donoghue, 2024), lecturers' engagement with IoC at TU Dublin (Ryan, Faulkner, Dillane and Flood, 2022; Ryan, 2020) and Irish scholars examining other contexts such as

internationalising Architectural curriculum in Germany, the Netherlands and the UK (Cleary, 2015); understanding IoC through the lens of staff and senior management in ten countries, including Ireland (Clifford and Montgomery, 2017), to mention a few.

As outlined in *Chapter 3 (sub-section 3.5)*, Ireland's new talent and innovation strategy, Global Citizens 2030, promotes the development of global graduates through Irish HEIs that can live, work and thrive in multinational and multicultural societies and workplaces at home or abroad (DFHERIS, 2024, p.2). Moreover, the strategy highlights the potential of IaH to develop these international competencies of graduates, which can prepare them to become global citizens (DFHERIS, 2024, p.5). The concept of global citizenship and the 'curriculum as a system' approach is rooted in the internationalised curriculum framework by Leask (2015) and, therefore, is considered appropriate for this study (Leask, 2022, p.169). This framework has the potential to identify gaps in practices in curriculum design and aid in addressing the research question of this study focused on identifying opportunities and challenges in implementing IaH and contributing to a guiding framework for IaH, which is elucidated in the discussion *Chapter 6*.

4.2.3 Change Management Theories

Although as old as human history, the concept of change management still holds relevance in today's discourse (Ratana, Raksmeay and Danut, 2020). Meyer and Botha (2000) describe *change management* as a 'process of mobilising resources through the planning, coordinating and implementing initiatives and activities to bring about the desired change' (p.224). Interestingly, HEIs operate in a dynamic environment that can make managing change paramount, considering not just the subject of change but also the process and context in which that change takes place (Rieg, Gatersleben and Christie, 2021; Pettigrew and Whipp, 1991). Therefore, change management theories can help address this study's final research question by providing strategies to 'embed' a culture of IaH in Irish HEIs. In this regard, the 'organisational cultural transformation framework' (Armenakis, Brown and Mehta, 2011) and 'learning organisation through systems thinking approach' (Senge, 1990) are deemed suitable and build on the theoretical foundations of organisational design outlined in *sub-section 4.2.1*. The final set of theories is presented in the following sub-sections.

4.2.3.1 Organisational Culture Transformational Framework (Armenakis, Brown, and Mehta, 2011)

Embedding a 'culture' of IaH in Irish HEIs can extend beyond implementation to a deep-seated organisational transformation. According to Belias and Koustelios (2014), *culture* can be 'the sum of the beliefs that shape norms of behaviour and dictate the ways things get done in an organisation' (p. 453). When striving for organisational transformation through culture, the 'organisational cultural transformation framework' (Armenakis, Brown and Mehta, 2011) appears relevant. This framework builds on Schein's cultural elements framework (Schein, 1983) and organisational change management model (Lewin, 1947) by combining cultural typologies at an individual level with ethical organisational transformation (Armenakis *et al.*, 2011, p.306). In this respect, the 'ethical' component responds to the stakeholders' interests, which can be relevant to this study, as highlighted in *sub-section 4.2.1* (p.325). Armenakis *et al.* (1993, 2002) were among the first theorists to explore 'readiness' as part of change management, later refining the elements to include ethics in institutionalising change (Armenakis *et al.*, 2011).

The theorists posit ethical change through their companion models, such as creating 'readiness for change' (Armenakis and Harris, 2002 and Armenakis, Harris and Mossholder, 1993) and 'institutionalising organisational change' (Armenakis and Bedeian, 1999), aligning with their internal and external contexts. The 'change readiness' can be assessed through the 'content,' i.e. 'what is to be changed' and the 'process,' i.e. 'how the change can be implemented' (Armenakis *et al.*, 2011, p.307).

The *readiness model* focuses on the change content, comprising the underlying assumptions, artefacts, attitudes, espoused beliefs, intentions, behaviours, and values of various stakeholders (Armenakis *et al.*, 2011, p.311). It emphasises introducing and instilling the acceptance of change among the recipients, which they describe as 'cultural carriers' of that change, by reflecting positively on the question, 'What is in it for me?' (Ibid.). The theorists assert that the change recipients may accept or adopt the change if the change message addresses five central change 'beliefs,' which can be referred to as an 'individual's conception about a specific behaviour or an object' (Kin and Kareem, 2016, p.3).

These change beliefs can include 'discrepancy' indicating the need for change, 'appropriateness' asserting the logic for the change, 'efficacy' suggesting that they are or will be well equipped with the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities required to perform tasks that can lead to the change, 'principal support' from the change agents (leadership), which

the theorists describe as 'cultural leaders' who are 'walking the talk' and lastly, 'personal valence' that can enable the cultural carriers to reflect 'what is in it for me?' positively (Armenakis *et al.*, 2011, p. 309). The theorists claim these steps can be measured qualitatively or quantitatively to identify readiness or resistance to change (p.310). In the case of resistance to change, the theorists recommend that additional resources may be expended to build confidence in change recipients towards the change (Ibid.). However, they emphasise that a pre-assessment to check the pulse before investing in the readiness to change can be beneficial (Ibid.).

After establishing readiness for change, the *institutionalisation model* suggests steps to guide cultural leaders in implementing change (Ibid.). The theorists posit seven institutionalisation strategies that reinforce each belief stated in the change message in the readiness model (p.311). These strategies include 'commitment,' which can be evident through human resource practices that comprise selection, compensation, performance appraisal, rewards for adopting change, training and development for change recipients; 'persuasive communication' through formal (speeches about success or failures /gains or losses in market share, performance appraisals) and informal forums (ongoing feedback to implement change); 'symbolism' through rites and ceremonies to celebrate success; 'diffusion practices' through sessions and training for new practices needed for implementing change by change recipients who 'learn the talk, walk the talk and sustain the talk and walk'; 'formalisation activities' involving revised vision or mission statements, organisational structure, active participation from change recipients in problem-solving and decision-making processes.

Moreover, 'management of internal and external information' through publications of positive impacts of change and inviting experts supportive of change, and finally, 'assessment' to ascertain the 'extent to which the change recipients have incorporated the values and behaviours associated with the transformation' through 'assessment of change recipients' affective, cognitive and behavioural reactions to the transformation' (p.312). Ultimately, the theorists suggest that organisations with more adaptive cultures are likelier to succeed in change management efforts in dynamic contexts (p. 313).

Interestingly, this framework has roots in organisational/business contexts, with some application in academia, such as utilising this theory to assess organisational readiness for change through staff perceptions towards introducing a new educational model in transnational universities in China (Liu, 2024); change readiness towards leadership change among lower and mid-level academic leaders in five public HEIs in Ethiopia (Mamo

Gebretsadik, 2022), change readiness, resistance and race in faculty attitudes towards faculty diversification in US HEIs (Rawls, 2020) and variables in inducing change management among staff in private HEIs in Indonesia (Kusumaputri, Himam, Afiatin, and Meiyanto, 2014).

Although this framework can help aid cultural change management, it has sparked some criticism for providing an incomplete view of evaluating the change when faced with resistance to change from employees, tracking small failures and, as a result, oversimplifying a complex process of change (Mugenyi, Karemera, Wesana, and Doods, 2022; Saetren, and Laumann, 2017). Moreover, El-Hage and Sidani (2023) argue that the overreliance of the companion models on utilising 'communication' as a strategy to enforce change can be insufficient to inspire individuals/change recipients to bring a transformative change (p. 181).

Nonetheless, the organisational cultural transformational framework has the potential to address the pulse of the problem, which is implementing and sustaining efforts in IaH across stakeholders and departments within an HEI. The framework points out companion models utilising change readiness and institutionalising culture changes by working on change beliefs of change recipients, which in this case are the various stakeholders, some of which have been identified in *sub-section 4.2.1.1*.

Furthermore, the strategies in institutionalising change can help create 'change messages' for IaH. This can be done through 'persuasive communication,' clearly articulating the need for and implementation of IaH, which can be necessary when embedding a culture of IaH in Irish HEIs. Moreover, 'leadership commitment' can be assessed through motivation, systems, investment in CPD, resources, policies, rewards, and recognition for embedding a culture for IaH.

As such, ascertaining the 'commitment of leadership, symbolism and diffusion practices' in catalysing change through academic staff buy-in, administrative staff support, student engagement and necessary resources to drive IaH; 'formalisation activities and internal and external communication' through alignment with institutional values such as including IaH in the strategic planning and resource allocation and lastly, 'sustaining initiatives' through CPD, reinforcement of good practices, internationalised curriculum design and reward and recognition can significantly contribute to embedding a culture of IaH. However, this process may necessitate a systemic approach, which is examined in the subsequent sub-section.

4.2.3.2 Learning Organisation through Systems Thinking Approach (Senge, 1990)

Embedding a culture of IaH can be a comprehensive institution-wide effort extending beyond stakeholder engagement and curricular reform. Whilst the 'organisational cultural transformation framework' (Armenakis, Brown and Mehta, 2011) offered valuable guidance in managing change for embedding IaH by working on change readiness and institutionalising change, Irish HEIs may need a 'systemic' response to this reform. Scholars such as Jooste (2022) use the term *systemic internationalisation*, which they refer to as 'not just comprehensive internationalisation of the institution, but also to the internationalisation of the student and faculty mind, to eliminate fragmentation and marginalisation' (p. 103), which can be relevant to this study. Systemic internationalisation builds on the advocacy of early scholars such as Mestenhauser (2011, 2007, 2006, 1998), where they emphasise a 'systems thinking' approach to IaH.

In this context, Senge's theory on learning organisation appears relevant. In their theory, Senge (1990) substantiates their learning organisation framework through what they describe as the five disciplines, namely 'personal mastery, mental models, team learning, shared vision and systems thinking' (Ibid.). They propounded that 'personal mastery' could be achieved through self-discipline or meditative practice to develop a holistic view of the world, such as a mind-body system (Senge, 1990, p.23). Following this, 'mental models' such as a shared vision or understanding can be created and managed (Ibid.). Similarly, the 'team learning' aspect focuses on the collective understanding and dialogue regarding the new change (Ibid.). Lastly, pertinent to this research is 'systems thinking,' which Senge describes as 'a discipline for seeing wholes (Ibid.). It is a framework for seeing interrelationships rather than individual things and patterns of change than static snapshots' (Ibid.). The theorist asserts that systems thinking integrates the other four disciplines and forms the cornerstone of linking theory with practice (p.12).

Connecting Senge's (1990) systems thinking with the current study offers a theoretical grounding on how individuals, departments, leadership, and institutions perceive their agency in implementing and embedding IaH. Mestenhauser claims that Senge's systems thinking approach can be 'crucial for understanding international education's complex, intertwined, multidimensional nature' (Pembleton and Fry, 2022, p. 45). This can be possible in two ways. The first is 'differentiation,' which they describe as 'the ability to identify the parts and the relationships among them and between them and the whole' (Mestenhauser, 2011, p.72). The second is 'integration,' which they describe as 'the recognition of how these parts connect

with each other and the meaning of their connections in theory and practice' (Ibid.). Understanding these two sides of the coin can enable international educators and leaders to recognise the parts and the whole of their work and navigate between the two (Ibid.). They also argue that the complexities and challenges of systems thinking increase when educators and leaders focus on the 'transactional parts,' neglecting the 'whole,' which can be a missed opportunity (Ibid.). This could imply the nature of 'silos' in which different disciplines, units and departments operate, focusing on their day-to-day transactions.

Besides Mestenhauser's influential contribution to the field of IoHE, other scholars have utilised the model in different HE settings, such as Simanjuntak, Heriyanto and Hasibuan (2023) employing Senge's theory to improve the quality of Christian HE in Indonesia; Elsayah, Ho and Ryan (2022) proposing teaching systems thinking in HE; Teqja and Dennis (2016) validating Senge's theory in transforming HE system in Albania; Bui and Baruch (2010) building their own construct for HEIs upon the five disciplines proposed in Senge's model; Vo, Chae and Olson (2006) integrating systems thinking into information systems education, Srikanthan and Dalrymple (2005) implementing Senge's theory as a holistic model for quality in HE, among others.

Albeit popular, Senge's theory (1990) invited critiques describing their work to be approached with caution as it comprises 'many faces' (Ortenblad, 2007), being an 'underdeveloped theoretical construct' (Caldwell, 2012). Moreover, Friedman, Lipshitz and Popper (2005) argue that Senge's theory is disjunct between the utopian rhetoric of learning and change and practical advice on creating learning organisations. Furthermore, Grieves (2008) remarks that Senge's theory intends to sell an intangible end state of learning organisation as a practically relevant construct.

Notwithstanding these limitations, Senge's learning organisational theory can provide insights into examining various stakeholders' mental models regarding IaH that impact their implementation. This can explain the conceptual understanding of IaH. Moreover, focusing on CPD for staff and students can enable 'personal mastery' in IaH. Furthermore, co-designing curricula with students and engaging in communities of practice can support 'team learning.' As such, embedding a culture of IaH can span beyond 'parts' such as fragmented efforts or activities to a 'whole' such as an internationalised curriculum, student and staff engagement and leadership commitment and support. Ultimately, Senge's theory can guide the systemic embedding of IaH, overcoming potential barriers and sustaining efforts through an institution-wide approach.

Table 4 below summarises the key aspects of each of these theories, informing the theoretical construct for this study. The overall theoretical stance presented recognises embedding a culture of IaH as a multi-layered organisational process rather than a series of discrete internationalisation initiatives. It acknowledges that embedding such a culture is a systemic endeavour that influences the institution's values, culture, curriculum and campus life. These aspects are shaped by competing stakeholder priorities, curriculum imperatives and ongoing institutional change processes. In this regard, the theories of organisational design emphasise the stakeholder claims and internal resource challenges alongside the need for pedagogical advancements to support an internationalised curriculum. Additionally, the change management theories frame the systemic reforms needed to embed a culture of IaH and sustain it as a practice. Collectively, these theories inform a coherent framework for Irish HEIs to implement, negotiate, and embed a culture of IaH to develop interculturally competent global citizens who thrive in multicultural societies and workplaces in Ireland and abroad.

Table 4: Theoretical Framework for Embedding a Culture of IaH in Irish HE

Theory	Framework	Phenomena of Interest	Keywords
Organisational Design Theories	Stakeholder Identification and Saliency Theory (Mitchell, Agle and Wood, 1997)	Identifying stakeholders relevant to IaH and understanding their saliency at an individual level	Influence, power, legitimacy, urgency to adopt IaH individualist, managerial perceptions towards IaH
	Stakeholder Culture Theory (Jones, Felps and Bigley, 2007)	Extending individual saliency to organisational culture influencing IaH implementation	Stakeholder power, legitimacy, egoistic, instrumentalist, moral, altruism, emotional and ethical decision making, organisational culture, competing priorities, resource allocation towards IaH
	Job Demands Resources Theory (Bakker and Demerouti, 2007)	Stakeholder motivation and engagement towards IaH implementation	IaH champions, employee/stakeholder engagement, value-cost, job demands resources, study demands resources, wellbeing and performance
Curriculum Design Theory	Conceptual Framework for Internationalisation of the Curriculum (Leask, 2015)	Internationalising formal, informal and hidden curriculum at course and program levels, incorporating contextual influences	Multidimensional view of curriculum design, institutional embedding of an internationalised curriculum, global citizenship
Change Management Theories	Organisational Cultural Transformation Framework (Armenakis, Brown and Mehta, 2011)	Individual and organisational ethical transformation to embrace the need for engaging in IaH and support/participate in its implementation and embedding	Change readiness, institutionalising change to implement IaH
	Learning Organisation Framework through Systems Thinking (Senge, 1990)	Systemic embedding of IaH across all departments/levels in an HEI	Systems thinking, intentional integration of IaH, comprehensive internationalisation

4.3 Conclusion

This chapter presented this study's theoretical framework, which was informed by organisational and curriculum design and change management theories. The organisational design theories such as stakeholder identification and saliency (Mitchell *et al.*, 1997) can enable identification of stakeholders and their saliency, i.e. power, legitimacy and urgency in implementing IaH, stakeholder culture (Jones *et al.*, 2007) emphasises the continuum of self-regarding to other-regarding cultures that can inform the approach of Irish HEIs when striving to embed IaH and lastly, job demands and resources (Bakker and Demerouti, 2017)

can explain the motivations or the lack thereof in institutional leadership, policymakers/influencers, staff and student engagement in IaH through concepts such as burnout and engagement.

Furthermore, the curriculum design theory utilises the conceptual framework for an internationalised curriculum by Leask (2015), which can offer insights into internationalising formal, informal and hidden curricula conducive to IaH, viewing 'curriculum as a system.' Finally, the aforementioned theories are unified through the organisational culture transformational framework (Armenakis, Brown, and Mehta, 2011) that can guide the readiness for change and institutionalising culture change facilitative of IaH. Additionally, the learning organisation through a systems thinking approach (Senge, 1990) can provide a comprehensive view to holistically embed IaH at each level in the institution to move from fragmented 'parts' to a 'whole.' In summary, combining these theories offers a unique approach to addressing the central research questions of this study. Moreover, these theories influence the study's design, data collection, and analysis stages and contribute to the body of knowledge in the field of IoHE, particularly in IaH.

In light of the theoretical framework, the following chapter presents the research methodology, including the methodological rationale for the theoretical framework.

CHAPTER 5: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

5.1 Introduction

Burns (1997) describes research as a systematic inquiry where the researcher collects, analyses and interprets data to 'understand, describe, predict an educational phenomenon or to empower people in such contexts' (Mertens, 2005, p.2). In this study, the researcher examines the development of IaH in the Irish HE context through the participants' experiences. Following an extensive examination of the literature from the global and Irish higher education context and the theoretical framework outlined in *Chapters (2), (3) and (4)*, respectively, this chapter presents the methodology and methodological considerations of this study. This chapter has been categorised into six sub-sections. These include (1) aims, objectives and central research questions; (2) research philosophy; (3) research design; (4) data analysis; (5) researcher's role and reflexivity; and lastly, (6) verification strategies.

The chapter prefaces the aims, objectives, and central research questions that have informed this study's methodology and research design. It outlines the constructivist and interpretivist research philosophy and the methodological rationale for the theoretical framework that has scaffolded the philosophical underpinning for this study. Furthermore, the research design, which comprises a descriptive qualitative research approach, research setting, sampling strategy, data collection procedures and methods, and ethical considerations, is elucidated. Moreover, the role of the researcher and reflexivity throughout the research process are discussed. Finally, the chapter concludes with the verification strategies that establish trustworthiness for this research.

5.2 Aims, Objectives and Central Research Questions

The extant literature alludes to a growing need for a comprehensive understanding of the concept of IaH and guidance that can support embedding a culture of IaH in Irish HEIs to benefit all students and staff. This study aims to address this gap in the Irish context.

The **primary purpose** of the study is to:

- Critique how IaH is interpreted in the Irish context, considering its development globally.
- Draw on findings related to the opportunities and challenges in implementing IaH at Irish HEIs, as presented by the participants in this study.

- Develop a guiding framework that can assist Irish HEIs in embedding a culture of IaH.

In order to achieve the aim of the study, the following **central research questions** have been identified:

1. *What are the opportunities and challenges for developing a culture of IaH in an Irish higher education context?*
2. *What strategies can be developed to embed a culture of IaH in Irish HEIs?*

To this end, the following **research objectives** have been outlined:

- a) Carrying out focus groups with students and individual semi-structured interviews with the academic staff, academic managers, international officers, senior managers, and policymakers/influencers within the Irish higher education sector. The purpose is to explore, classify, and discuss their experiences and perspectives of IaH and how it could be implemented and embedded.
- b) Analysing national and institutional strategies from the perspective of IaH.
- c) Providing recommendations as to how Irish HEIs can cultivate a culture of IaH within their institutions.
- d) Proposing a guiding framework that assists Irish HEIs in embedding of a culture of IaH.

5.3 Research Philosophy

In order to address the research questions highlighted in the preceding section, the research methodology or philosophy can assist the researcher in systemising, analysing, and comparing various research methods (Farrow Iniesto, Weller and Pitt, 2020). Notably, the methods employed by the researchers underpin their philosophical worldviews, which can represent beliefs that guide action (Guba, 1990) and reflect the nature of the philosophical foundation (Kuhn, 1997) underpinning the researcher's project. Considering this, I adopt a constructivist-interpretivist stance within a relativist metatheoretical framework for this study as a fitting philosophical foundation to respond to the research questions.

Theoretically, the philosophical foundations underlying the researcher's choice of methodology are based on three elements- Ontology, Epistemology and Axiology (Creswell and Creswell, 2018; Crotty, 1998; Heron and Reason, 1997; Guba and Lincoln, 1994).

Ontology is the study of being, the beliefs, existence, and the researcher's experience that they bring to the study (Bryman, 2016). On the other hand, *epistemology* seeks to create steps to gather systematic and reliable knowledge (Farrow *et al.*, 2020). It tries to establish the relationship between the knower (the researcher) and the known (the research) (Ibid.). This relationship is established through methods that lead to knowledge creation and validation (Ibid.). Fundamental to both ontology and epistemology, *axiology* refers to the value and value judgements of the researcher (Bell and Waters, 2018). Axiology can form the foundation for value-based, ethical research that commits to scientific rigour (Ibid.). The ontological and axiological positions of the researcher guide the epistemologies or the methods (Ibid.). These philosophical foundations are situated within 'paradigms' that aim to address the research questions (Mertens, 2019; Creswell and Creswell, 2018; Lincoln, Lynham and Guba, 2011). The following sub-section elucidates the chosen paradigm for this study.

5.3.1 Constructivism and Interpretivism

The paradigm adopted for this study is '*Interpretivism*' or '*Relativism*' (Cohen *et al.*, 2018). According to Cohen *et al.* (2018) and Schwandt (1994), interpretivism is based on the belief that humans and social sciences cannot be confined like the model of physical sciences. They argue that humans live in a social world, and the world around them can influence their worldviews (Ibid.). Moreover, every human experience is unique and influenced by several factors that define the truth at a point in time (Ibid.). These influences can include emotions, socio-cultural aspects, people, and past experiences (Ibid.). Considering this, the experiences of each individual can be relative to a situation somebody finds themselves in (Ibid.). This can be attributed to the fact that humans are not the owners of every decision they make or control (Ibid.). Therefore, their experiences can be considered contingent (Ibid.).

Consequently, the interpretivist seeks to understand that part of the human experience (the subjective) rather than emphasising finding the truth (the objective), as opposed to the positivists and post-positivists and, therefore, adopts a relativist position (Ibid.). However, Farrow *et al.* (2020), Neuman (2013), Carson *et al.* (2001), and Guba and Lincoln (1994) argue that emphasis on the subjective over the objective may obfuscate the rigour and validity of the research being conducted as it reflects participants' subjective experiences at a point in time.

Notwithstanding the limitations, interpretivists can take constructivism as their ontological position and relativism as their epistemological position and generalise from the narratives of individual or group experiences (Mertens, 2019; Berger and Luckmann, 2016; Lincoln *et*

al., 2011; Crotty, 1998). They can adopt a qualitative methodological approach (Ibid.). Their data collection methods can include case studies, semi-structured interviews, focus groups, phenomenology, conversational analysis, description analysis, document analysis, thematic analysis, and grounded theory, to mention a few (Ibid.).

In this study, the meaning-making of participants' interpretations and practices of IaH at their institutions is relevant. This can entail the researcher's understanding of how the participants view the topic and then meaningfully constructing knowledge (O'Donoghue, 2018; Robson and McCartan, 2016). Accordingly, the knowledge from the participants' experiences can allow the researcher to contribute to the discourse on IaH and inform about its development and practice in Irish HEIs.

Notably, other paradigms, such as 'Critical realism' and 'pragmatism,' were also explored before determining 'interpretivism' as a suitable approach for this study. For instance, *critical realism* can be emancipatory at the societal level and include subjects that promote social justice or reduce inequalities, such as those of marginalised groups (Godwin, Benedict, Rohde, Thielmeyer, Perkins, Major, Clements and Chen, 2021; Bergin, Wells and Owen, 2008). The methodology adopted by the critical realists can include a combination of positivist and interpretivist worldviews and action research (Ibid.). Whilst IaH can be a transformative change, the research questions seek to address the current understanding and practice in Irish HEIs because the topic is understudied to date. More importantly, this research is intended for 'all students,' including 'marginalised groups' in Irish HE. Therefore, critical realism was not considered appropriate.

Besides critical realism, the *pragmatism* paradigm was also explored. Pragmatism does not seek to find the truth but focuses on using a research outcome for a particular end (Foster, 2024; King, 2022; Morgan, 2007; Biesta and Burbules, 2003). For a pragmatist, the situation and actions are more critical than the historical conditions, such as that in post-positivism (Ibid.). Moreover, pragmatists emphasise the research outcomes rather than engaging in philosophical and academic arguments (Ibid.). As a result, pragmatists can adopt a mixed-method approach to complete time-bound projects (Ibid.).

However, Farrow *et al.* (2020), Sarantakos (2017), and Bryman (2016) argue that the research outcomes conducted under a pragmatist research paradigm can be questioned for their validity and rigour. They claim that the pragmatists utilise methods from the positivist and interpretivist paradigms (Ibid.). Moreover, the pragmatists are less likely to foreground their ontological, axiological and epistemological positions when using different quantitative and

qualitative methods (Ibid.). Subsequently, this may only sometimes result in finding a genuine solution to issues the researcher aims to address through this paradigm (Ibid.). Therefore, pragmatism was not considered a suitable approach for this study. In essence, the paradigm most suited for this research adopts a constructivist ontology and interpretivist epistemology within a relativist metatheoretical framework because of its potential to make meaning of participants' experiences of IaH and construct knowledge that can effectively support Irish HEIs in embedding a culture of IaH. The ensuing sub-section presents the rationale for adopting the theoretical framework for this study.

5.3.2 Methodological Rationale for the Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework described in *Chapter 4* informs this study's research design, data collection, and analysis. Due to the complex nature of this research topic, theoretical plurality addressing different aspects was considered appropriate. Moreover, there is no one-size-fits-all approach, and therefore, each theory contributes to the multi-layer and multi-faceted characteristics of IaH. The theoretical plurality can address stakeholder roles, salience, influence, culture and values (Mitchell *et al.*, 1997; Jones *et al.*, 2007); dynamic relationship between job demands, resources and well-being (Bakker and Demerouti, 2017); development of an internationalised curriculum (Leask, 2015); change readiness and institutionalising organisational change (Armenakis *et al.*, 2011) and systems thinking approach to embedding IaH (Senge, 1990).

The qualitative nature of inquiry for this study emphasises participant perspectives on the development of IaH in Irish HEIs. In this regard, the stakeholder theories influenced the research design. For instance, the stakeholder theories (Mitchell *et al.*, 1997; Jones *et al.*, 2007) enabled the identification and inclusion of different participants in the sample that can be relevant to address the central research questions. These included influential individuals, such as senior managers, and those with marginalised voices, such as non-mobile students and others. Moreover, Leask's (2015) framework particularly guided the recruitment of academic staff and managers involved in curriculum development.

Furthermore, the job demands-resources theory (Bakker and Demerouti, 2017), a conceptual framework for the internationalisation of the curriculum (Leask, 2015), organisational cultural transformation framework (Armenakis *et al.*, 2011) and learning organisation framework (Senge, 1990) informed the questions included in the topic guides for the focus groups and semi-structured interviews. These theories guided the exploration of participants' perspectives on their individual and organisational values, influence, culture,

internationalisation practices, curriculum design, challenges, support mechanisms, institutional policies, strategic plans, collaboration, knowledge sharing and learning practices, among others.

Notwithstanding the influence of the theories on sampling strategy and research design, the data analysis and interpretation were underpinned by the theoretical framework that highlighted elements from the theories, such as stakeholder relationships, power dynamics, challenges and resourcing IaH, curriculum design and patterns in internationalisation practices, assessing cultural shifts, readiness for change and systemic embedding of IaH. Collectively, the theoretical framework can provide a multidimensional understanding of IaH in Irish HE, addressing stakeholder influence, organisational dynamics, curriculum internationalisation and the need for change management.

5.4 Research Design

The research design elucidated in this sub-section encapsulates the methodological framework, highlighting the qualitative research approach, sampling strategy and data collection procedures and methods. It outlines the sampling strategy encompassing the sampling methods, sample population and equality, diversity and inclusion (EDI) considerations in recruitment. Additionally, the data collection procedures and methods, which comprise the rationale and protocols for the focus groups and semi-structured interviews, have been explicated.

5.4.1 Descriptive Qualitative Research Approach

The extant literature indicates that interpretivists predominantly utilise qualitative methods for data collection that can assist them in gaining an in-depth understanding of the relationship between humans, their environments and their role in it (Thanh and Thanh, 2015; Nind and Todd, 2011). Interestingly, interpretivists engage in meaning-making through participants' experiences and interpretations of reality. Considering that this study is grounded in the constructivist-interpretivist methodology within a relativist metatheoretical framework, it can enable the researcher to comprehend the context and depict knowledge that is 'socially constructed, complex and everchanging' (Thomas, 2003, p.6).

Given the above context, a descriptive qualitative research approach was deemed appropriate. Descriptive qualitative research focuses on analysing words rather than numbers, which describe human understanding, interpretations and experiences of the social world and its inquiry (Cohen *et al.*, 2018; Hammersley, 2013; Bryman, 2008; Sandelowski,

2001; Schon, 1987). As a result, qualitative researchers can predominantly engage in an open-ended inquiry where individuals share their views based on their historical, cultural and social perspectives (Ibid.). The interpretations of the world by participants in this form of inquiry may also reflect the researcher's own background and experiences (Ibid.). Additionally, the meaning-making in this approach is mainly inductive as the researcher generates interpretations based on the data collected from the field (Ibid.).

Moreover, the qualitative research method in the interpretivist paradigm can allow the researcher to construct knowledge through multiple realities embedded in different voices and events (Ibid.). In this paradigm, the researcher can be directly involved with the participants, so the knowledge gathered can be subjective and comprehensive, depicting the participants' experiences and interpretation of reality at a point in time (Ibid.) Moreover, qualitative research can assist the researcher in gleaning greater insight into the topic that contributes to the growing body of knowledge in the field (Ibid.). As a result, the qualitative semi-structured interviews and focus groups are considered the most fitting when aiming to understand participants' interpretations of IaH in an Irish higher education setting.

Whilst the descriptive qualitative approach to data collection is considered relevant to this study, the researcher is cognisant of its limitations. According to Lune and Berg (2017), Harry and Lipsky (2014), Silverman (2011), and Richards and Richards (1994), qualitative research can emphasise the participant experience more than contextual realities and problems. Moreover, the small samples in this method raise concerns about generalising the findings to the whole population (Ibid.). Additionally, the data collected in words makes the analysis and interpretation complex and may take considerable time (Ibid.).

Notwithstanding the limitations, it was considered the most suitable approach to glean insights into IaH. The extant literature posits other studies in relation to the topic of utilising this approach. For example, Sierra (2013) uses the qualitative approach through the case study method. They engage participants through semi-structured interviews, focus groups, and document analysis to identify factors influencing internationalisation at home at a Spanish university (Ibid.).

Moreover, Almeida et al. (2019) adopt a qualitative approach using multiple case study method to understand and address the conceptual fog around IaH in two UK and Brazilian higher education institutions (HEIs). Similarly, Ganassin, Satar and Regan (2021) chose qualitative methods such as training and interviews to understand the staff perspectives on IaH in Chinese institutions. Whilst the application of qualitative research in the field is not

new, the topic itself is understudied to date in the Irish context. As a result, a descriptive qualitative approach has been adopted for this study.

5.4.2 Research Setting

The study was carried out in the Republic of Ireland. However, prioritising equity of access, participants' convenience and preferences and acknowledging logistical constraints, participants were offered online and offline options (Carter, Shih, Williams, Degeling and Mooney-Somers, 2021). For focus groups encompassing students studying in geographically spread universities, logistical and time limitations were considered, and hence, online participation through Zoom was offered. In the case of semi-structured interviews, both offline and online options were offered.

In relation to online participation, particular attention was given to addressing the social, technological and ethical aspects of utilising a virtual environment for data collection for this study (Carter *et al.*, 2021). Although the use of online data collection methods is not new in qualitative research, the extant literature posits the rise of online data collection due to social distancing requirements imposed by the COVID-19 pandemic (Hatch, 2023; Waterhouse *et al.*, 2022; Newman, Guta and Black, 2021; Moises Jr, 2020). Post the pandemic; qualitative researchers increasingly use online data collection to widen access and gain rich insights (Ibid.). Given the rationale of equity considerations and institutional licensing protections, offering online participation was deemed appropriate and explicitly outlined in the informed consent forms.

The online data collection modality can offer numerous advantages, such as widening access to participation across geographically spread participants and saving time and cost in organising and conducting focus groups or interviews (Ibid.). However, I am cognisant of its challenges. This may include brief responses to questions, limited contextual information and relational satisfaction, and digital fatigue (Davies, LeClair, Bagley, Blunt, Hinton, Ryan and Ziebland, 2020). Furthermore, while using online modality can *prima facie* appear as inclusive, it has the potential to exclude participants who are not equipped with good internet bandwidth, software permissions or access, a comfortable environment to contribute to the discussion or people with specific disabilities which can be a hindrance to their participation (Khoa, Hung and Hejsalem-Brahmi, 2023).

Moreover, there can be ethical concerns with using online modalities such as data and privacy risks that can include viewing and hearing participants' domestic space, use of platforms that can require participants' personal information such as date of birth, email address or phone

number which participants may not be willing to disclose (Newman, Guta and Black, 2021). This can be particularly a situation for students relying on university or public libraries for systems and the internet that can impose risks when sharing personal information (Ibid.). Additionally, whilst offline participation was offered to interview participants, it is acknowledged that there can be a loss of embodied care when developing a rapport with the participant in an online environment, particularly in a focus group setting (Boland, Banks, Krabbe, Lawrence, Murray, Henning and Vandenberg, 2022).

To counter these concerns, ethical approval was sought from SETU's Research Ethics Committee. Moreover, the participants were offered optional pre-research briefings to address these risks (Olliffe, Kelly, Gonzalez Montaner and Yu Ko, 2021). Furthermore, the institutional license was used for Zoom, and the recordings were stored in the institutional cloud service, i.e. one-drive, password-protected, that complied with the EU's GDPR (Lobe, Morgan and Hoffman, 2020). Additionally, the gatekeeper and participant research packs clearly outlined the information to ensure informed consent and optional research briefings, as attached in *Appendices (C), (D), (E) and (F)*. Notably, the consent forms were circulated to participants through MS Word documents attached to the emails, which were returned, filled, and signed if participants consented to participate. Additionally, protocols were established and approved by SETU's Research Ethics Committee, ensuring mechanisms were in place to deal with distressed or disengaged participants, particularly in an online environment.

To mitigate technological challenges, the optional pre-research briefings were offered to address participants' queries and familiarise them with the platform, if required. However, this opportunity was barely utilised as most participants were familiar with using Zoom/ MS Teams through their institutions. Notably, Zoom was chosen as the platform because of its ease of access and interactivity tools (Tomás and Bidet, 2024; Farooq, Muhammad, and Mahmood, 2023; Fletcher, 2021). An institutional license can mitigate risks associated with data recording, privacy, security, and confidentiality settings for the research (Ibid.). The use of Zoom for data collection was approved by SETU's REC and accepted by all other participating institutions/organisations.

To facilitate discussion through Zoom in the focus groups and interviews, a platform functional checklist informed by Carter *et al.* (2021) was followed. This checklist assisted in managing the research space and ensuring the participants' privacy, security and confidentiality through passcode entries into the meeting room, waiting room management, admission and removal of participants and username display controls (Carter *et al.*, 2021, p.

715). Moreover, microphone and camera controls, chat functions, sub-titles, captioning, and breakout rooms were enabled to enhance social interaction (Ibid.). Additionally, the breakout room was facilitated to have a one-to-one discussion for any distressed and disengaged participants (Ibid.).

Furthermore, the use of subtitles and captioning greatly benefited participants, particularly non-native English speakers or those who might encounter challenges with accents or other factors affecting comprehension (Ibid.). The questions were presented on an MS PowerPoint that was intermittently displayed to facilitate participants' understanding. Participant screensharing, screen annotation and screenshots were disabled for privacy, security and confidentiality reasons (Ibid.). The focus groups and semi-structured interviews were recorded and stored in SETU's cloud storage, encrypted on OneDrive, in accordance with the approved protocols by SETU's REC.

Notwithstanding these support and risk mitigation measures, I recognise that there can be unforeseen interruptions to data collection, mainly online modality, which may be beyond my control. Therefore, the risks associated with their participation were outlined in the participant research pack during the participant recruitment process to facilitate informed decision making.

5.4.3 Sampling Strategy

Given that this study adopts a descriptive qualitative approach, as outlined in the previous sub-section, strategies such as stratified purposive sampling for focus groups and purposive sampling for semi-structured interviews have been employed to select suitable participants for the study. This sub-section elucidates the rationale for the sampling methods, population and characteristics of the sample participants.

5.4.3.1 Sampling Method

As a qualitative researcher, I draw insights from the sample population's experiences and gather understanding of the implementation of IaH within the context of Irish HE (Connolly, 1998). Interpretivism as a chosen paradigm enabled me to make sense of participants' interpretations of IaH in their practice (Onwuegbuzie and Leech, 2007; Denzin and Lincoln, 2005). In such a scenario, sampling, a process of 'selecting objects, participants, or respondents', becomes an important consideration (Islam and Aldaihani, 2022, p.4). The sampling strategy can assist in choosing a sample population, which consists of the select individuals, groups, and settings involved with or affected by the phenomena under

investigation, such as IaH (Onwuegbuzie and Leech, 2007). The sub-sections below outline the sampling strategy adopted for focus groups and semi-structured interviews.

5.4.3.1.1 Stratified Purposive Sampling (Focus Groups)

Stratified purposive sampling was employed to recruit a sample population for the focus group. I utilised 'non-probability sampling' techniques where not every subject has the likelihood of a chance to be selected, such as 'purposive sampling' (Sarstedt, Bengart, Shaltoni and Lehmann, 2018; Mugenda and Mugenda, 2003; Minichiello, Aroni, Timewell and Alexander, 1990). Purposive sampling is most commonly used in qualitative research as it accounts for individuals, groups and settings as important in understanding the topic under investigation if they are 'information rich' (Patton, 2014, p.169). However, this method could lack generalisability, but it is not necessarily the primary goal of qualitative research (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016; Omona, 2013). Mumtaz, Ting, Ramayah, Chuah and Cheah (2017) and Rowley (2014) claim that most social sciences and education research are inclined towards purposive sampling.

Stratified purposive sampling enables the researcher to study different sub-groups with varying characteristics to understand and contrast them (Islam, Khan and Baikady, 2022). In a higher education setting, various groups can be distinguished by age, stage, gender, ethnicity, race, discipline, and role as well as by 'typicality' or 'interest' in the research topic, which, in this study's case, appeared to best inform the aims of this research. Studying each of these groups may be meaningful in drawing patterns and comparisons. However, this process can be time-consuming (Adeoye, 2023; Omona, 2013). This technique assumes that data inside each stratum or sub-group can be relatively homogenous for one or two characteristics and relatively heterogeneous across strata, i.e. sub-groups concerning these characteristics (Ibid.).

5.4.3.1.2 Purposive Sampling (Semi-Structured Interviews)

In the case of semi-structured interviews, I employ purposive sampling, also known as 'judgemental sampling,' which enabled me to select specific elements for the population based on their characteristics and experience, such as roles and expertise, that can be beneficial to address the research questions (Islam, Khan and Baikady, 2022). This selection can entail prior knowledge by the researcher gained through literature and institutional website reviews or other reliable sources of knowledge (Czernek-Marszalek and McCabe, 2024). The samples selected for interviews can be 'homogenous,' i.e. participants with similar characteristics; 'maximum variation' with participants representing different organisations,

places, roles, and familiarity with the concept IaH and expertise; 'experts' that have a good understanding of IaH in practice and 'selective,' particularly for some organisations that can be considered best practice (Onwuegbuzie and Collins, 2007).

Purposive sampling can provide a broad variety of perspectives on IaH experiences and practices that can produce a good understanding of the concept. Recruiting participants through this method has the potential to enhance the representation of the relevant sample population, contributing to the enhanced reliability of the research outcomes (Higginbottom, Boadu and Pillay, 2013). This technique can be efficient, cost-effective, and bound to reduce errors in sample selection. However, identifying information-rich participants can sometimes be challenging (Gill, 2020).

Combining sampling techniques such as stratified purposive sampling for focus groups and purposive sampling for semi-structured interviews can enhance the methodological repertoire by elevating the likelihood of diversity, inclusivity and richness of data collected (Berry, Clark and McClure, 2011; Kemper, Stringfield, and Teddlie, 2003).

5.4.3.2 Sample Population

As highlighted in the previous sub-section, focus group participants were recruited using stratified purposive sampling, while purposive sampling was utilised to recruit participants for the semi-structured interviews. This approach enabled the specific recruitment of groups, such as students for focus group discussions and individuals with the experience and expertise suited for individual semi-structured interviews, including academic staff, academic managers, international officers, senior managers and policymakers/influencers in Irish HE. Outside Ireland, staff from academic support units were recruited from Europe and the UK from the best practice institutions³ identified through the literature review.

Table 5 represents the sample population for this study. As the table below depicts, thirty-six participants were recruited from eight institutions/organisations. This comprised six Irish institutions/organisations and one best practice institution from Europe and the UK. The Irish HEIs encompassed two traditional and two technological universities, selected for their geographical positioning. Notably, each HEI differs in type, size, focus, history and regional

³ These HEIs were considered 'best practice' because of their advanced nature in implementing and monitoring IaH within their HEIs, evidenced by their innovative approaches, scholarly work, reputation and recognition in the field (Hénard, Diamond and Roseveare, 2012).

impact. The oldest university in the sample dates to the second half of the nineteenth century, whereas the youngest university was merged to form a technological university in 2022. In addition to Irish HEIs, one organisation was chosen for its policy-making and another for its policy-influencing role in internationalising Irish HEIs. Furthermore, one best practice institution from the UK and Europe was chosen for its scholarly contribution and reputation in the field.

The participants from these institutions/organisations were recruited based on their role, experience and expertise to contribute to the research topic. The category of participants chosen for the study was informed by the literature (Finn, Mihut and Darmody, 2022; Clarke and Hui Yang, 2021; Ryan, 2020; O'Neill, 2019; Clarke and Yang, 2019; Clarke, Yang and Harmon, 2018; Finn and Darmody, 2017) and further validated through the EAIE Barometer Ireland spin-off (2024) which was released during the data collection phase.

The rationale for recruiting these specific groups for this study was to gain insights into the interpretations of IaH and its current practice and development from the perspectives of different stakeholders within Irish HEIs. The intention was to construct what 'IaH' represents for some of the key stakeholders in Irish HEIs and to explore how a culture of IaH can be embedded and sustained in order to develop students or learners as global citizens, which aligns with the objectives of the current national strategy – Global Citizens 2030 (DFHERIS, 2024).

Recruiting these participants implied bringing different voices forward, such as the students, academics (staff and managers), and the administrators (international office), as well as the influencing role of the leadership (senior managers) that can be conducive to IaH (Marchbank and Letherby, 2006; Letherby, 2002). Additionally, two external stakeholders, such as policymakers and influencers, were included to examine their role and influence in IaH in Irish HEIs. This was later complemented by views of staff from academic support units in two best practice institutions. However, I am cognisant that the findings from best practice institutions cannot be generalised.

Ethical approval was obtained from SETU, and permissions based on the ethical approval were obtained to access participants from each institution. A total of nineteen students participated in the focus groups, and seventeen staff participated in the semi-structured interviews. *Table 5* below illustrates the sample population for this study.

*Table 5: Sample Population
(n=36)*

The sample population illustrated in *Table 5* was recruited based on the inclusion criteria of participants being eighteen years or older, comprising full-time students or employees, Irish or international, who have spent at least one year in their current role at their respective institutions, are comfortable with participating through Zoom and keeping their cameras ON for online interaction, as appropriate. On the other hand, the exclusion criteria entailed vulnerable participants, new students or staff, part-time students or staff and those who were reluctant to access Zoom or present for a video discussion.

Based on the aforementioned inclusion and exclusion criteria, thirty-six participants were recruited into the study. Whilst attempts were made to ensure gender balance, the participation was skewed towards female participants (twenty-two) rather than their male counterparts (fourteen). The participants did not identify with a gender other than male and female. *Table 6*, depicted below, summarises the participant demographics for this study.

<i>Table 6: Participant Demographics</i> (n=36)									
Type of Institution (a)	Region (b)	Number of Institutions (c)	Number of Focus Group Participants (d)	Number of Semi-Structured Interview Participants (e)	Irish Participants (f)	International Participants (g)	Male Participants (h)	Female Participants (i)	Total Participants (d+e)
Traditional Universities	Ireland	2	10	6	8	8	6	10	16
Technological Universities		2	9	7	9	7	6	10	16
Stakeholder Organisations		2	-	2	2	-	2	-	2
Best Practice HEIs	Europe and the UK	2	-	2	-	2	-	2	2
TOTAL		8	19	17	19	17	14	22	36

5.4.3.3 Equality, Diversity and Inclusion Considerations

From an 'Equality, Diversity and Inclusion (EDI)' perspective, that provides a 'framework that ensures people are treated fairly, valued for their differences, and given equal opportunities to thrive' (SETU EDI, n.d.), attempts were made to ensure that a wide range of perspectives, voices and experiences are represented that can contribute to 'comprehensive, accurate and generalisable findings' (SETU EDI policy, 2024; SETU TU

RISE, 2024). This was done through careful participant recruitment and retention practices and by reducing unconscious bias in recruitment. Unconscious bias refers to 'the automatic, unintentional, and often unrecognised biases' that can potentially impact research design, conduct, interpretation, and reporting research, leading to distorted findings and reducing the reliability and validity of the results (SETU TU RISE, 2024; Safir, 2016).

When investigating a topic such as IaH, which encompasses the need for diverse voices, I was reflexive to avoid biases in the selection, confirmation, stereotype, culture, gender and any implicit associations (SETU TU RISE, 2024; Suttie, 2016). For instance, when recruiting participants, I acknowledged the diversity in student and staff composition, such as Irish and international. An attempt was made to ensure all voices got an equal opportunity to partake in the study, regardless of their background, distinguished by age, stage, ethnicity, gender, culture, or any other characteristic.

While I acknowledge that it can be challenging to identify unconscious bias, I mitigated it with greater awareness, reflexivity and intentional efforts. I also undertook a project pathway module on 'EDI for Transformative Research' and training on EDI for researchers. I served on several institutional committees, such as the SETU Global Engagement Strategy Group, the IaH working group, the SETU Athena Swan University group, Race Equality and the Yellow Flag committee, which exposed me to different cultures and made me more reflexive in challenging homogenous thinking, embracing other perspectives, reducing bias and promoting fairness. Being intentional and reflexive has enabled me to be more inclusive and objective and produce high-quality research.

In addition, emphasis was placed on intersectionality, where 'different aspects of identity, such as race, gender, and socioeconomic status, intersect' (SETU EDI, n.d.). To this end, thoughtful consideration was given towards the representation of different races, sexes, and genders to address any structural barriers and foster an inclusive environment where participants can share and feel heard (European Commission, 2022; Fradella, 2018). Notably, ethical approval was sought at the research design phase to reduce the risk of biases influencing research decisions. Furthermore, in the first year, I undertook the universal pathway module on 'Research Integrity and Ethics' and 'Epigeum' training to ensure an inclusive design and transparent and accountable processes.

5.4.4 Data Collection Procedures and Methods

The research employs a qualitative approach to data collection through focus groups and semi-structured interviews. This sub-section outlines the procedures for recruiting participants, the rationale for the methods chosen, and the protocols followed for each method.

5.4.4.1 Data Collection Procedures

Ascertaining participants' understanding and practice of IaH requires intensive exploration of their experiences, which can form qualitative data through the language describing those experiences (Polkinghorne, 2005). While 'data' is a commonly utilised terminology in quantitative research, scholars such as Van Manen (2016) and McLeod (2011) posit using 'accounts' as opposed to the use of the term 'data' when engaging in qualitative research. In concurrence with Polkinghorne (2005), for simplicity, I utilise the term 'data' to provide evidence of participants' accounts regarding their experiences with IaH (Ibid.).

For this study, the data was collected through a three-stage process to access the desired samples, which can best inform and support the research question, as outlined in the sample strategy. Before beginning the data collection process, ethical approval was sought from the home university, SETU, where this research is being conducted. Once the ethical approval was obtained, a three-stage process was implemented to access the sample.

The first stage comprised the 'HEI/Organisation access stage,' which implied contacting the RECs of the sample population, wherever appropriate, with the ethical approval obtained from SETU. The objective was to determine any additional requirements or processes needed to access the sample from the respective institutions. This was particularly relevant for HEIs with a REC to evaluate research proposals. Fortunately, the ethical approval from SETU served as adequate and permissions to access participants were provided through email. This stage was not relevant for external stakeholder organisations⁴ as they did not have a REC.

The second stage encompassed the 'gatekeeper access stage.' Berg and Lune (2017) describe gatekeepers as individuals or groups with the authority and influence to grant or refuse access to a field or research setting (p.112). The gatekeepers act as watchdogs protecting the setting,

⁴ In this study, external stakeholder organisations represent those with a policymaking and policy-influencing role in the internationalisation of Irish HEIs.

people, and institutions sought as research subjects and are primarily in pivotal positions of the hierarchy in an institution (Ibid.). The Vice President (VP)-Academic Affairs or equivalent acted as the principal gatekeeper for my study. The VPs connected me with the additional gatekeepers, such as the Dean for students or equivalent or Director-International offices, to access student participants. Most RECs advised direct communication with staff at various levels, with the exception of one institution. In the case of external stakeholder organisations, the secretary or equivalent was approached. However, they also advised direct communication with staff who could participate in this research.

The gatekeepers were approached with an invitation letter, ethical approval from SETU, approval from their institution's REC, wherever appropriate, a gatekeeper research pack (attached in *C and D*) that included information about the study and informed consent to access participants, a topic guide outlining questions, a poster of the study and participant research pack. The topic guides listed the suggestive questions for the focus groups and semi-structured interviews (Barbour, 2013).

Furthermore, the gatekeepers were invited to optional pre-research briefing online meetings on Zoom at their convenience to clarify any questions. Pre-research briefings can help explain and clarify doubts, set clear expectations, and make participants familiar with research settings, which, in this case, mainly involve online data collection through the Zoom platform (Carter *et al.*, 2021). Gatekeepers from two institutions engaged in these pre-research briefing meetings, while the majority directly consented to support the research and distribute information to the potential participants in their institution. The gatekeeper consent forms were signed and returned by email.

The final stage culminated in the 'participant access stage.' This resulted from the information distributed by the gatekeepers, primarily to the student participants for focus groups. Additionally, most staff were identified based on their role and profiles on the institutional website. As previously stated, the staff were contacted directly with an invitation letter, ethical approval from SETU, approval from their REC, participant research pack, topic guide and research poster. The participant research packs are attached in *Appendices (E) and (F)*.

All potential participants were invited for an optional pre-research briefing to explain the study, their roles and to address any queries. Only two semi-structured interview participants availed of the pre-research briefing facility, while others either accepted or declined the invitation to the study. The ones who agreed responded to the email with their signed consent forms. Participants were recruited until data saturation was achieved.

Interestingly, some participants declined the invitation for this research, stating that they did not work with international students, did not have an internationalised curriculum, and understandably did not show interest in the pre-research briefing to clarify. Likewise, this misconception of the need to work with international students or curricula was also visible to those who agreed to participate and is also prevalent in the global literature (Beelen, 2023).

Furthermore, accessing student participants became particularly challenging as the institutions were geographically spread, and students had different timetables and commitments. This resulted in some last-minute cancellations and sign-ups, so the informed consent process continued until a few days before the scheduled focus groups. In addition, several follow-ups and back-and-forth communication occurred during the run-up to schedule focus groups and interviews. Fortunately, all participants who returned consent forms and committed turned up either in focus groups or interviews. Although, due to the slow response rates to the emails, the data collection consumed an entire academic year in the third year of the research (2023-24).

Furthermore, a similar process was followed in the case of best practice institutions. Alongside this, my participation in internationalisation symposiums at these institutions complemented the interviews and resulted in site visits (Fitriyani and Dewi, 2024). One of the site visits was followed by an in-person face-to-face interview. In contrast, the other participant from another best practice institution preferred to follow up with an online interview after the visit. This is understandable because, on both occasions, the experts who were the study participants (De Wit, 2009) were also organisers of the internationalisation symposiums at their respective institutions.

Whilst the prime purpose of engaging with best practice institutions was to get insights into their advanced practices in IaH, the site visits, such as institution visits, occurred in conjunction with the internationalisation symposiums and a participant's preference for a face-to-face interview. Lawrenz, Keiser and Lavoie (2003) assert that site visits can be 'sensing instruments that provide valid information through firsthand encounters with the object being evaluated' (p.343). The institutional visits provided a cursory glance at how internationalisation is reflected and made visible on campus. This visual representation can impact awareness of IaH initiatives amongst students, staff, and visitors and their implementation. Notably, there were no planned campus tours or evaluations.

Moreover, the best practice site visits were not the methods adopted for this study. However, they complemented the narrative presented by the participants in the interviews. Consequently, Lawrenz *et al.* (2003) argue that visits without an evaluative purpose may not be considered site visits. However, if they lead to rich descriptions through the method adopted to create them, the method utilised becomes the principal method for the study, which in this case was semi-structured interviews (Lawrenz *et al.*, 2003, p. 344). In summary, the three stages of accessing HEIs/organisations, gatekeepers, and participants enabled the recruitment of suitable participants for this study. The subsequent sub-section outlines the data collection methods and protocols adopted.

5.4.4.2 Data Collection Methods

As described earlier, this study adopted a descriptive qualitative approach with a constructivist ontology and interpretivist epistemological stance within a relativist metatheoretical framework, based on the transferability and generalisation of new knowledge created. Taking this into account, focus groups and semi-structured interviews were deemed appropriate methods for this study. The sample composition for each method has been thoughtfully considered to achieve methodological precision.

For instance, the participants for focus groups were students in Irish HEIs. This can be attributed to students feeling more comfortable sharing their views and experiences with other peers, reducing any element of power dynamics as there is categoric homogeneity for the focus group (Caillaud, Nikos, and Doumergue, 2022; Akyıldız and Ahmed, 2021; Danner, Kinzie, Pickering and Paredes, 2018; Conradson, 2013; Longhurst, 2003). Additionally, the categoric homogeneity can lead to contextual relevance and discussion of student-centric experiences of IaH, which may encourage student participation and confidence in voicing views and experiences (Ibid.).

Similarly, semi-structured interviews were considered appropriate for other categories, such as academic staff, academic managers, international officers, senior managers and policymakers/influencers. This can be owed to the complexity of viewpoints demanding in-depth exploration of individual perspectives, knowledge and experiences with IaH (Ruslin, Mashuri, Rasak, Alhabsyi and Syam, 2022; Karatsareas, 2022; Adeoye-Olatunde, and Olenik, 2021; Brown and Danaher, 2019). The participants in these categories provided a more nuanced insight into the institutional strategies, practices and challenges in embedding a culture of IaH that sometimes required further probing for meaning-making (Ibid.).

Besides, some aspects of the discussion, such as staffing and policies, can be sensitive to some individuals, who may not be comfortable sharing in a group setting (Ibid.). The semi-structured interviews offered flexibility in design and role-specific explorations of IaH (Ibid.). As a result, it facilitated the collection of 'thick and rich' descriptions of data that address the central research questions for this study (Ibid.). The following sub-section outlines the protocols adopted for focus groups and semi-structured interviews.

5.4.4.2.1 Focus Groups

The inception of focus groups as a method for data collection can be traced to the 1920s in the field of market research (Robinson, 2020; Delamont, 2012). It was introduced in academic research as a 'focused interview' by sociologist Robert Merton in the 1950s (Merton, Fiske and Kendall, 1956). Krueger (2014) characterises focus groups as a discussion with 'people who possess certain characteristics, provide qualitative data in a focused discussion to help understand a particular topic of interest' (p.10).

In this study, I organised two focus groups, each comprising nine-ten participants from four geographically spread traditional and technological universities, to construct IaH from the lens of students in Irish HE. As Morgan, Krueger and King (1998) eloquently describe, focus groups are a fundamental way of listening to people and learning. They are structured to facilitate discussion between participants, i.e., students, in this case. The decision of two focus groups was made primarily to broaden the scope of diverse representation, glean comparative insights and data saturation, and enhance the richness of data aligning with the research design (Ibid.).

Interestingly, focus groups, in contrast to interviews, emphasise creating a social space for participants to interact with each other and generate rich data and insights (Morgan, 2010; Duggleby, 2005). However, I was mindful of my role as a researcher and facilitator when utilising this method. This implied ensuring that the discussion and interaction occur smoothly and provide a conducive social environment where participants can freely share their views and experiences with IaH (Litoselliti, 2003).

With a view to hone the skill of successfully facilitating a focus group, I engaged with a pilot focus group comprising four students from my institution. When organising the pilot focus group, I made a conscious attempt to consider EDI in recruitment by including a balance of students studying at undergraduate and postgraduate levels, Irish and international, male and female in the group. The pilot focus group was organised, resembling the actual setting-online through Zoom with the protocols preceding, during and after focus groups. One of

my co-supervisors assumed the role of an observer and provided feedback that enabled me to improve my communication, delivery and managing interaction between participants (Delamont, 2012; Lehoux, Poland and Daudelin, 2006).

The protocols followed for the pilot focus group and the feedback received from the observer enabled me to pay particular attention to details for the two focus groups for data collection to ascertain my style and the impact on the participants (Ismail, Kinchin and Edwards, 2018). This feedback helped refine my communication and questions to facilitate a better understanding and use slides for presenting the questions in the focus group (Crossman, 2007). The data collected from the pilot focus group has not been included in the analysis, as the primary purpose of engaging in it was to hone my facilitating skills and simplify questions, where appropriate.

For the main discussions, a reminder email drawing attention to the login details, basic housekeeping rules, and topic guide was circulated a week before the scheduled focus group to help participants reflect and prepare for the discussion. On the day of the scheduled focus groups, I was cognisant that establishing a rapport with participants can be challenging as the prior communication was focused on the administrative details and informed consent. The geographical spread and diversity of student composition in my study implied that the participants were unfamiliar with each other or myself. While an optional pre-research briefing was proposed, none of the focus group participants opted for it. This resulted in the online focus groups being the first interaction between the researcher (myself) and the researched (participants). Consequently, at the outset, I focused on warming up through brief introductions and 'small talk' to make the participants comfortable with the setting (Krueger, 1998; Kitzinger, 1994).

The focus group was video-recorded for note-taking purposes (Ibid.). I commenced by displaying the welcome and ground rule slides and briefly highlighted the study's purpose, the participants' roles, and the expectations from the discussion. As mentioned in their participant research packs, the participants were also reminded about the support mechanisms available should they feel distressed at any stage. They were also reminded of their right to withdraw during the focus group. A breakout room and chat feature were also enabled should the need arise.

Additionally, the participants were informed of the option to request their transcripts for amendments or withdraw them within two months of the focus group discussion. Moreover, I explicitly requested participants to maintain confidentiality in a group setting. Notably,

anonymity for them and their institutions for their participation was reinforced, as outlined in the informed consent. At the end of the introduction, the participants were provided the opportunity to ask questions to clarify any doubts.

Subsequently, I facilitated the focus group discussion. The suggestive topic guide utilised for the focus groups was included in the participant research packs, and the questions were presented on a slide, one by one, to facilitate participants' understanding. A brief pause after every question helped participants process and reflect before sharing their views and experiences. This was considered crucial as the group composition was very diverse, comprising international students in the majority, many of whom were non-native English speakers (Barbour and Kitzinger, 1999).

During the discussion, I was reflexive to keep a neutral stance and use my judgement to bring topics which were provided in the topic guide, follow leads, recognise any blind alleys and direct conversations to ensure a productive discussion (Currie and Kelly, 2012). The questions encompassed introductory and key probe questions. The questions were framed based on the insights gained through the literature review. The introductory questions explored students' understanding of internationalisation, ascertained their need to include intercultural and global perspectives in the curriculum, international initiatives on campus and their role in engaging with them, and reflected on their skills and competencies developed through these internationalised experiences in their home institutions.

On the other hand, the probe questions facilitated comprehension and compared participant experiences of IaH and the extent to which they concur or diverge with each other (Breen, 2006). They comprised key questions that can address the research questions for this study. These encompassed how students can be actively and systematically involved in IaH through formal and informal curricula, existing opportunities they found useful, barriers that prevent them and other students from engaging with IaH, their reflections on how institutions can overcome these barriers and incentivise students to engage in IaH initiatives actively.

Pertinently, the focus group format enabled a discussion comprising ten questions in a span of one and a half hours for each focus group, conducted in February 2024. The duration and protocols followed for the focus group are in congruence with existing literature on focus groups (Chai, Barrios, Gómez-Benito, Berrío and Guilera, 2024; Robinson, 2020; Abrams and Gaiser, 2017 and Delamont, 2012). All participants kept their cameras ON, an important inclusion criterion outlined in the informed consent. This helped in capturing not only the text of the ideas generated and levels of interaction but also participants' non-verbal gestures

that could point to their agreement or disagreement with the discussions (Dwyer, Uveges, Dockray and Smith, 2022; Gadalla, Abosag, and Keeling, 2016; Reid and Reid, 2005; Campbell, Meier, Carr, Enga, James, Reedy and Zheng, 2001).

The discussion concluded with me reflecting on the conversation, summarising key points to verify participant contributions, inviting any final thoughts and thanking them for their involvement (Ibid.). The participants were reminded about the opportunity to amend or withdraw their discussions (transcripts) within two months of the focus group, through email. Although none of the participants approached with this request. An email thanking each participant was sent out on the same evening as the focus group was conducted, appreciating their contribution.

As a next step, the recording was uploaded to OneDrive, SETU's secured cloud-based storage system, in an encrypted folder, capturing a 'gallery view' that assisted in viewing all participants (Falter, Arenas, Maples, Smith, Lamb, Anderson, Uzzell, Jacobs, Cason, Griffis and Polzin, 2022). This was particularly helpful in an online focus group setting to gauge non-verbal gestures during discussions, resembling an in-person focus group (Ibid.). Moreover, on the same day, I prepared reflection notes that could be utilised later with the transcripts for meaning-making from the data (de Souza, Gillett, Salifu, and Walshe, 2024).

It is worth noting that Zoom allowed for a transcription facility, which was helpful, but inadequate functionality as it lacked flow, continuity, and inaccurate capture of statements, which could be due to the different accents of participants (Chai *et al.*, 2024). Therefore, the focus groups were manually transcribed, which was time-consuming (Ibid.). The following sub-section presents the data collection through semi-structured interviews for this study.

5.4.4.2.2 Semi-Structured Interviews

Kvale (1996) describes an interview as an exchange of ideas between two people about a topic of mutual interest, where one acts as an interviewer (the researcher) and the other the interviewee (the researched). According to Sewell (2009), an interview allows for an opportunity to uncover the world from the point of view of the research subject, where the interviewer attempts to make meaning of the interviewee's (participant's) experience of their lived world. A semi-structured interview is a widely applied method in social sciences and education that can provide an in-depth exploration of the topic, which in this case was embedding a culture of IaH in Irish HE (Ruslin *et al.*, 2022). Scholars such as Magaldi and Berler (2020) posit that semi-structured interviews are exploratory and driven by a topic guide focused on a central theme with limited questions and can provide a general pattern. This

method is formalised yet flexible, permitting new questions arising from discussions with the participants (Ruslin *et al.*, 2022).

Early scholars such as Rubin and Rubin (2011) posit that a 'balance between main questions, follow-ups, and probes' characterises a good semi-structured interview framework (p.171). However, the topic guide outlining the main questions must be circulated in advance for participants' preparation (Ibid.). The flexibility emerging from this method can assist the researcher (interviewer) to present questions differently without constraining them to a particular format (Lindlof & Taylor, 2002).

Notably, in the case of qualitative research, knowledge is situated and contextual (Mason, 2002; Kvale, 1996). Therefore, the semi-structured interview can focus on relevant contexts (Ibid.). By focusing on the context, semi-structured interviews can construct or reconstruct knowledge rather than excavation (Ibid.). Additionally, this method permits in-depth exploration of the topic's nuance, complexity, and comprehensiveness, as opposed to other methods, such as surveys that may only provide topographical patterns (Ibid.).

Whilst the semi-structured interview was deemed suitable for this study, I was cognisant that it can be time-consuming, labour-intensive and require interviewer sophistication (Karatsareas, 2022; Petrescu, Lazar, Cioban, and Doroftei, 2017; Adams, 2015; Opdenakker, 2006). The interviewer's sophistication can enable skilful management of the interaction (Ibid.). This can be possible through heightened language awareness of participants' implicit attitudes, values, and beliefs, which can shape the interaction (Ibid.).

Moreover, there could be an element of contextual and social influence, such as prior knowledge about each other, the influence of spatial and temporal settings, and any power imbalance that could significantly frame the interaction (Ibid.). Additionally, an acquiescence bias for being socially desirable by speaking the language the interviewer may want to hear, regardless of the participant's actual views or beliefs, can pervade (Ibid.). Notwithstanding these limitations, the semi-structured interviews can be effective depending upon the 'relationship, rapport, and level of trust developed between the researcher and the researched' (Brown and Danaher, 2019, p.77).

For this study, the interview questions emerged from the thorough literature review and reflections from attending prominent conferences in the field, such as the European Association for International Education (EAIE) annual conferences. The questions were further honed through discussions with the supervisory team, critical colleagues, and experts

in this area (Barriball and While, 1994). The preliminary interview guide was tested through a pilot interview with my lead supervisor, a specialist in the field (Turner, 2010; Krauss *et al.*, 2009; Barriball and While, 1994). The protocols resembling the actual interview were followed. Notably, the feedback received from the supervisor enabled me to fine-tune my questions and interview style, mainly to allow more probing into important topics. In essence, it enabled me to determine if the questions elicit the varied perceptions and experiences of IaH (Chenail, 2011). As a result, I refined some of the questions and reflected on the communication style to probe as appropriate. I utilised the framework for developing a semi-structured interview guide by Kallio, Pietilä, Johnson and Kangasniemi (2016), as depicted in *Table 7* below.

Table 7: Semi-Structured Interviews Topic Guide Framework (Kallio, Pietilä, Johnson, and Kangasniemi, 2016)			
Steps	Themes	Application	Trustworthiness of the Study
Step 1	Identifying the prerequisites for using semi-structured Interviews (Cridland <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Turner, 2010)	Rationale for choosing semi-structured interview for this study in relation to the purpose and research questions under investigation	Credibility
Step 2	Retrieving and using previous knowledge (Rabionet, 2011; Krauss <i>et al.</i> , 2009)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Literature review Empirical knowledge through expert consultation and insights from leading conferences in the field of international higher education Consulting supervisory team and critical colleagues for their input/feedback 	Credibility and Conformability
Step 3	Formulating the preliminary semi-structured interview guide (Whiting, 2008; Dearnley, 2005 and Astedt-Kurki and Heikkinen, 1994)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interview/Topic guide as a tool for data collection utilising previous knowledge in a structural, logical and coherent form, yet loose and flexible Comprise main themes in a logical and progressive order (introductory) and follow-up questions (probes) to clarify main themes for fluency and gaining accurate and optimal information Pre-designed and spontaneous 	Conformability
Step 4	Pilot testing of the interview guide (Chenail 2011; Krauss <i>et al.</i> , 2009)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evaluation of content, interviewer bias and practicality Internal & field testing with lead supervisor (expert) and co-supervisors to refine questions and communication style 	Confirmability and Dependability
Step 5	Presenting the complete semi-structured interview guide (Krauss <i>et al.</i> , 2009; Barriball and While, 1994)	Production of a complete, clear and logical topic guide aligning with the purpose and research questions of the study for data collection	Dependability

Importantly, I focused on intuitive self-reflection that questioned my thought processes, motives, and interpretations to hone my interview skills besides practice (Roberts, 2020; Peredaryenko and Krauss, 2013). This led me to be consistently mindful of subjectivity or personal bias when engaging with the topic (Ibid.). Moreover, I amplified my awareness of the CHE principles of 'connectivity, humanness and empathy' with the participants to effectively facilitate the process (Brown and Danaher, 2019, p.76).

Notably, the protocol for semi-structured interviews mirrored that of focus groups. For instance, invitation emails were sent to the participants, and a participant research pack was attached to the emails. The participant research pack comprised information about the study, informed consent, a topic guide and a participant poster. The participants were also invited to an optional pre-research meeting to understand their role and ask questions through Zoom at their convenience. However, only two participants utilised this facility. Most interested participants responded with the signed consent form through email. Those who were not interested either did not respond or declined the invitation. The recruitment continued until the data saturation was achieved. The recruitment process for semi-structured interviews was very slow as multiple follow-up emails and back-and-forth communication took place to transition to the interview stage. This could be due to staff workload, busy schedules, digital fatigue and initial reluctance to engage with a less familiar topic.

Consequently, seventeen participants were recruited, comprising fifteen from Ireland and one each from the best practice institutions in the UK and Europe. The data collection process consumed the entire academic year 2023-24. While the response rates were slow, the participants who signed the consent forms and agreed to a scheduled date and time showed up. Therefore, fortunately, there were no last-minute cancellations. A week prior to the scheduled interview, each participant was sent a reminder email with the meeting link and topic guide to help them prepare for the discussion. The interviews through Zoom lasted about an hour to an hour and fifteen minutes, which is congruent with the literature on semi-structured interviews (Mannan and Afni, 2020; Galletta and Cross, 2013). It comprised sixteen questions for academic staff, academic managers, senior managers, international officers, and ten for policymakers/influencers. Sixteen interviews took place online through Zoom, and one took place face-to-face.

Moreover, the topic guide included similar questions for academic staff, academic managers, and senior managers. While academic staff and academic managers are closely involved with

students, the senior managers, such as Vice Presidents-Global or equivalent, were posed similar questions in accordance with their role of working with academics on implementing IaH. Comparable questions were posed to the staff from academic support units in the best practice institutions relevant to their context. The flexibility of the format of semi-structured interviews enabled consistency of themes discussed, yet discussion tailored to the role and experience of the interviewee. While most questions were similar for international officers, some differed based on their role. The policymakers/influencers had a different set of introductory questions. However, the probe questions highlighted some common themes with the other categories to enable comparative analysis.

Specifically, the themes in the topic guide comprised the introductory questions that were focused on participants' awareness of IaH and its inclusion in their institutional strategy, their understanding of how it relates to their work, and whether they designed any IaH interventions. The participants were asked to reflect on their experiences with the hidden curriculum, provide examples of using ICT in internationalisation, IaH in practice at their institution, publication/research projects/reports on internationalised curricular interventions, and ascertain their awareness of best practices in IaH globally.

On the other hand, the probe questions in the topic guide focused on participants' interpretations of how IaH is implemented across the institution, necessary conditions needed to implement IaH, reflection on support structures needed for staff and student engagement in IaH, existing challenges, views on overcoming challenges, success metrics, making IaH visible at the institutional level and influencing national strategies/policies that can be conducive to IaH. The topic guide for policymakers/influencers varied in terms of introductory questions that explored the current landscape of internationalisation from a national perspective, the positioning and influence of IaH in national strategies, and the impact of COVID-19. The probe questions were mainly similar to those of HEIs, exploring the key topics that can address the research questions for this study. The topic guides are attached in [Appendix G](#).

Additionally, the interview protocols were informed by the interview structuring tool by Henderson and Mathew Byrne (2016), who posit a seven-step process for organising the interview that includes preparing for an interview, setting the scene, explaining the protocols for the discussion, gathering information, exploring perspectives, reflecting and summarising (p.13). During the opening of the one-to-one interview, I welcomed the participant and engaged in 'small talk' to build rapport and trust (Brown and Danaher, 2019; Krueger, 1998;

Kitzinger, 1994). I then briefly explained the study, purpose, and ground rules for the discussion, provided information regarding confidentiality, recording, employee assistance programmes available should the participant feel distressed, their right to withdraw during the discussion and right to amend or withdraw transcript within two months after the interview, all displayed as well on a slide. The participant was made aware of the anonymity of their contribution. The participant was provided the opportunity to ask questions should they wish.

The questions from the topic guide were discussed one after the other, with appropriate pauses for the participant's reflection. I focused on 'active listening' and took notes to capture broad points from the discussion (Wahl-Jorgensen, 2021). In some cases, I utilised probe statements to explore the topic in-depth, such as 'Could you elaborate more?' or 'Please tell me more about this.' In the case of online interviews, the interviews were video recorded. However, for one in-person interview, the recording was in audio format using a 'Dictaphone' (Tomás and Bidet, 2024). After the discussion, I reflected and summarised the main themes to ensure the points were well understood and correctly captured the participant's views. The interviewee was prompted to share any final thoughts, and they were thanked for their time and contribution.

While most interviews went as planned, I experienced an interruption with my internet connection in one of the interviews. It led to network breakage, and the participant, a senior manager, had other meetings scheduled thereafter. Internet connectivity issues can deter discussion flow when gathering descriptive data (Tomás and Bidet, 2024). However, the participant was kind and engaged in joint problem-solving through emails so that I could complete the rest of the questions. This unfortunate episode, instead, became an 'unintended benefit' that developed further rapport and trust with the participant who empathised with my situation (Archibald, Ambagtsheer, Casey and Lawless, 2019, p. 5). Although we could not reconnect on the same day, they allocated extra time a week later to complete the rest of the discussions.

Following each interview, an email thanking the participant and outlining their right to amend or withdraw the transcript within two months was sent on the same evening. Moreover, a reflective journal summarising some key themes and observations was captured. The recording and the Zoom transcription were cross-checked and securely uploaded to SETU's OneDrive cloud storage in a password-protected folder. Since the interviews were scheduled on a staggered timeline, each transcript was transcribed verbatim immediately following the

interview, which took about a week to complete. The following sub-section presents the ethical considerations for this study.

5.4.5 Ethical Considerations

According to Punch (2014), qualitative research encompasses data collection from people about people. Therefore, researchers must anticipate ethical issues that can emerge with the chosen methods in their study (Creswell and Creswell, 2017; Hesse-Biber and Leavy, 2011). This can be crucial to protect participants, promote research integrity, develop participant confidence and trust, anticipate and prevent misconduct for participants or their institutions/organisations and respond to any challenges that may arise (Israel and Hay, 2006).

For this study, the ethical considerations were informed by the National Policy Statement on Ensuring Research Integrity in Ireland (IUA, 2024; NIRF, 2015), HEA Principles of Good Practice in Research within Irish HEIs (HEA, 2022), British Educational Research Association's (BERA) Ethical Guidelines for Educational Research (2024) and NAFSA's Code on the Role of Ethics in International Education (n.d.). These codes articulate potential risks associated with human research participants and provide guidance on the relevant principles for high-quality research, such as respect for the rule of law, quality, transparency, responsiveness, and excellence that shape professional and personal conduct (Ibid.). Therefore, by understanding and complying with the above relevant codes and principles in this research at an early design stage, I ensured that the Research Integrity and ethical considerations form the centre of the research practice.

Prior to engaging in the ethical review process, I had completed the universal pathway modules on 'Research Integrity and Ethics,' 'Academic Writing for Researchers' and 'Introduction to Research Methodologies.' Each module has helped me gain knowledge on how to conduct high-quality research. The module on Academic writing underscored the need and understanding of giving credit to the other authors involved in the research. Moreover, the Research Integrity and Ethics module has been insightful in exploring potential risks in research, the importance of consent and confidentiality, and other ethical considerations in conducting research.

Additionally, I undertook Epigeum Ethics training as part of this module to sensitise myself and prepare for ethical approval. Furthermore, I undertook the Epigeum research integrity certification. It is a specialised training in research ethics and integrity which aims to train students in the core skills needed to become an ethical researcher. The two courses taken in

the module were 'Becoming an Ethical Researcher' and 'Research Ethics in Practice.' On the other hand, the Introduction to Research Methodologies taught me an overview of the research philosophy and how to choose an appropriate methodology to address this study's central research questions.

Besides the formal modules, I participated in guided seminars on 'Methodology and Methods in Educational Research' by Professor Maggie Gregson, University of Sunderland, UK and 'Research Integrity – A Virtue Approach' and 'A Virtue Approach to Research Integrity & Good Authorship Practices,' CIRIT – Cross Institutional Research Integrity Training, a consortium of Higher Education Institutions in Ireland involving Atlantic Technological University, Maynooth University, Munster Technological University, Technological University of the Shannon: Midlands Midwest and the National Institute for Bioprocessing Research and Training.

The ethical approval for this study was sought from SETU's Research Ethics Committee (REC) in two phases. The first phase, comprising Irish HEIs and organisations, was received in the second year of the PhD. The second phase, comprising the addition of two samples each from the best practice institution in Europe and the UK, was received in the third year of the PhD when the data collection with Irish HEIs was in process. Whilst the second phase was not part of the initial plan, the research team realised that it could be beneficial to explore the perspective of institutions leading IaH in practice and draw parallels with the experiences of participants from Irish HEIs. As a result, ethical approval was sought for the additional samples.

Unexpectedly, the ethical approval process in the first phase became rather challenging. Compiling the necessary documents and attending multiple review meetings required seven months of hard work. This prolonged process could be due to the complexities associated with involving multiple institutions as the targeted sample for the study, requiring meticulous attention to ethical compliance and assessing the additional need to obtain permissions from each institution. This process became tedious and increased the researcher's burden immensely, particularly when faced with the pressures of finite time and funding for the project (Brown, Spiro and Quinton, 2020).

The tension in seeking ethical approvals for non-contentious research is also evident in the literature, with Brown, Spiro and Quinton (2020) arguing that 'ethics committees tend to over-dramatise the seriousness of ethical problems in educational research, even though such research is not in reality very different from many ordinary everyday activities' (p. 750), which

in this case was with the nature and topic of this research study. This concurs with the view of early scholars that assert that ethical regulation in education and social science research may not necessarily be ethically justifiable as it can lead to the imposition of 'unnecessary prescription, excessive regimentation and exaggerated precautions' (Hammersley and Traianou, 2012; Halse, 2011; Hammersley, 2009). Notwithstanding these challenges, once the ethical approval was obtained from SETU, it was accepted by the institutions included in the sample, streamlining the research process.

The ethical considerations regarding the chosen methods encompassed protecting the well-being of participants, as well as informed consent, privacy, and confidentiality. These ethical considerations and associated contingency plans and protocols to deal with these concerns were documented and approved by the SETU REC. While no issues of a personal or sensitive nature were discussed, I did not anticipate the process would be distressing for the participants. To protect the 'well-being of participants' and address the concern of any private and sensitive information revelation by a participant during the focus groups or one-to-one semi-structured interviews, the indicative topic guide was included in the participant research pack at the time of participant recruitment and sent again a week before the focus group or interview. This allowed participants to facilitate their preparation and reflect on their responses for the main occasions.

Additionally, information about the university support systems for students and staff, such as the Employee Assistance programme for staff and Students Life and Learning for students, was included in the participant research packs, should they feel distressed. Moreover, the participants were reminded about their right to withdraw and the option to amend/withdraw their transcripts up to two months after the focus group/interview. Besides, the primary supervisor's contact details were also included, if necessary.

The second ethical concern pertained to 'Informed Consent.' I made every attempt to ensure that the research did not cause any inconvenience to the participants and that they clearly understood their role and the project's requirements. The informed consent process followed the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki (1964). The Declaration of Helsinki (1964) states that the well-being of the participants should precede the interests of science and society. As a result, the informed consent process included capacity, information, time, voluntariness, withdrawal, and recording.

Additionally, an optional pre-research briefing was offered to briefly explain the participant's role and clarify any questions about the project. However, I ensured that the participant research pack was clear and detailed, allowing participants time to read and consider their participation in the research process. The informed consent forms were exchanged by email, and the filled-in signed forms were stored on SETU's OneDrive and encrypted with a password to avoid unauthorised access.

Lastly, there could be an anticipated concern regarding participants 'privacy and confidentiality,' particularly in the focus groups with the participants' communication outside the group. My priority was to protect the identity of the participants. As a result, a clause regarding privacy and confidentiality was added to the informed consent forms for focus groups and interviews. Besides, at the start of the focus groups, the participants were reminded about non-disclosure of the discussions and the identity of other participants, as well as maintaining confidentiality in the group setting.

Furthermore, the data was video-recorded on Zoom for most participants, except one who opted for a face-to-face interview, which was recorded through a dictaphone. The recordings were uploaded to OneDrive and password protected. These recordings were then transcribed verbatim. During transcription, the participants were attributed pseudonyms to protect their privacy. Moreover, any data revealing a participant's identity was adjusted accordingly while using their direct quotes during the data analysis using NVivo. Notably, the research team has complied with SETU's GDPR policy and Code of Conduct for the Responsible Practice of Research. Although maintaining privacy and confidentiality was the priority, the research team acknowledges that anonymity and confidentiality cannot be guaranteed. This risk was also clearly outlined in the informed consent. In summary, ethical considerations were central to the research process, ensuring the participants' well-being, informed consent anonymity and confidentiality.

5.5 Data Analysis

According to Marshall and Rossman (2014), qualitative data analysis is a process that brings order, structure and meaning to the mass of collected data. This can entail understanding the phenomena by pursuing the relationship between categories and themes, which requires flexibility, agility and positive interaction between the researcher and the data collected (Hilal and Alabri, 2013). This relationship can be an inductive exploration of data to 'identify recurring themes, patterns, or concepts and then describe and interpret those categories' (Nassaji, 2015, p.130).

Notably, in order to select an appropriate method to analyse the data, scholars such as Denzin and Lincoln (2003) urge researchers not to get over-obsessed with choosing the proper method than focus on communicating the research appropriately and indulge in 'methodolatry' which is an amalgamation of method and idolatry (p.64). Heeding to this, I adopted a generic approach to analysing data, such as the Reflexive Thematic Analysis (RTA) (2021), which was also informed by the Moustakas Heuristic Approach (1990), as illustrated in *Table 8* below.

<i>Table 8: Data Analysis Techniques (Braun and Clarke, 2021 and Moustakas, 1990)</i>	
Reflexive Thematic Analysis Braun and Clarke (2021, 2006)	Moustakas' Heuristic Approach Moustakas (1990)
Step 1: Familiarising with the research data and writing notes	Initial Engagement: Engage with the topic and the research questions
	Immersion: Read through samples of the materials to be analysed and connect emotionally and cognitively to the data, noting important elements
Step 2: Generating systematic codes	Immersion: Begin coding the materials, elaborate many of the codes into themes, evaluate the higher-order codes or themes and give names or labels to the themes and their subthemes
Step 3: Generating initial themes from the coded and collated data	Incubation: Step back and take reflexive pauses, allowing the unconscious to process insights that occur naturally between coding and theme development
Step 4: Defining and reviewing themes	Illumination: Receive insights or 'aha moments' as themes emerge
Step 5: Refining, defining and naming themes	Explication: Deepen understanding and reflection by exploring meaning and structure and utilising writing to prompt thinking
Step 6: Producing the final report	Creative Synthesis: Present a rich, coherent account with reflexivity, emphasising meaning-making and researcher voice

As depicted in *Table 8*, RTA (Braun and Clarke, 2021) was chosen because of its flexibility to fit into the broad constructivist and interpretivist paradigm, making it 'artfully interpretive' (Braun, Clarke, Hayfield, Davey and Jenkinson, 2023, p.20). This flexibility manifests in my dominant role in selecting theories and epistemology that can permit RTA to fit into the philosophical approach for this research (Braun and Clarke, 2019, p. 2013).

Interestingly, the RTA can combine the elements of both induction and deduction when analysing data (Braun *et al.*, 2023). For instance, induction can permit attachment to 'interpretative primacy to the experiences and perspectives within the dataset' (p. 26). On the other hand, deduction can provide a 'light' theoretical analytical lens to the data, offering new insights and developing theoretical understanding (Willcox, Moller and Clarke, 2019). In conjunction, RTA analysis is grounded in the data collected. However, theoretical constructs and literature reviews can enrich analytic interpretation (Shah-Beckley, Clarke and Thomas, 2020).

Considering the combined approach, the six steps mentioned in *Table 8* were closely followed, engaging productively with the data. The lexicon of Moustakas's Heuristic Approach (Moustakas, 1990) added a layer of affective and reflective techniques to analysing data. Heuristic means to find, discover or explore, in this case, experiences with IaH (Sela-Smith, 2002). Corresponding to the first stage of Braun and Clarke's (2021) RTA on 'familiarisation,' Moustakas recommends initial engagement with the research topic and immersing into the 'fullness and experience' of IaH (Moustakas, 1990, p. 28). This can be done by 'surrendering' to the research being unfolded rather than controlling the process (Ibid.). This prompted me to engage with the participants deeply, view the recordings multiple times, pore over the transcripts, and read and edit reflection notes. This process enabled me to become thoroughly familiar with the data.

The immersion into the data led to emerging themes that were becoming apparent. This pivoted to the next stage of 'incubation,' which synchronised with the RTA steps on 'coding, generating initial themes, reviewing and developing themes.' Moustakas contends that in the incubation stage, the researcher 'retreats' and 'detaches' from the questions and allows the inner tacit dimension, i.e. intuition, to realise its potential to sink deeper and ferment new understandings (Moustakas, 1990, p.29). This can lead to delving into the story of each theme and the overall analytic story (Braun *et al.*, 2023).

Following incubation, the 'illumination' stage concurred with 'refining, defining and naming themes' in the RTA, which led to 'breakthroughs, new understandings, revelations, and disclosure of hidden meanings' (Mihalache, 2019, p.137). These themes were continually reflected upon, checked and further refined to ensure alignment with the participant's views, culminating in an 'interpretative story' (Braun *et al.*, 2023). The final stages of 'explication' and 'creative synthesis' in Moustakas' heuristic approach coincided with the 'producing the report' in Braun and Clarke's RTA. This step utilised my experience with previous stages,

leading to an enhanced understanding and explanation of insights (Moustakas, 1990, p.13). These insights were distilled and communicated in conjunction with the tacit knowledge through literature and theoretical constructs to present an interwoven narrative of IaH, as presented in the discussion *Chapter 6*.

Notably, I utilised the latest version of qualitative data analysis (QDA) software – NVivo 15 to analyse the data. The software was recommended by my institution for its excellence, and I attended a training programme to use it for my research (Mortelmans, 2025; Vieira, Ortega-Alvarez, Magana, and Boutin, 2024 and Zamawe, 2015). As a preliminary step, I set up a project file before the data collection and uploaded the transcripts for the focus groups and interviews, whenever conducted, to code the data. Coding entails storing, organising and categorising the text to draw trends, themes and patterns (Baralt, 2011, p.3).

For this project, I analysed nineteen transcripts, which included two focus groups and seventeen semi-structured interviews. Following each coding exercise, I updated the reflection notes that could serve as an aide memoire for later use. As I revisited the transcripts and reviewed the interviews, taking time for reflection and reflexivity allowed me to glean new insights. I subsequently consolidated the data into broader categories that could effectively address the research questions. This phase-wise coding is presented in *Appendix H*. The steps followed in this process aligned with Braun and Clarke's (2021) RTA and were synchronised with Moustakas's (1990) heuristic approach.

Whilst NVIVO can be an efficient software, time and investment need to be made to skilfully code the data, which is not an 'end in itself' (Gadner, Buber & Richards, 2003, p. 103). Moreover, Fielding and Lee (1998) assert that the software can be an efficient data analysis supporting tool. However, the researcher must be firmly in charge of intuitively analysing the data and not leave the hermeneutic task to the logic of the computer (p.167).

Despite the substantial task of learning and mastering the complex QDA software NVivo, it proved beneficial for easy retrieval, organisation, and navigation between files stored in a single project. Although NVivo can provide a more accurate and transparent picture than manual analysis, learning the software application can take as much time (Sanusi, 2019; Robson and McCartan, 2016; Bergin, 2011). The following sub-section will present the role of the researcher in the entire research process.

5.6 Researcher's Role and Reflexivity

According to Hammersley and Atkinson (1983), reflexivity can be imperative for a researcher because they are 'inescapably' a part of the social world being researched, and this social world is interpreted by actors such as researchers themselves (p.14). This can imply that the researcher becomes the 'primary instrument' for data collection and analysis, which can necessitate reflexivity (Glesne, 2016; Watt, 2007). Moreover, Cohen, Manion, and Morrison (2018) posit that the 'researchers bring their biographies to research and participants behave in particular ways in their presence' (p. 171). As a result, researchers must acknowledge their 'self' in the research and attempt to understand their role, selectivity, background, processes, and paradigms that can influence the research and its outcomes (Ibid.).

With the aim of being self-reflexive during the entire research process, I maintained a journal capturing the progression of my thoughts at each step. These thoughts were captured as small notes or memos (Maxwell, 2013; Watt, 2007). These notes included my own experience or positionality with the study, intuitive insights into this learning process, and engagement with participants without imposing my opinions or thoughts. At all times, I was conscious of my position and experience in shaping the study's methods, interpretation, and results (Jones, 2012; Wengraf, 2001).

Regarding my background, I am a passionate international education professional with more than fourteen years of academic and practitioner experience in internationalisation, about half of which has included implementing IaH at an Indian HEI. My background and experience have led me to be mindful of my position as a 'practitioner-researcher' (Postholm and Skrøvset, 2013), 'an international student' from India (Harrison, 2015), a woman (Burkhard, 2021), and an 'outsider' (Hellawell, 2006) in the Irish context.

Furthermore, I also acknowledge the role of reflexivity in the chosen methods for this study, such as the focus groups and semi-structured interviews. For instance, the researcher is 'often seen to be, or is, in an asymmetrical position of power with the participants by his/her role and can have more power than the participant due to her 'status, position, knowledge' (Cohen *et al.*, 2018, p.136). By sending the topic guide in advance and organising the focus groups and interviews, I may be perceived to be in a position of power. To counter this, I organised optional pre-research briefings as well as began the focus groups and interviews in an empathetic way, with 'small talk' and creating an ambience of power equality through an 'informal, anti-authoritative, and non-hierarchical atmosphere' (Karnieli-Miller, Strier & Pessach, 2009, p.279). Moreover, being a practitioner and living a student's life in Ireland, I

discovered that I was 'sharing important common ground' (Drever, 1995, p.50) when participants shared their experiences with IaH, which could have levelled the perceived power distinctions.

Besides power relations, during the data collection through focus groups, I was conscious of the 'dominance bias' that may stifle some student voices in the discussions (Stewart and Shamdasani, 2014). This dominance bias can emanate from vocal power, where those with excellent communication skills may try to control the group, marginalising less assertive students; normative power, where one culture can be dominating over the other; and structural power that comes with age, gender, race, and ethnicity (Ibid.). Additionally, there are ethical concerns with the conversations being disclosed outside the group. I consciously addressed this through informed consent, optional pre-research briefings with participants, and interjection during the focus group to include all the voices. I thoughtfully steered the direction of the discussions and included as many divergent views as possible within the set time frame of the focus group (Morgan, 1996, 1993).

In essence, during the data collection, I was conscious of the complexity of the subjective narratives presented by the participants in the study through the chosen methods. The discussion brought out emotions, power patterns, interconnections, and life worlds, which have the potential to offer detailed, in-depth, rich and thick descriptions. When participants presented their experiences, I was self-reflexive and detached myself from situations that could induce my opinions, beliefs, and experiences onto the participants or the research project. This enabled me to become cognisant of potential blind spots in this research journey and utilise journals, member reflections and checks to address them. I confidently established trust and rapport with the participants, exercised empathy and active listening, reflective questioning or probing, documented and analysed researcher bias, engaged with critical colleagues and the supervisory team and reported the results transparently.

Notably, adopting a qualitative paradigm allowed me to develop a nuanced and comprehensive understanding of the research topic by investigating the critical self, human relationalities, and the complexities of the participants' everyday experiences. This enabled me to be more detailed and perceptive of the fluid identities of the participants, the power interplay, the 'nomadic' perception of internationalisation, contradictions, and ambivalences in participants' experiences. Self-reflexivity has deepened my understanding of the difference between the researcher and the researched. I was informed, intuitive, and mindful when collecting data and navigated the terrains of openness, obstacles, similarities, and differences

with my participants, accurately reporting and interpreting the findings. The following subsection presents the verification strategies adopted to establish the trustworthiness of this research.

5.7 Verification Strategies

Verification strategies in qualitative research are an incremental process contributing to reliability and validity, popularly known as 'rigour' in quantitative research (Morse, Barrett, Mayan, Olson and Spiers, 2002, p. 17). The authors claim that 'without rigour, research is worthless, becomes fiction, and loses its utility' (p.14). However, qualitative inquiry scholars have contested terms such as 'rigour,' 'validity,' and 'reliability,' arguing that they are rooted in quantitative paradigms (Altheide and Johnson, 1998; Leininger, 1994; Schön, 1995 ;1987; Lincoln and Guba, 1985).

Interestingly, scholars such as Lincoln and Guba, in their seminal work in the 1980s, posited verification strategies that could accurately represent the qualitative paradigm. They substituted 'validity' and 'reliability' with 'trustworthiness' that can comprise credibility (truth value), conformability (neutrality), dependability (consistency) and transferability (applicability) (Lincoln and Guba, 1985; Guba and Lincoln, 1982; Guba and Lincoln, 1981). Four years later, Lincoln and Guba (1989) added 'authenticity' (truth value and neutrality) for constructivist research to evaluate research quality beyond methodological dimensions. [Table 9](#) below depicts the various approaches adopted to demonstrate the 'trustworthiness' through this research.

<i>Table 9: Trustworthiness of the study</i>	
Verification Strategy	Approaches
Credibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Methodological and theoretical triangulation • Member checking and reflections • Researcher's positionality • EDI considerations • Adaptive approach • Thick description
Conformability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Audit trail • Self-reflexivity • Methodological and theoretical triangulation
Dependability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Topic guide informed by Kallio <i>et al.</i> (2016) framework • Pilots prior to data collection • Engagement with the supervisory team, experts and critical colleagues • Ethical approval • Multiple data analysis techniques • Reflection journal • Audit trail • Confirmation viva voce with an external examiner evaluating the research (<i>Appendix I</i>)
Transferability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multiple sampling strategies • Thick description • Conceptual guiding framework
Overall Quality	Criteria for excellent qualitative research based on Tracy's Eight "Big-tent" (<i>Appendix I</i>)

As illustrated in *Table 9*, the first dimension of trustworthiness can be 'credibility.' It refers to a believable, authentic and accurate representation of participant's perspectives (Guba and Lincoln, 1989). It closely aligns with the 'authenticity' dimension and is aimed at the internal validity of the research conducted (Ibid.).

In order to make this research credible, I engaged in methodological and theoretical triangulation. Triangulation involves multiple data sources to investigate a social phenomenon (Bryman, 2016, p.760). Notably, using multiple methods can increase the 'potency' and confidence in findings, thereby addressing the problem of bias (Smith and Kleine, 1986, p.57). Furthermore, Miles and Huberman (1984) posit that utilising multiple data sources and modes of evidence can lead to the verification process being primarily built into the data-gathering processes (p.235). Consequently, triangulation is sewn into my study that utilises multiple methods (focus groups and semi-structured interviews), theoretical framework (theoretical plurality) and sources (different stakeholders, types of institutions in Ireland, best practice institutions from Europe and the UK), contributing to its credibility.

Furthermore, I was upfront with my positionality, which includes my background and experience that can shape the interpretations of the study (Creswell and Creswell, 2018). The role of the researcher has been highlighted in *sub-section 5.6*. Moreover, I took utmost care from an EDI perspective when recruiting participants to represent diverse voices. Additionally, I adapted my approach as I moved further into the process, such as adding best practice institutions to the data set that were not an initial part of the planning. During data collection, to ensure accuracy, I engaged in member reflections summarising the points discussed to check for understanding at the end of each focus group and interview. Moreover, during data analysis, I contacted two participants to verify specific descriptions, aiding in member checking (Creswell and Creswell, 2018).

The second dimension, 'conformability,' on the other hand, indicates the degree to which the findings present the participant's perspectives rather than being informed by the researcher's interests, beliefs or positionality (Shenton, 2004). I countered this by immersing myself in self-reflexivity throughout the research process, documenting journals and reflection notes to track the evolution in thinking, challenging assumptions and being aware of my positionality. This ensured that I was not imposing my beliefs and perspectives influencing participants' views and the interpretations presented in the findings and discussions *Chapter 6*. Furthermore, an audit trail documenting the processes and protocols followed was created, and qualitative software for data analysis was used to enhance accuracy. Moreover, triangulation, as mentioned previously, enabled me to capture varied perspectives through different methods underpinning conformability.

The third dimension is 'dependability,' which focuses on the consistency of the research process over time that can be logical, traceable and well-documented (Merriam and Tisdell, 2016; Lincoln and Guba, 1985). This dimension overlaps with credibility, informing and strengthening the dependability dimension (Shenton, 2004). To address this, I carefully planned the research design, data collection and analysis stages. For instance, the topic guide was informed by the framework by Kallio *et al.* (2016). This encompassed conducting pilots and seeking feedback from the supervisory team, experts in the field and critical colleagues.

Furthermore, ethical approval was sought, contributing to the process's rigour. Moreover, utilising multiple data analysis techniques and maintaining a reflective journal and audit trail ensured the dependability of the research process. More importantly, a confirmation VIVA was also conducted with an external examiner to validate the approaches followed. According to Creswell and Creswell (2018), an examiner can play the role of an 'external

auditor' as they are not familiar with the researcher or the project and can provide an independent objective evaluation of the research process, thereby enhancing the trustworthiness of the study (p. 275). A copy of the presentation of the Confirmation VIVA is attached in *Appendix J*.

Lastly, the fourth dimension of 'transferability' refers to the extent to which the findings can be suited to other contexts or settings. Whilst this study was conducted to enhance the understanding and practice of IaH from an Irish HE perspective, the research outputs, such as the working definition of the IaH (*sub-section 6.4.2*) and the IaH CPR conceptual framework (*Figures 28 and 29*), can be adapted to other contexts. Multiple sampling strategies, such as stratified purposive and purposive, can enhance the analytic generalisations through rich and thick descriptions. However, as Shenton (2004) argues, it is up to the readers to decide if the research is transferable to their context.

In essence, considering the dimensions of establishing trustworthiness for this study, I frame the broader context of quality in qualitative research by reflecting on the notions of the widely cited Tracy's eight "Big-Tent" Criteria (2010) highlighted in *Appendix I*. Here, I thoughtfully reflect on every minute aspect of the research in conjunction with each parameter in the criteria that has been meticulously planned and carried out, ensuring thoroughness.

5.8 Conclusion

This chapter presented the research methodology and methodological considerations grounded in a qualitative paradigm utilising a constructivist-interpretivist approach within a relativist metatheoretical framework. The theoretical framework's methodological rationale was adumbrated, progressing into explaining the research design for this study. The research design encapsulated the choice of qualitative approach, research setting in online data collection, sampling strategies such as stratified purposive for focus groups and purposive sampling for semi-structured interviews. Moreover, the sample population and EDI considerations were elaborated upon when recruiting the desired sample. Furthermore, a discussion of the data collection procedures and justification for the methods suited for this study were outlined. The ethical considerations were set forward, and the data analysis techniques were explained. Notably, the researcher reflected on their role in the entire research process. Consequently, this study was situated through the verification strategies that establish the trustworthiness of this research and assess the overall quality through Tracy's eight "big-tent" criteria for excellent qualitative research (2010), outlined in *Appendix*

I. The following chapter presents the findings and discussion from the data collected through this research.

CHAPTER 6: FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

6.1 Introduction

The primary purpose of this study was three-fold. First, to critique how IaH is interpreted in the Irish context, considering its development globally. Second, to draw on findings related to the challenges and opportunities in embedding a culture of IaH at Irish HEIs, as presented by participants in this study and finally, to develop a guiding framework that can assist Irish HEIs in embedding such a culture. These objectives align with this study's two research questions that sought to investigate the challenges and opportunities in embedding a culture of IaH in Irish HEIs and to explore the strategies to develop such a culture. To this end, this chapter presents the findings in relation to the study's aim and research questions and provides a critical discussion of their implications for the Irish HE context.

This chapter has been categorised into three main sub-sections. These include (1) an overview of the analytical strategy, (2) a presentation of findings and discussion of key themes addressing the first research question, and lastly, (3) a presentation of findings and discussion of the key theme addressing the second research question, a working definition for embedding a culture of IaH and a guiding framework – IaH Content, Positioning and Reflection (CPR) addressing the final research aim.

To contextualise the findings, the overview of the analytical strategy summarises the methods employed, the theoretical foundations underlying this study, the profiles of participating individuals, and the analytical techniques utilised, specifically Reflexive Thematic Analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2021), informed by the Heuristic approach (Moustakas, 1990). In accordance with this analytical strategy, the thematic findings and critical discussions related to the research questions and aims are presented in conjunction with participant reflections, existing literature, and theoretical foundations. Consequently, a working definition for embedding a culture of IaH, along with an evidence-based guiding framework that can assist Irish HEIs in this endeavour, is introduced. *Table 10* below illustrates an overview of the key themes and sub-themes that constitute embedding a culture of IaH in Irish HEIs based on the outcomes of this study presented in this chapter.

Table 10: Embedding a Culture of IaH in Irish HEIs- An Overview

Table 10: Embedding a Culture of IaH in Irish HEIs- An Overview							
Research Aims		1	Critique how IaH is interpreted in the Irish context, considering its development globally.				
		2	Draw on findings related to the challenges and opportunities in implementing IaH at Irish HEIs, as presented by participants in this				
		3	Develop a guiding framework that can assist Irish HEIs in embedding a culture of IaH.				
Research Questions		1	What are the opportunities and challenges for developing a culture of IaH in an Irish higher education context?				
		2	What strategies can be developed to embed a culture of IaH in Irish HEIs?				
Themes	Conceptual Construction	Rationale	Enablers	Challenges	Overcoming Challenges		
Sub – Themes	Terminology	Development of Intercultural Competence and Global Citizenship Skills	Internationalisation of the Curriculum	Learner and Staff Engagement	Institutional	Change Management	Systemic Approach
	Curriculum	Equality, Diversity and Inclusion Considerations	Stakeholder Engagement	Leadership Commitment and Support			Stakeholder Engagement
							Measuring Success
							Awareness and Visibility
							Continuous Professional Development
							Rewards and Recognition
							Funding
							Intentional Integration
							Accessibility
							Communities of Practice

Table 10: Embedding a Culture of IaH in Irish HEIs- An Overview

Theme	Conceptual Constructions	Rationale	Enablers	Challenges	Overcoming Challenges		
Sub – Themes	Assumptions	Impact on Teaching and Learning	Collaborations, Alliances and Networks	Awareness and Visibility	Institutional	Curriculum Design	Curriculum Renewals
	Mobility		Institutional Strategic Planning	Fragmented Implementation			National
	International Learner Diversity	Employability Prospects for Learners					
	Cross-Cultural Engagement	Sustainability Considerations					Policy Vs Strategy
					Working Definition of Embedding a Culture of IaH (<i>sub-section 6.4.2</i>)		
					An Evidence- Based Framework for Embedding a Culture of IaH in Irish HEIs-IaH Content, Positioning and Reflection Framework (CPR) and Continuum (<i>Figures 28 & 29</i>)		

6.2 Overview of the Analytical Strategy

As outlined in *Chapter 5*, this study is grounded in constructivist ontological and interpretivist epistemological methodology within a relativist metatheoretical framework, employing qualitative data collection methods with two learner (students) focus groups (FG) and seventeen staff semi-structured interviews (SSI). The participant profile comprised thirty-six participants from eight institutions/organisations, of which six institutions/organisations were Irish and one best practice institution⁵ each from Europe and the UK. The Irish HEIs encompassed two traditional and two technological universities with equal participant representation. In addition to Irish HEIs, one organisation with a policymaking role and another with a policy-influencing role in internationalising Irish HEIs were represented. The participant demographics can be viewed in *Table 6*.

The thirty-four participants drawn from six Irish HEIs/Organisations varied in their roles and engagement with IaH, such as learners (students) for focus groups and academic staff, academic managers, international officers, senior managers and policymakers/influencers for semi-structured interviews.

As can be seen in *Figure 14*, two focus groups collectively comprised nineteen full-time learners enrolled in undergraduate and postgraduate programmes, with marginally more participants studying at the undergraduate level. The majority group of learners were in the second year of their higher education journey. The number of learners from traditional universities marginally exceeds that of technological universities (TUs). From a gender representation view, there were more female than male participants.

Interestingly, the percentage of international learners was more than twice that of the Irish learners, which could indicate the perception of the gatekeepers (Vice President-Academic Affairs or equivalent) that this study is more suited to international students, in consistency with the literature (Clarke *et al.*, 2018; Beelen and Jones, 2015). Additionally, these learners represented a range of disciplines with non-STEM disciplines (such as applied language, education, and sociology, to mention a few), marginally surpassing learners from STEM

⁵ These HEIs were considered 'best practice' because of their advanced nature in implementing and monitoring IaH within their HEIs, evidenced by their innovative approaches, scholarly work, reputation and recognition in the field (Hénard, Diamond and Roseveare, 2012).

disciplines (such as pharmaceutical sciences, computer science, and engineering, to mention a few).

Figure 14: Focus Groups Composition

Figure 15 illustrates the participant profile for semi-structured interviews. Notably, there was a greater representation of female staff rather than males. Similarly, most staff were Irish, and a small cohort of international staff participating in this study mainly worked or led the international/global engagement office. There were marginally more staff from the TUs than their traditional counterparts, and the remaining few were working in external stakeholder organisations.

In terms of their role, an equal distribution of academic staff, academic managers (Head of the Departments) and international officers participated in the study. The senior managers (Vice president - global engagement) from all four HEIs in the study were represented. The remaining staff included policymakers and influencers. From a disciplinary perspective, most staff were engaged in non-STEM disciplines, such as education, international business or languages, with some staff representing STEM, such as engineering. The higher representation from the non-STEM staff could be attributed to their discipline's international 'inherent nature' compared to STEM-related disciplines (Kokkonen, Natri, and Moisio, 2025; Zadavec and Kočar, 2024; Leask, 2015).

Figure 15: Semi-Structured Interviews Composition

Additionally, one academic support unit staff responsible for IaH from a best practice HEI in Europe and the UK participated in the study. However, the primary rationale for adding a best practice HEI was mainly to understand practices that Irish HEIs could adopt, and it is acknowledged that no specific claims can be made for the institution or country. While all transcripts were coded, the results and interpretations reflect the Irish traditional and technological universities, with specific perspectives from the policymakers and influencers and some references from the best practice HEIs.

In line with the methodology and participant profile, reflexive thematic analysis (RTA) (Braun and Clarke, 2021), informed by the Heuristic approach (Moustakas, 1990), was adopted as an analytical strategy for this study, as elucidated in *Chapter 5 (sub-section 5.5)*. The rationale for choosing this strategy was its flexibility to fit into the broad constructivist and interpretivist paradigm, making it 'artfully interpretive' (Braun, Clarke, Hayfield, Davey and Jenkinson, 2023, p.20). Moreover, the lexicon of Moustakas's Heuristic Approach (Moustakas, 1990) added a layer of affective and reflective techniques to analysing data aligning with the steps of the RTA, as highlighted in *Table 8*.

The NVIVO 15 qualitative data analysis software was utilised to analyse data. To get a deep insight into the participant's experiences with IaH, the data was transcribed and read multiple times to aid familiarity, and a reflection journal was maintained. The transcribed data was then pseudonymised and fed into the NVIVO 15 software for inductive coding. This process enabled the creation of free nodes, which were descriptive broad participant-driven codes, as showcased in *Appendix H*.

Following this step, the free participant data-driven nodes were grouped into main categories and sub-categories. The next step involved the researcher's reflexivity in converting different categories and sub-categories into broader themes and sub-themes that are associated with research questions. Throughout the process, the data was revisited continuously to ensure accurate capture of the codes and merge codes into broader themes to reduce redundancy. The themes were refined until direct connections with the research questions were established, such as constructions, rationale, enablers, challenges, and overcoming challenges in IaH, which addressed the research aims for this study. These themes resulted from the iterative coding process in NVivo 15, theoretical framework constructs, literature review and the researcher's reflections, facilitating critical thinking and establishing clear connections with the research questions.

For instance, themes such as 'learner and staff engagement' and 'leadership commitment' emerged as central to understanding challenges in embedding a culture of IaH in Irish HEIs. Similarly, the theoretical framework comprising theories of organisational and curriculum design and change management deductively offered unique themes connected to the suggestions offered by the participants to overcome such challenges. As a result, the data, participant and researcher's reflections, theoretical constructs and the literature culminated into a working definition (*sub-section 6.4.2*) and evidence-based framework for embedding a culture of IaH known as the 'IaH Content, Positioning and Reflection (CPR)' framework in *Chapter 6: Figures 28 and 29*, which addressed the second research question and final aim for this study.

To gain deeper insights, the analytical strategy adopted enabled a combination of elements of both induction and deduction when analysing data (Braun *et al.*, 2023). For instance, induction permitted attachment to 'interpretative primacy to the experiences and perspectives within the dataset' (p. 26). On the other hand, the deduction provided a 'light' theoretical lens to the data through the emerging themes, offering new insights and developing theoretical understanding (Willcox, Moller and Clarke, 2019). For example, some themes were informed by the theoretical construct underpinning this study, such as the organisational and curriculum design and change management theories, which are elucidated in *Chapter 4*. As a result of the conjunction of the inductive and deductive approaches, the analytical strategy adopted is grounded in the data collected, enriching analytic interpretation (Shah-Beckley, Clarke and Thomas, 2020).

Based on the earlier described rigorous process, the themes were extracted and examined alongside existing literature and the theoretical construct for this study, recognising the similarities and differences from the previous knowledge created in the field. Moreover, the researcher employed the verification strategies outlined in *Table 9* to establish trustworthiness for this study. The following sub-section presents the findings and critical discussion on the key themes in response to the first research question.

6.3 Findings and Discussion in Response to Research Question One

The primary purpose of this study is to critique how IaH is interpreted in the Irish HE context and draw on findings related to the opportunities and challenges in embedding a culture of IaH at Irish HEIs, as presented by participants in this study. This purpose connects with the first research question – '*What are the opportunities and challenges for developing a culture of 'IaH' in an Irish higher education context?*'. To address this, themes such as conceptual

constructions, rationale, enablers and challenges were identified. These themes are aligned with the key themes in the Global literature review, as presented in *Chapter 2*. The following sub-sections present the findings and discussions on these themes.

It is worth noting that the data visualisations presented in the themes and sub-themes have been created using contextual coding references, which implies the number of times a discussion was held around the topic. These coding references, which identify voices and patterns combined with the researcher's reflections, have led to selecting themes and sub-themes. The NVIVO 15 software has aided analysis, but the researcher's judgement preceded the software coding (Zamawe, 2015; Fielding and Lee, 1998). The researcher acknowledges that the depth and richness of the participants' accounts, as presented, ultimately matter in qualitative research (Christou, 2025; Jones, 2023; Mattimoe, Hayden, Murphy and Ballantine, 2021). Arguably, the software has been used primarily for efficiency and transparency, logging an audit trail, which is attached in *Appendix H*.

Furthermore, as indicated earlier, the participants' voices in this study are equally distributed between traditional and technological universities. However, the references to experiences and reflections in the analysis process reveal greater input on almost every theme by the participants from traditional universities. This could be due to the legacy nature of the traditional universities that attract significantly more international students and can be considered further along in advancing internationalisation at their universities than their technological counterparts, as elucidated in *Chapter 3 (sub-section 3.2)*. Additionally, the merger of IoTs to become technological universities is a recent feature of Irish HE, and the universities are relatively in the early years of the merger, which could have impacted the stakeholder experiences (Twomey and Murphy, 2025; McSharry, 2024; Hazelkorn, 2024; Houghton, 2020; Ryan, 2020).

6.3.1 Conceptual Constructions

To address the first question, it was imperative to capture insights into how IaH is understood and practised in the Irish HE context, since there has been a dearth of evidence from the existing literature. As explained in *Chapter 3 (sub-sections 3.4 and 3.7)*, it is relatively recent that IaH has begun to gain currency in Irish HEIs, mainly evident through the national strategy – Global Citizens 2030, the strategic plans of most publicly funded universities, this research project that began in 2021 at a TU, an Erasmus project by a traditional university (TRIP, n.d.) and a practice-based paper by a TU (Kelly and O'Donoghue, 2024).

The first theme presented in this sub-section focuses on participants' constructs of IaH. The data shows that most learners were unfamiliar with the term IaH prior to the focus group invitation and often used the term 'internationalisation' to describe the 'at home' experiences. However, the term was modestly known, albeit not explicitly amongst most staff. The staff familiar with the term actively engaged through formal or informal curricula, except for a few participants with contrary views.

When explaining the term, the participants consistently emphasised cross-cultural activities engaging with international learner diversity and mobility experiences, mainly through Erasmus, with few referring to internationalisation from a formal curriculum perspective. Moreover, some assumptions and remarks were made regarding the terminology. *Figure 16* presents the themes that emerged from the data through stakeholders' framing of IaH in Irish HEIs.

Evidence from the data indicates that most participants understand IaH from the presence of international learners on campus. As one Irish learner (L1) from a TU states

"I suppose when I hear the phrase, I just think of maybe cultural integration and students from different countries who are attending the university."
(Irish Learner 1, Technological University)

Similarly, another participant, an Academic Manager at a TU (AM 2), speaks about the 'intentionality' of having international learners on campus.

"The presence of international students is a kind of tilted, deliberate objective, learning objective that we want Irish students to have the experience of studying with the international students without having to study abroad... it is about shared experience."
(Academic Manager 2, Technological University)

Moreover, the diversity of learners (mainly international) in their universities prompted most participants to discuss cross-cultural engagement. For instance, an Irish learner in a traditional university (L6) noted that the presence of international students enables a positive environment and facilitates understanding about other cultures, including Irish culture.

"So, for me, internationalisation at the home university means that other cultures outside of Ireland get to experience, well obviously Irish culture, but it also helps us learn and broaden our knowledge about other people's cultures, which helps things like create a positive environment."
(Irish Learner 6, Traditional University)

It is worth noting that learners and staff mainly highlighted the diversity of international learners. While two participants in the learner focus groups identified themselves as Irish citizens of international descent during the discussion, there were barely any references around how that might have impacted their own experience in Irish HE.

Furthermore, many participants expressed similar views about IaH through cross-cultural activities.

"We have an international day... and the International Office organises it...and they have all the different stands from all the different countries that students are here, and the students are asked to make a dinner or food that is traditional to their country...and all the students have all the stands...and everybody comes down and everybody tastes a little bit or has a little bit of spoonful of something. It is a really nice day on the campus...and I think that is one way that internationalisation is, I suppose, promoted on this campus...and I think it is very, it is a very useful way to be honest."
(Academic Manager 3, Technological University)

"You know, there are a lot of student societies. They do a lot of really great cultural events, highlighting their own and welcoming cross-cultural people from other cultural backgrounds to attend."

(Senior Manager 4, Traditional University)

Interestingly, many participants emphasised the role of mobility when expressing their understanding of IaH. However, conceptually, IaH primarily encompasses the internationalisation of the curriculum within the domestic learning environment (Beelen and Jones, 2015). Whilst this concept appears synonymous with IoC, as highlighted in *Chapter 2 (subsection 2.5.1)*, it notably excludes mobility abroad (which is a part of IoC) but incorporates preparation for mobility abroad and the reflections and debriefings of returning mobile learners at their home institutions (Zadravec, 2025; Beelen and Jones, 2018). This subtle distinction contributes to the confusion surrounding these concepts.

"I find it hard sometimes to separate internationalisation at home and mobility, you know, because we do, we try, and I try and push the mobility a lot."

(Academic Staff 3, Technological University)

"In our university, the Erasmus program is built into the programmes. So, when the student signs up for a four-year undergraduate program, they are aware that there is an outbound, study abroad placement as part of their program. So, internationalisation at home and internationalisation in general is a huge part of what we do."

(International Officer 1, Traditional University)

The presence of international learners, cross-cultural engagement and learner mobility, when describing IaH, is consistent with the broader discourse around the terminology. However, Jones (2017) critiques these constructs as 'misconceptions' (p.23). These misconceptions can take the form of 'assumptions' that surfaced in the discussions with some participants (Ibid.).

For instance, learners and academic staff describe IaH as the presence of international learners, which is a widely acknowledged misconception in the literature (Zou and Timmermans, 2025; Beelen, 2023; Jones, 2017).

"When I think about how international my university is, I would say fairly international because we have lots of international students, and that is kind of where my thought would end."

(International Learner 3, Traditional University)

"Internationalisation at home, is it just parading those international students without understanding exactly what internationalisation is?"

(Academic Staff 3, Technological University)

Similarly, a shared belief existed that the fundamental metric for successful internationalisation is learners undertaking mobility abroad experiences, as highlighted by an Academic Manager in a TU (AM 2) below (Zadravec, 2025; De Wit, 2017).

"If a student packs his bags, gets on a plane and goes away. That is success."
(Academic Manager 2, Technological University)

Other assumptions include a senior manager (SM3) speculating that IaH is more developed in other parts of the world than in Europe. This reveals an unanticipated insight as the origins of IaH were at a Swedish university (Crowther *et al.*, 2000), and it spread to many other institutions in Europe, as highlighted in *Chapter 2 (sub-section 2.3.1)*.

"I think internationalisation at home is so much better understood in the Middle East, Asia, North America, and South America. In Europe, it is still very much all Erasmus Mobility." (Senior Manager 3, Technological University)

Interestingly, some participants mentioned about internationalising the curriculum when describing IaH, for example,

"So, internationalisation at home means we want to incorporate those learnings into our curricula, which is being transmitted to the students...and also, when we transmit the curricula to the students, we want to make sure that the cultural sensitivities and the cultural aspects of people are taken into account while teaching stuff."
(Academic Staff 3, Technological University)

"I was fortunate enough when I was doing some business modules that we got to see some case studies relating to Southeast Asia...my home country. So, I definitely see that it is a great way to integrate people from different areas."
(International Learner, Traditional University)

This perspective was further illustrated by a senior manager (SM1) at a traditional university, who highlighted the efforts at his institution to emphasise internationalisation through the formal curriculum.

"We are probably pretty well set up to deliver internationalisation of the formal curriculum because that has been part of our approach for quite a long time, and it is embedded in our learning and teaching strategy, and so I think where we have kind of put more effort in it."
(Senior Manager 1, Traditional University)

Lastly, there were mixed perspectives regarding the terminology of IaH, where some participants had slight apprehensions that could have emanated from conceptual confusion (Beelen, 2023). In contrast, others, particularly at the senior management level, emphasised its comprehensive nature. For instance, an international officer at a traditional university (IO3) challenges the ‘second best nature’ of the term (Širca, Trunk, Moustaghfir and Malek, 2024).

"Do you know there is something about the naming as well of internationalisation at home that I think is really off-putting for students because they see it as being second best or, you know. It is well like an internationalisation abroad is like, oh great, I get to go and do something, whereas for internationalisation at home, I think, for students, like, oh, I stay at home and do stuff, and it is not as enticing."

(International Officer 3, Traditional University)

This perspective can be seen as contested in the literature further contributing to conceptual confusion such as UUKi (2021) report terming IaH as an ‘alternative’ to physical mobility and a second-best option to internationalisation. This view was challenged by Beelen (2022) calling it a ‘misconception’ (p.326). Beelen (2022) argues that IaH can address the needs of all learners, in contrast to mobility abroad, which has a limited reach. Furthermore, IaH can inspire learners to undertake mobility abroad experiences and share their reflections upon return, which can contribute to developing intercultural competencies not only among the mobile minority but also among those who could/did not participate. In this view, IaH complements mobility rather than competes with it, which is also shared by other scholars such as Zadavec (2025), Jones (2017) and Harrison (2015).

On the other hand, an international officer at a technological university (IO2) demonstrates unfamiliarity with the term IaH.

"I mean, it is a new topic, okay, so people are always a bit, you know, wary of new concepts. Even though it is probably not a new concept, most people would not know what internationalisation at home is."

(International Officer 2, Technological University)

The unfamiliarity of the term at TUs may allude to the absence of institutional commitment towards IaH. Moreover, participants' experiences indicate that IaH appears to be rather more developed from an informal curriculum perspective, where the international office is

expected to lead. However, while the university staff (mainly the international office) engage with IaH, they are not necessarily familiar with the term per se.

In contrast, a senior manager from a traditional university (SM 1) critiques the term 'internationalisation of the curriculum (IoC)' for being narrow in focus but appreciates the comprehensive nature of IaH.

"I have never liked the term internationalisation of the curriculum because it seems to me too limited.... I think something like internationalisation at home; I even prefer internationalisation of the learning experience.... Just for a look for students, but internationalisation at home is probably a better, more comprehensive term for it."
(Senior Manager 1, Traditional University)

Overall, equating internationalisation experience, including IaH, with presence of international learners and linking it with learner mobility abroad are predominant narratives in Irish HE learners and staff, as is with much of the wider literature referring to it as 'misconceptions' or 'erroneous beliefs' (Beelen 2023, 2022; Jones 2017). Notwithstanding the critiques, the presence of international learners imposes the sense of 'urgency to internationalise' for staff and institutions, as quoted by Academic staff from a traditional university (AS 2).

Moreover, it appears that IaH takes the form of cross-cultural engagement, mainly through informal or co-curricular activities which seems to be on top of the list of different stakeholders when describing their perspectives on IaH. These findings are in alignment with the broader literature around internationalisation in Irish HE (Clarke *et al.*, 2018). For many learners and some staff, IaH appeared to be relatively nuanced in comparison with the wider institutional efforts to internationalise and a call for conceptual consensus was imminent to clarify the concept and its implications for various stakeholders. In the words of Senior Manager from a traditional university (SM 4) '*definitions can cause problems...golden circles*'.

In essence, IaH can be interpreted through the prism of cross-cultural engagement, international learner diversity, and mobility abroad, with relatively less development through the formal curriculum in Irish HEIs. The terminological divide and conceptual confusion, alongside assumptions of what IaH is, are evident. In order to enhance the understanding and collectively synthesise the data obtained through this study, the researcher offers a working definition for embedding a culture of internationalisation at home that is elucidated in *sub-section 6.4.2* in this chapter.

6.3.2 Rationale for IaH

This sub-section presents the prime reasons prompting Irish HEIs to consider IaH as one of the key priorities when engaging in internationalisation. Evidently, the development of intercultural competence and global citizenship skills, as well as the impact of learner diversity and equality, diversity, and inclusion (EDI) considerations, appeared to be at the top of the list for the participants. In contrast, the less emphasised yet important rationale included IaH's impact on teaching and learning, learners' employability prospects, and sustainability considerations, as presented in *Figure 17*.

6.3.2.1 Development of Intercultural Competence and Global Citizenship Skills

Participants from both types of universities emphasised the development of intercultural competence and global citizenship skills as the prime rationale for engaging in IaH (O'Reilly, 2024; Markey, Graham, Tuohy, McCarthy, O'Donnell, Hennessy, Fahy and O'Brien, 2023; Dauber and Spencer-Oatey, 2023; Ryan 2020). Some aspects of this finding contrast with Clarke *et al.*'s (2018) study, where the development of 'intercultural competence' was the least

emphasised in terms of skills and competencies support for international learners in traditional universities and IoTs (some of those that might have merged to become a TU now) (p.66). The growing importance of intercultural competence and global citizenship skills could be due to the increased impetus towards IaH in the COVID-19 pandemic, looming geopolitical tensions and the growing need for employers seeking learners with these competencies, which confirms some of the propositions asserted by Soulé, Parmaxi, and Nicolaou (2024); Buckner, Denenberg, Gelashvili, Kontelli, Marroquin Rodriguez, Wang and Zhang (2022); Ferencz and Rumbly (2022) and Manning and Colaiacomo (2021).

When elaborating on the skills learners gained through internationalisation, the participants described intercultural competence development using phrases such as 'cross-cultural understanding,' 'cultural/global awareness,' 'cultural sensitivity,' 'intercultural communication,' 'cultural integration,' 'global perspectives,' 'adaptability,' and 'overcoming stereotypes or biases.' Additionally, many staff spoke about the need to develop 'global citizenship,' 'intercultural communication,' and 'cultural intelligence' through IaH. The learners apparently were more familiar with the term 'international' while describing the 'intercultural' concept; however, 'global citizenship' was significantly less used by the learner participants than the staff, who were more aware and acknowledged the need to develop global citizenship through IaH.

For instance, an international learner from a traditional university (L2) described the skills they acquired through the informal curriculum (co-curricular) activities.

"And the biggest thing about being international (IaH) is that integrating global perspectives with the domestic culture as well.... during that phase of my college (co-curricular activities), I significantly improved my, uh, intercultural communication skills, global awareness and adaptability."
(International Learner 2, Traditional University)

On the other hand, an Irish learner (L1) describes an elective course in the formal curriculum as providing them with new perspectives on other cultures.

"Yeah, I think that the stand course (elective) that I did, I definitely, I suppose, like thinking about kind of skills, it definitely, I suppose, challenged like assumptions I had about, like the course material, hearing the speakers from Africa, like I learnt a lot, and kind of even just like challenged like stereotypes or like things I thought I knew about, and say like international aid, and definitely made me more curious about like international development. Because in my course it's kind of mainly focused on like the West. There was no focus, maybe on the global South. So yeah, I would say curiosity and awareness about international development are definitely for me."
(Irish Learner 1, Technological University)

Interestingly, an international learner in a traditional university (L7) mentioned the importance of 'global' as a catchphrase for learners when applying to universities abroad. However, he urged Irish policymakers and institutions to clarify what 'global' means, which could also allude to what it means to be a 'global citizen' to learners.

"There is no actual metric to say how global something is. It is just an idea of how policymakers could maybe define how you can quantify how global a university is because I don't know how you say you are the number one global university based on what factors. But if there was an actual definition behind that by universities were actually striving to get better at it, I feel like that would be a big incentive for the university itself to be able to say that because it is a big deal for many people when they are applying to universities."

(International Learner 7, Traditional University)

In relation to developing global citizenship, an academic manager from a traditional university (AM 1) shares their specific module on the topic. However, this module is only for those who do not have the opportunity to experience mobility abroad.

"We have an alternative to the Erasmus module that was developed because of COVID, but it is now featured in this suite of modules we offer. It is called Global Citizenship. So, that is a really nice module for students who do not go on Erasmus. There was no mobility. So, this gave them that intercultural experience, which was really nice."

(Academic Manager 1, Traditional University)

Arguably, a specific module on global citizenship is meaningful progress. However, its implication that IaH is an alternative to physical mobility experiences may reinforce the 'misconceptions' highlighted in *sub-section 6.3.1*.

Furthermore, an international officer from a traditional university (IO 1) considers global citizenship important when discussing the rationale for engaging in institution-wide internationalisation efforts.

"And student mobility is a big part of it. But it is also very much around the research. It is around the integration. It is around the social experience. It is around ensuring that we have global citizens at the end of their four-year undergraduate program."

(International Officer 1, Traditional University)

Moreover, a policy influencer (PI) recognises the need for IaH to develop '*skills and competencies that help them (learners) thrive culturally, professionally and socially*' (PI) and further links it with employability, '*we would be doing a very bad disservice to our graduates, whether they are Irish or non-Irish graduates if we didn't prepare them for a globalised workplace.*' However, PI emphasises that the responsibility for the development of such skills and competencies in learners (intercultural competence and global citizenship) rests with the university. This perspective

is supported by the policymaker's view (PM), which asserts that embedding a culture of IaH must be in the remit of the university presidents and senior leadership. Additionally, the best practice HEI participants in Europe and the UK also echo the need to develop intercultural competence and global citizenship as one of their institutions' key rationales for engaging in IaH.

The development of intercultural competence and global citizenship from IaH in Irish universities as the prime rationale for engaging in IaH corroborates the findings of the EAIE Barometer Survey (2024) at the European level, as highlighted in *Chapter 2 (sub-section 2.4)*, where 'increasing global, international and intercultural knowledge, skills and competencies for students and staff' is the second most important acknowledged benefit of internationalisation at the European HEIs.

6.3.2.2 Equality, Diversity and Inclusion Considerations

The equality, diversity and inclusion⁶ (EDI) considerations were the second most emphasised rationale. The findings reveal that as Irish HEIs and society increasingly become multicultural, there has been a greater national, regional and institutional focus towards investing in EDI efforts. Both traditional universities and TUs place greater emphasis on the need to strengthen EDI, which can be possible through IaH.

An academic manager from a TU (AM 2) highlights the importance of diversity and how they reinforce the message for EDI.

"We want to kind of, you know, be diverse in all respects from gender, nationality and ethnicity standpoint because that is really the reality of the modern workplace....and we want it to make sure that the educational environment reflects that... In my email, I have a rainbow with a message on the diverse community with a welcoming space for everyone, so I am sending out a continuous message that this is something that is important to me and my office."
(Academic Manager 2, Technological University)

⁶ Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion (EDI) are the 'key principles organisations and communities aim to uphold to create fairer, more supportive, and respectful environments for all individuals. Together, they form a framework that ensures people are treated fairly, valued for their differences, and given equal opportunities to thrive' (TU Rise, 2024, p.9).

An Irish learner from a traditional university (L4) touches on accessibility and inclusion through cultural celebrations on campus.

"I think they (the university) did a good job with the Lunar New Year because they put it in the middle of a building that a lot of people like traffic through....and so even if you don't know about it in advance, you know, maybe you'll not be on campus for a long time that day. If you happen to walk through that building, you're a part of the event already; you can look at the performances that were going on. And I think these open situations and open places on campus is a good way to just get passersby who might not have had the interest to go and find it themselves....but when they are confronted with it, they'll actually be like oh okay, I'll look at this thing for like you know maybe five minutes maybe they are there the whole time like me and my friends did."

(Irish Learner 4, Traditional university)

In addition to the learners' and staff experiences, the emergence of EDI as one of the key rationales for IaH in Irish HEIs is consistent with the findings of the EAIE Barometer Ireland Spin-Off (2024), which indicates that 84% of leadership in Irish HEIs is committed to EDI initiatives being pursued, which is significantly higher than the EHEA average of 58% (p.38). However, an international officer from an Irish traditional university (IO 3) remarked, '*EDI in Irish HEIs at the moment is very staff focused.*' This implies more efforts are needed to integrate EDI for the learners, and IaH can be a catalyst in that direction, as the data reveals.

The emphasis on EDI as a rationale for IaH, in part, reflects a broader ideological stance by the policymaker (PM) that Ireland is '*an open, outward-looking and welcoming country for international learners and talent,*' which can be both an aspiration and a presumed national identity.

6.3.2.3 Impact of Learner Diversity

The impact of learner diversity was the third most emphasised rationale and linked closely with the previous two rationales that result incidentally from the growing learner diversity in Irish HEIs. The findings indicate that the traditional universities' perspective primarily emphasises this rationale. This can be attributed to greater diversity in traditional universities than in the TUs, as elucidated earlier in *Chapter 3 (sub-section 3.2)*. Moreover, the analysis shows that learner diversity is typically interpreted from the perspective of the presence of international learners, with considerably less attention given to Irish learners from migrant backgrounds or international descent (Mihut, 2024). A senior manager in a traditional university (SM 4) remarked that '*often the intercultural contribution of domestic students who have international ancestry, backgrounds, etc..... by that I mean people who are maybe first, second, third generation Irish do not fit the stereotypical definition of Irish but of course are Irish..... are overlooked.*'

Furthermore, many participants echo academic staff from a traditional university (AM 2) perspective that the presence of international students imposes an urgency to internationalise the curriculum.

"I know that it (IaH) does not become something seen as important or urgent until many of my academic colleagues have large numbers of international students and they realise something has gone wrong and I need to think about how I deal now with international students rather than ...oh we have got these international students in our class and it is a great asset and we can actually use them in all of these really interesting pedagogical ways and they can all learn from each other and they can get to know each other...so the truth is that most faculty academic members are going to be responding to what they see in their classroom. So, if they see lots of international students in their classroom, the urgency of an internationalised curriculum will be more apparent to them."
(Academic Staff 2, Traditional University)

Similar sentiments can be observed in the narratives of the policy influencer (PI) and policymaker (PM) in this study.

"The universities themselves are quite diverse now. They are more diverse than they were 15 years ago... and if you want to successfully collaborate with a broad range of students and academic staff and other staff during your time in university.... well, you know, some of the softer, international competences that internationalisation at home is trying to support would be useful."
(Policy Influencer)

"We are open to the international student body, but we also see the value of this process to Irish students themselves. If you look at the context in which our students are now working, they work in multicultural environments. They are working in contexts where, you know, technology is at the heart, they are engaging, you know, like Zoom, Teams, whatever online platforms, and they are working with peers in other countries. So, we see a multinational campus as helping to prepare our students for the eventual work context in which they will operate...the fact that they have seen and been exposed to different cultures will help prepare them for that context."
(Policymaker)

The findings point to IaH's role in preparing Irish, including those from international ancestry or migrant backgrounds and international learners, for a multicultural workplace and global society, addressing shared local and global challenges, which is in alignment with the previous studies (Eftekhari, Yousefzadeh and Coelen, 2025; Sierra-Huedo *et al.*, 2024; Li and Xue, 2023; Temmerman, 2016; European Commission, 2014). Albeit the diversity of learners can be an emergency response for staff (and institutions) to internationalise their curricula. However, as suggested by the findings, it can prepare learners for the reality of the societies and workplaces in present times.

6.3.2.4 Impact on Teaching and Learning

Besides the aforementioned rationales, the participants' account reveals that internationalising the formal and informal curriculum can positively impact teaching and learning experiences.

An international learner in a traditional university (L 19) describes how group work with other learners improves their cognitive learning.

"I really witnessed how my lecturer gives us an opportunity to collaborate with other students because I have diversity in my classrooms; a lot of the students are from different countries. So, it is really a mixture, and it is essential to have a cross-cultural understanding in the class. So, giving us the opportunity to work in a team or apply cognitive learning... that is really helpful to us."
(International Learner 10, Traditional University)

Moreover, an Irish learner in a TU (L 6) reflects on the need for IaH and comments on how staff diversity provides them different perspectives on similar topics.

"I think it (IaH) is very important because, especially for the career in which I want to go into, it is important to see and hear how like I have one lecturer from Russia, I have another one from Croatia, and all of the laws are different and the views on types of medicines are different in chemicals and this, that and the other. Also, from what it has said in the classroom, you can talk to them about their specific thoughts and own experiences outside the classroom. So, it is very important to understand problems from a global point of view, how different things work in different countries and what is accepted and what is allowed."
(Irish Learner 6, Technological University)

Interestingly, the traditional universities appeared to be further along in their efforts towards continuous professional development (CPD) for academic staff to internationalise the formal curriculum offerings compared to their TU counterparts. A senior manager from a traditional university (SM 1) highlights the investment their university is making towards CPD and improving teaching and learning practices at their institution.

"I suppose there is quite a lot of professional development work that goes on to help prepare them to design a curriculum. That is inclusive, accessible, and internationally oriented. Because some of them will struggle to see how that will work. So, we probably put, to the extent that we have invested extra resources in this process. We have done it at the front and start of the process. By putting the resources into the training to support staff to develop the curriculum, once they actually teach the students, it is built in as part of what they do."
(Senior Manager 1, Traditional University)

These findings correspond to the results from the EAIE Barometer Ireland Spin-Off (2024), which concur that 85% of the participants from Irish HEIs perceive that 'strengthening international/intercultural content of the curriculum' is the most pressing topic requiring more attention to achieve institutional internationalisation ambitions in the next three to five years (p.28).

6.3.2.5 Employability Prospects for Learners

Building on the previous rationales, IaH's influence in enhancing the employability prospects for learners was perceived as valuable by both types of HEIs. Interestingly, for the TUs, the impact of IaH on the employability prospects of its learners was marginally more emphasised than the impact of IaH on teaching and learning. This finding can be linked to the practical, applied and industry needs-based orientation of the TUs (Dwyer and Seery, 2024; McTaggart, 2024; Morales, 2021).

For instance, some Irish learners (L 6 and L 10) assert that the skills they gain through international and intercultural interactions and projects are helpful for their professional development and employability prospects.

"It (IaH) just helps us learn about how to work with people and be in a classroom with people worldwide, which is important when you go into the work environment."
(Irish Learner 6, Technological University)

"Yeah, I just think it is our skills and knowledge. I think it is just the ability to talk to people you do not know. Just that skill of chatting to people.... internationally about broad topics and not offending anybody. That is a real skill I think that you learn through this (IaH)."
(Irish Learner 10, Technological University)

Moreover, many staff in both TUs and traditional universities concur with the need for IaH to develop the skills and competencies necessary to meet work-life demands.

"Intercultural competence and sensitivity are actually a really key skill for a lot of students in schools of nursing and medicine because they have graduates that need to acquire the ability to deal with the public and all different types of people in their work."
(Academic staff 2, Traditional University)

"I think it (skills and competencies through IaH) are valued more by the larger companies because the larger companies generally involve travel and communication with people in different countries."
(Academic Manager 3, Technological University)

"I have seen it recently with Irish and international students having difficult conversations around what is happening with Israel and Palestine.....and it is very, very difficult....and students are trying to make sense of that. They are having those conversations that they would not have been able to have if they had not been in the classroom together. I think that is critically important because I think that learning is really invaluable....and I think that might inform your mindset as you go out into the world of work and life."

(Senior Manager 3, Technological University)

Interestingly, the policy influencer (PI) also highlights the importance of IaH in preparing graduates for a multicultural work environment.

"I have been saying this for many years, and most of the reasons why internationalisation at home should be important are very explicit...it is really about working around the world or working in Ireland for multinational companies or companies with significant international partnerships. But the fact that even if they are working for an Irish company, the chances are... it is more or less guaranteed to have a number of colleagues who come from different backgrounds....and if you want to work effectively with them, then you need to learn how to do that, and higher education is the best place to do it if you haven't already."

(Policy Influencer)

The above findings closely connect to the previous insights from *sub-section 6.3.2.1* in relation to intercultural competence and global citizenship. Additionally, these findings are aligned with the existing literature on the importance of these '21st-century skills', which are significantly valued by employers and can be developed through IaH (Price, 2024; OECD, 2023; Beelen, 2019; Watkins and Smith, 2018; Jones, 2013).

6.3.2.6 Sustainability Considerations

Lastly, sustainability considerations were the least emphasised as a rationale for IaH, yet valuable when ascertaining climate-conscious ways to internationalise and create awareness around the United Nations' sustainable development goals (SDGs). However, the polysemic nature of the term 'sustainability' can invite varied interpretations when connecting it with internationalisation (Alam, 2023; Ilieva, Beck and Waterstone, 2014). For simplicity and breadth, we refer to Wals's (2012) definition, i.e. 'to enable citizens around the globe to deal with the complexities, controversies and inequities arising from issues relevant to the environment, natural heritage, culture, society and economy' (p.12).

The analysis brings to light that sustainability considerations were significantly more prominent for participants from traditional universities than their TU counterparts. This might reflect the proactive stance adopted by traditional universities towards embedding sustainability through the curricula and internationalisation practices (TRIP, n.d.; Gibson and Hazelkorn, 2025).

For instance, an Irish learner (L 7) discusses the importance of integrating the United Nations' SDGs into curricula and expanding perspectives on the global South.

"I think education as a whole serves a broader purpose. We had a core module on global development education, and we talked a lot about the SDGs, colonialisation, and the global South. So, looking at how we can utilise education to achieve various sustainable development goals....and if we kind of neglect education in the global South and only focus on the global north I think it can be like we are working in silos, and I think, as a whole, we need to know what is going on in the wider world."
(Irish Learner 7, Traditional University)

On the other hand, an academic manager from a traditional university (AM 1) highlights a CPD module for staff that links IaH with EDI and sustainability.

"We developed a professional development training course for academics and staff. It is online, and each module in it is 45 minutes long. The first module is an introduction to internationalisation at home, and we then align it to EDI, human rights, SDGs, our existing policies and practices, and how we can make internationalisation at home more inclusive and sustainable."
(Academic Manager 1, Traditional University)

The growing intersections between IaH and sustainability can primarily be attributed to COVID-19, which halted physical mobility and may have prompted climate-conscious thinking, as described by an international officer at a traditional university (IO 3) in a comment below.

"There is huge value as universities progress along the internationalisation journey that we need to be able to reap the benefits of internationalisation in diverse ways....and this is one of the ways, but also it really has to be champions from a sustainability perspective that the future of physical mobility is really, you know, going to be tested in terms of the changing patterns of travel and changing desires of travel experiences for students who are increasingly more climate-conscious."
(International Officer 3, Traditional University)

Albeit not extensive, some studies in Ireland, such as Kelly and O'Donoghue (2024), have provided examples of linking sustainability through IaH. Moreover, the researcher's own interest and core committee role in organising a 'Sustainability in the Arts Festival' at their institution enabled them to establish intersections between the two themes. This festival was recently awarded the National Forum Teaching and Learning Strategic Alignment of Teaching and Learning Enhancement (SATLE) funding for educational impact by the Higher Education Authority (HEA). The researcher has presented on several occasions at the institutional, national and international levels, linking their research on internationalisation at home with sustainability since 2023, which may have contributed to

the discourse (Piplani-Kapur, O'Neill, Murphy and Denieffe, 2025; Piplani-Kapur *et al.*, 2024; Piplani-Kapur *et al.*, 2023). Moreover, the finding on sustainability considerations supports the results of the EAIE Barometer Ireland Spin-Off (2024), where 58% of the respondents from Irish HEIs concur that 'environmental sustainability and climate action' warrant attention for Irish HEIs to achieve their internationalisation goals in the next three to five years (p.28).

In summary, the findings reveal that the development of intercultural competence and global citizenship, EDI considerations, impact of learner diversity, impact on teaching and learning, employability prospects for learners and sustainability considerations are some of the key rationales being pursued by Irish HEIs when engaging in IaH. Whilst these rationales have been demarcated into different categories, however, the researcher reflects a similar view with that of a Senior Manager from a TU (SM 2): *'You can't always slice and dice internationalisation, you can't, you know, put them into really clean categories, they're overlapped, they all have an impact on each other.'* The ensuing sub-section presents the enablers for IaH in the Irish context.

6.3.3 Enablers of IaH

In response to the first research question and the second research aim of identifying the opportunities for embedding a culture of IaH in Irish HEIs, this sub-section highlights the key 'enablers' for IaH, as described by the participants of this study. The findings reveal that the concept of IaH is nascent in Irish HE. However, some aspects of it have been in practice in institutional contexts for some time. These aspects, such as an internationalised curriculum, stakeholder engagement, collaborations, alliances and networks, institutional strategic planning, and mobility abroad, as depicted in [Figure 18](#), enable IaH in present-day Irish HEIs, creating opportunities for the further development of these themes and are explored in detail in this sub-section.

Figure 18: Enablers of IaH

6.3.3.1 Internationalisation of the Curriculum

This sub-section presents the first and most significantly emphasised enabler of IaH, an internationalised curriculum (Eftekhari *et al.*, 2025; Jones *et al.*, 2023; Trinh, 2019; Leask, 2015). An internationalised curriculum, elucidated in *Chapter 2 (sub-section 2.5.1)*, can comprise a formal curriculum (teaching, learning and assessment), an informal curriculum (co-curricular activities) and a hidden curriculum (implicit and unintended messages). As illustrated in *Figure 19*, the participants' accounts suggest that the informal curriculum is relatively more developed than the formal curriculum in the traditional universities than the TUs.

Figure 19: Enablers (IoC-University Perspectives)

Internationalisation of Curriculum

An academic staff from a traditional university (AS 2) comments about the development of an internationalised curriculum at their institution. Other participants expressed similar views.

"I think probably that it (IaH) is far more developed at the professional level (informal curriculum through the international office) rather than the faculty level (formal curriculum)... that would be my sense, although there have been over the last number of years, the development of all kinds of new programmes and modules in our university specifically with a global focus and that has been stronger in certain parts of the institution than others so certain colleges or schools have been more, I suppose, more keen to develop modules with a kind of more global focus than others some see it as inherent to their discipline and others see it as something an add-on that their discipline their fields don't naturally sort of speak to a global orientation."

(Academic Staff 2, Traditional University)

Interestingly, TUs emphasise relatively more examples of formal curriculum in practice than informal curricula; however, it could be due to the participants representing the disciplines more amenable to internationalisation.

An academic staff member from a TU (AS 1) remarks about the inherent nature of her programme, which makes embedding IaH easy.

"For me, it (internationalisation) is part of my programme. The module that I deliver is about international business culture. So, for me, internationalisation at home comes easy. I look at the literature that I share. I try and ensure that my content is about internationalisation. My content includes cases and the curriculum itself, the module descriptor, and case studies that are international. My students are international. The assessments that I do are COIL projects. I also link, where possible, with lectures from other institutes. I have guest speakers coming in that are from outside of the country as well. So, but yeah, do I see it then embedded in other modules or other programmes? I am not so sure. I think it is a little bit easier for me because of the programme that I am on."
(Academic Staff 1, Technological University)

Furthermore, despite the relatively modest emphasis on the internationalised formal curriculum as an enabler compared to the informal curriculum, there appears to be isolated but impactful pedagogical strategies adopted at traditional universities.

For instance, an academic manager in a traditional university (AM 1) describes a staff CPD in 'Universal Design for Learning (UDL),' enabling the staff to be more culturally responsive in all facets of university life, starting with the curriculum. According to Brown, David and Smallman (2017), UDL can be referred to as 'a learning framework meant to improve learning for all students by creating a flexible learning environment that accommodates learning differences—an approach based upon the core value of making resources accessible to all students' (p.81). Other participants from traditional universities also shared the significance of UDL when considering an inclusive curriculum design. Interestingly, the scholarly interest in this approach to internationalising the curriculum is gaining traction (Shohel, Sall, Ashrafuzzaman, Babu, Siddik, Tasnim and Akter, 2025; Akintayo, Eden, Ayeni, and Onyebuchi, 2024; Flood and Banks, 2021).

"So, we have a training course with a module specifically around internationalising the curriculum. But also, we have had training in 'Universal Design for Learning (UDL)' for many years. So many people have already done that training course. So, we are expanding UDL to be culturally responsive in our curriculum, in our teaching practices, and in our interactions across the university."
(Academic Manager 1, Traditional University)

Additionally, the findings indicate that virtual internationalisation through collaborative online international learning (COIL), virtual exchanges (VE) and Blended Intensive

Programmes⁷(BIPs), as explained in *Chapter 2 (sub-section 2.5.2)*, are gaining in popularity in Irish HEIs. The TUs appear to be pursuing virtual internationalisation relatively more actively than their counterparts at traditional universities (Kelly and O'Donoghue, 2024). It could be due to the TUs being inherently attuned to digital and technological advancements compared to traditional universities and benefitting from the synergies of a practical, low-investment nature of COIL, VE and/or BIPs initiatives in developing intercultural competence (Grover, Phutela and Yadav, 2025; Hackett *et al.*, 2023; Kučerová, 2023). However, participants' accounts reflect mixed practices where an academic staff has embedded COIL in the formal curricula, whereas others engage with it sporadically.

When reflecting on COIL, a senior manager from a traditional university (SM 1) described their candid views and shared their preference for a blended approach such as BIPs.

"I think the COIL movement has shades of MOOCs (Massive Online Open Courses). MOOCs were going to take over the planet, and no one was going to go to a boring university...and it proved to be like fiction. It never really took off...and I think it was never going to take off because people go to university not just for the knowledge and skills but they go for the social experience of learning and the transformation effect of being in a cohort for 3-4 years. It is called the 'sheepskin effect,' where the students carry the brand of the universities from which they were educated for a better life. You know, having bits of paper (certificates/diplomas) from different institutions has never fulfilled its potential...and I think COIL is probably somewhat similar in that sense. It was an excellent stopgap during COVID-19. You know, some people say we changed the world forever. Nothing would go back to normal. I think the truth was probably closer to the 'It was a flash in the pan.' We still use COIL for some things...however in a blended course where a chunk of it is done online, and then there is an intensive residential component. There are a few more of those around at the postgraduate level."
(Senior Manager 1, Traditional University)

Notwithstanding this critique, the rising significance of virtual internationalisation as an enabler of IaH from the participant perspectives reflects similar patterns to those identified by the EAIE Barometer Ireland Spin-Off (2024), where 74% of the respondents from Irish HEIs reflect a belief that virtual internationalisation will need more attention to achieve the internationalisation goals of their institution in the next three to five years (p.28). These findings align with the growing importance of the theme at the European (EAIE Barometer Survey, 2024) and international level (IAU Global Survey, 2024), enabling IaH.

⁷ Blended Intensive Programmes (BIPs) are 'short, intensive programmes that use innovative ways of learning and teaching, including the use of online cooperation. By enabling new and more flexible mobility formats that combine physical mobility with a virtual part, BIPs aim at reaching all types of students from all backgrounds, study fields and cycles' (European Commission, n.d.).

Moreover, the best practice HEI participants in this study indicated evidence of growing institutional focus towards embedding virtual internationalisation in the curricula, which could speak to the theme's relevance in IaH.

Furthermore, in the context of an internationalised curriculum, there has been some discourse around the hidden curriculum in traditional universities, with occasional remarks from the TUs. However, it remains a relatively underexplored concept (Fitzsimons and O'Neill, 2024; Clifford and Montgomery, 2017; Hughes and Tan, 2017). While the participants describe different aspects of the formal and informal curriculum, as well as CPD and EDI initiatives related to the theme, the term 'hidden curriculum' from an internationalisation perspective is unfamiliar to most of them. Additionally, references to the English language provision emerged infrequently, and participants from traditional universities touched upon it more than participants from the TUs. Moreover, it was mainly viewed from the standpoint of academic support for international learners and staff. A possible interpretation for this could be the legacy nature of the traditional universities with greater campus diversity, which thus stand to gain more from such provisions, as noted also by Clarke *et al.* (2018).

Overall, internationalisation of the curriculum was more prominent in conversations with the staff, in contrast to the findings by Clarke *et al.* (2018), which reported that 'Internationalisation of the curriculum,' albeit important, had limited resonance with academic staff (p.56). This shift may be attributed to rising global uncertainty and the health and climate crisis, which could have led to the gradual reevaluation of established views. For example, an academic staff from a traditional university (AS 2) captures this sentiment.

"Internationalisation is actually a kind of inevitable part of education in the sense that you know, and I think in a strange way the COVID-19 pandemic illustrated a lot of this because suddenly you had a threat that actually affected all of us on the planet all at once, and I think as we move into the 21st century, the world becomes closer right... so you start realising that you know what is happening in another part of the world is not entirely unconnected or disconnected to what is happening in Ireland... and I think that all of that sort of has, maybe shifted some people's ideas about how important it is to think about global dimensions or international dimensions in their curricula at a more theoretical level rather than an urgent issue that's come up in their classroom... so there can be these kinds of reflective decisions."

(Academic Staff 2, Traditional University)

Moreover, further unpacking of an internationalised curriculum reveals insights from the learners' perspective, as illustrated in *Figure 20*. The learners' reported perspectives correspond with the overall findings for this theme, where the informal curriculum appears

to be more developed than the formal curriculum. Notably, the literature remains contested on the impact of either curriculum in reaching all students. According to Brewer and Leask (2023), the informal curriculum can be perceived as impactful as the formal curriculum as learners 'learn everywhere' (p.247). However, Van Mol and Perez-Encinas's (2022) study findings indicate a greater impact of formal curriculum in achieving inclusive internationalisation that can overcome obstacles hindering learner participation outside their formal study schedules (p. 2523). In the case of Irish HEIs, it is acknowledged that more efforts may be needed to develop the formal curriculum across disciplines, reinforcing the findings from Clarke *et al.* (2018) report.

Interestingly, the analysis reveals that international learners demonstrate higher levels of engagement in the informal curriculum than domestic Irish learners (Mihut, 2024; Darmody, Groarke and Mihut, 2022). This finding is consistent with Van Mol and Perez-Encinas's (2022) study that learners with a 'migrant background,' which can include international learners, domestic learners who have experienced mobility abroad or first-generation learners, are more likely to engage in internationalisation activities (p.2535). Notably, the Irish

and international learners appear to value the internationalised formal curriculum to a similar extent, which could explain the broader reach of the internationalised formal curriculum to all learners and is not wholly dependent on learner motivation but on the requirements of the degree programme, as opposed to the informal curriculum that could be driven by learner motivation (Van Mol and Perez-Encinas, 2022). Most other learners agreed with this view, which was shared by an Irish learner from a traditional university (L7).

"I think that the informal curriculum or what you might be exposed to outside of the classroom... are all events that maybe the university organises, maybe society organises it, but it depends on people's goodwill or free will. They want to be there; they want to do this. And there is not any level of commitment required because it is not a class; it is just something that might be happening... and you are just attending it. So, I think if you were to fully reap the benefits of internationalisation at home, it needs to be embedded within formal programmes and not just within the hidden curriculum or just within the informal activities."

(Irish Learner 7, Traditional University)

Moreover, no explicit references were made to the hidden curriculum and virtual internationalisation by the international learners, enabling their experience. However, there were occasional references made by the Irish learners to the themes. Although understandably, the learners were unfamiliar with the lexicon, it may indicate that the discourses around hidden curriculum and virtual internationalisation practices are only beginning to surface in Irish HEIs. It is worth noting that a dearth of scholarly evidence exists around these themes from a learner's perspective.

Additionally, the best practice HEIs indicate a substantial focus of their institution on the formal curriculum, as it has the potential to reach all students. The participant from a best practice HEI in Europe highlights specific credits earmarked in some programmes supporting learning through IaH.

"In the first year, we have a couple of courses that we have clearly earmarked as Internationalisation at Home elements. But in the later years of the programme for a four-year degree course, students will have to make choices, and they will have to show at the end that they have actually taken 30 ECTS...so they are clearly earmarked as Internationalisation at Home elements, which includes COIL...as that is also in our educational strategy. So, I think that was a very clever idea of, you know, making students aware of how to develop international competencies and the choices that they can make to fit that. So, I think that from an implementation perspective, it was very interesting to do something like that."

(Best Practice HEI 1, Europe)

The aforementioned practice of identifying elements across a programme that reflect dimensions of IaH can offer learners flexibility and the opportunity to make choices that

meet their learning needs while facilitating the development of international and intercultural competencies. This process indicates alignment with a few aspects of the UDL approach, highlighted by some participants from traditional Irish universities and may need further exploration.

In essence, *Table 11* demonstrates IaH through the formal, informal and hidden curriculum initiatives drawn from various experiences through participants' accounts. In line with existing scholarship, an internationalised curriculum can be a significant enabler for IaH, albeit there is potential to further develop these themes in Irish HEIs (EAIE Barometer Survey, 2024; IAU Global Survey, 2024; Beelen, 2023; Sierra-Huedo et al., 2022; McCarthy and Butler, 2019; Jones, 2017; and Leask, 2015).

Table 11: Internationalisation of the Curriculum in Practice at Irish HEIs

Formal Curriculum

International learning outcomes in modules and programmes	International case studies	International academic staff	International seminars and masterclasses
International comparative perspectives and assessments, particularly leveraging learner diversity in the classroom	International guest speakers, as well as guest speakers from the local community working on global issues	Peer-to-peer learning through intentional mixed group work (Irish and international learners)	
International projects	International references in the module reading list	Hybrid joint degrees with international partners	Joint campuses abroad
Learner joint supervision or presentations to an international panel	Core and elective modules relating to globalisation, peacebuilding, international development, and sustainability, to mention a few	Accredited module on intercultural communication	
Teaching assistantships in Irish HEIs for international learners	Virtual internationalisation through virtual exchanges, collaborative online international learning (COIL) and blended intensive programmes (BIPs)		
Academic managers for internationalisation in different faculties	Modules that complement international placements or mobility	Integration of learner and staff reflections from mobility experiences	
Erasmus+, European University Alliances and research projects that link directly and indirectly with IaH	Community-based learning: International learners engaging with local communities and organisations in Ireland or Irish learners engaging with overseas communities for volunteer work or projects		
Language and culture area study centres for other countries in Irish HEIs	Internationalisation as an agenda item in faculty and programme review boards	Connecting internationalisation, equality, diversity, inclusion and sustainable development goals in the curricula	
Online courses or materials included in the curriculum on global issues/subjects or the global south	Community of practice on intercultural learning	Academic staff research fellowships developing an intercultural toolkit	
A compendium on university practices in internationalising the curriculum at home			

Table 11: Internationalisation of the Curriculum in Practice at Irish HEIs

Informal Curriculum

Multi-functional activity-based hubs such as global lounges	Promotion and education about forthcoming cultural celebrations	Tandem language learning through language learning hubs
Cultural events and festival celebrations of different countries, such as St. Patrick's Day, Diwali, Ramadan, Eid, Lunar New Year, Christmas, and Halloween, to mention a few		
Clubs and student societies (including societies representing different countries)	International days, nights, and weeks, festivals, orientation programs, and freshers' balls, to mention a few	
Newsletters and social media engagement posts (Instagram) regarding all updates of campus and residential life activities and events	Field trips and visits to Irish historical and cultural landmarks, and Christmas markets, to mention a few	
Campus public space sessions on topical international themes with international speakers such as black history month, film screening on Gaza	International student ambassadors, buddy programmes and global guides	Podcasts for international learners on different topics
International case competitions	Part-time projects with not-for-profit organisations working on international issues	Multicultural house sharing in dorms or campus residences
Intercultural volunteering opportunities on campus, such as with the international office, global lounge, and language learning hubs, to mention a few	Multidisciplinary, intercultural events on campus	English, Gaelic or foreign language workshops
Listing international and intercultural events, news and updates on websites, learning management systems, social media (Instagram), magazines, and newsletters, to mention a few	Socialisation events for Irish and international learners	
	Global leadership and international learner entrepreneurship programmes on campus	
International conferences and summits on campus	Academic English writing supports	International and Irish learners' participation in St. Patrick's Day parades
International learners actively involved in hosting international university delegations, organising immersion activities for international guests, and taking guests on campus and laboratory tours, to mention a few	Special needs support for international learners with disabilities	
Mental health and wellbeing counselling services for international learners (in English as well as their native languages)	Pastoral care for international learners	Resilience training, clinics for visa and immigration
	Internationalisation lunchtime seminar series for staff	

<i>Table 11: Internationalisation of the Curriculum in Practice at Irish HEIs</i>		
<i>Informal Curriculum</i>		
International guest speakers, as well as guest speakers from the local community working on global issues	Community-based learning: International learners engaging with local communities and organisations in Ireland or Irish learners engaging with overseas communities for volunteer work or projects	
Learners in international conference committees	International students' union, multicultural staff networks, Erasmus students' network chapters, and ICOS, to mention a few	
Advocacy on critical global incidents, including those from learners and staff-affected countries	Engaging with international alumni for seminars, outreach and brand-building	Workshops and trainings on global citizenship
Gaelic cultural events in joint campuses abroad	Working with local radio and groups that portray positive stories about migrant communities and international expats	
<i>Hidden Curriculum</i>		
International sources, illustrations, and references in the module reading list (particularly Indigenous people, underrepresented regions such as the Global South and marginalised voices or groups)	Communication with international learners by university staff, mainly professional support services, avoiding jargon, Irish colloquialisms, and acronyms, even in automated messages	
Decolonisation of the curriculum	Integrated intercultural communication/awareness training/workshops for learners and staff	Unconscious bias and equality, diversity and inclusion training

6.3.3.2 Stakeholder Engagement

This sub-section presents the stakeholders currently enabling IaH in Irish HEIs. As showcased in [Figure 21](#), the findings point to uneven patterns in engagement across various stakeholders. The stakeholders predominantly include the international office's influential role in shouldering IaH in Irish HEIs through informal activities and pastoral care (Clarke *et al.*, 2018). However, it is becoming increasingly evident that academic staff, senior leadership, and learners are playing their part in driving IaH, albeit mostly unconsciously.

Figure 21: Enablers (Stakeholder Perspectives)

Stakeholder Engagement

At the outset, participants from both types of institutions highlight the influential role of the international office in driving IaH initiatives, with some references to the role played by the academic staff in it.

"I think we could go back to the international office again, and I think they would definitely have to play a role. Now, in the department here, we have a large number of international lecturers, so we have lecturers from Venezuela, India, China, and lecturers from all other parts of Europe, basically...and so, they would also have a key role to play in. So, I think the lecturers from within the department would need to be consulted as well."

(Academic Manager 3, Technological University)

"I suppose it's (IaH) drivers are the Global Engagement office and the Assistant Deans International. But obviously, it involves all the different agencies, but in particular, we have a team in the Global Engagement Office, the International Student Engagement Team, and they look at the interests of international students, making sure that their needs are catered for. So, we already have an inclusion policy, an EDI policy, a human rights policy, all of that exists, but we make sure that in particular, the human rights and issues around equality and the needs of international students, the additional needs around language support, around cultural training, that they are addressed. So, it is the Assistant Deans and the global engagement office... it (IaH) is under the remit of the global engagement office."

(Academic Manager 1, Traditional University)

Similarly, in terms of structure, the best practice institution in the UK (BP HEI 2) is positioned comparably with that of Irish HEIs, with the international office playing a key role.

"Our Pro Vice Chancellor in globalisation, who might be the lead, but he is not from this subject area (expertise in IaH). So, he is kind of admin role from my perspective....and we have the international office colleagues kind of leading this. And then, we have a head of student life... another central team...and they are trying to build a community and connect with all the practitioners, scholars, researchers who are doing anything with international students."
(Best Practice HEI 1, UK)

In contrast, the best practice institution in Europe (BP HEI 1) considers the influential role of the academic staff in driving IaH at their institution.

"I work at the central level. So, we identified a number of gaps where we thought the academics are really in the driving seat for Internationalisation at Home. So, we invested heavily in professional development programmes. The international office, in our case, is very small, and it is basically an admin office for mobility. So, they deal with all the forms and the agreements, etc. Internationalisation at Home is divided across a few stakeholders. So, the teaching and learning labs are kind of loose. Then, there is a strategy team that sits within the board's office...and in that team, we have a COIL coordinator. So, it is his job to improve the overall quality of our COIL practice and increase the number. So, this person advises and assists academics, as well as programmes on how to sustainably embed COIL in the curricula. As COIL specifically mentioned in our latest institutional strategy, so that this position was created....and in the current structure, I would say that the overall responsibility lies with the team strategy. So, there is a manager, and they actually oversee everything that is happening. So, they liaise with the research group, liaise with the Centre for Teaching and Learning, and try also to get a grasp of what the teaching and learning labs are doing."
(Best Practice HEI 1, Europe)

Whilst the international/global engagement office may play a key role in Irish HEIs, this study's analysis reveals varied engagement patterns of stakeholders with IaH. For instance, the stakeholders such as learners, academic staff and support services in traditional universities tend to be relatively more engaged than their counterparts in the TUs. This could be due to greater awareness among staff and learners about activities and opportunities disguised as IaH initiatives. However, there is a noticeable gap in the literature regarding this dimension in the Irish context. An academic manager in a traditional university (AM 1) highlights the CPD supports for learners and staff when engaging with IaH at their institution.

"We have designed intercultural training for all support staff, intercultural training for all academics, training in internationalising the curriculum for academics, training in linguistic and culturally sensitive teaching for all academics, or anyone who is involved in working with international students. So, they are all interventions that, or let us say, supports that we provide. All students who come to our university receive intercultural training, both international and domestic students. So, they receive that orientation, and it is ongoing. We have a Global Lounge. So, this is an intercultural space in the university where intercultural training and intercultural events, celebrations, and initiatives happen all year round... and that is organised by the Global team with the faculties and the Student Union. So, the Student Unions at the undergraduate and postgraduate levels play an important role in this as well."
(Academic Manager 1, Traditional University)

Additionally, from the learners' reflections on IaH, there appears to be a greater level of satisfaction among learners from the traditional universities compared to the learners in the TUs. It could allude to a more advanced state of IaH in traditional universities mainly because of greater diversity, activities, events, and international learner support. This issue does not appear to be directly addressed in the existing research.

"I have seen that my university has done a great job in creating a department that helps solve all kinds of problems for international students (international office and global lounge)....and it covers everything from immigration, emergencies, medical help, or documents. Besides that, my university has a lot of societies, and I feel like they have done a great job of inculcating different kinds of cultural activities. Like I have been away from home for a few years, but I feel like I haven't missed out on the main festivals of my country at my university. So, it has been a great experience so far....and I have also got to go to different events of different countries, which has also improved my cultural knowledge. So, I think these are the two very strong things that my university is doing great in terms of being international."
(International Learner 2, Traditional University)

Moreover, in both types of institutions, while the role of senior leadership support in driving IaH is considered significant, it appears that they are currently formally less engaged in the process, except for one traditional university that is relatively more progressive than other institutions participating in this study.

An academic manager from that traditional university (AM 1) shares their organisation structure that facilitates IaH.

"So, it (IaH) is in our strategic plan, and there is an implementation strategy set out in our strategic plan, and there are targets in each category. The committee on internationalisation implements the strategy, so it is implemented across the university through the faculties, first of all, through the Assistant Deans International in each faculty, and then through the various agencies, so for example, the Disabilities Agency, the Academic Registry, the Library, and all of the services. There is a strategic person and a contact person for each of those, and we regularly meet. We meet every month."
(Academic Manager 1, Traditional University)

Besides HEIs, there is minimal evidence of policymakers' engagement to support the development of IaH in Irish HEIs, even though the national strategy emphasises IaH as important. However, policymakers/influencers primarily view IaH as a responsibility of the institutions.

"Broadly because what happens within the institutions is really up to each university. They are very autonomous; they are organised differently. They have different, not just different structures, but also, they are different schools and faculties, different cohorts of students from different places and different resourcing levels."
(Policy influencer)

"Our role at the department is to provide a framework. It is up to the institutions to implement that framework. Because of institutional autonomy, each president has to prioritise the actions within their institutions. You know, we cannot implement internationalisation within an institution. It is the people within the institution...that's where it lies."
(Policymaker)

Moreover, policymakers point to a role played by the Vice President (VP) of Global Engagement in Irish HEIs informing the government's understanding of international standing and internationalisation.

"On the whole, our experience from engagement with VPs that are responsible for a global engagement is that Ireland has a very positive message and a very welcoming message to find and that we are actually getting traction out there."
(Policymaker)

As the data reveals, the senior leadership can play a key influencing role in steering IaH, not only within the institution but also by actively advocating with policymakers and other external stakeholders that can impact the development of IaH in their institutions (Van den Hende, Whitsed and Coelen, 2023; Musiał, 2023). This finding echoes elements of the core theoretical perspective for this research on learning organisation (Senge, 1990) and organisation culture (Armenakis *et al.*, 2011) through 'commitment, persuasive communication, symbolism and diffusion practices' and most importantly, 'management of internal and external information', as explained in [Chapter 4 \(sub-section 4.2.3\)](#).

The engagement of various stakeholders could present an opportunity for the universities to drive IaH more systematically, backed by government support through resourcing (Garwe

and Thondhlana, 2022). Ultimately, the researcher concurs with a view by a senior manager in a traditional university (SM 4), '*IaH has to be everybody's responsibility in the university*'.

6.3.3.3 Collaborations, Alliances and Networks

This sub-section elucidates the role of collaborations, alliances and networks in facilitating IaH at Irish HEIs. The data analysis highlights that the participants from traditional universities and the TUs appear to value building and strengthening relationships through collaborations, partnerships, alliances such as the European University Alliances (EUA), and networks, in enabling IaH. Building on previous research by Clarke *et al.* (2018), which indicated that Irish HEIs identified a few challenges with maintaining collaborations and partnerships, such as the academic staff's investment of time and effort and difficulty in monitoring implementation (p.7). The current analysis, however, reveals that while time can be a significant constraint, the partnerships that emerge organically and are closely aligned with academic staff's teaching, learning or research goals tend to be more successful. For instance, accounts from some participants suggest that academic staff demonstrate enthusiasm for the EUA, Erasmus projects, and joint campuses abroad. This enthusiasm is primarily driven by their creativity, access to funding and the freedom to co-design and actively engage in teaching, learning and research activities, all of which can facilitate IaH (Frame and Curyło, 2025; Twomey and Murphy, 2025; Kelly and O'Donoghue, 2024).

Academic staff from TUs (AS 1 and AS 2) describe how they leverage collaborations and partnerships to enhance the COIL dimension in their programmes and contribute to Erasmus projects.

"The COIL project is an assessment that we link with another college abroad. I work with two. One is in Finland and the other is in France...and we set up an assessment that students in Finland and Ireland must complete....and the project this year, for example, would be a podcast, and they need to, together as a group, present or develop a podcast and publish it. We have run this project with the Finnish partner for maybe about five years now....and every year we still learn something new, but fine-tune a little bit."
(Academic Staff 1, Technological University)

"I got invited to be a part of the X Alliance. It is a kind of Erasmus thing where universities collaborate with the idea of perhaps developing joint programmes, doing research, and all that. The X has been going for 2 years. We are now 2024, and it is only now that I have been invited because they have just realised that we cannot do everything through English, and I was like, well, of course not, you know. So, internationalisation at home is a lot of reminding yourself of, you know, there are others that there are different ways of doing things, and it is not necessarily better. It is not necessarily worse. It is just different ways of working and communicating, and you know, getting these relations going and, you know, connections."
(Academic Staff 2, Technological University)

On the other hand, many staff in traditional universities highlight the role of joint campuses abroad, EUA, and networks in nurturing relationships and cultivating a culture of IaH in their institutions and offshore campuses.

"We have a centre for Chinese language and cultural studies and a centre for Irish language and cultural studies that also form part of our global engagement office. It is about the wider experience, including how to bring the best of Ireland to the world and the best of the world to Ireland. So, it also encompasses Irish language culture and heritage within that instead of just being focused on recruiting international students to come to Ireland."

(Senior Manager 4, Traditional University)

"Our university is part of a European University Alliance, and we have been doing some really good work, organising global summits, conferences, round tables, joint courses, programmes, publications, seminars, reports, etc. Academic staff have travelled through that and embedded some aspects in their curriculum....I think through existing alliances, and networks.... there is a lot of opportunity for good practice sharing. We also have a few networks with our institution, such as a multicultural staff network that is such an amazing group, and a network for intercultural competency to facilitate entrepreneurship that offers students the opportunity to develop valuable intercultural and entrepreneurial skills by completing a virtual learning programme developed by a consortium of many European universities in the EUA. So, there is a lot of potential and synergies that are contributing to internationalisation at home through these alliances and networks."

(International Officer 3, Traditional University)

The policy influencer (PI) also highlights the importance of EUA in developing IaH at Irish HEIs.

"I mean, a very significant development is underway at the moment with the European University Alliances. Some Irish institutions are still in their infancy... and have just been awarded additional national funding to support them for the coming couple of years, but they have very significant European funding. Part of the implicit objectives of all these alliances, which span across six to nine European universities across different countries, is to improve or enhance the opportunities available to students through all these soft internationalisation at home measures, so that it becomes part and parcel of, you know, a normal student's normal experience. So there is a lot of funding. I don't know if people even refer to it as internationalisation at home, but there is a lot of small, there are a lot of small low key developments taking place across these new European university alliances and twelve Irish universities are involved with them seven traditional universities plus five TUs and it will be interesting to see, you know, on the ground.... how those develop over time, but the opportunities are there for students to engage in learning, formal and informal, across the network of partners.. it is quite considerable. But it is very much positioned within a European context as opposed to a global context. But that is still internationalisation."

(Policy Influencer)

The policymaker (PM), too, reinforces the importance of maintaining partnerships and collaborations to advance IaH.

"The new strategy is more than recruiting students and having international students in Ireland, where they bring income and everything like that to institutions. First, this has to be a very clear national message that we want partnerships and institutions to engage with other institutions...and I suppose what that would mean in some respects is that this is not about having as many as possible. This is actually about encouraging institutions to grow relationships with, like I said, like-minded and similarly valued institutions. The Irish institutions have to make sure that they can follow them and maintain them. But that they also align with their values, their mission, their policy domains and disciplines, and stuff like that. Instruments such as joint awards etc... It will start seeping into all those other curriculum dimensions and IaH activities."

(Policymaker)

In regards to partnership building, the policymaker (PM) further emphasises the importance of EUA and the need to strengthen ties with the UK.

"For instance, when you look at things like the European University Alliances and other European movements of that nature, that is very important to us. We also value the relationship with the UK very strongly, and we want to see that maintained, and we want to see, post-Brexit, how we can keep this going, particularly as the UK is out of the EU. And yet, you know, outside the EU, they are still very close to Ireland, and Ireland is still very close to them on an institutional basis. How can we maintain those? So, you can see things of that nature... how we work with institutions to build those relationships and partnerships. So, when focusing on these relationships, an institution is maximising opportunities for themselves and their students."

(Policymaker)

The above findings align with recent literature, including a study by Frame and Curylo (2024) that reinforces the impact of EUA on IaH such as 'encouraging HEIs to go beyond existing forms of cooperation to bring Europe home to the wider higher education community' and 'multiplying the levels and types of cooperation between partner institutions and making this an everyday occurrence throughout the domestic higher education experience' (p.334). As a result, the scholars argue that 'EUA can be seen as potentially promoting a form of everyday Europeanhood' (Ibid.). Moreover, the finding is in convergence with other scholarly research pointing to the positive impact of collaborations, alliances and networks in developing IaH (Kokkonen, Natri and Moisiu, 2025; Soulé, Parmaxi, and Nicolaou, 2024; and Beelen, Wimpenny and Rubin, 2021).

In essence, Ireland, as a nation, along with its institutions, possesses a welcoming, open, and friendly approach to partnerships, which can significantly enhance teaching, learning, and research. These collaborations may serve as a vehicle to fulfill their aspirations in IaH, as reflected in the participants' accounts.

6.3.3.4 Institutional Strategic Planning

This sub-section highlights the importance of institutional strategic planning, which is currently beginning to enable IaH in Irish HEIs. This could primarily be because of the legacy nature of the traditional universities in hosting international learners and staff and comprising advanced processes and functions that support an international learning environment, as described earlier. Moreover, the IoT's merging into the TUs is a recent feature in Irish HE, as outlined in *Chapter 3 (sub-section 3.2)*. The evidence portrays that the participating TUs during the interviews were in the early stages post-merger, working out mechanisms to integrate systems and processes. This may impact their capacity to institutionalise and embed IaH (Ryan, 2020). However, they are making progress in relation to IaH in their strategic planning. Notably, except for one traditional university, all other universities in the sample consider themselves in the formative stages of institutionalising and embedding IaH, even though each institution engages in various initiatives that enable IaH, either consciously or unconsciously.

Most Irish HEIs in this study have explicitly articulated IaH in their institutional strategies, as described in *Chapter 3 (sub-section 3.7)*. Moreover, many HEIs have recently established working groups for IaH at a university level and are exploring ways to further develop and systematically embed IaH within their institutions.

An academic manager from a traditional university (AM 1), which is relatively more advanced than other institutions in the study, highlights the clear articulation of IaH in their institutional strategy and a committee that has facilitated its implementation for many years.

"Yes, so it (IaH) is explicitly stated (in their strategy), and we have a working group, a committee that meets every month, a university-wide committee, that is, we have representatives from all over the university, all agencies, all faculties, all services are represented in that committee."
(Academic Manager 1, Traditional University)

Moreover, AM 1 describes their institutional efforts to embed IaH in accordance with their strategic plan. They are adopting a collaborative approach that combines top-down (governance, senior leadership) with the bottom-up participation (staff, learners, departments and functions) (Price, 2024; Van den Hende *et al.*, 2023; Villares Maldonado, 2022; Ryan, 2020).

"So, we have the Vice President for global engagement, and then in each faculty there is an Assistant Dean- International, so we are not in the same line, but we are working horizontally, I suppose, across the faculties with the global engagement office, and then at the higher level. So, we have our own faculty strategic plans, but they mirror the higher-level university plan in internationalisation at home, so we obviously look at the higher-level plan and make sure that our faculty plans align with that."
(Academic Manager 1, Traditional University)

"I am very lucky that I do have an admin team. So, as part of my job, I am very much involved in building systems and processes. So, we have the SharePoint hub, the internationalisation activities, and internationalisation at home activities, making it easy to see what's happening. So, people can check that there are regular updates around that, that it is mentioned at the faculty board, and that it is mentioned at the management committee. So obviously, trying to make sure it is an item that is always included. We do not just discuss academic regulations; we also discuss internationalisation at home, which is given equal weighting. So that is really important...and we have contact links in every discipline and committees. So, we have committees at the faculty level, global level, and school and department level, that are all feeding up and feeding down to each other."
(Academic Manager 1, Traditional University)

For another traditional university, although the term 'IaH' is not explicitly articulated in their institutional strategy, the statements suggest an implicit orientation towards it, as indicated by their senior manager (SM 4).

"So, I would say yes. Not that it is articulated as such, but if you go to our current university-level strategy, the core objective talks about an inclusive educational experience and prepares our graduates to thrive in present and future societies. Recognising that it is... you read into it what you want; I want to read into that internationalisation at home."
(Senior Manager 4, Traditional University)

Similarly, staff from the TUs also acknowledge that IaH has found its place as a priority in their institutional plans.

"From an institutional point of view, it does inform our strategy, and it is part of the priority that they hold to ensure that internationalisation at home is achieved and by doing that, they want integration of intercultural dimensions into the formal and informal curricula."
(Academic Staff 1, Technological University)

"In the lead up to our first overall strategic plan for the university, there were several working groups set up...and one of those working groups focused specifically on international... and all of these working groups, including this international working group, was asked to, after, you know, consideration, consultation, research, all of that, they were asked to put forward three high level strategic objectives for their areas. The international working group put forward its three, and one of those three was specifically Internationalisation at Home. So, I think that, you know, that's important. So that found its way into a prominent enough position in our new overall strategic plan. And, you know, our strategic plan does require that we put in place an Internationalisation at Home strategy, a five-year strategy. So now that the strategic plan is published, we are now developing other supporting plans under that umbrella plan."
(Senior Manager 2, Technological University)

During a discussion about the working group for IaH, an international officer from a traditional university (IO 3) expressed relief that she was not expected to represent everything 'international'.

"It was one of the first meetings I attended in fourteen years at my institution, where there was a representative from every discipline, function, and support service in a working group. It was the first time I wasn't asked to be the representative of everything 'international'. You know, they (the chairs) asked everybody about what they were doing to bring the international and intercultural dimension in their work...it made it clear that internationalisation (IaH) is everybody's responsibility. I was impressed!"
(International Officer 3, Traditional University)

An academic staff from the same traditional university (AS 2) further highlights how the working group for IaH is developing.

"Well, at present it (IaH) is in development. There is a working group focusing on internationalisation at home and looking at where we are. We are currently mapping out areas for us to focus on and areas where there is activity, whether in the formal or informal curriculum. So, people from different parts of the university working in very different types of capacities have come together in this working group to sort of map out those areas of activity, which is a relatively new phenomenon. It is something that I'm part of. In terms of the kind of institutional rollout of internationalisation at home... my understanding is that it's at a very early stage, even though the language of internationalisation has been used. It is kind of interesting to see or not see how this seeps into the activities of the university. So, it is being part of that working group has actually opened my eyes to activities and work that's being done in different parts of the university, particularly outside of the kind of formal academic provision, to see the types of work that my colleagues are doing in the institution."
(Academic Staff 2, Traditional University)

As the data suggests, the strategic rhetoric is beginning to exhibit IaH as one of the key priorities for most institutions. Many participants appreciate the institution-wide consultation through the working group that has the potential to enable a culture of IaH in their institutions (Cunningham, Topping and Levy, 2024; Sierra-Huedo *et al.*, 2022; Jooste and Hagenmeier, 2022), with the exception of one traditional university that is further along the

curve in embedding IaH. However, these developments have a general positive sentiment across universities and staff stakeholder groups. Interestingly, the growing strategic attention towards IaH is timely with this study's contribution. Some senior leaders and the policy influencer highlight the potential of this research in informing their approach with remarks such as *'your research will be really interesting for us to read as well and hopefully apply some of your findings'* (SM 4, Traditional University) and *'this is part of my latent criticism of previous strategies... they have talked about the importance of internationalisation at home, but nobody has ever gone out to create an evidence base as far as I am aware, and maybe your study is going to change that...I am sure some of the work that you are doing could help inform the implementation of the strategy along the way'* (PI).

In summary, the global (IAU Global, 2024) and European (EAIE Barometer, 2024) surveys on internationalisation ([Chapter 2](#)), the Irish government's Global Citizens 2030 strategy (DFHERIS, 2024), and the institutional plans of most Irish HEIs ([Chapter 3](#)) underpin the relevance of IaH in the present-day Irish HE landscape. The institutional strategies and the working groups for IaH can be considered as laying the groundwork towards systemic embedding of IaH, which presents a valuable opportunity to further build on the efforts towards the theme to benefit all learners and staff from internationalisation.

6.3.3.5 Mobility Abroad

The final sub-section presents the role of mobility abroad as an enabler for IaH in Irish HEIs. The wider literature remains contested on the relationship between IaH and mobility abroad, where many scholars characterise IaH as an 'alternative' to mobility (Coelen, 2024; Blanta and Karras, 2024; Antonopoulou, 2021), whilst few others consider it as 'complementary' (Bulnes and de Louw, 2022; Beelen, 2022; Phùng and Phan, 2021; Jones, 2019). The findings from this study reinforce the complementary nature of IaH. Moreover, they align with the results from Clarke *et al.* (2018) report that 'outward mobility is not just important for students themselves but also contributes hugely to internationalisation at home in Irish HEIs' (p.88). The participant accounts across the traditional universities and the TUs suggest a broadly shared perspective on this view that mobility abroad enables IaH at their institutions.

For instance, Irish learners who had gained international experience reflected a positive outlook towards international learners and internationalisation in their institutions. They became more engaged when they experienced being an international learner themselves during their time abroad.

"I actually participated in the buddy program this year. So, I was a leader. I had a student from India, a student from France and a student from Algeria. So, it was my job to kind of give tours of the campus. There were events organised. Things like that, I could offer my Irish perspective, and they could meet fellow international students. But this program has always run at my university, but for my first 3 years, I am in my final year now, I didn't know it existed...and I feel like it's something that Irish people, Irish students, are kind of hesitant to get involved in. I am not sure why. But in my personal experience, when I first heard of it, I thought: What do I have to offer these international students? I thought that I had nothing to offer. However, it was only when I had my own experience abroad and when I found it hard to mix with French students... that is when I realised then how important it is for the international students to have someone from the actual country to interact with, learn with, ask questions, from a cultural perspective, everything, it kind of all started making sense to me. I realised how important it actually is."

(Irish Learner 11, Traditional University)

An international officer from a traditional university (IO 1) reinforced the perspective presented by L 11, who noted that Irish learners returning from abroad tend to be more involved in campus activities (informal curriculum). Many of these students express a desire to give back by assisting other international learners through buddy programs.

"Just to give you an example last year I had X international students paired with Y volunteers and we run that twice a year so, in autumn and in spring, because in spring we take in a new cohort of visiting students so, we are currently in the process of there of recruiting volunteers for that...and what we are finding actually, interestingly enough, in the last few years is that we are not getting a lot of students that want to volunteer for it in autumn because they are going abroad themselves but in spring-term I am oversubscribed. So those students themselves have gone abroad to Spain, France, Portugal, wherever...and either had help or didn't have help and what we are noticing is in the spring term of the third year, we are oversubscribed with students who want to volunteer for the buddy program. The feedback we get at that stage is unbelievable ...you know, if I had this while I was abroad, or I did have it. I now want to repay and offer it to other new international students, so there is a real sense of awareness, particularly for those students who did go abroad for one semester, when they return, of the challenges that international students face."

(International Officer 1, Traditional University)

A senior manager at a traditional university (SM 1) sheds light on the 'intentional' pairing of domestic and international learners for buddy programs based on the domestic learners' mobility abroad destination aspirations (Zadavec, 2025; Cunningham *et al.*, 2024; Beelen and Jones, 2015).

"For our buddy scheme, we have a domestic student and an international student. Many of those international students are coming from the country where domestic students will go to on their own business exchange...so, suddenly now having Spanish friends is really useful because you are going to be spending a semester in Spain and having Spanish friends who can tell you about the culture and the food and the language and help you prepare your conversation in Spanish. It is a real essence. So, we are always trying to find positive situations for engaging students. You can't assume it will happen naturally."

(Senior Manager 1, Traditional University)

It is worth noting that staff mobility was less emphasised and primarily appeared in the accounts from traditional universities. Moreover, mobility abroad for international learners was conspicuous by its absence in participants' narratives. This omission may stem from the assumption that international students are already 'mobile,' pursuing higher education abroad (Van Mol, Clevén, and Mulvey, 2024; Kommers and Bista, 2021). Nonetheless, an international learner from a traditional university (L 16) emphasises the university's 'responsibility' to give international learners global exposure.

"The thing is that I am an international student here. I mean, doing anything in this country would technically be international for me but it is not enough but it is like the responsibility for the university as well to give you the opportunity to like learn more about different cultures and have more experiences...just not Irish or from the EU but learning more globally in that sense."
(International Learner 16, Traditional University)

In essence, mobility abroad, in its present form, is viewed as enabling learners to engage in campus activities, participate in Erasmus programmes embedded in their curricula and improve teaching and learning practices at home for some staff. The latter is an area that presents an opportunity for further development in Irish HEIs, particularly through Erasmus, EUA, networks and partnerships, as described in *sub-section 6.3.3*.

Overall, an internationalised curriculum, stakeholder engagement, collaborations, alliances and networks, institutional strategic planning and mobility experiences abroad significantly enable IaH in Irish HEIs. However, each of these enablers is confronted with challenges that may be systemic and hinder Irish HEIs from fully realising their ambitions in IaH. The following sub-section presents the participants' accounts of the prime obstacles they face in their everyday practice when implementing IaH.

6.3.4 Challenges in IaH

Whilst the enablers discussed in the previous sub-section contribute to implementing IaH in Irish HEIs to some extent, a few challenges persist, meriting targeted efforts to move from 'implementing' to 'systemic embedding' of IaH in Irish HEIs. The barriers that continue to surface include learner and staff engagement, leadership commitment and awareness and visibility for IaH that were predominantly emphasised in participant accounts. Other challenges that were marginally less emphasised but were considered of significant relevance encompassed fragmented implementation of IaH initiatives and inadequate support through national policymaking. These challenges are illustrated in *Figure 22*.

As described in the previous sub-sections, the relatively advanced nature of internationalisation in traditional universities may have resulted in greater emphasis across multiple discussion points by the participants from those universities. However, challenges around awareness and visibility and national policymaking accorded similar levels of significance in participants' reflections in both the traditional universities and TUs. Additionally, there was marginally more emphasis by the traditional universities on learner and staff engagement, leadership commitment and support and fragmented implementation of IaH initiatives.

6.3.4.1 Learner and Staff Engagement

The first predominant challenge across the participants' accounts was learner and staff engagement towards IaH. *Figure 23* showcases the challenges in engagement with IaH for academic staff, learners and support services staff. The support services cited in participants' accounts refer to the professional, administrative and student support services. This encompasses the offices/departments of admissions, academic registry, international

relations/global engagement, academic and language supports, careers, health and wellbeing, students' union, EDI, teaching and learning (CPD), information technology (IT), human resources, finance, estates, alumni relations, to mention a few (Clarke *et al.*, 2018; O'Reilly, Hickey, and Ryan, 2013).

Interestingly, academic staff engagement, as a barrier, was comparably significant for both traditional universities and the TUs. Moreover, while the learners from traditional universities shared more, a deep insight into the data reveals that learner engagement in IaH is a relatively significant challenge in the TUs than in the traditional universities, possibly due to a lack of access to opportunities for engagement in IaH initiatives.

Moreover, support services as an area of concern were significantly more prevalent in the accounts of staff participants than learners in the traditional universities, as opposed to the TUs, where there was a limited reference. The minimal attribution to support services by TU participants may be due to a lack of clear understanding regarding their role in shaping

internationalised learner experiences that may be prevalent in the assumption that the *'international office is responsible for all things international'* (AM 2). The literature reveals a noticeable gap in relation to the role of support services in the internationalisation of Irish HEIs.

When considering learners' impediments in fully engaging with IaH initiatives, reasons such as interactions with the academic staff, curriculum, scheduling of events, accessibility through infrastructure, accommodation, funding, time and space and, most importantly, 'cultural ghettos' were cited as prime concerns. Most of these challenges were of comparable significance for both Irish and international learners.

It is interesting to note that the international learners commonly shared their concerns about the 'cultural ghetto' characteristic of the Irish learners that made it challenging to develop or maintain friendships with them. Cultural 'ghettos' refer to cliques or groups of people with similar socio-economic-cultural characteristics that naturally bond them (Lavakare, 2025; Kelly, 2022; Webb, 2007). Interestingly, Clarke *et al.* (2018) report highlights the 'stickiness' or 'cultural ghetto' nature of the international learners pointed by their study's participants (p. 68), however, because the current study comprised more international learners than Irish learners, the cultural ghetto characteristics of Irish learners received comparably significant attention. In any case, Clarke *et al.* (2018) findings acknowledge that 'some domestic students felt that as they were busy with coursework, they did not put effort into meeting new people' (p.68) which may reinforce the findings of the study that cultural ghettos was a common characteristic for both learner groups.

When sharing their experience, an international learner from a traditional university (L3) expresses their disappointment regarding the lack of social opportunities to stay with other Irish or international learners in campus accommodation, which may inadvertently reinforce the ghettos rather than promote intercultural learning.

"So, this is what has been on my mind the entire conversation. I am an American, and I only have American roommates this semester in my on-campus accommodation. I am honestly quite disappointed, and I feel like they are not trying to group students together by background and all that kind of thing. But I think they really need to make sure that students who are living on campus have access to a diverse household because it does us no benefit to be sectioned off. It does the Irish students also no benefit to be separating the international students in such a way. But yeah, I think meeting people in their house is one of the best ways to actually make friends without feeling like there is too much pressure and structure from the school, and I don't know what has gone wrong in their planning."

(International Learner 3, Traditional University)

While L3 demonstrates a sense of discontent, an Irish learner (L9) describes their struggle to find accommodation closer to the university, which could have been an obstacle for universities mixing learners in campus accommodation. The housing crisis and lack of student accommodation in Ireland are concerns that appear to directly impact how students engage with each other cross-culturally, which has also been highlighted in the Clarke *et al.* (2018) report.

"The university is having such an accommodation problem at the moment...and I think one of the things causing private university accommodation to be given and allocated to international, Erasmus, etc. I think that the problem of the way people end up being housed actually runs deeper than just choosing where to put people. I think it goes beyond that....and a great example is I am not even living on campus. I have not been at the university for most of this year. I am operating remotely because I was not able to get accommodation...and the university is doing this thing where every single year it is taking more and more students in, both international and national...and there aren't enough houses...and I think what's unfair about that is it is putting people in this scenario. I know many international students who are living in hotels. Like, that is shocking...and I am so embarrassed as a student of the university to hear that people are coming and trying to study at our university, and that they are being faced with that issue. I am lucky I can stay at home. I am here, I am fine, but not everybody has a home."
(Irish Learner 9, Traditional University)

In addition to a mixed accommodation that may facilitate intercultural encounters, the informal campus activities labelled as 'international' may inadvertently reinforce cultural ghettos. This phenomenon is observed by many learners, who note that such events often seem primarily organised for and by international learners, which can further marginalise these groups. As a result, individuals may retreat into their familiar cultural enclaves, ultimately undermining the potential for meaningful intercultural connections (Moran, Green, and Warren, 2021; O'Connor, 2018; Clarke *et al.*, 2018).

"I wanted to add that we also face the same thing in the Global Lounge, where we find it hard to attract Irish students because the word global sometimes puts off Irish students. I guess they think that the Global Lounge is only for international students."
(International Learner 16, Traditional University)

"I was just thinking that the institution I am in does not do much to create experiences that promote internationalisation, and I have a very small number of societies. But just like an interesting thing was...I tried to join the international students society but I was told I couldn't because I'm not an international student because I really wanted to meet different, you know, students from like different countries that have come but I wasn't allowed so I think that was kind of, I just found that strange."
(Irish Learner 1, Technological University)

Additionally, one international learner in a traditional university (L15) describes the need to 'seek out' international exposure as they study in a programme majorly comprising learners from their home country, which may inadvertently result in cultural insularity.

"I look at my cohort, there are about 160 students, out of which you know probably 135 would be Indians with a few from China, Europe and America... so I mean I have to kind of 'seek' an international experience of whether it is in the form of creating projects together, or doing assignments together which I find really difficult as I came abroad to get a global exposure and not have similar classroom set ups that I had back in India."
(International Learner 15, Traditional University)

Although a skewed distribution of diversity in classrooms can perpetuate a sense of exclusion from IaH experiences due to structural factors, some participants recognise their personal limitations that lead them to retreat into these cultural ghettos.

"I think there is a huge culture in Ireland of leaving secondary school and going to university with people you already know. I am in a university which is 2 hours from where I live at home, and I could name 20 people already in that university before I even got there. We have a tendency to just stick together. I don't know what it is, but it is just a thing we all Irish students need to stick together. If there were a mix, it would be the international students themselves approaching us to make friends or whatever, it would never be the other way around."
(Irish Learner 11, Traditional University)

"I find it easier to talk to and become friends with international students more than Irish students. I don't understand why, but whenever I talk to Irish students, that same level of connection is not maintained as compared to international students... may maybe because our journeys and challenges are common with other international students."
(International Learner 5, Technological University)

Furthermore, International learners often note that Irish learners tend to return home on weekends, which reduces opportunities for interaction and socialisation (Clarke *et al.*, 2018). This also highlights universities' difficulties scheduling after college hours or weekend events, as many Irish students leave for home.

"I also feel like the events here at my university, when casual, cool, and fun are organised...they are on the weekends....and that means that the Irish students who go home on the weekends generally can't attend or, you know, they don't want to attend because, you know, who would want to stay on campus when it is dead."
(International Learner 3, Traditional University)

"Yeah, I think I am just thinking like the main barriers for students in my course, not to get more involved in say student life is like everyone is working like part-time jobs and like time management is like a problem for a lot of students and that is a barrier for them getting really involved in kind of stuff that will be on in say the evenings or, you know, outside of the 9-5 kind of college times...and yeah, definitely another barrier is like the lack of a network, like an existing one...and that is kind of easy to join or, you know, easy to be informed...and yeah, another barrier is like difficulty in accessing the funding available either through societies or different avenues. It is just not like known about to many students."

(Irish Learner 1, Technological University)

Additionally, some learners from the TUs noted that the 'whiteness' of their curriculum and lecturers hindered their opportunities for international exposure through formal curriculum (Kieran and McDonagh, 2021).

"I was surprised throughout my degree that the majority of my lecturers are Irish, and there were not really that many different kinds of experiences introduced, which I think would have been, I don't know, more valuable because a lot of people in my course would go on to do things like social work...and like, yeah, I think it is definitely important...and I was kind of surprised that there weren't more international perspectives kind of brought into my course."

(Irish Learner 1, Technological University)

"I think one of the worst cases of lack of international knowledge I have seen was actually from a lecture to students in the class. I saw just a really bad attitude from a lecturer saying they couldn't understand the person (an international learner) and asking the class, can you tell me what they said? The person was right in front of them, pretending they couldn't understand somebody with an accent, and dismissing their international examples because they weren't Irish examples."

(Irish Learner 10, Technological University)

Besides the predominantly white curriculum and staff, many learners from the TUs pointed out the scarcity of social spaces and infrastructure that cater to the specific needs of learners with disabilities and women on campus for planning or organising activities and events.

"My university has a serious lack of social spaces on campus. It is very difficult to book a room, even if you are trying to set up a society or, say, organise an event, and it is very inaccessible and quite intimidating. Like, so the only really social space we have is... in the Students' Union, which is, from speaking to a lot of women, particularly feel intimidating to go to, it's like pool tables and play station games, it's just full of guys, it wouldn't be really welcoming, it is not really nice space. And then maybe like just the accessibility of events, like the college is quite inaccessible, say for students with disabilities."

(Irish Learner 6, Technological University)

It seems clear that many of the challenges learners encounter have resulted in an unintentional cultural insularity between Irish and international students (Kelly, 2022). This separation may stem from gaps in existing systems or from the learners' own choices, which is consistent with the findings of the Clarke *et al.* (2018) report. In contrast to the existing literature, there were no mentions of barriers related to language or differing working styles affecting assessment grades of Irish and international learners (Harrison, 2015; Rienties *et*

al., 2014). Instead, the predominant themes that emerged were the limited opportunities for international exposure on campus, inadequate infrastructure and the cultural ghettos that impeded learners' engagement with IaH, particularly for those from the TUs.

Overall, reflections from the learner participants indicate a notable sense of dissatisfaction among learners at the TUs compared to those at traditional universities. TU learners primarily cited insufficient opportunities within the formal and informal curriculum and accessibility supports, making their engagement in IaH quite challenging. In contrast, learners from traditional universities expressed significant satisfaction with the informal curricular opportunities provided by their institutions. However, they acknowledged that more could be achieved through the formal curriculum in certain disciplines, scheduling of events and campus housing. This finding supports the analysis presented in the enablers [sub-section 6.3.3](#), where both staff and senior leadership recognise that the informal curriculum is more developed and that there is a greater need to enhance the international and intercultural dimensions in the formal curriculum in Irish HEIs.

Furthermore, a systemic approach may be necessary to integrate all experiences cohesively, in line with the 'curriculum as a whole' philosophy articulated by Brewer and Leask (2023). While most challenges learners face can be found to some extent in the broader literature on internationalisation, and in the Irish context as discussed by Clarke *et al.* (2018), there is a notable lack of comprehensive evidence on how these themes collectively shape the learner experience in Ireland. Ultimately, the challenges in learner engagement call for Irish HEIs to adopt a thoughtful and intentional approach if they aim to advance their IaH objectives (Clarke and Hui Yang, 2021; Ryan, 2020).

From the perspective of academic staff, the challenges associated with engaging in IaH relate to a perceived disruption to their academic self when attempting to internationalise curricula, as well as insufficient time and space to develop meaningful internationalised interventions. While the staff at both traditional universities and TUs share concerns regarding the impact of curriculum internationalisation on academic identity and autonomy, the issue of inadequate time and space is markedly more pronounced among academic staff from the TUs. This discrepancy may be attributed to the significantly higher teaching loads in TUs, which range from 16 to 18 hours per week, nearly double the load of their counterparts at traditional universities, as noted in [Chapter 3 \(sub-section 3.2\)](#) (Houghton, 2020; Boland, 2016).

Remarkably, the participants from the TUs consistently articulated that their significant teaching responsibilities directly impede their ability to internationalise the curriculum, in contrast to the academic staff at the traditional universities (Ryan *et al.*, 2020). While staff at traditional universities also express concerns regarding time management and workload distribution, these issues can blur the lines between engagement and burnout, aligning with the theoretical framework for this study on the 'job-demands resources' model (Bakker *et al.*, 2014, 2007).

When discussing the challenges in IaH through the formal curriculum, some participants' reflections indicate internationalising a curriculum as altering their academic self and autonomy in their academic practice (Green and Mertova, 2016; Sawir, 2013). This notion is closely aligned with stakeholder salience theory (Mitchell *et al.*, 1997), which suggests that academic staff in Irish HEIs have the autonomy to make decisions about internationalising their curricula based on the 'power, legitimacy, and urgency' (p. 872) of the claims involved (in this case, IoC). It also resonates with stakeholder culture theory (Jones *et al.*, 2007), where academic staff prioritise their practices between self-regarding or learner-regarding when considering engagement in IaH (p. 152), as described by an academic staff from a traditional university (AS 2).

"It (IoC) can be very disruptive to the academic sense of how they are and how they have done things before, so it means interrogating a lot of practices that they would have taken for granted as the gold standard in higher education, and the professional identities are very connected to these practices. So, it is a cultural change itself to support academics in reimagining what an internationalised curriculum would look like. It is not just about the curricula; it is also about the identities of the people involved in redesigning their curricula. So, my sense is that internationalising the curricula is an emotional process for many staff."

(Academic Staff 2, Traditional University)

In addition to the sense of academic self, certain effective practices in internationalising the curriculum tend to be overlooked, possibly because academic staff have concerns about their legitimacy.

"We will have, like they have been colleagues of mine who have talked about you know group work that they have had their students do, but that is not reflected formally in their learning outcomes or even in you know a description of their modules and in the module descriptors. So sometimes I think there is a perception that that kind of work isn't legitimate enough for learning outcomes...so it (IoC) goes by silent or hidden and not formally captured... it is not a predictable way of teaching and learning. So maybe there is a reluctance to formally name it as a thing they are doing."

(Academic Staff 2, Traditional University)

Additionally, AS 2 states that the staff who internationalise their curricula do so as an emergency response to the increasing number of international students in their classrooms, rather than as a planned initiative.

"It is (IoC) very often framed still as in this deficit model and I think that that is often because the issue of internationalisation comes up for many academics in a kind of emergency rather than a planned decision as a programme team to sit down and kind of do this kind of work where they start planning their curriculum and thinking about the different types of students they have. I think it often is a kind of emergency response where things haven't gone quite as well as they wanted to and they have large numbers of international students and that is when they start thinking about this in their own practice so yeah I think it is rare for programme teams to be prompted to think about internationalisation unless there is a problem that they are looking to address."

(Academic Staff 2, Traditional University)

The perspectives on academic self can be linked to time and space constraints that arise from the heavy workloads of academic staff. Moreover, the results of their efforts, specifically, the enhancement of learners' intercultural competencies, can often be perceived as a long-term gain, with outcomes that may not be immediate or guaranteed (Zadravec, 2025).

"I mean, there are a million other you know competing agendas on their plate, trying you know vying for their attention, and there is limited time, so they think it is (IoC) is very time-consuming and space needs to be created."

(Academic Staff 2, Traditional University)

"It is hard to get staff to commit (to IoC)...and because it is a lot of extra work, so why change something that's not broken... we have to do 18 hours of teaching a week, which is heavy because, as you know yourself, you have to correct whatever, so that's a heavy workload. We do get nice holidays, so we have nearly the whole summer off. So that's compensation for the very heavy workload, but the heavy workload is still there, you know it's not like, say, if you have traditional universities in Ireland, you would have 8 hours of teaching a week. So, we do twice, yeah, the amount."

(Academic Staff 3, Technological University)

"Everyone already has too much that they are doing. They are trying to get through the week, let alone think about how we can change the system for the future, right? So, you think about the faculty members; they have already taught this class, and they just want to teach it again. If they have to do a completely new prep or completely redesign the class, that takes a lot of work. Meanwhile, they are trying to get publications done, they are trying to get research grants, and they are trying to get all of this kind of thing. It takes effort, which is an investment for a future payoff, not just getting to the next step. So, I think that's a major challenge there."

(Senior Manager 4, Traditional University)

In addition to considerations of academic identity and the constraints of time and space, some academic staff perceive that international students come to Ireland primarily for its

higher education system. This perspective suggests a standardised teaching and learning experience, which can imply that 'internationalisation is merely a nice-to-have' and optional, reinforcing the notion of 'this is how we do things here' (Cunningham *et al.*, 2024; Jones, 2019; Beelen, 2017).

"Not really, we offer a standardised teaching experience and the expectation is that international students will be taught in the way Irish students are taught so at beginning there was a lot of emphasis placed on that this how we would do in Ireland so that the students will have a clear understanding....we teach all students in the same way as you say that is deliberate, it is not some unconscious Irish or European bias, it is a deliberate policy that we want the students to have the same experience as the Irish students and of course you know students going to the same workforce as Irish students so they have to be prepared for that. So, you know the idea is not to keep them in a box like you know you have different experiences than Irish students; that is not what we want; we want all the students to have the same experience."

(Academic Manager 2, Technological University)

"I would say we are not actively trying to get an international viewpoint, say, from the global south, or so let's say if we have a lecturer from India or wherever, and if they are lecturing, I would imagine that they will have examples from their experience. But I would imagine that if we have an Irish lecturer, I would have guessed that their examples would be based locally. I suppose people tend to go for what they know... and draw from their own experiences...and I do not think we actively try to look for different viewpoints."

(Academic Manager 3, Technological University)

Although the disciplinary contexts among participants may vary, the statements above underscore a shared experience among learners from the TUs, who feel that the curriculum lacks global perspectives. This concern may stem from the perception among academic staff that internationalising the curriculum is optional. Notably, an academic staff member from a traditional university (AS 2) suggests that the standardised teaching narrative is a misconception.

"Sometimes academic staff will come back and say, but you know it is an Irish university so these international students are here to have this Irish education and there is something about you know the idea that well it is an Irish education isn't that surely that is what they are here for without realising that internationalisation, it is actually a kind of inevitable part of education in the sense that you know."

(Academic Staff 2, Traditional University)

Additionally, some academic staff in applied disciplines like Engineering approach their curriculum with caution due to the requirements set by professional bodies, which add a level of rigidity to the curriculum (Bulnes and de Louw, 2022).

"I mentioned earlier that Engineers Ireland is important for us and their credit. So, I sit on the board of accreditation for Engineers Ireland...and I do a lot of accreditation visits in Ireland and nowhere, and I have looked at their curriculum and I have looked at lots of curricula, and in none of the engineering programs that I have seen, there is not a requirement or a focus on internationalisation, it is just not there."

(Academic Staff 3, Technological University)

Notably, most participants expressed similar opinions about academic staff being the primary drivers of IaH within the formal curriculum.

"I mentioned earlier that faculty members are key stakeholders in this, in my view. I think that they have to be convinced of its value of it (IoC). I think that they have to be convinced that it adds to their disciplinary knowledge. In other words, that being able to take on a global view on their discipline is academically and intellectually important. Their students will have an enriched experience and be better equipped, not only in terms of having a richer knowledge of the discipline but also coming out with a whole set of skills related to intercultural competence...and I think at the core of that is the condition of time."

(Academic Staff 2, Traditional University)

As highlighted in various discussions and the literature in [Chapter 2 \(sub-section 2.5.3\)](#), academic staff, who are considered one of the key drivers of IaH, often find themselves 'time-poor' (Beelen, 2023, 2022; Clarke and Hui Yang, 2021). The internationalisation of the curriculum at home often manifests itself as 'extra work' demanding considerable time and resources, which poses a significant risk to the process of internationalisation (IAU Global Survey, 2024; Clarke and Hui Yang, 2021; Ryan *et al.*, 2020; Courtois and O'Keefe, 2015). Furthermore, challenges related to academic identity can add to these complexities, as indicated in participant reflections.

Scholars such as Wimpenny, Beelen, Hindrix, King, and Sjoer (2022) emphasise the imperative to 'decolonise the academic self' when engaging in IoC (p.106). Additionally, for some programs, the mandates of professional bodies can render the curriculum inflexible, making it challenging to incorporate internationalisation explicitly (Goronga, 2025; Gallagher, Lauridsen, and Peschken, 2021). These observations align with the findings reported by Clarke *et al.* (2018) and resonate with the results of the EAIE Barometer (2024) and IAU Global surveys (2024), as elaborated in [Chapter 2](#).

Finally, besides the academic staff, the internationalisation of support services staff seems to be an overlooked aspect in Irish HEIs, mentioned by a few participants.

"There are many staff in the support services that do not have that intercultural sensitivity, lack the ability in the interaction, whether it is in the fees office, the academic registry, or even those computer-generated messages that come up, they are not accessible to students. Students do not understand what they are being told because the language is not precise, it is not clear enough, it is overly idiomatic."
(Academic Manager 1, Traditional University)

"To me, that is a weakness, the communication, I see how communication can really be an obstacle when students, you know, and students are reluctant to ask for clarification or to complain because they kind of beat themselves up about it, thinking it is their English, when in fact, it is a very overly colloquial type of English that is being used, that sort of thing. So, I think we have a lot of work to do, in particular around the support services, you know, making sure, first of all. But I think the challenge is perhaps the support services' understanding of how their institution is changing. To me, that is probably the biggest challenge here."
(Academic Manager 1, Traditional University)

"I think what has happened is universities of just embarked on this internationalisation agenda and they haven't actually really brought all stakeholders along with them...and so like through my meetings with different stakeholders in our university, particularly student support services, they feel like they have been totally left out of the internationalisation journey and just being told, okay, now we are going to have a lot more diversity in our student population. Just deal with it. Basically! So, without any training or guidance or, for example, the Student Health Service, is really grappling with different languages, different understandings of healthcare, different requests for medication, different experiences of health conditions, and health systems in different parts of the world. You know, they are not being told here the different competencies that you might need in terms of communications or interaction with students. They are not being invited out to any of the missions that are travel or any of the experiences, actually, to engage and enhance their own understanding. So, I think a lot of staff support service staff feel left behind in the internationalisation space."
(International Officer 3, Traditional University)

The narratives presented highlight the significance of support services in shaping the internationalisation experiences of learners, an area that remains underexplored in the literature within the Irish context. However, this aspect is highlighted as relevant in the study by O'Reilly *et al.* (2013) and has been examined more thoroughly through the 'Systemic University Change Towards Internationalisation (SUCTI)' Erasmus project for administrative staff (SUCTI, n.d.), which identifies them as vital change agents in transforming the internal mindset of European universities.

Interestingly, research by Clarke *et al.* (2018) indicates that over 90% of international learners in the Irish context expressed satisfaction with the support services. While accounts from international learners in traditional universities reflect higher satisfaction with the international office (the only support services highlighted), the participants from the TUs

reported lower satisfaction levels. Additionally, staff reflections reveal a notable sense of dissatisfaction within the support services, indicating they have been overlooked in the internationalisation journey of the institution.

In summary, while factors such as time and space, academic self-considerations, and professional regulatory body requirements can impede embedding a culture of IaH in Irish HEIs, the substantial teaching load of staff in Irish HEIs, particularly the TUs necessitates attention. It can be essential to create a level playing field for both traditional and the TUs, as internationalisation impacts all institutions, ensuring that learners are not disadvantaged based on their choice of educational institution. Furthermore, the role of support services in an institution's internationalisation efforts remains underexplored, yet it holds significant potential for helping institutions realise their aspirations to cultivate a culture of IaH.

6.3.4.2 Leadership Commitment and Support

The second predominant challenge highlighted in participants' accounts, particularly among staff, was the insufficient leadership surrounding IaH. Although IaH is gradually gaining traction within Irish higher education, as evidenced by its inclusion in the national strategy, *Global Citizens 2030* (DFHERIS, 2024) and in the institutional plans of most publicly funded Irish HEIs (*Chapter 3: sub-section 3.7*), further action is needed to transform strategic rhetoric into practical reality.

Concerns were raised about leadership commitment and support for IaH, particularly regarding the necessary resources such as funding to manage IaH initiatives, and investment in CPD. Additionally, issues surrounding inadequate rewards and recognition and competing priorities related to EDI and sustainability emerged as significant themes in the participants' discussions. These challenges may have negatively impacted both learner and staff engagement with IaH initiatives. The themes of reward and recognition and competing priorities were pertinent in both traditional universities and the TUs. However, concerns about resourcing, particularly concerning CPD and recruiting international staff, seemed particularly pressing for TUs in their attempt to embed IaH.

For example, an academic manager at a TU (AM 3) explains that insufficient funding complicates hiring international staff, which hinders engagement with IaH.

"So, if we advertise a lecturer position here, we will get lots of excellent CVs from those who can drive research and drive the students to be involved in research...and also, to bring in research funding as well. When we advertise this online, I will get really, really good, qualified, well-educated PhD international candidates...and they may not have a visa to work in Ireland, ok? So, they may be abroad, but I cannot interview those candidates because HR here says they do not have a visa. Alternatively, they could be in Ireland, doing post-doctoral research, having a stamp four, or being on a hosting agreement and if they will apply here for a job as a lecturer, I am still not allowed to shortlist them...and to me, that is a huge barrier to internationalisation at home, I would love nothing more than to have lecturers from other countries."
(Academic Manager 3, Technological University)

Additionally, many staff members emphasise the lack of adequate CPD support to develop their expertise in internationalising the curriculum at home.

"I will be very beneficial. But I suppose once again, I am going to condition that with what I think is a good idea. I think we will be open to it, but there will be a resourcing issue.... If the Irish lecturer is to give examples from, say, the Global South, I think they would need support, I think they would need resources, and they would need time actually to go on to research that... Where would that time and resourcing come from? Possibly not sure... because I definitely think IaH is a great idea and very open to it, but in my role as a head of department, I take things very operationally."
(Academic Manager 3, Technological University)

"The word internationalisation at home, I think there is a bit of scaremongering of, 'oh what does that entail?' you know, people kind of think automatically of a field trip abroad or online collaboration or you know if it is those of other ways of doing it as well you know, but I think it requires training, and it requires training for staff, whether they are academic or management as well."
(Academic Staff 3, Technological University)

"Because everybody is so busy, the space has to be created. So obviously, training is really important."
(Academic Manager 1, Traditional University)

Moreover, some staff members emphasise the importance of training support to effectively navigate diversity in the classroom and assess an internationalised curriculum.

"In my class some students mentioned how his mom makes donuts very, very differently because it is a recipe from the granny in the Congo but it is tricky as well because I am aware that their parents might have come here as asylum seekers under really harsh conditions so you don't really know if you open Pandora's box what you are going to get, you know, it is a fine line knowing what to get out of them or not...and would you be able to assess that (IoC)? I don't know, you see...I guess we would need training on that aspect, you know."
(Academic Staff 3, Technological University)

"There is a need to invest time, training and resources into the support services and academic staff...because everyone is delivering. Everything in the institutional context. There are a lot of tensions and frustrations, and staff feel excluded and unprepared, and students feel like the university is not meeting their diverse needs."

(International Officer 3, Traditional University)

Whereas some staff noted that the lack of leadership around IaH makes its implementation challenging.

"Staff don't necessarily have the same understanding of the impact of internationalisation at home and what it could bring in terms of positives, and then if that is not really made obvious by the senior leadership...what is the point of even thinking about it? We have so much to take into account already that it is another, you know, another thing added to the list without proper proof of what it brings, proper proof of impact, proper proof of how to do it or good examples you know like a toolkit or something it makes it much harder even to consider it."

(Academic Staff 3, Technological University)

While other staff indicate that the lack of time and competing priorities, particularly with EDI and sustainability, impact focused efforts towards IaH.

"It is not embedded in the institutional culture, so those activities (IaH) go hidden. They are not as visible because there is no space to make them visible in the way that maybe other initiatives which are topical... so people will name inclusive learning approaches when they are taking more internationalised approaches...because they know that will get them the traction and funding."

(Academic Staff 2, Traditional University)

"Probably the biggest challenge is fitting it in within the curriculum. Because you will have a big resistance to that, you know, because VP for EDI wants to see EDI in the curriculum, the VP for sustainability wants sustainability in the curriculum, I want to see globalisation within the curriculum...and if you add it all up you know, it might not be the best learning experience for the student and that is when you have the faculty say, we have to give our time to teach in the discipline, we cannot have all this thing thrown on top of us."

(Senior Manager 1, Traditional University)

In contrast to other perspectives, a senior manager from a TU (SM 3) suggests that curriculum development is an important aspect of the academic staff's responsibilities. They emphasise that there is sufficient time and opportunities available for academic staff to work towards creating an internationalised curriculum.

"Well, I would say they have plenty of time to do this. Like academics teach 16 hours a week, so let us say conservatively there is another 20 hours prep, you know, for their preparation for classes or marking, etc, but they don't teach 52 weeks of the year. So, academics generally teach at the most about 26 weeks of the year. That is half a year. So, as a head of school, I would say that there is plenty of time for this. I think a university needs to provide resources for people to learn about internationalisation at home, to ensure they understand what it means, to provide training, CPD, and access to good resources that can help people build a knowledge base. I think heads of faculty, heads of school have a job to do in terms of ensuring it's on school or faculty agendas, that we can talk about this, that we can look to see how we embed this across the faculty or the school. But I think faculty do have opportunities. I think there is plenty of time. I think... You know, I don't think we should have to incentivise faculty to do this. This should be part of their job because it is part of their job. Like developing curriculum, developing courses is part of an academic job. Now we're asking people to look at the curriculum in relation to internationalisation in its many guises, not just at home, but at home is one really important aspect of it. Conscientious educators will do that, in my opinion."
(Senior Manager 3, Technological University)

Remarkably, many staff highlighted the need for reward and recognition for IaH, which is somewhat linked to the funding. These perspectives resonate with stakeholder culture theory (Jones *et al.*, 2007), where most academic staff reflect an instrumentalist orientation towards internationalisation. This inclination towards instrumentalism is primarily motivated by the need to secure additional incentives, resources, and recognition to engage with IaH (Clarke and Yang, 2019).

"And maybe also recognition for staff...and that they are recognised...and maybe rewarded for doing a good job (in IaH). I think that is kind of the key thing that is missing. The rewards and recognition systems for academics currently stem from research grants, and innovation and internationalisation in teaching tend to take a back seat. If we are interested in driving internationalisation at home, it must be rewarded and recognised somewhere. People are not going to drop other responsibilities and redirect their attention to internationalisation at home...unless it is recognised as important."
(Academic Staff 2, Traditional University)

"I guess we would also need some recognition from the leadership for the work undertaken. You can go to the CPD, but you don't have to. So, it goes back to why bother if you know you don't get anything out of it."
(Academic Staff 3, Technological University)

"Funding issue is a big issue and it has been there for a while. I think recognition for staff is a bigger concern."
(International Officer 1, Traditional University)

"There are these day-to-day frustrations with resources or with you know when it comes up that the recognition for what is being done is not always there."
(Senior Manager 4, Traditional University)

In essence, the academic and support services staff have noted a lack of preparedness in implementing IaH initiatives, which can be attributed to insufficient CPD opportunities that equip them with the necessary skills for both classroom and external engagement (Weissova, Gregersen-Hermans, and Pantelic, 2024). Additionally, EDI alongside sustainability appear to be perceived as competing for resources and attention, rather than being viewed as interdependent. This viewpoint may relate to the theoretical framework of this study (*Chapter 4: sub-section 4.2.1*), which examines stakeholder salience and resource claims based on 'power, urgency, and legitimacy' as senior leadership makes decisions regarding institutional priorities and resource allocation (MAW, 1997). Additionally, the job demands and resources model illustrates the relationship between staff job demands and the resources available to meet those demands (Bakker and Demerouti, 2007). Jones and de Wit (2025) emphasise the 'pressing need' to align these priorities.

Notably, the absence of rewards and recognition for staff investment in IaH is a significant barrier to their full engagement with the initiative (Pleschová, 2024; Clarke and Hui Yang, 2021; Ryan, 2020; Clarke *et al.*, 2018). These themes highlight the importance of institutional leadership in signalling the significance of IaH, which may require moving beyond mere strategic rhetoric to genuinely embed it into the culture of the institution (Van den Hende and Riezebos, 2023; Kelly, 2023), as reflected in participant experiences. While academic staff play a crucial role in driving IaH, the importance of leadership cannot be underestimated. This aligns with findings from the EAIE Barometer Ireland Spin-Off survey (2024), which indicates that 89% of participants from Irish HEIs view senior leadership as the most influential stakeholder in advancing institutional internationalisation goals, surpassing the EHEA average of 74% (p. 27).

6.3.4.3 Awareness and Visibility

The third prime challenge in embedding a culture for IaH, as reported by participants, revolves around the awareness and visibility of IaH initiatives. Most learners from the TUs expressed considerable dissatisfaction with this aspect, citing a lack of communication about informal curriculum events and societies, compared to the participants in the traditional universities.

"I was just thinking about that, like, if the institution I am in does much to create experiences that promote internationalisation.. I would say there is a severe lack of communication about these events if they are happening, which I don't think they really are."
(Irish Learner 1, Technological University)

"Yeah, so I am surprised actually, I don't get any such information from my university, like about international events or intercultural experiences. I don't know why that is. So maybe I am not subscribed to the relevant societies. I don't know why, but I should get some information that something is happening. If it is happening, perhaps it is not happening then."
(International Learner 8, Technological University)

"Very rarely I would see some nice events on social media. But they are posted after they took place and I was never invited to any of them...and I am Irish, but I actually have two nationalities, and I might fit into some other groups that people might be aware of but I was never invited to anything."
(Irish Learner 10, Technological University)

Another related challenge identified by learners from traditional universities pertains to the need for a more apparent distinction between mobility and IaH. This misconception is also prevalent among staff from both types of HEIs, as discussed in *sub-section 6.3.1* and supported by existing literature.

"I am just thinking if the difference between internationalisation at home versus mobility could be made.... maybe one of the big things would be to create a distinction between that... among the student body. I am not talking about categorising people into us and them, but maybe if there was an awareness that all international students are not Erasmus students, and if every international experience is not for international students... that there is a difference that could be drawn... that could be helpful."
(Irish Learner 9, Traditional University)

The lack of awareness surrounding the term IaH, compared to more recognised terms like mobility through Erasmus or partnerships, may contribute to its diminished visibility, as an academic staff member from a traditional university (AS 2) pointed out.

"I think that it is (IaH) still relatively new. That language, unlike Erasmus mobility, hasn't quite become part of our everyday way of talking about our internationalisation practices."
(Academic Staff 2, Traditional University)

Moreover, many students have highlighted difficulties organising and participating in events due to a lack of social spaces, funding, and inconvenient venues. These challenges can considerably impact awareness and visibility for IaH, which is consistent with the findings from *sub-section 6.3.4.1*.

"I think in general; the problem is often with accessibility for one reason or another, which we discussed before. Either you are busy, there is no funding or place to organise events, or you simply don't know about it. Sometimes, especially for students who are not living on campus, I feel like locations can be tricky and discourage them from participating. Oh, I have to go find this room and this thing."
(International Learner 3, Traditional University)

For the staff, the themes of awareness and visibility relate to the previous *sub-section 6.3.4.2*, where insufficient awareness was tied to inadequate continuing professional development (CPD), alongside constraints in time, space, and opportunities for reward and recognition. Notably, an academic manager from a traditional university (AM 1) remarked that long-serving employees may become "fossilised" in their practices, hindering the implementation of IaH.

"You may have people there who have been in the university for more than 30 years, who came in when it was a very different university, when it didn't have that cultural diversity. You know, they are very much fossilised, if you like, in their own practices. And they may not understand the needs of international students or how they may work with domestic students...so it is a task to make them aware of internationalisation at home and figure out how to make it visible."
(Academic Manager 1, Traditional University)

Furthermore, there is a general lack of awareness regarding the opportunities IaH can provide.

"I think the general awareness (about IaH) is the main issue... to have training and a proper framework that we can follow that is easily understood... you know... if you print 50-20 pages handbook, they (staff) are not going to read it."
(Academic Manager 2, Technological University)

Additionally, preliminary findings from some working groups suggest that awareness may pose significant challenges to effectively implement IaH.

"I mean, one of the findings that we found thus far, preliminary finding if you will..through the working group on internationalisation at home is the awareness gap...staff across campus don't recognise these opportunities that exist and how it could be beneficial for them."
(Senior Manager 4, Traditional University)

These findings highlight the conceptual unfamiliarity prevalent in the literature, as discussed in *Chapter 2 (sub-section 2.6.1)* (Beelen, 2023, 2016; Kirk *et al.*, 2019; Stohl, 2007; Knight, 2006). This may further underscore that IaH is an 'underdeveloped concept with great potential' (Coelen, 2024; Manning and Marku, 2021; Robson *et al.*, 2018). Interestingly, the term 'internationalisation of the curriculum' (IoC) is relatively familiar to academic staff, particularly in light of the Clarke *et al.* (2018) report and the earlier international education strategy (DoES, 2016) and some existing scholarly work (Ryan *et al.*, 2022; Clarke and Hui Yang, 2021; Ryan, 2020). In contrast, the term 'internationalisation at home (IaH)' is relatively new, featuring more prominently within the government's recent talent and innovation

strategy (DFHERIS, 2024) and is starting to gain traction through the strategic initiatives of various publicly funded Irish HEIs, as detailed in *Chapter 3 (sub-section 3.7)*. However, the conceptual ambiguity and lack of support for IaH within current processes and systems, as discussed in *sub-section 6.3.4.1*, pose significant challenges for enhancing awareness and visibility of IaH in Irish HEIs.

6.3.4.4 Fragmented Implementation

The fourth challenge in embedding a culture is the fragmented execution of IaH initiatives, which a best practice HEI in Europe describes as '*some good loose activities*' (BP HEI, 1). The tendency for internationalisation to be integrated in a siloed manner within curricula and systems may inhibit a systemic approach, as reflected in the participants' accounts. Additionally, the challenges previously identified, pertaining to learner and staff engagement (*sub-section 6.3.4.1*), leadership commitment and support (*sub-section 6.3.4.2*), as well as awareness and visibility of IaH (*sub-section 6.3.4.3*), collectively contribute to this fragmented landscape within Irish HEIs.

As institutions continue to evolve, it is important to recognise that the risk of heightened fragmentation may grow without the implementation of a comprehensive strategy for IaH. This growing fragmentation is reflected in the insights of participants from traditional universities. While these institutions have made notable strides in their internationalisation efforts compared to TUs, they still face significant challenges stemming from fragmentation (Kaldewey, Rymarzak, Stoppa, Schmitt, and Riedmiller, 2024; Kyvik, 2009; Knight, 2008).

For instance, from a curriculum perspective, some learners have noted the limited influence of internationalisation within a largely traditional curriculum and the variability in informal curriculum initiatives that shape their global awareness (Gibbons, 1994). This observation resonates with Mestenhauser's (2011) viewpoint that academic staff may sometimes demonstrate ethnocentrism in their disciplines, which can result in fragmented approaches where the internationalisation of the curriculum is perceived as an optional enhancement, often relegated to specific projects or courses (p.19). Additionally, this scenario raises important considerations regarding inclusion, as it may not fully engage all students.

"If we kind of neglect education in the global South and only focus on global north..as is the case with many of our modules... and I think it can be very kind of working like we are in silos and I think as a whole we need to know what is going on in the wider world."
(Irish Learner 7, Traditional University)

"I am fully Irish. I am just an Irish student at an Irish university, and I found that in my situation, I study languages...within the languages department of the university, there are a lot of events organised through international festivals, like say last week we had the Chinese New Year, things like that. It is great to have that, but I found that it is marketed towards just the language department. Only we receive the email; only we get notified about things. I have friends in science courses and education courses who were never told about the events. So, while things like that do happen at the university, it feels very secluded to one area, one faculty, and I think that kind of defeats the purpose of internationalisation and inclusion because it's not just international students in the languages department, there are lots of science students, medical students. etc, they are everywhere. It's not one department. So, I think while it is good, there is still a lot of work to be done."
(Irish Learner 11, Traditional University)

Whereas most staff express dissatisfaction regarding the lack of a cohesive approach among various disciplines, departments, and functions related to IaH. This disconnection may hinder efforts to enhance the visibility and integration of IaH, echoing the challenges outlined earlier in this sub-section. This sentiment aligns with Mestenhauser's perspective that 'we are divided by various administrative and instructional units, reporting to different structures, and fluctuating in emphasis from process to product learning' (Mestenhauser, 2011, p. 2).

"I feel it (IaH) is probably isolated, like we are not all talking to each other, perhaps as much as we might. Maybe others feel that way as well. I certainly do. I am a bit like on an island on my own doing this stuff... there is nowhere to showcase that in any kind of centralised space." (Academic Staff 2, Traditional University)

"At the moment, people are coming up with good ideas and implementing them on an ad hoc basis. Then it becomes kind of just nice things to do. As opposed to, you know, really strategic things..it is just lots of lovely activities."
(International Officer 3, Traditional University)

"There is quite a bit of disconnect, and you know the thing is as well. At the start of the year, I did not have access, for instance, to a database that tells me who has come over from which French-speaking area and is doing what. Though I have informed the international office that I can engage French students in language classes and events. So, it's only by fluke I find them out, you know, in the campus corridors. And you know, these could be tapped into very easily, you know, there is a lot of good stuff that could be done that is not being done really...because of these siloes."
(Academic Staff 3, Technological University)

"There is an awful lot of good practice on internationalisation at home on the ground in the universities. It is just they are terribly isolated."
(Policy Influencer)

Interestingly, the fragmentation observed in IaH is not unique to the Irish HE context; it is also found in other best practice HEIs that have made significant progress in the area.

"We have been looking to see where do we position internationalisation as it is entirely. But it is difficult because, as I said, it is still pretty fragmented...lots of great, but loose activities. There are new structures but people still finding their way in how do we do this."
(Best Practice HEI, Europe)

"I think the framework and good practices are still very isolated, and I think the institution definitely needs to engage in an exercise to bring everything together."
(Best Practice HEI, UK)

The findings presented above suggest that embedding a culture of IaH may benefit from a more comprehensive and systemic approach, as opposed to a fragmented one (Beelen, 2023, 2022). This fragmentation may stem from an emphasis on a centralised international/global engagement office entrusted with guiding international initiatives. This observation is consistent with findings from the EAIE Barometer Ireland Spin-Off survey (2024), where 47% of participants from Irish HEIs indicated that the central international office oversees all international/global engagement matters (p.21). This contrasts with only 24% in the European Higher Education Area (EHEA) and highlights the complexities associated with fragmentation, particularly when internationalisation is primarily viewed as the responsibility of a single department rather than a collaborative effort among all stakeholders within the institution.

Moreover, it is noteworthy that 93% of participants indicated they feel pressure from senior leadership to demonstrate impact, suggesting that the responsibility for this significant expectation largely rests with the international/global engagement office (EAIE Barometer, 2024, p.33). These insights align with broader literature (Sierra-Huedo *et al.*, 2022; De Wit and Deca, 2020; De Wit *et al.*, 2015; and Mestenhauser, 2007). D'Angelo, O'Brien, and Marty (2022), in parallel with Mestenhauser's perspective, point out that 'we continue to focus on the transactional parts of international education in their rhetoric and agendas, which further fragments the field and disregards the impact of interrelationships on the entire system' (p.213). This reflection appears particularly relevant within the context of Irish higher education.

6.3.4.5 National Policymaking

Finally, the disconnect between national strategic rhetoric and the reality presents a significant challenge in embedding IaH in Irish HEIs. Some participants noted that although intercultural competence and global citizenship, which can be cultivated through IaH, are emphasised as key priorities in the national strategy for international education- Global Citizens 2030 (DFHERIS, 2024), there exists no accompanying policy to support its implementation or to assess its impact. This absence may lead HEIs to perceive the initiative as less urgent. A strategy can be defined as a high-level, overarching plan shaped by broader contextual and external factors, while a policy serves as a framework that outlines how specific issues can be addressed to achieve the ambitions set forth in the strategy (Mishra and Mohanty, 2022). The distinction between these two concepts often becomes unclear, as indicated by some participants' reflections, leading to their frequent interchangeability in understanding.

"So, the targets can be set in some areas that can be easily monitored, but whether that is being done or not, I am not too sure. But who knows what happens if the targets aren't reached? There is no, you know, there is no set of measures attached to it... because it is only a strategy... it is not a policy."
(Academic Staff 3, Technological University)

"And at a policymaking level, it appears in some of the strategic documents, even if it (IaH) has been mentioned, it has really been something that the institutions try to do, with greater or less success, in my opinion. But it is not really something that is monitored or supported at a strategic level across the country."
(Policy Influencer)

Furthermore, concerns have been expressed regarding the internationalisation of higher education being primarily driven by economic motives, in contrast to the multifaceted approaches observed in other European countries (Burke, 2021; O'Neill, 2019).

"In Ireland, as you know, the thing is rather obscenely driven by finance. Whereas in other European countries, the financial factor is quite limited. So, it is more driven by looking for good diversity or strategic opportunities with partner countries abroad as opposed to ...where can we get the money?"
(Policy Influencer)

Despite the economic rationale for pursuing internationalisation, inadequate funding remains a significant challenge for numerous HEIs seeking to enhance IaH. For instance,

employment control frameworks that limit HEIs from hiring a sufficient number of full-time staff lead to lower staff-student ratios in Irish universities compared to their counterparts in other OECD countries (OECD, 2021). These constraints directly impact the quality of the internationalised experiences that both staff and institutions can offer, a concern that resonates with reflections from academic staff in the study and aligns with findings from Clarke *et al.* (2018), Houghton (2020), and Dowling-Hetherington (2014).

"The lack of money is a very significant issue in Irish higher education. Government funding for students is still below what it was in 2008. The staff student ratios, that is, the amount of time that any academic or other staff member has per student, are lower than in 2008 and one of the worst in the OECD. These sorts of things...and all that is down to funding and other government controls...and these sorts of things actually, you know, make it difficult to implement the little bits and pieces that are necessary to encourage more internationalisation at home, more engagement between students more of that informal curriculum more of that hidden curriculum and certainly, more of the explicit curriculum...and because at every step of the way people are asking should we be spending money on this? Can we afford to do it? If we didn't do it, we would save money. So, the, while none of the IaH initiatives per se cost a lot of money but when you add it all up and if you want to do it effectively across the whole institution as opposed to just with one class it does actually, you know more resource would be of considerable benefit."

(Policy Influencer)

"Many of the academic staff have very heavy workloads because of the very large student staff ratios... It's about one full-time equivalent to 23 students...and before it was one to 18. But in comparative European countries, where we would like to see ourselves, and which are many of the European University Alliance partners, it is somewhere between one to 12, one to 15. In Northern Ireland, it is one to 16. Like that, an academic staff member in the Republic of Ireland has 50% more students to manage than in Northern Ireland. I mean...and it's not sustainable. This means that all sorts of things, such as the quality of the student experience, student engagement, etc., are compromised. So, that maybe doesn't leave an awful lot of time to try and do things differently or to think about how to do things differently. Yeah...and they are driven by their performance metrics, for most academic staff aren't really about nice soft measures like graduate competences, they are driven by other harder, harder measures like publication citations and other things."

(Policy Influencer)

"I think the biggest challenge I mentioned was funding already, and then the second one is staffing, and they are related, obviously. The university sector, unlike most other sectors of the public service, still has an employment control framework in place. This employment control framework was imposed as a part of the financial crash in 2008 or 2009, which severely restricts the number of full-time permanent staff the universities can employ....and that is why the staff student ratio is so poor...and it will get worse unless some significant steps are taken."

(Policy Influencer)

Policymakers recognise that funding can present certain challenges. Nevertheless, they are dedicated to adopting a thoughtful approach to the broader educational landscape in Ireland. They emphasise their continued support through various policies, particularly highlighting internationalisation as a key area of investment. Furthermore, they underscore the

importance of senior management teams within HEIs in shaping priorities, as institutional autonomy empowers these teams to make informed decisions regarding the allocation of funds for internationalisation initiatives (Courtois, 2017).

"So, it is you know, like if you are expecting, I suppose, when you talk to HEI, how strong is the message going to be (for IaH)? It's kind of a subtext, like, will there be money here? You know, going along with that, we see this (internationalisation) is not just about money ... Why we should be engaging in international education, but also what we should be looking to maximise...and how we should be facilitating that engagement. There is a whole-of-government approach to this."

(Policymakers)

"If it relies on the department to assign those priorities to an institution. What does academic independence mean? What does autonomy mean? So, there is a balance to be struck here. When the Irish economy collapsed, it was internationalisation that helped to address deficits within the institutions. Now, over the past two budgets, the minister has secured additional funding to pass it to institutions. So, therefore, we can quite frankly ask, well, all of this money that you are getting from international education, what are you using it for? How are you prioritising internationalisation within your campus? How is the institution itself leveraging that money to improve the quality of its commitment to internationalisation? Is this just getting the money, or is this genuinely about transforming the international setting within their institution? That is a decision that rests with the president and senior management structures of that institution. It doesn't rest with the department."

(Policymaker)

The policymakers express confidence that the funding available for internationalisation is sufficient to support the development of IaH within HEIs. However, many participants indicated that their institutional strategy is informed by the national strategy on international education, which can impact the successful embedding of IaH, particularly when the strategy may not be supported by relevant policies.

On the other hand, a senior manager from a technological university (SM 2) expressed scepticism about the potential impact of the national strategy on the university's internationalisation trajectory, suggesting that a deeper commitment might be necessary to embed internationalisation effectively.

"I have worked in higher education for almost three decades, and I am not sure national strategies are hugely influential. I think how you address them, how you understand them, and then how you decide to work with them or not would be very much a local decision for universities. I still think we're very naive when it comes to the area of internationalisation and using policy. That report (Global Citizens 2030) is incredibly vague to me. I don't see and don't hear any commitment. I see that words and lots of loose language around internationalisation are important. So, for me, the jury is out on those. I have no evidence yet of how it has really informed any organisation's direction around this topic."

(Senior Manager 3, Technological University)

Additionally, some participants express that IaH may not directly apply to their institutional reviews under the HEA Compact. This perception could introduce additional complexities in embedding IaH within their institutions. This sentiment aligns with the findings of Clarke *et al.* (2018), which indicate that 61% of Irish HEIs connect their strategic plans to the framework outlined by the HEA Compact (p.24).

"So, funding in higher education is tied to an HEA compact statement. So, the compact statement is a performance review framework. International is interwoven into some elements; however, it has been removed as one of the key pillars. So that tells me everything I need to know about how important it is to our government."

(Senior Manager 3, Technological University)

The aforementioned arguments suggest that the absence of explicit references to IaH within the HEA Compact, along with the lack of specific policy measures to support the national strategy to guide HEIs in achieving and monitoring their impact in IaH, and the challenges related to funding, could present significant barriers for HEIs in aligning their strategic objectives related to IaH with actual outcomes. While policymakers appear confident in the support and funding currently provided to HEIs, there is an opportunity for additional resources to facilitate a more effective flow of support for IaH through the higher educational system in Ireland.

6.3.5 Summary

This section presented the findings and discussions related to the primary aim of this study, which was to critique how IaH is interpreted in the Irish context and draw on findings related to the challenges and opportunities in embedding a culture of IaH in Irish HEIs, as presented by participants in this study. This purpose connects with the first research question – *'What are the opportunities and challenges for developing a culture of 'IaH' in an Irish higher education context?'*. To address this, themes such as conceptual constructions, rationale, enablers and challenges were identified through the participant accounts comprising the traditional and technological universities (TUs), supplemented with perspectives from the policymakers/influencers and in some cases best practice HEIs from Europe and the UK.

The participants' accounts indicate that the term 'Internationalisation at Home (IaH)' is largely unfamiliar to most learners and some staff. Participants tend to describe IaH through the perspectives of cross-cultural engagement, international learner diversity, mobility, and curriculum, while also expressing assumptions and opinions about the term. The conceptual

ambiguity is evident in the accounts. Importantly, participants conveyed that the rationale for their involvement in IaH is motivated by the aspiration to cultivate intercultural competence and global citizenship skills. Additionally, they emphasised the significance of equality, diversity, and inclusion (EDI), learner diversity, effective teaching and learning practices, enhancing learner employability, and promoting sustainability.

While the concept of IaH is still in its early stages in the Irish HE context, its current implementation has been mainly through an informal curriculum, primarily within the international office, rather than being fully integrated into the formal curriculum. Notably, IaH has found a more prominent place in inherently international disciplines, such as International Business, while it appears less prevalent in applied fields such as Engineering. At present, IaH is somewhat enabled by an internationalised curriculum, stakeholder engagement, primarily involving enthusiastic learners and staff, collaborations, partnerships, alliances, and networks. The institutional strategic planning for most HEIs also recognises IaH as one of its key priorities, along with mobility opportunities embedded in curricula for certain programs.

The findings suggest that traditional universities may have a more progressive approach to IaH compared to the TUs, even if they do not explicitly label their efforts as such. This progress is reflected in their long-standing practice of welcoming international students, which fosters greater diversity within their student and staff populations. Additionally, students engaged with the informal curriculum at traditional universities report higher satisfaction levels compared to those at TUs, as highlighted by participant reflections.

While these strengths provide a solid foundation for advancing the goals of IaH, the challenges facing the Irish HE system may hinder its further development. For example, issues related to learner and staff engagement beyond a few champions, insufficient leadership commitment and support, limited awareness and visibility of IaH initiatives, fragmented implementation across a few programs or through international/global engagement offices, and the absence of a national policy to support the strategy are significant factors that could hinder the effective establishment of a culture of IaH in Irish HEIs.

Although the foundations for IaH can be observed in most institutions, substantial efforts may be necessary to transition from implementation to fully embedding a culture of IaH. The subsequent sub-section addresses the final research question and seeks to offer strategies for navigating the barriers identified by participants in the pursuit of embedding such a

culture. Additionally, the researcher proposes a working definition of what it means to foster this culture, alongside a guiding 'Content, Positioning, and Reflection' (CPR) framework intended to support Irish HEIs in their ongoing journey.

6.4 Findings and Discussion in Response to Research Question Two

The previous sub-section detailed the conceptual construction, rationale, enablers and challenges associated with embedding a culture of IaH, thereby addressing the first research question. This sub-section responds to the final research question on '*What strategies can be developed to embed a culture of IaH in Irish HEIs?*'. It highlights the participants' suggestions on navigating the challenges outlined previously. Moreover, in order to address the final research aim, which is '*developing a framework that helps HEIs foster the embedding of a culture of IaH in the Irish higher education context*', a working definition for embedding this culture, along with the evidence-based IaH content, positioning, and reflection (CPR) framework, is presented.

6.4.1 Overcoming Challenges in IaH

The previous sub-section delineated specific challenges related to learner and staff engagement while emphasising the importance of enhanced leadership commitment and support. Furthermore, it highlighted the need for increased awareness and visibility regarding IaH initiatives, alongside the necessity for a holistic institutional approach to IaH. Additionally, the absence of a supportive policy to back the national strategy, which acknowledges the significance of IaH, presents further considerations. This sub-section draws on participants' insights on effectively addressing these challenges at the institutional level, which can be possible through considerate change management, proactive stakeholder engagement, and thoughtful curriculum design.

The themes outlined have emerged from participants' narratives and are shaped by key theoretical constructs for this study. As discussed in [Chapter 4](#), these frameworks include organisational design theories, such as stakeholder identification and salience (Mitchell, Agle, and Wood, 1997), stakeholder culture (Jones, Felps, and Bigley, 2007), and the job demands and resources model (Bakker and Demerouti, 2007).

Additionally, curriculum design theory, as articulated in Leask's (2015) conceptual framework for an internationalised curriculum, as well as change management theories, specifically the organisational culture transformational framework (Armenakis, Brown, and Mehta, 2011) and the learning organisation through a systems thinking approach (Senge, 1990) also inform this analysis. At the national level, participants emphasise the importance of supportive

policies backing the international talent and innovation strategy (Global Citizens 2030), including funding and accountability systems, to promote a culture of IaH within HEIs. Collectively, this sub-section addresses the final research question and the aim of the study.

6.4.1.1 Institutional Level

As noted in the preceding sub-sections, IaH has the potential to act as an internal reform within an institution, as suggested by the participants' accounts. In this context, this sub-section outlines the strategic approaches highlighted by participants to address the challenges of embedding a culture of IaH at the institutional level. These approaches may involve change management, stakeholder engagement, and curriculum design.

6.4.1.1.1 Change Management

The themes in change management, illustrated in *Figure 24*, were articulated through a systemic approach to IaH, integrating the internationalisation efforts of various disciplines,

departments, functions and levels. Moreover, participants' accounts reveal that while IaH is envisaged to be a shared responsibility, there is a need for a dedicated department and resources to further advance these initiatives across the institution. The other key aspects include identifying metrics or progress markers to measure success and impact and enhancing the awareness and visibility of IaH by continuously educating the university community. These dimensions hold comparable significance for both traditional universities and the TUs. However, participants from traditional universities indicated a heightened need for a systemic approach, likely reflecting their more advanced stage of internationalisation, as previously noted.

When describing a systemic approach, many staff members emphasised the significance of a collaboration that integrates both top-down and bottom-up strategies, which is also supported by existing scholars (Jooste, 2022; Robson *et al.*, 2018; Mestenhauser, 2011, 2007; Teekens, 2007). A key area of agreement among staff was the critical role that university leadership plays in influencing the extent to which IaH permeates various institutional systems, a point also highlighted by the policymaker and policy influencer in this study. This perspective is corroborated by findings from the EAIE Barometer Ireland Spin-Off survey (2024), which indicated that 89% of respondents from Irish HEIs perceive the executive board or senior leadership as the most significant stakeholders in advancing internationalisation objectives within Irish HEIs (p.27).

"It will need to come from the registrar's office because they are responsible for academic oversight. So, if all the departments are going to have something academically embedded into their programs, they need to be given a common direction from above, and it needs to be very clear. So, I think you do not want to have a dispersed approach. So, you want to have a very clear set of guidelines. This is what you have to, well, not have to do, but this is what you should do...and this is how you do it, and this is how success can be achieved, okay? That is the direction."
(Academic Manager 3, Technological University)

"I think it needs to be articulated as a university priority, and that comes from leadership, obviously. Then I think beyond that, the successes that happen need to be celebrated, right? So, persistent internal communication saying you know, X has held this award for Teaching across the curriculum, or there is an example of what teaching across the curriculum looks like, recognising that not everyone is going to jump on board. But if you can reward good actors and shine the spotlight on them, then, you know, this concept of positive deviance from psychology is really useful. People say, Oh, I want to be like that. I will follow their lead. I think that can be really powerful. So that's the strategy I would suggest: buy-in and explicit articulation from leadership and persistent communication where you celebrate those that are contributing and the wins that came from that."
(Senior Manager 4, Traditional University)

An academic manager from a traditional university (AM 1) shared their best practices for embedding IaH at the faculty and school levels.

"I meet with all the schools and departments regularly, and we discuss internationalisation and internationalisation at home. So yeah, there is a structure from the lowest level, the school or the department, going upwards, and at the school and department level, all academics are expected to attend their school meetings. So, it is a standing item. Internationalisation at home is a standing item at the school and department level meetings and the faculty board. It is part of our mission statement. It is on the faculty, it is a mission statement, it is in the mission statement of all the faculties...and there are lots of initiatives where people work in that kind of multidisciplinary way. Internationalisation at home has to involve everybody. That is the whole point of it, you know, it has to be across the university."
(Academic Manager 1, Traditional University)

Furthermore, while it is recognised that the IaH should be a collective responsibility of all stakeholders within the university, the dedicated department for IaH can play a crucial role in educating the university community about its purpose, benefits, while also addressing the pertinent question of 'What's in it for me?' to garner staff support. As highlighted from the participant accounts, staff serve as 'cultural carriers,' and fostering a 'readiness for change,' as described in the organisational culture transformational framework (Armenakis *et al.*, 2011), can be essential to this process (*Chapter 4: sub-section 4.2.3.1*).

"If there is an awareness between the difference you know at a student level between the difference of mobility and internationalisation at home, people might make more of an effort because they realise it has a longer impact and they realise it does."
(Irish Learner 9, Traditional University)

"As I said before, I think the size of the institution, and it is making sure that everybody is aware of what is happening, and what the opportunities are, and what the benefits...how they can be achieved...what can success look like... isn't it?"
(Academic Manager 1, Traditional University)

"I think you definitely need buy-in from everybody. You need to showcase you know the benefits, and it has to come from the top down."
(International Officer 2, Technological University)

"Then to make it (IaH) happen, you need resources...as everybody here is very busy. So, you actually need an office to focus on that...and the office then will have to align that across, and not just the campus, it should be across the whole university equitably and everyone should be treated the same and it should all be aligned across all the faculties across all the campuses...and then clear metrics must be established to determine success."

(Academic Manager 3, Technological University)

"I think you definitely need buy-in from everybody. You need to showcase you know the benefits, and it has to come from the top down."

(International Officer 2, Technological University)

Additionally, the staff from the best practice HEI in Europe highlighted their institutional structure for IaH.

"I would say that the overall responsibility lies with the team strategy. So, there is a manager and her team, and she should actually oversee everything that is happening. So, she liaises with the research group, liaises with the Centre for Teaching and Learning, and now tries also to get a grasp of what the teaching and learning labs are doing."

(Best Practice HEI, Europe)

Notably, many participants emphasised the need for institutions to establish clear indicators of progress and success. This can help elevate the concept of IaH beyond mere abstraction and demonstrate its feasibility without being perceived as 'extra effort' or an 'add-on,' as highlighted by participants' accounts and existing literature (*Chapter 2: sub-section 2.6.3*).

The success measures reflect the strategic, teaching and learning, curriculum, support services, research, and employability dimensions from participant perspectives, as shown in *Table 12*. The quantitative components include metrics such as the number and percentage of diverse learners, particularly Irish learners, which also includes those of international ancestry or from migrant backgrounds, as well as international learners, and the involvement of both academic and support services staff. However, the qualitative assessment of these initiatives is equally important, as it can provide insights into the engagement and impact of each initiative. Ultimately, several participants recognised key measures of success as the learners' ability to articulate and exhibit intercultural competence and global citizenship.

"The core goal of whether or not every student graduates with an intercultural competency would be my measurement of success and so I would say the breadth of that... how many students can we identify and graduate with that competency would be one metric and then the other metric would be..what is the nature of that kind like... how deep that competency is and that would be something we would probably need to set up in advance. I would want to recognise mobility experiences as one aspect of it, but I certainly wouldn't want to limit it because there is Internationalisation at home. I think it will also be really useful for students as they graduate to be able to articulate what that competency is and why it is beneficial to them both as they are going onto the job market...but also just as a citizen like... so that might be another metric. It is the ability for students to articulate it and why they feel it is useful to them... so if someone comes out of an architecture program, they have certain skills to which they can point. They can say, okay, well, I can run Autocad, I can design a building, I am familiar with the requirements for design, and I am familiar with these elements of the building, things like that. I think they should also be able to articulate- I am comfortable operating within an intercultural environment, I am aware of what aspects of my communication reflect on my own culture and how I should engage with people from other cultures...I think the core competency is being able to articulate what it is that you have now learned."

(Senior Manager 4, Traditional University)

"I think we can measure success by the extent to which, in our graduating students, we have kind of inculcated a global mindset...a sense of global citizenship...and we do try to do that... that is one of our graduate attributes...and so, it is one of the learning outcomes. We seek to assess. So, they know what success looks like. Graduating students that have clearly demonstrated intercultural competence and cultural sensitivity, global awareness through internationalisation...we have assessed that and we have kind of in a sense assured that they have got that kind of mindset and then I guess the you know, further downstream it's you know... what kind of employment success these students are having in terms of gaining jobs."

(Senior Manager 1, Traditional University)

Table 12: Measuring Success through IaH

<i>Criterion</i>	<i>Various means, practices and methods through which achieved</i>
Strategic	IaH in the institutional, international, faculty and school level planning.
	Staff participation in university working groups/committees for IaH.
	External mentors in university committees for IaH.
	Formal leadership positions (Assistant Deans/Assistant Head of Departments) for internationalisation in each faculty.
	Dedicated department and resources for IaH.
	Capacity building projects on IaH at the institutional, national, European or international level.
	Culture and language area study centres on campus.
	Learner and staff satisfaction surveys on internationalisation.
	Representation of learners in various committees in the university.
	Rewards and recognition for best practices in IaH.
	IaH linked with professional progression.
	Learners with intercultural competence and global citizenship graduate attributes.
	Reduction in carbon footprint through IaH initiatives.
Teaching and Learning	CPD training modules for all staff and learners on an internationalised curriculum, intercultural communication, unconscious bias, to mention a few.
	Strategic partnerships, alliances, networks and programmes linked with teaching and learning, including staff mobility abroad.
	Learner participation in common orientations and training.
	Curricula co-designed with learners.
	Staff communities of practice (CoPs) on IaH.
	International PhD researchers employed for academic staff roles post PhD.
	Multicultural staff networks/communities on campus.
Curriculum	Core modules that have explicit internationalised learning outcomes.
	Core modules that have an international or intercultural dimension.
	Elective modules on intercultural communication and/or global citizenship.
	Core and/or elective modules that embed virtual internationalisation and blended intensive programmes (BIPs).
	Learner participation in virtual internationalisation initiatives such as COIL, VE and BIPs.

Table 12: Measuring Success through IaH

<i>Criterion</i>	<i>Various means, practices and methods through which achieved</i>
Curriculum	<p>External curriculum reviewers, such as employers, national or international partners.</p> <p>Modules updated to include international and intercultural dimensions through programmatic reviews.</p> <p>International resources in libraries.</p> <p>Learner participation in Irish Gaelic and foreign language courses/programmes.</p> <p>International guest speakers.</p> <p>Learner mobility/placement abroad embedded in the formal curriculum, and post-return sharing of reflections.</p> <p>Learners' participation in mobility abroad after IaH experiences in the initial years.</p> <p>Learner participation in community engagement projects.</p> <p>Learner participation in informal curriculum activities/events, international learner clubs and societies, including global lounges, ambassador/buddy schemes, international volunteering programmes, to mention a few.</p> <p>Disadvantaged/marginalised learner participation in informal curriculum.</p>
Support Services	<p>Multicultural cuisines offered in campus café/canteens.</p> <p>International learner uptake of counselling services.</p> <p>International learners and staff participation in English language and academic support.</p> <p>Counselling in foreign languages.</p>
Research	<p>Publications on IaH.</p> <p>Academic development fellowships for staff to develop an internationalised curriculum and resources.</p> <p>Funding and projects for IaH initiatives.</p> <p>Research groups and PhD students on internationalisation.</p>
Employability	<p>International learners interning/employed in various departments of the university.</p> <p>Employers seeking intercultural competence and global citizenship skills in graduates.</p> <p>Employer feedback on the intercultural competence and global citizenship skills of the graduates employed.</p> <p>Graduate and alumni surveys to evaluate the impact of intercultural competence and global citizenship skills in securing jobs locally, nationally, and internationally.</p>

Participants indicated that a clear understanding of what IaH entails, its associated benefits, and robust institutional structures endorsed by leadership are vital. Furthermore, establishing a dedicated department to oversee IaH initiatives and defining clear indicators of progress or success can cultivate 'readiness for change' (explained in *Chapter 4: sub-section 4.2.3.1*) among staff and learners (Armenakis *et al.*, 2011, p. 311).

Once change readiness is achieved, and in line with the theoretical framework of this study, the Irish HEIs can 'institutionalise' this change (Armenakis *et al.*, 2011, p. 311) through a strong 'commitment' by dedicating resources such as departments, policies, and systems specifically for IaH initiatives. Additionally, 'persuasive communication' plays a crucial role, with strategically organised events and leadership speeches that emphasise IaH, effectively framing these messages as a persistent call for change.

Additionally, 'symbolism' can foster a positive culture by recognising and rewarding successful IaH initiatives. The practice of 'diffusion' can be essential too, as investing in continuous professional development (CPD) for IaH can strengthen institutional efforts. Moreover, 'formalisation activities' can be crucial, embedding IaH into the strategic planning processes at the university, faculty, and school levels, as well as within the professional progression framework.

Further, the 'management of both internal and external information', through publications, press releases, and inviting experts and mentors, can enhance the awareness of IaH within the university community. Equally significant is the 'assessment' of IaH initiatives, allowing institutions to measure their success and impact effectively, as highlighted in *Table 12*. These efforts can be further strengthened by embracing the learning organisation model put forth by Senge (1990, p. 12).

As explained in *Chapter 4 (sub-section 4.2.3.2)*, this model emphasises 'personal mastery,' encouraging all members to actively practice IaH, nurturing 'mental models' that cultivate a shared understanding of a culture centred on IaH, and promoting 'team learning' through CPD. Most importantly, it can encourage 'systems thinking', viewing IaH as a comprehensive, institution-wide approach rather than a series of fragmented initiatives across different departments or disciplines. These strategies can help mitigate the 'pars pro toto' effect of IaH, where a few initiatives are inadvertently perceived as the 'whole' or 'all' of IaH as described by Beelen (2023) and Beelen and Doscher (2022).

6.4.1.1.2 Stakeholder Engagement

As outlined in the previous sub-section, stakeholder engagement can be an important driver for facilitating change management. The findings indicate that investment in continuous professional development (CPD), effective rewards and recognition systems, and adequate funding can play a significant role in engaging staff and learners in this process, as illustrated in *Figure 25*. The insights from the data suggest that while CPD holds comparable significance in both traditional universities and the TUs, the need for funding is significantly greater emphasised by the participants from the TUs.

Conversely, reward and recognition are more prominently emphasised by participants from traditional universities. This distinction is understandable based on the arguments presented in the literature (*Chapter 3: sub-section 3.2*) and participant accounts, which suggest that traditional universities, due to their more advanced level of internationalisation, may have access to broader funding opportunities. As a result, there is a heightened demand for systems of reward and recognition. In contrast, TUs, which face considerable staff workload pressures, in contrast to the staff from traditional universities, require increased funding and

incentives to effectively focus on developing IaH (Houghton, 2020; Ryan, 2020). Nevertheless, these concerns remain significant in both types of institutions.

"If we are interested in driving internationalisation at home, it has to be rewarded and recognised someplace. People are not going to drop other responsibilities and redirect their attention to internationalisation at home...unless it is recognised as important."

(Academic Staff 2, Traditional University)

Additionally, the data highlights the necessity for greater accessibility to resources to organise or participate in IaH initiatives, as previously mentioned. Moreover, 'intentional' collaboration among Irish and international learners has been more emphasised by stakeholders from TUs compared to their counterparts at traditional universities (Gosling and Yang, 2022; Ryan, 2020; Harrison, 2015).

"I think it is easier for the international students to stick with the international students because they are all on the same boat, having the same experiences...and they just naturally bond together, whereas the Irish people stay with the Irish people because they naturally bond together and it is just it is a really complex situation and if the university doesn't break down the wall it is going to stay like that."

(Irish Learner 6, Technological University)

Furthermore, while some traditional universities have established Communities of Practice (CoPs) for internationalisation, which they find beneficial, this aspect has received less attention from TUs. It would be worthwhile to investigate how CoPs can foster the development of a culture of IaH (Ryan *et al.*, 2022).

Interestingly, as described earlier, while CPD may be on the top of the list for staff engagement with IaH, some participants share that it may not fully address the challenges associated with effectively embedding a culture of IaH. This perspective highlights the reality that staff members frequently face, which is limited time and competing priorities, leading to the perception of IaH as an 'add-on' rather than an integral part of their responsibilities (Beelen 2022, 2018).

"Because everybody is so busy, the space must be created. So obviously, first of all, training is really important; it is online and accessible. People can dip in and out when they have time, but making them aware of that....and you also use the institutional structures to create that space, so for example, in school meetings, you have that (IaH) as a standing item. You have an opportunity to discuss it, which is really important there, and you showcase good practice...have a system to recognise those efforts.. which is really important."

(Academic Staff 3, Technological University)

The reflections from participants indicate that achieving more may require a rebalancing of workload distribution. This can ensure that staff have the necessary time and resources, along with rewards and recognition, to develop IaH (Clarke and Hui Yang, 2021; Ryan, 2020; Dunne, 2013). Additionally, establishing a dedicated department for intercultural and global learning (IaH) could drive and unify all efforts within the institution. *Table 13* illustrates both learner and staff perspectives on the incentives for engaging in IaH.

"Staff training incentives. You know, it might be that there would be some kind of like credit linked to professional progression."

(Academic Staff 2, Technological University)

"I think the only way we can fully incentivise is by having it recognised in, you know, your work allocation, and in the professional progression...and that has not yet happened in our institution. You can take on certain roles, and you might get a reduction in your teaching hours. But if you want to really embed this, you have to, I think, incentivise it in a way that connects with the workload allocation model, you know, model in the university...it is about having the supports in place to encourage the academics in so many areas, so that there are regular opportunities for training, for workshops, but that it is incentivised professionally."

(Academic Manager 1, Traditional University)

Table 13: Learners and Staff Perspectives on Incentives for Engagement in IaH

Stakeholder	Various means, practices and methods through which achieved
Learners	Funding to organise events.
	Paid internships/jobs in different departments of the university.
	Easy accessibility in booking spaces and infrastructure for organising events.
	Scheduling events in college hours and at preferably central/popular locations on campus.
	Language learning hubs to practice a foreign language with native speakers.
	Free food and drinks at events.
	Interdisciplinary credited modules that contribute to the development of intercultural competence and global citizenship skills
	University leadership volunteer awards that foster collaboration between Irish and international learners.
	Evidence of IaH captured on the learners' transcripts.
Staff	Funding for IaH initiatives.
	Time buy-outs from teaching or course reductions to focus on developing IaH initiatives.
	Trainings related to IaH count towards their professional development hours.
	Staff mobility to learn from best practice HEIs abroad and improve teaching and learning offerings.
	Grants or fellowships to develop publications and resources in IaH.
	Explicit mention of IaH as one of the parameters in staff professional progression.
	Teaching and learning awards recognising IaH.
	Research funds and CPD vouchers recognising contributions in IaH.

In considering a more structured framework for linking IaH with staff professional development and career advancement, some participants noted that a singular focus on CPD might not be sufficient to sustain IaH as a viable practice (Weissova *et al.*, 2024). This sentiment is echoed in reflection from staff at best practice HEIs in Europe, which suggests that simply investing in CPD is not a sustainable strategy. These institutions have sought to establish teaching, learning, and research labs and engage in action research to develop in-house expertise for IaH initiatives. In contrast, best practice HEIs in the UK highlight the necessity of integrating CPD with staff training plans to enhance their overall effectiveness.

"We invested heavily in professional development programmes. So initially, we worked together with our institutional centre for teaching and learning and tried to have an open offer of courses and workshops. But yeah, after the initial wave of champions that were looking for that, it kind of dried up. So, we changed our strategies, and we started organising what we call a teaching and learning lab...and we have numerous teaching and learning labs. They all focus on certain areas of expertise that our general teaching and learning specialists do not have, as they tend to have a broader look at curricula. Also, we started what we currently call the Global Educators Lab, which is really a combination of open offers and inspiration in terms of workshops or masterclasses, as well as offering guided trajectories and consultancies for programmes to embed internationalisation. That is still based on a voluntary kind of reaching out, either through programme managers or internationalisation coordinators. But it is there, and we are joining forces with the other teaching and learning labs. So, we kind of create some synergy there. So, for example, when it is about blended learning, then we try and work with them and see, OK, so how can we do a joint session on COIL, for example."

(Best Practice HEI, Europe)

My colleagues and I have been doing some action research, interviewing a fairly new colleague, and he was given hours at the faculty level to support colleagues in the development of COIL projects... and he did not know what COIL was, what his role was, etc. So, we had three interviews with him. And then slowly, slowly, not only did he gain an understanding of what COIL is, got a sense of how he could support lecturers from his role, but also is increasingly becoming curious about how COIL fits in the Internationalisation at Home landscape and what else is there. So, you are turning someone who is, first of all, unknown, into an ally who can do a lot of work within one of the faculties... and we are actually modelling that approach in other faculties as well, and so, learning through that...and as I said, through research projects like these, we are also developing instruments. So, one that I think is very useful is looking at how different academic disciplines enact Internationalisation at Home."

(Best Practice HEI, Europe)

"The professional development course was created for academic and support services staff, and we communicated with the head of each department and the dean of education from each faculty. So, it is pushed to colleagues, saying, oh, you have to have a look. Some schools are actually giving each staff member 10 hours per year to go through the materials and attend relevant trainings around internationalisation."

(Best Practice HEI, UK)

Whilst best practices can provide valuable insights based on experience, the core theoretical framework for this study on organisational design suggests that stakeholder theory and job demands-resources theory are particularly relevant to Irish HEIs in navigating institutional aspirations, work demands, resource allocation, and prioritisation of IaH (*Chapter 4: sub-section 4.2.1*). For example, the 'stakeholder identification and salience theory' proposed by Mitchell *et al.* (1997) emphasises 'power, legitimacy, and urgency' in determining which stakeholders should be prioritised and how IaH claims can be effectively implemented amidst competing priorities. The aspects of 'legitimacy' and 'salience' relate closely to organisational culture. It can indicate that if this culture is aligned with IaH, it is more likely to prioritise it as a significant claim. Furthermore, the ongoing messaging advocating for IaH can assist middle

management in deciding the extent of attention and resources allocated to IaH and in determining its priority level, a sentiment echoed in the participants' accounts (p.867).

Furthermore, stakeholder salience is connected to the stakeholder culture theory (Jones *et al.*, 2007), which posits that stakeholders, such as managers, staff, and learners must decide whether IaH is 'nice to have' or genuinely valuable for developing the skills and competencies necessary to thrive in modern society and the workforce. This perspective can vary from 'self-regarding' interests, focused solely on completing tasks, to 'other-regarding' cultures that recognise the significance of IaH, even if it does not yield immediate tangible benefits. Such recognition can be vital in shaping learners' mindsets as 'global citizens' (p. 142). Lastly, the job demands-resources theory (Bakker and Demerouti, 2007) can facilitate the redistribution of workloads and provide essential resources, such as funding, CPD supports, and a dedicated department for IaH, which support both staff and learners in transitioning from a state of 'burnout' to 'engagement' with IaH (Bakker *et al.*, 2014, p. 399).

Collectively, if the change management efforts are complemented with investments in CPD, rewards and recognition, and funding for IaH initiatives as reflected in the participant perspectives illustrated in *Table 13* (Clarke and Hui Yang, 2021; Ryan, 2020; Clarke *et al.*, 2018), there is a greater likelihood of success. Furthermore, fostering a culture of intentional collaboration between Irish and international learners, along with the establishment of Communities of Practice (CoPs), can greatly empower leaders in their change management endeavours by facilitating the sharing of experiences and collaborative problem-solving.

6.4.1.1.3 Curriculum Design

Finally, at the institutional level, academic staff can explore innovative approaches to curriculum design and renewal processes, as depicted in *Figure 26*. The findings reveal that staff at both traditional universities and the TUs place comparable importance on curriculum renewal through programmatic reviews, viewing this as an opportunity to incorporate international and intercultural dimensions. This viewpoint is consistent with the approaches discussed in the literature (Ryan, 2020; Clarke *et al.*, 2018).

Figure 26: Overcoming Challenges at the Institutional Level (Curriculum)

Curriculum Design

"So, it is important that the knowledge base is not just based on a European population. We are thinking about a really good example, such as looking at rashes on arms, for instance. A lot of colleagues in the school of medicine spoke about that, like all the pictures that they found in their textbooks are of white skin. You are if you are a doctor or nurse and you are looking at a patient who is presenting with a rash or with skin cancer or any of these things. You are only seeing these presented on skins of particular hue, which means that your knowledge base is incomplete. So, there's kind of a discussion around the types of examples that are used, the illustrations that are used, the images that are used in textbooks and become more attuned to a lot of that. So then if they see blind spots in the textbook, they will actually put up supplementary slides in their lectures to kind of say, well, actually, I found these online and these are what it looks like on brown skin or black skin. So, I think that is actually really been really interesting to have these discussions around formal and hidden curriculum."

(Academic Staff 2, Traditional University)

"Make it (IaH) more systemic and make sure it is very clearly part of their process when the academic staff engage with programmes on curriculum renewal or quality assurance, that it is really part of that."

(Best Practice HEI, Europe)

Furthermore, there was a notable emphasis on a multidisciplinary approach through Universal Design for Learning (Healy, Banks, and Ryder, 2024). This included offering interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary electives and community-based learning (Bruce McLean, 2025), alongside electives focused on intercultural communication and global citizenship. This approach was more pronounced in traditional universities than in the TUs, which may be attributed to the advanced level of internationalisation in the traditional universities. However, participants from traditional universities recognised that while UDL can be beneficial to embed IaH, implementing this approach is complex and challenging; they find themselves in the early stages of applying it to some of their programmes (Healy *et al.*, 2024; Brown, David and Smallman, 2017; Heelan, 2015).

"You know, we have had a big push on our learning and teaching towards universal design for learning...and I think what has flowed out of that is then the need to be much more conscious of inclusive communications in the way that things are framed and explained and so on."
(Senior Manager 1, Traditional University)

"I would definitely love more elective options and like the mixing of courses. Like, so I was only with other students in the humanities department, but I would love a kind of cross-course learning. I think that would be great because maybe a lot of international students are... like mainly in say a certain type of course like therein my course was no international students so I don't know maybe if we got to do a module with another kind of type of course maybe that would have been better for internationalisation and work with international students, I would love it."
(Irish Learner 1, Technological University)

"We have a community-based learning programme, a year-long programme around global citizenship and international volunteering. I suppose the majority of that programme is based on campus because there is a lot of weekend evening workshops or a global citizenship, intercultural learning, preparation for working in a diverse area thinking about the ethics of international volunteering and, and how that plays out in terms of power relationships and how, you know, how a group of students working in, marginalised communities in the global said, thinking about that, really challenging some of those questions, before, people travel. And then there is a lot of work with people, people travel. And then there is a lot of work with people on return. So, really, it is about packing with people on return. So really unpacking what their experience has meant for them, encouraging them, engaging them in activism, awareness raising, really thinking about the global citizenship and potential and what that means for young people...and so that whole area, has been so, so transformative for students that you see."
(International Officer 3, Traditional University)

"I think the learning environment at home, you know, if we can really design that as an exciting space, that you can do maybe even more learning from your peers, your fellow students, than from your teacher. Which might be, you know, very contradictory to how students actually expect to be educated and what they think the role of the teacher is. So, creating that very exciting space and also taking, you know, education outside the university doors and really going to the local context and seeing what issues those citizens and companies are struggling with and what is happening...and, you know, how can we invite outsider perspectives, novel ways of thinking into the, you know, into the problem-solving process. And seeing that, you know, through this experience, either in the classroom or in the local communities, that it is inevitable that the local and the global are so linked, you can't opt out...and that on the one hand, that makes things very complex. But also, it is so enriching to unlearn things."

(Best Practice HEI, Europe)

In addition to multidisciplinary approaches, traditional universities have emphasised the importance of co-creating curricula to engage learners, as discussed in *Chapter 2 (sub-section 2.7.3)*. Although this practice is still in its early stages within traditional universities and is regarded as valuable by them, it has yet to fully develop. The TUs have also acknowledged co-creation approaches to curricula with learners as partners to some degree. However, there is limited evidence in the literature pertaining to this approach within the Irish context, with some scholars urging further exploration (Corcoran, Hamm and Weiner, 2022).

"In our teaching and learning department, have a students as partners initiatives. So, students are like employees; they are paid by us at the institutional level to work on developing resources from the student perspective or work with us to, you know, look at our website and kind of give us advice."

(Academic Staff 2, Traditional University)

"I think if it is, if you were to fully reap the benefits of internationalisation at home, it needs to be embedded within formal programmes and not just within the hidden curriculum or just within the informal activities. I think it needs to be systematically embedded, and in relation to how students can be involved in that process. I think maybe if we are developing a module on intercultural communication, or even if it is just embedding perspectives from other countries into existing modules and maybe involving students in the development of those modules. But I do think from my perspective anyway, and it could just be it is just so tight for time trying to squeeze other things into people's schedules that maybe embedding it into current modules or making it part of a formal programme would be the most kind of systematic way of doing it rather than just hit or miss organising events."

(Irish Learner 7, Traditional University)

To enhance the process of internationalising the curriculum, the staff from best practice HEIs in Europe and the UK demonstrate their commitment by offering guided consultancies and CPD courses to their academic staff. While some participants from the traditional universities indicated the availability of CPD opportunities through their teaching and learning centres, there is an opportunity for more targeted initiatives in IaH. In contrast,

the staff from the TUs did not report similar course offerings at their institutions, suggesting potential scope for development in this aspect.

"So sometimes it helps just to give a little bit of inspiration. So interesting topics to discuss about, which kind of are open platform, you know, open invitation, open to all...and that works, I think, really well with newcomers to the institution. So, people who are getting to know the institution and want to see what is happening. You get them hooked on this, which is cool. This is exciting. I want to know more about it. I have also worked with our programmes and faculties. Sometimes we are asked, you know, my colleagues and I are involved in the research group or global learning or the global educators' lab, can you help us?...and what works really well is a very hands-on approach with our lecturers. Also staff want to see immediate results. So, hosting workshops is very kind at a micro level. Take your module. Here are some methods that we can use to model internationalise the content. See how it works first on the fictitious module. Then apply to yourself and discuss it with colleagues from different disciplines. Because that helps in exposing the blind spots and seeing more opportunities, so that very practical hands-on approach that is showing that it is not, yeah, it requires maybe creativity, a little bit of out-of-the-box thinking, but it is doable...and it does not mean to add a whole new module or, you know, a very different approach, but it is really about resetting your thinking. I think that kind of workshop is always very popular...and it is really like an aha moment. Okay, we can do this... and it is fun as well. So, they can create a vision document and how to continue what the next steps is, what the next steps are. We have also helped programmes in trajectories."

(Best Practice HEI, Europe)

The school of education they are doing loads of great stuff, including the framework for internationalisation at home. They have been doing so much, but are focused more on the research side of it. So I developed a course for staff and PhD researchers... I developed it is quite necessary and timely because I think people in different departments or different parts of the university know what they are doing, but everyone is lacking some kind of central provision, central support, and integrating internationalisation in the curricula. To make everything like in a cohesive way."

(Best Practice HEI, UK)

Taken together, curriculum renewals, multidisciplinary approaches and co-designing curriculum with learners can lead Irish HEIs to achieve their ambitions towards IaH at the grassroots level. This approach is consistent with the foundational theoretical framework for this study on internationalised curriculum design (Leask, 2015), which highlights a multi-dimensional perspective of curriculum design (*Chapter 4: sub-section 4.2.2*). It encompasses the internationalisation of formal, informal, and hidden curricula, necessitating course, program, and institutional changes pertinent to emerging professional practices and the dynamic external environment in which the institution functions (Leask, 2015, p. 2). This framework has provided a theoretical lens for understanding 'curriculum as a system,' facilitating a more systematic embedding of internationalisation by examining not only curriculum design, content, pedagogy, learning activities, and assessment but also considering broader influences such as institutional, national, regional, and global contexts (Leask, 2022, p. 169).

6.4.1.2 National Level

The preceding sub-section presented participants' reflections on strategies that can be implemented at the institutional level to overcome the challenges in embedding a culture of IaH, thereby responding to the final research question of this study. While it is broadly acknowledged that IaH is intrinsic to Irish HEIs, there is an opportunity for national support in advancing these initiatives. This is particularly relevant given the emphasis placed on IaH in the national talent and innovation strategy, *Global Citizens 2030* (DFHERIS, 2024), which underlines its significance in cultivating intercultural competencies and global citizenship skills essential for graduates from Irish HEIs to excel in today's multicultural societies and workplaces.

6.4.1.2.1 Policy Vs Strategy

Many participants reflected on the role of government funding and accountability mechanisms in promoting IaH within their institutions, as illustrated in *Figure 27*. However, this need was emphasised more by the participants from the TUs, likely due to their distinct workload models and varying access to government funding (Haughton, 2020), as highlighted in *Chapter 3 (sub-section 3.2)*. While policymakers acknowledge the crucial role of university leadership in determining the allocation of the internationalisation budget and resources, the absence of direct policy support for IaH in the national strategy raises concerns among many staff members. This issue is particularly pressing given the challenges confronted by an underfunded Irish higher education sector (Burke, 2021; O'Connor, 2018; Courtois, 2017).

Figure 27: Overcoming Challenges in IaH at the National Level

National Strategy vs Policy

In order to drive IaH in HEIs, one of the best practice HEI in Europe illustrated how their government and national agency play a supportive role in fostering the development of IaH initiatives.

"In our case, we have recently had a national subsidy, which is very easy to apply for lecturers. That is a huge catalyst, and we see that that is, you know, money means that people get freed up from teaching responsibilities and get time to develop. So, these monetary incentives from our Ministry of Education are very helpful indeed, and we have seen a blossoming of COIL practices, and a lot of newcomers are engaging in them, so that is very good."
(Best Practice HEI, Europe)

"I know nationally that our national agency, and I have been working with them together with other institutions, have recently, I think last week, launched a dedicated theme page on Internationalisation at Home...showing many resources, you know, showing the rationales, models, but also a lot of examples and instruments. So that is really putting Internationalisation at Home out there...and obviously we want to see it, you know, included in the strategic agenda of our universities and universities of applied sciences."
(Best Practice HEI, Europe)

Moreover, staff within Irish HEIs perceive that establishing a culture of IaH relies significantly on adequate funding and accountability mechanisms. This perspective aligns with the findings of Clarke *et al.* (2018), which indicate that the lack of sufficient incentives for internationalisation in Irish HEIs hinders the effective implementation of institutional strategies, which are informed by the national strategy in most universities (p. 32).

"Well, I think he probably connects with my previous answer..around the kind of funding model. So having, grants being able to fund initiatives of institutional level at national level. Like the national forum for teaching and learning is a great kind of medium for, creating energy around different types of initiatives. So, at the national level, I think it would, funding is kind of key."
(Academic Staff 2, Traditional University)

"Funding opportunities on a national level...there obviously needs to be governmental support for this. There needs to be, you know, probably a national board (for IaH)... There needs to be national advertisements. There needs to be an awareness campaign. You need to have a lot of things like that... the minister for education brings it to the registrar's office and the registrar's bring it down to the faculties. So, there are layers there. So, they need to say that this is a focus, this is a focus on a national level."
(Academic Manager 3, Technological University)

In order to reconcile the strategic rhetoric with the realities on the ground, additional measures may be necessary. As highlighted by Hackett, McAllister-Wylie, and Saxil (2025), *'Irish universities continue to face increasing student numbers as budgets dwindle, causing deficits in education quality and offerings threatening the very aim of the new international education strategy (Global Citizens 2030)...continued underfunding of HE in Ireland and lack of meaningful integration policies will both prevent internationalisation and intercultural learning opportunities...causing deficits in education quality and offerings'*.

In addition, an academic staff member from a traditional university (AS 2) emphasises the importance of enhancing the visibility of IaH by incorporating a global dimension into national funding grants.

"Linking teaching and research so that it is not just a teaching and services focus is also connected to research....and so, just like we have that kind of gender dimension in our kind of national grant writing process that actually, you know, thinking about the global dimensions or international dimensions or intercultural dimensions of our research might also be a way of driving some of that too."
(Academic Staff 2, Traditional University)

Furthermore, certain staff members highlight the importance of implementing clear accountability measures to monitor IaH at the institutional level in accordance with national policy.

"I think it is important to have reporting structures... as an accountability, to say, you know, this is what you (the HEI) are doing in line with the national strategy is what you are doing in line with your institutional strategy and then reporting specific metrics, accountability, annual monitoring at the national level, that kind of thing."
(International Officer 3, Traditional University)

In essence, establishing clear connections between the national strategy and a policy for IaH, supported by targeted funding and accountability measures, can strengthen the case for a systemic approach to internationalisation in Irish HEIs. While policymakers make decisions based on national demands, as reflected in their deliberations, linking these decisions to IaH is essential. This is because IaH has the potential to foster tolerant, peaceful, and inclusive societies amidst the current geopolitical uncertainty, where many societies are grappling with conflicts. By investing in developing IaH, Ireland can reinforce its reputation as a welcoming nation and enhance its standing on the global stage. Although IaH serves as a catalyst, it also plays a vital role in achieving the goals of global citizenship, which extend beyond higher education per se. As noted by staff from the best practice HEI in Europe, *'Internationalisation is not optional. It is a fact of life. You can't opt out. Our society is already international. Employment sectors, everything is so inherently interconnected.'*

6.4.2 Working Definition for Embedding a Culture of IaH

The previous sub-section discussed some of the suggestive strategies to overcome challenges associated with embedding a culture of IaH in Irish HEIs, informed by the participant reflections, theoretical perspective and best practice guidance. In alignment with the empirical nature of this study, the researcher proposes a working definition that presents a holistic institution-wide approach to IaH, aimed at fostering this culture in a meaningful way. *Embedding a culture of Internationalisation at Home (IaH)* can be defined as

"A systemic approach to a co-creative internationalised experience for all learners and staff within the domestic learning environment, aimed at cultivating interculturally competent global citizens. It can be achieved by purposefully, inclusively and sustainably incorporating intercultural and global dimensions into the curriculum and support services driven by committed leadership and engaged staff and learners."
(Author)

This definition is grounded in the understanding that internationalisation represents a collective responsibility within the institution and often unfolds as a collaborative endeavour. Co-creation signifies a shared commitment among various stakeholders within the university, including all departments, functions, and learners, to advance the IaH initiatives while prioritising teamwork and diverse contributions over the formation of a singular, homogenous entity.

The objective is to nurture an internationalised learning environment within the domestic context, which can be realised through physical spaces on campus, engagement with the local community, or virtual interactions with learners, staff, and international partners. By establishing an enriching internationalised learning experience domestically, it aims to reach all learners and staff, thereby enhancing intercultural competence and promoting global citizenship, as elaborated in *Chapter 2*.

Furthermore, embedding a culture of IaH represents a thoughtful, inclusive, and sustainable endeavour. It contributes to minimising the environmental concerns associated with internationalisation activities such as mobility abroad. Moreover, it emphasises cross-cultural and cross-functional/departmental collaboration within the institution, supported by well-established processes and systems, ensuring its sustainability as a practice. To realise the vision of embedding a 'culture' of IaH, it can be crucial to incorporate intercultural and global dimensions into both the formal and informal curriculum, recognising the rich diversity of international learners and staff as well as the local diversity present in the regions where the institutions are situated.

Importantly, it strives to tackle the hidden curriculum by educating the university community, particularly the support services and academic staff, to enhance the experiential and educational outcomes from engaging in inclusive internationalisation for learners. Support services may include professional roles (such as those within international or global engagement offices and career services), administrative functions (encompassing registry, technology, accommodation, and finance), and student supports (including counselling, health and wellbeing, and accessibility), to mention a few. While the curriculum remains an essential component, the success of this embedding relies significantly on committed leadership and the proactive involvement of both staff and learners, as highlighted in the participant accounts.

In line with the above-described definition and the pursuit of embedding a culture of IaH, the researcher proposes an evidence-based framework focused on content, positioning, and reflection (IaH CPR). This framework aims to offer valuable guidance to Irish HEIs and is detailed in the following sub-section.

6.4.3 IaH Content, Positioning and Reflection Framework (CPR) and Continuum

The IaH content, positioning and reflection (CPR) framework, depicted in *Figure 28*, can guide Irish HEIs in embedding a culture of internationalisation at home within their institutions. The elements from this model are also transferable to other cultural contexts. The IaH CPR model emphasises three key stages, i.e. 'Content (C), Positioning (P) and Reflection (R).' Each of these key stages or sub-sections under each category is flexible, non-linear and can be adapted as an ongoing process in the face of dynamic circumstances in which the universities operate. The stages have been elucidated below.

Figure 28: IaH CPR Framework: An Evidence-Based Framework for Embedding a Culture of 'Internationalisation at Home (IaH)' in Irish HEIs

Internationalisation at Home (IaH) Content, Positioning and Reflection (CPR) Framework

A dynamic evidence-based framework for embedding a culture of 'Internationalisation at Home (IaH)' in Irish higher education institutions

Core Outcome: Intercultural Competence and Global Citizenship

Source: Author

Content (C):

The content stage encompasses three key elements: 'context, commitment, and curriculum,' which can be valuable for HEIs aiming to embed IaH. The '*context*' aspect represents the current landscape facilitating IaH, involving a comprehensive review of existing initiatives and an understanding of IaH across various functions and departments within the institution. This stage presents an opportunity to conduct a scoping exercise and needs analysis related to IaH, which can help assess current efforts within the institution. Additionally, this phase can enable HEIs to identify pertinent stakeholders who can be engaged in the process.

Following the context assessment for IaH, the content stage involves the '*commitment*' necessary to advance IaH initiatives. This includes leadership prioritising IaH through institutional strategic documents, allocating appropriate resources, such as establishing a dedicated department for IaH, and developing policies that facilitate its implementation at the faculty, school, and departmental levels throughout the institution. Key elements also involve fostering meaningful engagement with all stakeholders, particularly learners, as well as academic and support services staff. Additionally, it requires explicitly linking IaH to professional progression for staff and ensuring the sustainability of initiatives over time, rather than loose fragmented activities.

Finally, the '*curriculum*' in the content stage involves internationalising both formal and informal education for all students. This includes acknowledging and recognising the hidden curriculum and evolving practices and systems within the institution. Integrating an internationalised curriculum can be achieved during the design and renewal stages through programmatic reviews, considering professional practice requirements. Moreover, there is an opportunity to develop transdisciplinary⁸ offerings by incorporating intercultural competence modules, universal design for learning (UDL), and community-based learning initiatives, thereby enhancing the overall teaching and learning experience.

⁸ Transdisciplinary approaches are 'more than multidisciplinary (i.e., links between disciplines) and move across and beyond disciplinary boundaries, transcending learners to develop new learning experiences related to real problems in real-world settings' (McGregor, 2015, p.8).

Additional initiatives may include providing opportunities for English, Irish Gaelic, and foreign language learning, as well as integrating virtual internationalisation into the core formal curriculum. This could encompass collaborative online international learning (COIL), virtual exchanges (VE), and blended intensive programs⁹ (BIPs). Importantly, explicit connections can be made with sustainability, equality, diversity, and inclusion, as these areas are interdependent rather than independent. Furthermore, the integration of mobility experiences for learners and staff can be conducted thoughtfully, ensuring a cohesive approach within the formal curriculum.

Positioning (P)

In the subsequent phase following the content stage, the 'positioning' of IaH highlights the significance of 'planning, process, and practice.' The '*planning*' phase is particularly vital for cultivating awareness and a shared understanding of the IaH concept within the university community. Engaging in thorough consultations with stakeholders, possibly through university working groups or committees, can enhance this understanding and benefit from the insights of external experts in the field.

To effectively embed a culture of IaH, it would be advantageous to establish a practical working definition (*sub-section 6.4.2*), which can be further solidified by explicitly incorporating IaH into the university's strategic framework and creating supportive policies for its implementation. This could align with a comprehensive framework, such as the IaH CPR, designed to embed a culture of IaH into the university's operations, explained in this sub-section.

Prioritising the establishment of a dedicated department for IaH and ensuring that it is well-resourced, including the potential expansion of the international staff body, can be essential. Furthermore, it would be beneficial for IaH to be a regular item on the strategy and agenda at the faculty, school, and departmental levels. This may involve designating formal roles to link internationalisation in the curriculum, such as Assistant Deans International or Heads of Departments for Internationalisation and aligning IaH with quality assurance processes.

⁹ Blended Intensive Programmes (BIPs) are 'short, intensive programmes that use innovative ways of learning and teaching, including the use of online cooperation. By enabling new and more flexible mobility formats that combine physical mobility with a virtual part, BIPs aim at reaching all types of students from all backgrounds, study fields and cycles' (European Commission, n.d.).

It is also crucial to raise awareness within the university community regarding the significance and advantages of IaH, while emphasising the valuable graduate attributes developed through participation in these initiatives. Additionally, enhancing the infrastructure and accessibility to support IaH initiatives will be pivotal for their success. Ultimately, for IaH to be effective, it must be thoroughly integrated into the institution's systems, as previously outlined.

Transitioning from the planning phase to the '*process*' phase in the positioning stage highlights initiatives focused on preparing staff for implementing IaH and facilitating effective change management. This approach may require a collaborative strategy combining top-down and bottom-up methods. Significant investments will likely be necessary to enhance internal capacity through ongoing professional development (CPD) and post-training support for all staff members. A co-creative and participatory approach could greatly benefit the strategy for internationalising the curriculum or support services.

Additionally, collaboration with local communities, as well as regional, national, and international partners, along with guidance from IaH experts, can enrich learners' experiences and better equip them to become global citizens. To support these efforts, consistent communication regarding the importance of IaH within the institution is essential for managing expectations and navigating change throughout the process.

Post-planning and capacity building for IaH, the '*practice*' phase in the positioning stage, can be a foundation for effective IaH implementation. This phase can manifest through learner and staff diversity, an inclusive campus environment, an internationalised curriculum, and collaboration between Irish and international students, ultimately fostering interculturally competent learners and staff. Furthermore, stakeholder engagement is crucial in the IaH process.

Stakeholders can be involved through teaching and learning labs dedicated to IaH, offering continuous professional development (CPD) and post-training support, as well as global or intercultural lounges that intentionally collaborate Irish and international learners. Additional strategies include co-designing curricula with learners, establishing Communities of Practice focused on IaH, promoting virtual internationalisation, and creating joint offerings through European University Alliances, Erasmus, and various other networks and partnerships, to mention a few.

To maximise the benefits of these initiatives, institutions should enhance the visibility of their IaH efforts through university marketing and communication channels, while also leveraging

social media more effectively. Although 'practice' in the positioning stage drives the progress of IaH, it can also contribute to the development of institutional metrics for assessing and evaluating its impact, as highlighted in *Table 12*. Finally, institutions can expand their knowledge capital by publishing in reputable peer-reviewed journals and grey literature to share their experiences and practices, thereby advocating for IaH within the broader community. National policy supports can further strengthen these initiatives.

Reflection (R)

The 'reflection' stage focuses on 'reviewing, renewing, and reinforcing' effective practices for embedding IaH across various departments and levels. The initial aspect of this stage involves a '*review*' of the current practices established during the positioning stage, which may include a critical evaluation supported by feedback mechanisms. This step can also provide an opportunity for stakeholder consultation to assess effectiveness, identify gaps, and address challenges in the process. Furthermore, an internal review can be benchmarked against other national, European, or international institutions as exemplars of best practices.

The review measures offer the prospect of '*renewal*' in systems and processes that best embed IaH across different levels. This can take the form of revisions in curricula and experiences for learners, revisiting existing partnerships and offerings, refreshing training, learning and development of staff, reallocating resources and reimagining strategies for implementing IaH such as policies and support systems that may further facilitate its embedding.

Finally, reinforcing good practices can lead to the systemic embedding of IaH. This can be achieved through a robust commitment from leadership and ongoing support, alongside consistent messaging that emphasises the significance of IaH in fostering learner intercultural competence and global citizenship. Documenting progress during implementation, celebrating success stories, institutionalising innovative practices, identifying challenges, and proactively addressing them are all vital components of this process.

Remarkably, a crucial step in this journey can be to recognise and reward champions of IaH among learners, staff, and leadership, thereby motivating and encouraging their efforts. These initiatives hold the potential to systematically embed IaH across various faculties, schools, and departments, ultimately internationalising the campus and sustaining these efforts through continuous change management.

While the IaH CPR framework represents an ambitious vision, it is achievable through proactive leadership, staff and learners' commitment and engagement. The insights derived from participant accounts and existing literature, combined with the theoretical underpinnings and researcher's reflections in this study, inform the development of the IaH CPR framework. Ultimately, the goal is to enhance intercultural competence among both learners and staff, equipping them to thrive in a multicultural society as global citizens, one of the primary objectives of the talent and innovation strategy, Global Citizens 2030 (DFHERIS, 2024).

Whilst the IaH CPR model represents the 'what' and 'how,' the 'IaH CPR continuum,' as depicted in *Figure 29*, addresses the 'when' of embedding IaH. This continuum, characterised by its non-linear nature, can guide Irish HEIs as they consider strategies for internationalising their campuses.

Figure 29: Internationalisation at Home (IaH) Content, Positioning and Reflection (CPR) Continuum

The continuum is divided into three phases – foundation, implementation and consolidation. The *'foundation'* phase encompasses both the 'content' and 'positioning' elements of the IaH CPR framework. It involves evaluating the existing state of the art that supports IaH. This stage is subsequently followed by the 'planning' components outlined in the IaH CPR framework.

The subsequent phase, referred to as *'implementation,'* focuses on fostering commitment from various stakeholders. It entails the internationalisation of curricula, the establishment of transparent processes, and the execution through a range of initiatives. Additionally, this phase emphasises the importance of ongoing reviews of practices and potential challenges, allowing for thoughtful adjustments through alternative strategies as necessary.

Lastly, the '*consolidation*' phase includes renewing certain aspects of the IaH implementation process that need reinvigoration and rethinking. Furthermore, this phase also provides an opportunity to 'reinforce' practices that have contributed to developing intercultural competence among learners and staff, ultimately preparing them to become global citizens, one of the essential core outcomes for IaH. The IaH CPR continuum is adaptable, allowing various elements to be combined to address the evolving needs of the institution engaged in this initiative.

In essence, the evidence-informed IaH CPR framework and continuum (*Figures 28 and 29*) can offer a holistic and grounded approach underpinned by organisational and curriculum design and change management theories, literature review and participant reflections. The framework can facilitate adaptability in the face of change, which is peculiar to the institution and its context. Furthermore, it addresses the final research aim and highlights the practical contributions of this study.

6.4.4 Summary

This sub-section addressed the second research question in relation to the strategies Irish HEIs can adopt in embedding a culture of IaH as presented by the participants from the study. The theoretical framework guiding this research informed key themes such as change management (Armenakis *et al.*, 2011; Senge, 1990), stakeholder engagement (Mitchell *et al.*, 1997; Jones *et al.*, 2007; Bakker and Demerouti, 2007), and curriculum design (Leask, 2015). These themes are evident in the participants' accounts and are further supported by examples of best practices from HEIs in Europe and the UK. Irish HEIs collectively advocate for a systemic approach to embedding a culture of IaH, emphasising the need for collaboration across faculties, schools, departments, and functions, as IaH is viewed as a shared responsibility driven by institutional leadership, engaged staff and learners.

Additionally, participants highlighted the importance of establishing a dedicated department for IaH, as well as monitoring success (*Table 12*) and enhancing awareness and visibility of IaH initiatives as critical components for cultivating such a culture.

The processes and systems established through change management efforts can be further enhanced by stakeholder engagement, which can be the driving force for IaH, including academic staff, learners, and support services staff. There is a significant emphasis placed on the importance of continuous professional development, rewards and recognition, and funding for IaH initiatives, all of which can be crucial for establishing space and visibility for IaH amidst competing priorities. Additionally, attention was given to the intentional

approach of fostering collaboration between Irish and international learners, along with making IaH more accessible and further developed through staff communities of practice.

From a curriculum design perspective, the significance of programmatic reviews is highlighted for curriculum renewals that incorporate an international or intercultural dimension. Such renewal processes can significantly benefit from a multidisciplinary and/or transdisciplinary approach and co-designing curricula in collaboration with learners. Furthermore, to enhance institutional efforts, it can be crucial to establish a national policy that supports the national strategy through adequate funding and accountability measures, particularly for the underfunded higher education sector facing competing priorities. To embed a culture of IaH in reality within Irish HEIs, it may be essential for the government to go beyond mere strategic rhetoric.

Finally, to address the research aim of proposing a guiding framework to embed a culture of IaH, the researcher presented a working definition (*sub-section 6.4.2*) and content, positioning and reflection (IaH CPR) framework (*sub-section 6.4.3*) that can provide a holistic and systemic approach to embedding IaH in Irish HEIs and highlights the researcher's contribution to knowledge.

6.5 Conclusion

This chapter addressed the two research questions that aimed to examine the opportunities and challenges in embedding a culture of IaH alongside proposing strategies to facilitate this process. Additionally, it addressed the research aims by critiquing the understanding and implementation of IaH within the Irish context, highlighting the opportunities and challenges presented by participants, and proposing a guiding framework for Irish HEIs to embed this culture.

The research objectives were met by constructing a body of knowledge about embedding a culture of IaH, which included conceptual constructions, rationale, enablers that present opportunities and challenges facing IaH Irish HEIs in this area. The participants' accounts indicate that the term 'Internationalisation at Home (IaH)' is largely unfamiliar to most learners and some staff. However, their reflections suggest a practical understanding of the concept. Participants tend to describe IaH through the perspectives of cross-cultural engagement, international learner diversity, mobility, and curriculum, while also expressing assumptions and opinions about the term. The conceptual ambiguity is evident in the accounts. Importantly, participants conveyed that the rationale for their involvement in IaH is motivated by the aspiration to cultivate intercultural competence and global citizenship skills. Additionally, they emphasised the significance of equality, diversity, and inclusion

(EDI), learner diversity, effective teaching and learning practices, enhancing learner employability, and promoting sustainability.

While the concept of IaH is still in its early stages in the Irish HE context, its current implementation has been mainly through an informal curriculum, primarily within the international office, rather than being fully integrated into the formal curriculum. Notably, IaH has found a more prominent place in inherently international disciplines, such as International Business, while it appears less prevalent in applied fields such as Engineering. At present, IaH is somewhat enabled by an internationalised curriculum, stakeholder engagement, primarily involving enthusiastic learners and staff, collaborations, partnerships, alliances, and networks. The institutional strategic planning for most HEIs also recognises IaH as one of its key priorities, along with mobility opportunities embedded in curricula for certain programs.

The findings suggest that traditional universities may have a more progressive approach to IaH compared to the TUs, even if they do not explicitly label their efforts as such. This progress is reflected in their long-standing practice of welcoming international students, which fosters greater diversity within their student and staff populations. Additionally, learner participants engaged with the informal curriculum at traditional universities report higher satisfaction levels compared to those at TUs.

While these strengths provide a solid foundation for advancing the goals of IaH, the challenges facing the Irish HE system may hinder its further development. For example, issues related to learner and staff engagement beyond a few champions, insufficient leadership commitment and support, limited awareness and visibility of IaH initiatives, fragmented implementation across a few programs or through international/global engagement offices, and the absence of a national policy to support the strategy are significant factors that could hinder the effective establishment of a culture of IaH in Irish HEIs.

Although the foundations for IaH can be observed in most institutions, substantial efforts may be necessary to transition from implementation to fully embedding a culture of IaH. The latter part of the chapter addressed the second research question in relation to the strategies Irish HEIs can adopt in embedding a culture of IaH as presented by the participants from the study. These included overcoming barriers to embedding IaH, introducing a working definition and a guiding framework known as the IaH Content, Positioning, and Reflection Framework (IaH CPR). This framework is informed by

participant insights from both traditional and technological universities in Ireland, the wider global literature, and the core theoretical foundations of this study.

In addressing the challenges to cultivating a culture of IaH, the theoretical framework guiding this research informed key themes such as change management (Armenakis *et al.*, 2011; Senge, 1990), stakeholder engagement (Mitchell *et al.*, 1997; Jones *et al.*, 2007; Bakker and Demerouti, 2007), and curriculum design (Leask, 2015). These themes are evident in the participants' accounts and are further supported by examples of best practices from HEIs in Europe and the UK. Irish HEIs collectively advocate for a systemic approach to embedding a culture of IaH, emphasising the need for collaboration across faculties, schools, departments, and functions, as IaH is viewed as a shared responsibility driven by institutional leadership. Additionally, participants highlighted the importance of establishing a dedicated department for IaH, as well as monitoring success (*Table 12*) and enhancing awareness and visibility of IaH initiatives as critical components for cultivating such a culture.

The processes and systems established through change management efforts can be further enhanced by stakeholder engagement, which can be the driving force for IaH, including academic staff, learners, and support services staff. There is a significant emphasis placed on the importance of continuous professional development, rewards and recognition, and funding for IaH initiatives, all of which can be crucial for establishing space and visibility for IaH amidst competing priorities. Additionally, attention was given to the intentional approach of fostering collaboration between Irish and international learners, along with making IaH more accessible and further developed through staff communities of practice.

From a curriculum design perspective, the significance of programmatic reviews is highlighted for curriculum renewals that incorporate an international or intercultural dimension. Such renewal processes can significantly benefit from a multidisciplinary and/or transdisciplinary approach and co-designing curricula in collaboration with learners. Furthermore, to enhance institutional efforts, it can be crucial to establish a national policy that supports the national strategy through adequate funding and accountability measures, particularly for the underfunded higher education sector facing competing priorities. To embed a culture of IaH in reality within Irish HEIs, it may be essential for the government to go beyond mere strategic rhetoric.

Finally, to address the research aim of proposing a guiding framework to embed a culture of IaH, the researcher presented a working definition (*sub-section 6.4.2*) and content, positioning and reflection (IaH CPR) framework (*sub-section 6.4.3*) that can provide a holistic and systemic

approach to embedding IaH in Irish HEIs and highlights the researcher's contribution to knowledge.

This research addresses a gap in the literature regarding the theme from the perspective of Irish higher education, with the potential for transferability to other contexts; however, no definitive claims can be made in this regard. The following chapter concludes the overall study by presenting key recommendations at both the institutional and national levels, along with suggestions for future research in the field.

CHAPTER 7: CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

7.1 Introduction

This study aimed to examine the interpretation of internationalisation at home (IaH) within the context of Irish higher education, while also taking into account its development globally. The research sought to identify the opportunities and challenges associated with cultivating a culture of IaH in Irish higher education institutions (HEIs) and propose strategies that could effectively support embedding this culture. These research questions were closely aligned with the study's overarching objectives, ultimately leading to the development of a guiding framework designed to facilitate embedding IaH within Irish HEIs.

Given the above context, the concluding chapter has been organised into six sub-sections. These sub-sections include: (1) an overview of the study, (2) the theoretical and practical contributions of this study, (3) recommendations and implications for policy and practice, (4) limitations of the study, (5) suggestions for future research, and finally, (6) the researcher's reflection and reflexivity.

This chapter presents an overview of the study, emphasises both the theoretical and practical contributions to knowledge, and discusses the recommendations and implications of this study for policy and practice at both institutional and national levels. Furthermore, it acknowledges the study's limitations and explores the potential for future research in this field. Finally, the chapter concludes with the researcher's reflection and reflexivity on the overall experience of conducting this research.

7.2 Overview of the Study

Ireland has a long-standing tradition of welcoming international scholars and researchers, and it has become increasingly multicultural, particularly in response to the proactive initiatives introduced with the launch of the first international education strategy in 2010. However, there appears to be a noticeable gap in the scholarly discourse regarding the comprehensive examination of internationalisation at home in higher education in Ireland. The most significant study and seminal work on internationalisation, conducted by Clarke *et al.* (2018), offered an in-depth examination of the overall landscape of internationalisation in Irish higher education (HE); however, it was published seven years ago.

While other studies have addressed specific facets of internationalisation, they emphasise the need for a systemic approach within Irish HEIs. This can be important because mobility opportunities currently benefit only a limited number of learners and staff in Irish HEIs (HEA, 2023). As a result, there is a dearth of comprehensive evidence on IaH in the Irish HE context.

This research aimed to address this important gap, particularly considering the significant changes to the landscape of internationalisation that have emerged in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic and growing geopolitical uncertainty around the world. The increased global attention on internationalisation at home (IaH) and a notable focus within Ireland have informed this exploration since 2021. This sub-section summarises the discourse in each chapter that has shaped the study.

Chapter 1 introduced the subject of the thesis- *Embedding a culture of Internationalisation at Home (IaH)- Preparing for the changing context of higher education in Ireland*. It established the relevance of the study and articulated the aim and objectives of the research.

Chapter 2 presented a literature review for IaH from a global perspective examining the key rationales, enablers, challenges and strategies to implement IaH. Moreover, some existing frameworks were explored and the development of IaH during COVID-19 is elucidated.

Chapter 3 shifted its focus to Ireland, providing a literature review on the internationalisation of higher education in the country. It explored the developments in internationalisation, the limited scholarly discourse on IaH, and the increasing prominence of IaH in the strategic plans of Irish HEIs.

Chapter 4 described the theoretical framework for this study, which conceptualised IaH in the Irish HE context through theories of organisational and curriculum design and change management. In combination, this framework offered a unique yet comprehensive theoretical grounding for the study.

Chapter 5 outlined the research methodology and methodological considerations. Rooted in a constructivist ontological and interpretivist epistemological approach within a relativist metatheoretical framework, this study utilised a descriptive qualitative research design to address its aims and research questions. The theoretical framework's methodological rationale, research design, sample population, and EDI considerations for this study were adumbrated. Furthermore, a discussion of the data collection procedures and justification for the methods suited for this study was outlined. The ethical considerations were set forth, and the data analysis techniques were explained. Notably, the researcher reflected on their

role in the entire research process. Consequently, this study was situated through the verification strategies that establish the trustworthiness of this research, and the overall quality was addressed through Tracy's eight "big-tent" criteria for excellent qualitative research (2010) (*Appendix I*).

Chapter 6 presented the findings and discussion from the focus groups and semi-structured interviews. The findings provide strong evidence of the growing importance of IaH in Irish HEIs. However, there was a general consensus that IaH remains in the early stages of development within most of these institutions, even though notable progress has been made, albeit often without explicitly labelling it as IaH. Moreover, there was a regretful agreement that internationalisation is not sufficiently incentivised within Irish HEIs, highlighting the need for 'systemic awakening' to embed a culture of IaH. However, the hope rests on the potential of the senior leadership to drive this culture at various levels in the university, with IaH envisioned as a shared responsibility. Additionally, this chapter addresses the research aims and objectives, proposing an evidence-based working definition of IaH (*sub-section 6.4.2*), along with the IaH Content, Positioning, and Reflection (IaH CPR) framework (*Figures 28 and 29*), measures of success (*Table 12*) and incentives and recognition mechanisms (*Table 13*), which can guide HEIs in their efforts to embed a culture of IaH. The following sub-section delineates the theoretical and practical contributions of this study.

7.3 Theoretical and Practical Contributions

This study's theoretical contribution involves applying a distinctive combination of theories that provide a comprehensive perspective on IaH, which is not only integrated into curricula but also embedded in institutional values and campus life. As such, theories related to organisational design, curriculum design, and change management were employed (*Chapter 4*). These frameworks effectively addressed the research questions regarding the opportunities and challenges of cultivating a culture of IaH in Irish HEIs.

Organisational design theories, such as stakeholder identification and salience (Mitchell *et al.*, 1997), facilitated the identification of stakeholders and their respective salience, namely, power, legitimacy, and urgency in implementing IaH initiatives. This includes key stakeholders such as senior management, academic leaders, academic staff, international officers, learners, and policymakers. Furthermore, the concept of stakeholder culture (Jones *et al.*, 2007) highlighted the continuum between self-regarding and other-regarding cultures, which can inform the approach of Irish HEIs as they strive to embed IaH. For instance, the findings reveal instrumentalist or self-regarding cultures when engaging in IaH that rely on rewards, recognition and incentives to engage in internationalisation efforts. Presently,

policymakers and senior managers are beginning to strategically prioritise IaH and how IaH will develop in Irish HEIs remains to be seen.

Moreover, the job demands and resources framework (Bakker and Demerouti, 2017) sheds light on the motivations, or lack thereof, among institutional leadership, policymakers, and influencers, as well as staff and learner engagement in IaH. This framework introduced concepts such as burnout and engagement, emphasising the need for CPD, incentives, rewards, and recognition to create capacity, space and visibility for IaH initiatives for staff and learners.

From a curriculum design perspective, the conceptual framework for an internationalised curriculum (Leask, 2015) was employed. This framework provided insights into the internationalisation of formal, informal, and hidden curricula, conceptualising 'curriculum as a system' (Leask, 2022). Applying this framework highlighted the fragmented nature of practices within Irish HEIs and the necessity of investing further in the systematic integration of internationalisation across all disciplines.

Finally, change management theories were applied to address the second research question concerning strategies to embed a culture of IaH. The Organisational Culture Transformational Framework (Armenakis *et al.*, 2011) facilitated an assessment of the change readiness of Irish HEIs, as reflected in the strategic discourse surrounding IaH. This framework provided strategies for institutionalising IaH by embedding it across various faculties, schools, departments, and functions. Additionally, utilising systems thinking within the learning organisation framework (Senge, 1990) offered a systemic view for effectively embedding IaH throughout the institution, transforming fragmented components into a cohesive whole.

In addition to this distinctive theoretical pluralism, a key contribution of this study is the proposal of a working definition for embedding a culture of IaH. This definition is anchored in the widely cited definition of IaH (Beelen and Jones, 2015) but expands to encompass a university-wide, systems-based approach rather than being confined to the curriculum (*subsection 6.4.2*). An exclusive focus on the curricular aspect may have contributed to the misconception that IaH pertains only to the international office and academic staff. However, as the findings suggest, it can be crucial to recognise that embedding a culture of IaH must be acknowledged as a collective responsibility shared across different departments, schools and levels within the institution.

Moreover, the practical contributions of this study focused on a pragmatic, evidence-based guiding framework for cultivating a culture of IaH within Irish HEIs, thereby addressing the

final research objective of this study. The IaH Content, Positioning, and Reflection (CPR) framework is built upon existing literature, the theoretical framework, participant accounts, and the researcher's reflections (*Figures 28 and 29*). It aims to provide a comprehensive and systemic view of how IaH a culture of IaH can be embedded across the institution.

Furthermore, several participants emphasised the need for metrics to evaluate the success and impact of IaH initiatives. This research provides a tabular representation of the metrics that can assist HEIs in tracking progress and measuring impact through IaH (*Table 12*). Besides metrics, mechanisms to incentivise and reward good practices were also underscored and presented (*Table 13*).

In conclusion, this research provides targeted recommendations at both the institutional and national levels aimed at assisting HEIs in embedding a culture of IaH. These practical contributions align with the study's objective of presenting strategies to embed a culture of IaH and developing a guiding framework to support Irish HEIs in this endeavour.

7.4 Recommendations and Implications of Policy and Practice

This sub-section outlines recommendations aimed at influencing policy and practice at both institutional and national levels to cultivate a culture of Internationalisation at Home (IaH) based on the findings presented in *Chapter 6*. The findings suggest that Irish HEIs may benefit from a 'systemic awakening' to establish the necessary structures and support systems for embedding a culture of IaH in their institutions, reaching all learners and staff. This systemic embedding could be significantly enhanced through a collaborative approach between the leadership (top-down) and all staff and learners (bottom-up), promoting internationalisation across all levels. Furthermore, support at the national policy level can be crucial to advance and sustain IaH initiatives within the publicly funded Irish HEIs.

7.4.1 Institutional Level

While the rationale to engage in IaH often centres on the outcomes, such as the development of intercultural competence and global citizenship, rather than the input that IaH per se provides. However, participant accounts reveal that the perception of IaH as a relatively novel concept in Irish HE, in contrast to established terms such as internationalisation, mobility, or inclusion, stems from its terminology being symbolically obscured through various communication channels and bottom-up strategic planning within the institutions. Although numerous ongoing initiatives resonate with the principles of IaH, it can be imperative to make IaH more visible and leverage it as a strategic approach to cultivate the important graduate attribute of global citizenship at all levels within the institution.

Furthermore, while implementing IaH is acknowledged as a collective responsibility, its success and sustainability substantially depend on the support and commitment of the leadership within Irish HEIs, as indicated by the findings. The institutional leadership can consider exploring the following recommendations to engage staff and students meaningfully at all levels in internationalisation.

7.4.1.1 IaH in Institutional Strategic Planning

Irish HEIs can gain significantly by highlighting the importance of IaH within the institutional strategic plan and establishing a university-wide working group or management committee focused on this initiative. This group could draw on the expertise across stakeholder groups, such as senior leadership, academic and support services staff and learners at various levels, to gather valuable insights. It can also be beneficial to seek mentorship and representation on institutional committees from other Irish, European, or international HEIs that are advanced in their IaH journey.

Moreover, the impact of institutional strategic planning can be amplified if IaH is incorporated into the planning of faculties, schools, and departments, making it symbolically visible and emphasising its importance in achieving the broader goals of these entities. Additionally, the progress in IaH can be evaluated through specific metrics and indicators of progress, as outlined in *Table 12*. To this end, IaH can be positioned as one of the key strategic priorities embraced at both the top-down and bottom-up levels.

Furthermore, promoting a shared understanding of IaH within the institution is crucial. The working definition for embedding a culture of IaH (*sub-section 6.4.2*), alongside the IaH content, positioning, and reflection (IaH CPR) framework and continuum presented in *Figures (28) and (29)*, can provide an important reference point in this endeavour. Moreover, while succession planning was not explicitly highlighted in the findings, it can be of significant importance to ensure continuity for developing IaH initiatives into the future.

7.4.1.2 Space Creating Structures and Rewarding Mechanisms for IaH

In order to create structures and space for IaH, Irish HEIs should consider establishing roles such as Assistant Deans for Internationalisation or Assistant Heads of Department for Internationalisation within each faculty to enhance the internationalisation of the curriculum systemically. Furthermore, as emphasised earlier, it may be beneficial to make IaH a specific agenda item in faculty and school board meetings and meetings of support services staff to foster a culture of IaH.

Importantly, to encourage grassroots initiatives, it can be significantly beneficial to establish a dedicated department for IaH, such as an Intercultural and Global Learning Office. Ideally positioned within the hierarchical ambit of the Academic Affairs or the Registrar's Office, this department could liaise with the Teaching and Learning Office, the International/Global Engagement Office, faculty and school leaders, and the EDI office, among others, to develop and nurture capacity building and further advance the internationalisation agenda in a systemic way across the institution.

Although having a dedicated department for IaH can be advantageous, it is essential to recognise and reward effective practices and champions in IaH. This recognition can create space and encourage staff and learners to participate more actively in IaH initiatives. To incentivise involvement, as detailed in *Table 13*, rewards such as providing training and research funding linked to IaH, organising learning retreats with partner institutions or best practice HEIs abroad, offering course reductions, incorporating IaH into professional progression criteria, hosting award ceremonies to honour IaH champions, recognising global learning experiences on student transcripts, to mention a few can be implemented.

Moreover, investing in physical spaces and resources, such as global and intercultural lounges, can generate valuable opportunities for both Irish and international learners to collaborate and co-create cultural events, workshops, seminars, and festivals. These lounges appear to have a positive impact on the learner experience and can contribute to the development of intercultural competence in learners while enhancing the awareness and visibility of IaH on campus. Additionally, employing learners to work in these lounges could further enrich the overall experience.

Furthermore, it is essential to create policies and systems that support the recruitment of international staff in both academic and support services, as they can significantly enhance the internationalisation of the learner experience and contribute to the decolonisation of the curriculum. Lastly, investing in awareness-raising efforts to educate both the campus community and the local population about the potential of IaH in enriching their learning experiences, skills and competencies at the institution can contribute to enhanced engagement with IaH.

7.4.1.3 Investment in Capacity Building and Curriculum Development for IaH

The dedicated department for intercultural and global learning (or IaH) could liaise with the teaching and learning department to adopt structured CPD approaches in IoC. Rather than exclusively relying on intermittent CPD weeks, routinely offering one-on-one consultations with staff can amplify the embedding of IoC across disciplines. Furthermore, organising

common intercultural orientations/training for all learners and staff can promote inclusivity and understanding. Moreover, establishing staff communities of practice (CoPs) in this area could contribute to developing a culture for IaH.

For instance, a participant from one of the best practice HEIs in Europe shared insights from their experience of transitioning beyond CPD to establishing a teaching and learning global educators lab, which provides them with a platform for conducting action research on internationalisation with staff and learners. Initiatives such as these have the potential to not only enhance the intellectual capital on emerging topics and trends in internationalisation but also promote greater staff engagement, complementing the ongoing CPD initiatives. Irish HEIs could consider adopting a similar approach through their dedicated department for IaH.

Moreover, to enhance academic staff engagement with curriculum change, it can be beneficial to integrate IaH into the curriculum design and renewal processes. This approach can mitigate the perception of IaH as an additional workload, promoting a more collaborative and productive environment. Additionally, incorporating multidisciplinary approaches such as Universal Design for Learning (UDL), community-based learning, and co-designing the curriculum with learners can enhance embedding IaH more effectively.

Furthermore, leveraging the EUI, Erasmus+, and other collaborative partnerships and networks can be advantageous in developing internationalisation initiatives at home. This can include virtual internationalisation and enhancing teaching and learning experiences through joint initiatives while systematically assessing their impact.

It is also worthwhile to invest in CPD and international exposure for support services staff, as this may significantly influence the hidden curriculum and shape the experiences of learners and staff. Finally, it can be important to acknowledge various forms of internationalisation experiences on learners' transcripts, whether abroad or at home, to engage them actively in this process.

7.4.1.4 Purposeful Collaboration between Irish and International Learners

Irish HEIs need to be 'intentional' to encourage a collaborative dynamic between Irish and international learners, whether through formal curriculum elements (such as modules and group work), informal curriculum initiatives (including event organisation and learner-centric scheduling), or hidden curriculum opportunities (such as culturally sensitive communication and global referencing conventions, among others).

Furthermore, to nurture collaboration, create space and foster inclusivity among domestic Irish learners, including those with international ancestry or migrant backgrounds and international learners, it is essential for HEIs to implement unconscious bias, intercultural training sessions, and common orientation programmes. These initiatives can contribute to institutional EDI efforts, which have predominantly focused on staff, by actively engaging learners in the process.

7.4.1.5 Funding for IaH Initiatives

Lastly and most importantly, seeking avenues for funding IaH initiatives are crucial for its sustenance. While funding remains a critical challenge in Irish HE, institutions can leverage the income generated through other internationalisation initiatives. Additionally, there is potential to secure funding for IaH through other national programmes or schemes. These can include the European Universities Alliances Initiative, the National Integration Fund, the National Access Plan, the National Forum for Teaching and Learning, Global Citizenship Education grants, and Languages Connect, among others, as highlighted in *Chapter 3 (sub-section 3.6)*.

7.4.2 National Level

While the Irish government's international talent and innovation strategy – *Global Citizens 2030* (DFHERIS, 2024), recognises the importance of IaH, the Irish HEIs can benefit significantly from accompanying policies that address funding, accountability mechanisms, and enhancing visibility for IaH to align the national strategic rhetoric with on-ground reality. This sub-section delineates these aspects.

7.4.2.1 Funding Mechanisms for IaH

Funding in Irish HE poses a significant challenge for publicly funded HEIs when pursuing various initiatives related to IaH, as outlined in *Chapters (3) and (6)*. The existing employment control framework, inadequate staff-to-student ratios, and the increasing national and international demand for Irish HE suggests that current resources are insufficient to provide an internationalised learning experience for every learner enrolled in an Irish HEI. Although institutions value their autonomy in making decisions, this does not necessarily equate to robust support for IaH initiatives, which can be perceived as competing with other established priorities, including recruitment of international learners, learner mobility abroad as well as EDI and sustainability, which have gained considerable traction in recent times.

To effectively advance IaH, there is a pressing need for explicit, targeted strategies and policies that can facilitate its practical implementation, as IaH often becomes overshadowed

in broader policy dialogues. Therefore, embedding a culture of IaH would greatly benefit from dedicated funding initiatives to promote intercultural and global learning opportunities for all learners, irrespective of their circumstances.

Additionally, existing funding schemes and policies often lack explicit references to IaH, leaving potential applicants uncertain about the eligibility of their IaH projects for support. Whilst IaH is recognised as one of the important aspects of the Irish government's international talent and innovation strategy *Global Citizens 2030*, developing a dedicated policy that outlines the funding model or scheme would be advantageous in assisting Irish HEIs in meeting the strategic goals.

Moreover, explicitly linking IaH to current funding channels in other strategies and policies of the government, as outlined in *Chapter 3 (Table 2)*, can yield positive outcomes. As such, national support appears to have a considerable impact in driving IaH, as evidenced by the experience of the staff at the best practice HEIs in this study (*Chapter 6*), where they emphasised that having some level of national funding support or subsidies significantly contributed to advancing their IaH projects and strategy within their institutions.

Importantly, it is essential to create a level playing field for the technological Universities (TUs) through additional funding support for internationalisation, as many of these HEIs are still in the consolidation phase following their merger. The additional funding provision can contribute to learners gaining international exposure from Irish HE, regardless of their choice of institution and build TU's capacity for IaH. Currently, learners and staff at the TUs express lower satisfaction levels in internationalisation than their peers at traditional universities. Furthermore, reviewing the current workload model and sabbatical opportunities for academic staff at the TUs can be necessary, as these factors significantly influence their capacity to engage in IaH initiatives, as evidenced in *Chapter 6*.

7.4.2.2 Accountability Measures for IaH

Besides the funding mechanisms, it can be important to incorporate IaH into the institutional accountability measures, particularly through the HEA Compact Systems Performance Framework for 2023-28 and the Quality and Qualifications Ireland (QQI) requirements. By doing so, Irish HEIs can better synchronise their priorities in internationalisation with these critical quality reporting standards.

7.4.2.3 Visibility for IaH

The findings in *Chapter 6* indicated that IaH is not well known and understood across and within Irish HEIs due to insufficient promotion and visibility. Although it appears that Irish HEIs are making internal efforts to address this challenge, the 'Education in Ireland' brand at the national level has the potential to explicitly position IaH as a significant and distinctive proposition of Irish HEIs, thereby building the reputation and uniqueness of Irish HE. These efforts can be further strengthened by establishing a dedicated webpage featuring valuable resources, frameworks, toolkits, best practice examples and research related to IaH within Irish HEIs. Such a resource would help build credibility abroad among stakeholders, including prospective learners, researchers, and partners showcasing the progressive nature of the Irish HE system.

Lastly, establishing national communities of practice (CoPs) and networks focused on IaH can be advantageous, providing both traditional universities and the TUs with opportunities to connect, share best practices, and address common challenges. The establishment of the Irish Association for International Education (IAIE) in 2025, supported by the Department of Further and Higher Education, Research, Innovation and Science (DFHERIS), the Higher Education Authority (HEA) and 'Education in Ireland' signifies a commendable step in this direction and can position Ireland as one of the leading voices in internationalisation in HE, including IaH. Importantly, leveraging the platform through Ireland's forthcoming Presidency of the Council of the European Union in 2026 presents a unique opportunity to showcase its thought leadership in IaH at the European and international level. *Table 14* below summarises key recommendations and implications for policy and practice for embedding a culture of IaH in Irish HEIs.

Table 14: Summary-Recommendations and Implications for Policy and Practice

Recommendations	Core Themes	Recommendations and Implications
Institutional	IaH in institutional strategic planning	Include IaH explicitly in the institutional strategic plan and establish a dedicated university-wide working group or management committee, ensuring diverse representation.
		Invite external experts to serve as mentors for the IaH committee.
		Develop a shared understanding of IaH and promote it widely throughout the university community. This study's proposed working definition (<i>sub-section 6.4.2</i>) and IaH CPR framework (<i>Figures 28 and 29</i>) can serve as valuable reference points.
		Incorporate IaH into the planning processes of faculties, schools, and departments, as well as in public speeches and events.
		Consider succession planning to ensure the continuity of IaH initiatives.
	Space creating structures and rewarding mechanisms for IaH	Establish a dedicated department for IaH, such as an Intercultural and Global Learning Office.
		Create roles such as Assistant Deans for Internationalisation or Assistant Heads of Department for Internationalisation within each faculty.
		Include IaH as a specific agenda item in faculty and school board meetings, as well as in meetings of support services staff.
		Recognise and reward effective practices and champions in IaH. Some suggestions from this study, highlighted in <i>Tables 12 and 13</i> , can serve as reference points.
		Invest in physical spaces and resources, such as global and intercultural lounges, where Irish and international learners can collaborate on IaH initiatives.

Table 14: Summary-Recommendations and Implications for Policy and Practice

Recommendation	Core Themes	Recommendations and Implications
Institutional	Space creating structures and rewarding mechanisms for IaH	Develop policies and systems that support the recruitment of international staff for both academic and support services positions.
		Engage in awareness-raising efforts to educate the campus community and the local population about the potential and impact of IaH.
	Investment in capacity building and curriculum development for IaH	Embed IaH into the curriculum design and renewal processes.
		Incorporate multidisciplinary and transdisciplinary approaches such as Universal Design for Learning (UDL), community-based learning, and co-designing the curriculum with learners.
		Adopt structured Continuous Professional Development (CPD) strategies for internationalising the curriculum (IoC). Instead of relying solely on periodic CPD weeks, provide regular one-on-one consultations with staff based on their needs.
		Invest in CPD and provide international exposure for support services staff, as this can significantly influence the hidden curriculum and shape the experiences of both learners and staff.
		Organise common intercultural orientations/training for all learners and staff to promote inclusivity and understanding.
		Establish staff communities of practice (CoPs) in IaH.
		Create a teaching and learning global educators lab that offers a platform for staff and researchers to conduct action research on internationalisation in collaboration with both staff and learners.
		Leverage initiatives such as the European Universities Alliances, Erasmus+, and other collaborative partnerships and networks to enhance the development of IaH.

Table 14: Summary-Recommendations and Implications for Policy and Practice

Recommendations	Core Themes	Recommendations and Implications
Institutional	Purposeful collaboration between Irish and international learners	Create intentional opportunities for both Irish and international learners to collaborate effectively through formal, informal, and hidden curricula.
		Implement training sessions on unconscious bias and intercultural awareness and orientation programs in a shared space that includes Irish learners (including those of international ancestry and migrant backgrounds) and international students.
		Prioritise efforts in Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion (EDI) for all learners.
	Funding for IaH initiatives	Repurpose some of the income generated from other internationalisation initiatives, such as recruitment, to support initiatives related to IaH.
Apply for funding from various national funding programs, including the European Universities Alliances Initiative, the National Integration Fund, the National Access Plan, the National Forum for Teaching and Learning, Global Citizenship Education grants, and Languages Connect, among others listed in <i>Table 2</i> .		
National	Funding mechanisms for IaH	Supplement the Global Citizens 2030 strategy with a dedicated policy and funding scheme specifically linked to IaH and/or make IaH explicit in other existing national policies and funding schemes.
		Create a level playing field for the Technological Universities by providing additional funding support for internationalisation, improving staff workload models, and establishing sabbatical arrangements.
		Abolish the Employment Control Framework to create space for staff in Irish HEIs to engage more effectively with IaH initiatives.

Table 14: Summary-Recommendations and Implications for Policy and Practice

Recommendations	Core Themes	Recommendations and Implications
National	Accountability measures for IaH	Integrate IaH into the institutional accountability measures, specifically through the HEA Compact Systems Performance Framework for 2023-2028 and the Quality and Qualifications Ireland (QQI) requirements.
	Visibility for IaH	Leverage the 'Education in Ireland' brand to explicitly position IaH as a significant and distinctive proposition of Irish HEIs.
		Create and maintain a dedicated webpage on government departments/agencies' websites that features valuable resources, frameworks, toolkits, best practice examples and research related to IaH within Irish HEIs.
		Establish national communities of practice (CoPs) and networks focused on IaH.
		Strengthen Ireland's position in internationalisation (including IaH) by harnessing the platform of Ireland's Presidency of the Council of the European Union in 2026 and the newly established Irish Association for International Education (IAIE).

7.5 Limitations of the Study

In light of the paucity of literature on IaH within the Irish HE context, this study provides a valuable contribution to building a comprehensive knowledge base on the development of IaH in Irish HEIs. It engages various stakeholders from both traditional and technological universities while also considering the perspectives of policymakers and influencers. Additionally, where appropriate, the narratives have been enriched with insights from best-practice HEIs in Europe and the UK.

Whilst the aim has been to critique the development of IaH in Irish HEIs and to develop a guiding framework for embedding a culture of IaH that reflects participants' viewpoints, supported by the literature and theoretical constructs of this study, there are a few limitations. Firstly, this study captures the perspectives of only two traditional and two technological universities. It, therefore, cannot be considered representative of the Irish HE sector as a whole. Furthermore, the research focused exclusively on publicly funded HEIs in Ireland. Concomitantly, although the best practice HEIs in Europe and the UK may have offered valuable insights, these cannot be generalised to their stakeholders, institutions or national contexts. Their inclusion served primarily to explore additional strategies for realising a culture of IaH in Irish HEIs.

Secondly, data collection from Irish HEIs was conducted online without physical visits to the institutions. Due to logistical constraints and ease of scheduling, focus group discussions with learners were also held virtually. Moreover, all participants from Irish HEIs in the semi-structured interviews opted for online participation, citing their evolved habits from COVID-19 and maintaining that it was a 'sustainable way' to engage. Despite the online format, the multidimensional perspectives provided by different stakeholders in each institution added depth to the narratives and contributed to the credibility of the findings.

Lastly, there is a possibility of selection and unconscious bias that may have influenced the research design and outcomes. The chosen participants in this study were those who expressed interest and engaged with internationalisation within their HEIs. As such, the perspectives of individuals who may be indifferent, sceptical, or resistant to IaH could be underrepresented. Moreover, the researcher's own background in internationalisation may have influenced the framing of the topic guide as well as the interpretation of the findings. In order to mitigate the bias, the researcher has made a conscious effort through reflexive journaling and member checking; however, these biases cannot be entirely eliminated.

Nonetheless, the researcher has strived to present a comprehensive view of 'IaH as a system' within Irish HE, which is elucidated in the findings and discussion in *Chapter 6*. The resulting evidence-based working definition (*sub-section 6.4.2*) and IaH content, positioning and reflection (CPR) framework (*Figures 28 and 29*) are designed to support Irish HEIs in their efforts to embed a culture of IaH in their institutions.

7.6 Suggestions for Future Research

Whilst this study offers insight into the developments of IaH within some Irish HEIs, a thorough review of the literature, data collection, and researcher's reflections reveal several areas for further exploration and recommendations for future research in this field, which are presented in this sub-section.

This research suggests that additional efforts are needed to realise internationalisation through the formal curriculum in Irish HEIs. Disciplinary investigations on internationalising the curriculum (IoC), particularly in relation to professional practice requirements, can be beneficial. Importantly, examining the relationship between IaH and learners' employability prospects and employer preferences could yield valuable insights into the impact of IaH.

Furthermore, the findings indicated that the support services staff have been neglected as one of the key stakeholders in an institution's internationalisation process. To this end, developing a longitudinal evidence base that links the professional development of support services staff to their impact on achieving their institution's internationalisation goals would be of great value. Additionally, longitudinal studies examining the progression of staff from 'unknown' to 'ally' in IaH would provide substantial insights.

Another avenue for future research could explore measuring 'intercultural and global citizenship' competencies, which are proposed as a core outcome for learners engaging in IaH across various stages, particularly within the context of their graduate attributes. Furthermore, there are several underexplored topics related to internationalisation in Irish HE, such as the hidden curriculum and its effects on engagement among learners and staff in internationalisation, the experiences of international staff with IaH, and the effect of virtual internationalisation approaches such as Collaborative Online International Learning (COIL), Virtual Exchange (VE), or Blended Intensive Programs (BIPs) on teaching and learning. Finally, studies evaluating the impact of the European Universities Alliances (EUA) on IaH would also be worth pursuing.

7.7 Reflection and Reflexivity

Bringing an academic and practitioner perspective from India to this research, my exploration of qualitative inquiry within Irish HE has been a transformative experience. While collaborating with international colleagues was a routine aspect of my job, studying abroad at this stage of my career and life has presented a markedly different experience, particularly in the context of my doctoral research.

For instance, the introduction to self-reflection and reflexivity during the initial stages of my research has proven immensely invaluable. I recognised the importance of maintaining a journal to capture my impressions and evolving insights. I sought feedback from supervisors and critical peers, all of whom have significantly enriched my research journey. This process has prompted me to critically examine my own assumptions, unlearn previous understandings, and embrace a new system and way of being. As a result, I have engaged in deeper reflection on the literature and discussions I encountered at various events and conferences and, more importantly, with the participants in my study.

Moreover, during the data collection phase, I was captivated by the varied perspectives of different stakeholders. I noted hesitation around engaging in discussions on IaH, marked by unsurprising connotations of mobility, elitism, and feelings of nationalism that sometimes overshadowed the dialogue on internationalisation. Yet, I also encountered some staff members actively challenging the status quo around internationalisation. My deep engagement with the data coincided with what I would describe as a 'spiritual awakening,' leading me to recognise and appreciate the 'whole' picture. By integrating participants' insights and my intuition to interpret the data, I enhanced the reflexive thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2021) with a heuristic approach (Moustakas, 1990), adding depth and richness to my interpretations.

As I progressed in this research and on my spiritual awakening journey, I also realised that idolising best practices in IaH from afar may not yield the desired outcomes. As such, no system or institution has perfected IaH yet, although some may be more advanced in varying respects. This epiphany altered my initial perception that IaH is novel to Ireland, revealing the vast potential in the participant reflections. Irish HEIs exhibit a quiet yet transformative capacity to advance internationalisation.

Much like my spiritual awakening in Waterford, I have come to believe that the HEIs involved in my study may require a 'systemic awakening' to recognise and consolidate effective practices in IaH, challenge existing norms and understandings, create systems and processes that speak to each other and enhance investment in preparing citizens (learners

and staff) for a multicultural society and world. This transformation must transcend the notions of diversity and embody the need to develop a global mindset emphasising inclusion, peace, and solutions to shared global and local challenges. The IaH CPR framework proposed in *Chapter 6* of this study (*Figures 28 and 29*) can be a valuable reference in this endeavour. In essence, these experiences and reflections have helped me refine my critical thinking and problem-solving skills, enabling me to step back, reflect, and respond, embracing the 'whole,' a philosophy mirrored in this research.

7.8 Closing Remarks

In the context of increasingly polarised societies, rising nationalist sentiments, conflicts, and the challenges posed by climate change and public health crises like COVID-19, this study and some of its outputs, such as the working definition (*sub-section 6.4.2*) and the Internationalisation at Home Content, Positioning and Reflection (IaH CPR) framework (*Figures 28 and 29*), emphasise the need for nurturing intercultural competence and global citizenship at Irish HEIs. *Embedding a culture of internationalisation at home in Irish HEIs* must be viewed as an investment in a future characterised by inclusion, peace, justice, and opportunity, as the realities unfolding worldwide are not disconnected from Ireland, which continues to focus on enhancing its reputation and distinctiveness as a welcoming nation for international learners, talent, and innovation. As one staff member from a best practice HEI in Europe (BP HEI 1) aptly states, *'We can't opt out. Internationalisation is an inevitable part of our lives.'*

Essentially, this study develops a knowledge base in the Irish HE context by conceptualising 'IaH as a system' and emphasising a framework to support Irish HEIs in advancing internationalisation for every learner and staff. The study successfully met its research objectives of identifying both the opportunities and challenges associated with cultivating a culture of IaH and offering strategies for embedding such a culture in Irish HEIs. Furthermore, this study offers an opportunity to engage with some of the assertions presented in the government's international talent and innovation strategy, Global Citizens 2030 (DFHERIS, 2024) which highlights that *'more attention is also needed on internationalisation-at-home opportunities for learners who cannot travel'* (p.18) and *'we (DFHERIS) will work closely with Irish HEIs to support the development of innovative internationalisation-at-home experiences for learners that cannot undertake physical travel. We will develop our evidence base to analyse participation patterns across institutions, programmes and learner profiles to identify areas which need particular attention'* (p.20).

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APPENDICES

Appendix A: IaH in Practice

Mediterranean Region (Sirca, Ben Malek and Hammoud, 2023)

- Intercultural competence (ICC) in learners- focus on ICC theories and models for integrating ICC as a learning outcome in the formal curriculum.
- IaH in institutional structures, procedures and policies as an HEI Strategy and Action Plan that involves every stakeholder in the institution: students, academic and administrative staff, and management.
- Different approaches to integrate domestic and international students through social media, telecollaborative partnerships, e-learning (Liaw, 2006), film, theatre, music, or literature, comparative teaching, simulating customs, guided group activities, learner diaries, questionnaires, tandem exchange, peer teaching, cross-cultural study projects, speakers from other languages and ethnographic projects.
- Pre-service and In-service training faculty and administrative staff on intercultural communication, intergroup contact through Cooperative and Collaborative Learning, pedagogical approaches, or school institutional policies.
- Service-learning projects foster community links and partnerships by inviting visitors of different cultural backgrounds to come into contact with students.
- Intercultural and inclusive pedagogical approaches, such as encouraging students to reflect critically on their intercultural experiences and cultural affiliations and belonging through Autobiographies of Intercultural Encounters (AIE) (Byram et al., 2009) and the Autobiography of Intercultural Encounters through Visual Media (IEVM) (Barrett et al., 2013).
- Project-based learning.

Australia (Leask, 2015, 2009)

Formal curriculum:

- Questionnaire on internationalising the curriculum focused on academic staff's approach to teaching, thinking about the programme, teaching team's functions to support the development of intercultural and global attributes, aims, goals and learning outcomes, learning activities and assessment tasks
- Self-reflection by students and staff

Informal curriculum:

- A learning guide for Australian students is titled "What Do I Call You? —An Introduction to Chinese, Malay and Hindu Names"
- Online peer-mentoring system
- Conversation groups for international students to develop their social language skills throughout the academic year
- Cross-cultural lunches
- Business mates mentoring scheme
- Students experience questionnaires

Appendix A: IaH in Practice

UK (University of Kent, Manning and Marku, 2021)

- Internationalising welcome/induction and cross-community exchange such as Global hangouts, World Fest events, World Fest Bitesize Fund, Global Learning Online, Grad Goal and Global Officer Leadership Development Programme
- Curriculum Internationalisation projects such as Internationalisation clause in modules, curriculum internationalisation handbook, global engagement modules, language express, Advance HE IaH & Curriculum Internationalisation Network and IaH Conferences
- Sharing and promoting institutional internationalisation through Kent global newsletters, Think Kent document series and video lectures, Future Learn campus and Kent global showcase

India (Piplani-Kapur and Kirloskar, 2023 and Yeravdekar and Piplani-Kapur, 2022)

- Institutional policy and support for IaH
- Internationalised learning outcomes, a compulsory module on 'Vashudhaiva Kutumbakam- The world is one family' fostering global citizenship
- Embedding COIL in core curricula
- Floating credits for short internationalisation experiences at home, engaging interculturally with local community and international organisations

- Internationalising learning and university experience on campus through international student councils, student think tanks and networks, E- Academies on internationalisation for students and staff (capacity building), Beyond borders-Work from home international internship programmes, E-symposiums, guest lectures (physical/virtual) by international faculty, engaging diplomatic missions in various events, joint conferences with international partners, socialisation events, celebrating international festivals, and an annual conference on IaH
- Active participation with national and international government schemes such as SPARC, GIAN, Erasmus+, events, and conferences fostering global south and north connections
- Connecting IaH from K-12 schools to university projects and outreach programmes such as SCOPE

Sweden (Weissova, 2021)

In-House activities:

- Intercultural perspectives in curricula and teaching methods
- Utilising cultural diversity in classrooms
- External monitoring of the subject area
- Courses with an international focus and international learning objectives for all students
- Considering travel and comparing perspectives through experience
- Certificate of International Merits (CIM)
- Intercultural student organisations
- Offering English courses

Outside engagement:

- Students/staff from abroad as a source for IaH
- Seminar series with international lecturers
- Collaboration and projects with colleagues from other countries
- Acting as contact person/buddy for international students/lecturers/partners
- Receive international students

Digital Technology:

- Virtual exchanges
- Carrying research projects with colleagues from other countries
- Online weeks on different disciplines with other countries

Appendix A: IaH in Practice

Finland (Welcome, Hoffman, and Silvonen, 2019)

Formal curricula:

- Domestic students actively participate in one or two courses with international exchange students as part of the core curriculum, with an intentional focus on facilitating intercultural interaction among the students.
- Embedding language and communication modules on global topics in the core curricula
- Pedagogical training for teachers to develop teaching methods and navigate a multicultural classroom
- Virtual exchange, mobility and online courses with students/partners/lecturers/speakers from other countries
- Mixed study groups and joint projects between domestic and international students
- Well-defined mobility window in degree programs; if mobility is not possible, alternatives at home are substituted (taking a course in intercultural communication and taking a course with international exchange students)

Formal curricula:

- Café Lingua, where local and international students can meet and learn different languages
- International summer school offered by the Finnish degree program encourages all students to participate with international guests.
- Family friendship program: matching international students with local families
- Positive marketing/communication of IaH opportunities and value
- Inviting students to participate in international research projects
- A certificate program developed for administrative staff (who work with international staff and students) consisting of language and intercultural courses
- When an international opponent participates in a dissertation defence, in addition to the defence, they are invited to give a public presentation or workshop on their research
- Finnish students are tutors for international students

The Netherlands (The Hague Internationalisation at Home-THIAH, Claudia and Louw, 2022; NUFFIC, n.d.)

- Course content- international comparison of a subject, global or international subject, international/foreign case studies, cross-cultural/ intercultural communication, skills or collaboration-based assessments, online collaborative project, community outreach in the local environment
- Languages of instruction
- Pedagogy and teaching of foreign literature, literature in different foreign languages, other internationally oriented materials, international classroom setting, use of local knowledge and experience from students, group work in class with mixed groups, intercultural learning in group work/projects, shared supervision of students with lecturers from external institutions abroad

- Staff composition- full-time lecturers from abroad, international guest lecturers, live-streamed/recorded lectures from lecturers abroad
- Learning outcomes- explicitly formulated international and/or intercultural learning outcomes
- Informal curriculum- buddy programmes, celebrating events and festivals of other countries, local community inclusion, extracurricular activities with international companies and/or organisations

Appendix B: Key Milestones in Higher Education and Internationalisation Timeline at a Glance

Dominated by the traditional universities

• PRE 1970s

1970

Establishes *Regional Technical Colleges (RTCs)*

Establishes *Higher Education Authority (HEA)*

• 1972

1987

Joins European Commission's *Erasmus exchange*

Redesignates RTCs as *Institutes of Technology (IoTs)*

• 199

1995

Enters *Celtic Tiger* phase of rapid economic expansion

Abolishes fees in third-level education

• 1996

1997

Lays foundation of the Irish HE system

Establishes *Irish Universities Association (IUA)*

1999

Signatory to the *Bologna Declaration*

Appendix B: Key Milestones in Higher Education and Internationalisation Timeline at a Glance

Appendix B: Key Milestones in Higher Education and Internationalisation Timeline at a Glance

Appendix C: Gatekeeper Research Pack (Focus Groups)

Nidhi Piplani Kapur <nidhipiplani.kapur@postgrad.wit.ie>

Request for Permission to Access Student Participants from [REDACTED] for PhD Study

Nidhi Piplani Kapur <nidhipiplani.kapur@postgrad.wit.ie>

16 May 2023 at 14:58

To: [REDACTED]

Dear [REDACTED],

I hope this email finds you well. My name is Nidhi Piplani Kapur, and I am a PhD student at the South East Technological University (SETU), Waterford. I am writing to seek your permission and support to access student participants from [REDACTED] for my research project.

The project I am working on, titled "Embedding a culture of 'Internationalisation at Home' (IaH) - Preparing for the changing context of Higher Education in Ireland," is funded by the Irish Research Council.

The main aim of this research is to explore the opportunities and challenges in fostering a culture of internationalisation within Irish higher education institutions, based on the perspectives of the participants.

I am pleased to inform you that I have already obtained ethical approval from the South East Technological University Research Ethics Committee (Reference No: SETU2022REC0003). The [REDACTED] Ethics Committee has accepted the ethical approval obtained from SETU for my research project and has guided me to reach out to you to access student participants. I have attached a copy of the approval letter from SETU for your reference.

For my study, I am seeking permission to access four student participants from [REDACTED]. These participants will consist of a mix of undergraduate and postgraduate students, including both Irish and international students. The data collection will involve conducting online focus groups, which are planned to take place between September and October 2023.

In support of my request, I have attached the following documents for your consideration:

- Gatekeeper Research Pack
- Participant Research Pack
- Letter for Participants
- Study Poster for Participants
- Topic Guide

These documents provide detailed information about the research project, the role of the gatekeeper, and the participation requirements for student participants. The study poster is designed to attract potential participants and provide an overview of the research. The topic guide outlines the themes and questions that will be discussed during the focus group sessions.

I am aware that your role is a busy one, and I respectfully ask you to consider assisting me by sharing the attached study materials with your students. Their participation in this study will involve joining an online focus group session on Zoom, lasting approximately one hour and fifteen minutes.

To ensure a smooth process, I would like to invite you to a brief online meeting where I can clarify any questions you may have about the study. This briefing meeting is optional.

If you agree to support this research, I kindly request that you fill, sign, and return the attached gatekeeper consent form to me at nidhipiplani.kapur@postgrad.wit.ie.

I appreciate your consideration of my request, and I look forward to hearing from you.

Kind regards,

Nidhi Piplani Kapur

Nidhi Piplani Kapur (She/Her)

IRC PhD Scholar- Internationalisation at Home
South East Technological University (SETU)
Cork Road Campus - Waterford X91 KEOK - Ireland

IRISH RESEARCH COUNCIL
An Chomhairle um Thaighde in Éirinn
www.research.ie

Gatekeeper Research Pack

Project Title	Embedding a culture of ‘Internationalisation at Home’ Preparing for the changing context of Higher Education in Ireland
Researcher	Ms Nidhi Piplani Kapur PhD Scholar-Internationalisation at Home Email Address: nidhipiplani.kapur@postgrad.wit.ie
Primary Supervisor	Dr Don O’Neill Head of Department of Humanities South East Technological University (SETU), Waterford, Ireland Email Address: Don.ONeill@setu.ie
Co-Supervisors	Dr Helen Murphy Head, School of Education and Lifelong Learning South East Technological University (SETU), Waterford, Ireland Email Address: Helen.Murphy@setu.ie Dr Suzanne Denieffe Head of School of Humanities South East Technological University (SETU), Waterford, Ireland Email Address: Suzanne.Denieffe@setu.ie
Funding	Irish Research Council
SETU Ethical Approval Reference Number	SETU2022REC0003
Data Controllers	South East Technological University (SETU)
Data Protection Officer	Data Protection Officer SETU Cork Road Waterford +353 51 302608 dataprotection@setu.ie

Project Funded by

What is the purpose of the project?

In Irish third-level education, traditionally, a small minority of students have benefited from an international mobility experience as part of their studies. This project will explore ways to internationalise the student experience through 'Internationalisation at Home' (IaH), defined as 'the purposeful integration of international and intercultural dimensions into the formal and informal curriculum for all students within domestic learning environments' (Beelen& Jones, 2015).

The primary purpose of this research is to create a framework for IaH in the Irish higher education context that helps HEIs in Ireland to foster the embedding of a culture of internationalisation into the curriculum. The study will draw on the findings that have investigated the challenges and opportunities presented by the participants in this study.

Why has my institution been invited to take part?

The insights and experience your institution participants offer will help identify the challenges and pathways to create a framework for IaH in an Irish higher education context. It will enable the development and fostering of global competencies in students in Irish HEIs through the curriculum.

Does my institution have to take part?

Participation in this research is voluntary. You and the participants from your institution are under no obligation to participate. If you decide to nominate participants for this research, you will be asked to sign a gatekeeper consent form as attached below. The participants, too, will need to sign a participant consent form, as attached in the Participant Research Pack, if they agree to participate.

What does participation in this project entail?

Type of Participants Needed

Students

Number of Participants Needed from [REDACTED]

Four

Method of Data Collection

Focus Group (Refer to the attached Topic Guide)

Time required from the Participant

Briefing (scheduled any day prior to conducting the focus group at a time that is convenient to the participant) - 10 minutes

Focus Group -1 Hour and 15 minutes

Venue for Briefing and Focus Group

Briefing -Online (on Zoom)

Focus Group- Online (on Zoom)

If you are in agreement, we would greatly appreciate your support in recruiting **students** at [REDACTED] as suitable participants for this study who meet the criterion in the table below

Participant Selection Criterion

Students

-
1. Full-time Undergraduate and Postgraduate degree Students (a mix of Undergraduate and postgraduate students - Irish and International).
 2. Second year or above in their educational programmes.
 3. Eighteen years or older.
 4. Gender Balance, if possible.
 5. Students who are comfortable keeping their cameras ON and with the recording of the online focus group for note-taking purposes.

-
1. Vulnerable Students.
 2. New Students (first year of programme).
 3. Part-time or Certificate Students.
 4. Students who are uncomfortable keeping their cameras ON and with the recording of the online focus group for note-taking purposes.

Project Funded by

If you agree to support this research, the following outlines your role:

- Attend an **optional** ten-minute briefing meeting through Zoom to understand the project, type of participants needed and get answers to your queries.
- Carefully consider the documents and return the signed gatekeeper consent form to the researcher at nidhipiplani.kapur@postgrad.wit.ie
- Distribute the participant research pack that includes Participant Information Leaflet, Consent Form and Topic Guide to the potential participants.
- Re-distribute information if needed.

Are there any Expenses and /or Payments involved?

There are no expenses or payments for participation in the focus groups.

What are the benefits of participating?

It is anticipated that insight and knowledge produced from the findings of this study will contribute to shaping higher education policy in Ireland. The participant's experiences and insights will help develop a framework that will improve the internationalised outcomes for higher education.

What are the risks associated with participating?

There is a minimal potential risk of participants disclosing the discussions outside the group. However, this is unexpected for mature adults participating in the discussions. This risk will be minimised through the confidentiality clause in the consent forms. Due care will be taken as participants will be anonymised through codes, and the guidelines for focus groups, protecting the anonymity of the participants, will be announced at the start. The privacy and confidentiality of the participants and data collected will be maintained.

Should the participant from the focus groups experience discomfort, the participant can inform the researcher- Nidhi Piplani Kapur and withdraw from the study without being affected. The researcher will also guide the participant towards the student support systems available at [REDACTED]

What are the limitations to the researcher's confidentiality?

If the participant discloses something unexpected that raises concern about risk or harm to others because a participant discloses criminal behaviours, events or intentions they have engaged in or have knowledge of, the researcher will be under a legal and moral duty to report this incident. Under these circumstances, the researcher will be required to give evidence or reveal documents, which may make it impossible for certain information to be kept confidential.

Can participants withdraw from the study?

Participation in the research study is voluntary, and the participant can withdraw before or during the focus group. The participant in the focus groups can amend or withdraw their transcript up to two months after the focus group has been conducted by contacting the researcher at nidhipiplani.kapur@postgrad.wit.ie

Who will have access to the data from this research study?

The data in the form of focus groups will be collected by the researcher – Nidhi Piplani Kapur. Her supervisory team will access the pseudonymised data- Dr Don O'Neill, Dr Helen Murphy, and Dr Suzanne Denieffe. The data is confidential and will be anonymised. The data will not be made available to any third parties. The researcher will decline any request regarding data access by third parties.

What will happen to the results from this study?

The research outputs produced will be published in the thesis, research publications, conferences and dissemination events, etc. The results so published will be anonymous, and no person or organisation will be identified. Findings will be based on the information provided by the participants and include their direct quotations without revealing their identity.

Once the research study is completed, any research/project related data will fall under the responsibility of the Chair of the Joint School (Humanities and Education) Postgrad Research Board at SETU, where it will be securely held until destroyed at the end of their 10-year data retention period. At the end of the research study, the PhD Thesis will be available in the SETU library. If you wish to access this, this can be done by accessing: <http://repository.wit.ie/>

If you agree to support this research, please sign and return the consent form below.

GATEKEEPER CONSENT FORM

Title of Project: Embedding a culture of 'Internationalisation at Home'- Preparing for the changing context of Higher Education in Ireland

Name of Researcher: Nidhi Piplani Kapur

Please tick to confirm your understanding of the study and that you are happy for your institution to take part.

You voluntarily agree to allow access to your staff and facilities (if needed) to execute the data collection process for this study.

Please tick the boxes and sign below:

1. I confirm that I have read and understood the information provided for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions, and have these answered satisfactorily.
2. I understand that the participation of our institution and students in the research is voluntary and that the participants are free to withdraw at any time before or during the study without giving a reason.
3. I understand that in the circumstance that requires re-recruiting a participant for this study, I agree to re-distribute the information leaflet, topic guide, and consent form to the potential participants.
4. I agree that our institution and students will participate in the above study.

Signature

Date

Signature

Date

Nidhi Piplani Kapur
Researcher

We will be grateful if you could return the signed Gatekeeper Consent Form to the researcher at nidhipiplani.kapur@postgrad.wit.ie

Embedding a culture of 'Internationalisation at Home'
Preparing for the changing context of Higher Education in Ireland

We Want to Hear from you!!

The Focus Group

Approximately One hour and fifteen minutes in length
Will be held online through Zoom

Get involved if you are

- Full-time Undergraduate/Postgraduate degree Student
- Second year or above in your programme
- Eighteen years or older
- Irish/International
- Comfortable with keeping the camera ON and recording of the Focus Group for note-taking purposes

Contact details of the Researcher

nidhipiplani.kapur@postgrad.wit.ie

[LinkedIn](#)

[Twitter](#)

Participant Information Leaflet

Participant Informed Consent Form

Ethical Approval
Ref: SETU2022REC0003

Project Funded by

Appendix D: Gatekeeper Research Pack (Semi-Structured Interviews)

Nidhi Piplani Kapur <nidhipiplani.kapur@postgrad.wit.ie>

Invitation to the PhD Study- Internationalisation at Home (Academic Staff at [REDACTED])

Nidhi Piplani Kapur <nidhipiplani.kapur@postgrad.wit.ie>

25 May 2023 at 09:00

To: [REDACTED]

[REDACTED]
Vice President for Academic Affairs & Registrar
[REDACTED]
Ireland

Dear [REDACTED],

My name is Nidhi Piplani Kapur, and I am working on a PhD project at the South East Technological University (SETU), Waterford, funded by the Irish Research Council. The project is titled, 'Embedding a culture of "Internationalisation at Home"- Preparing for the changing context of Higher Education in Ireland'. I am writing to seek your assistance and support with the research and hope you will be able to help.

This PhD project has been approved by SETU's Ethics Committee (Reference No SETU2022REC0003) as attached. This has also been approved by the [REDACTED] Research Ethics Committee.

I would be very grateful if you could help in identifying one Academic Staff (Senior Lecturer/Lecturer/Assistant Lecturer) at [REDACTED] who would be willing to participate in the research. The participant can contact me directly, indicating their interest.

I have attached the Gatekeeper Research Pack, which includes more detailed information about the study, the consent form, and an indicative topic guide that will give a better insight into my research.

I am aware that your role is a very busy one and respectfully ask you to consider helping me by sending the attached poster and participant information leaflet to the academic staff.

Participation in this study involves a one-to-one semi-structured interview with the Academic Staff for about an hour that will be conducted in-person at [REDACTED] or online through Zoom, as per the participant's convenience. I plan to schedule the interview between September- October, 2023.

I would also like to invite you to a brief online meeting to clarify any questions you may have about this study. This briefing meeting is optional.

If you agree to support this research, I will be grateful if you could fill, sign and return the gatekeeper consent form to me at nidhipiplani.kapur@postgrad.wit.ie

I look forward to hearing from you.

Kind Regards,
Nidhi Piplani Kapur

Nidhi Piplani Kapur (She/Her)
IRC PhD Scholar- Internationalisation at Home
South East Technological University (SETU)
Cork Road Campus - Waterford X91 KEOK - Ireland

Gatekeeper Research Pack

Project Title	Embedding a culture of 'Internationalisation at Home'- Preparing for the changing context of Higher Education in Ireland
Researcher	Ms Nidhi Piplani Kapur PhD Scholar-Internationalisation at Home Email Address: nidhipiplani.kapur@postgrad.wit.ie
Primary Supervisor	Dr Don O'Neill Head of Department of Humanities South East Technological University (SETU), Waterford, Ireland Email Address: Don.ONeill@setu.ie
Co-Supervisors	Dr Helen Murphy Head, School of Education and Lifelong Learning South East Technological University (SETU), Waterford, Ireland Email Address: Helen.Murphy@setu.ie Dr Suzanne Denieffe Head of School of Humanities South East Technological University (SETU), Waterford, Ireland Email Address: Suzanne.Denieffe@setu.ie
Funding	Irish Research Council
SETU Ethical Approval Reference Number	SETU2022REC0003
Data Controllers	South East Technological University (SETU)
Data Protection Officer	Data Protection Officer SETU Cork Road Waterford +353 51 302608 dataprotection@setu.ie

Project Funded by

What is the purpose of the project?

In Irish third-level education, traditionally, a small minority of students have benefited from an international mobility experience as part of their studies. This project will explore ways to internationalise the student experience through 'Internationalisation at Home' (IaH), defined as 'the purposeful integration of international and intercultural dimensions into the formal and informal curriculum for all students within domestic learning environments' (Beelen& Jones, 2015).

The primary purpose of this research is to create a framework for IaH in the Irish higher education context that helps HEIs in Ireland to foster the embedding of a culture of internationalisation into the curriculum. The study will draw on the findings that have investigated the challenges and opportunities presented by the participants in this study.

Why has my institution been invited to take part?

The insights and experience your institution participants offer will help identify the challenges and pathways to create a framework for IaH in an Irish higher education context. It will enable the development and fostering of global competencies in students in Irish HEIs through the curriculum.

Does my institution have to take part?

Participation in this research is voluntary. You and the participants from your institution are under no obligation to participate. If you decide to nominate participants for this research, you will be asked to sign a gatekeeper consent form as attached below. The participants, too, will need to sign a participant consent form, as attached in the Participant Research Pack, if they agree to participate.

What does participation in this project entail?

If you are in agreement, we would greatly appreciate your support in recruiting an **Academic Staff** at [REDACTED] as a suitable participant for this study who meet the criterion in the table below

Type of Participants Needed

Academic Staff (Senior Lecturer/Lecturer/Assistant Lecturer)

Number of Participants Needed from [REDACTED]

One

Method of Data Collection

Semi-Structured Interview (Refer to the attached Topic Guide)

Time required from the Participant

Briefing (scheduled any day prior to conducting the interview at a time that is convenient to the participant) -10 minutes

Semi-Structured Interview- About an hour

Venue for Briefing and Semi-Structured Interviews

Briefing -Online (on Zoom)

Semi-Structured Interview- Online (on Zoom) or In-person (on campus at [REDACTED] dependent on the preference of the participant.

Participant Selection Criterion

Academic Staff

Senior Lecturer/Lecturer/Assistant Lecturer

1. Full-time Academic Staff.
2. They have spent at least a year working in the HEI in their current role.
3. Irish or International Academic Staff.
4. Academic Staff who is comfortable keeping their camera ON (in case of an online interview) and with the recording of the in-person/ online interview for note-taking purposes.

1. Vulnerable Academic Staff.
2. New Staff (in their first year of employment at their HEI and/or first year in their current role).
3. Part-time Academic Staff.
4. Academic Staff who is uncomfortable keeping their camera ON (in case of an online interview) and with the recording of the in-person/ online interview for note-taking purposes.

Project Funded by

If you agree to support this research, the following outlines your role:

- Attend an optional ten-minute briefing meeting through Zoom to understand the project, type of participants needed and get answers to your queries.
- Carefully consider the documents and return the signed gatekeeper consent form to the researcher at nidhipiplani.kapur@postgrad.wit.ie
- Distribute the participant research pack that includes Study Poster, Participant Information Leaflet and Consent Form to the potential participants.
- Re-distribute information if needed.

Are there any Expenses and /or Payments involved?

There are no expenses or payments for participation in the semi-structured interviews.

What are the benefits of participating?

It is anticipated that insight and knowledge produced from the findings of this study will contribute to shaping higher education policy in Ireland. The participant's experiences and insights will help develop a framework that will improve the internationalised outcomes for higher education.

What are the risks associated with participating?

Even though highly unlikely, the interviews may pressure the participant to reveal any private or sensitive information that can cause stress or harm. There are no issues of a personal or sensitive nature being discussed, and therefore the researcher does not anticipate that the process will be distressing for the participant. The topic guide for the participant has been attached in the Participant Research Pack. The privacy and confidentiality of the participant and the data collected will be maintained. Should the participant from the interviews experience discomfort, the participant can inform the

researcher- Nidhi Piplani Kapur and withdraw from the study without being affected. The researcher will also guide the participant towards the staff support systems available at [REDACTED]

What are the limitations to the researcher's confidentiality?

If the participant discloses something unexpected that raises concern about risk or harm to others because a participant discloses criminal behaviours, events or intentions they have engaged in or have knowledge of, the researcher will be under a legal and moral duty to report this incident. Under these circumstances, the researcher will be required to give evidence or reveal documents, which may make it impossible for certain information to be kept confidential.

Can participants withdraw from the study?

Participation in the research study is voluntary, and the participant can withdraw before or during the interview. The participant in the interviews can amend or withdraw their transcript up to two months after the interview has been conducted by contacting the researcher at nidhipiplani.kapur@postgrad.wit.ie

Who will have access to the data from this research study?

The data in the form of interviews will be collected by the researcher – Nidhi Piplani Kapur. Her supervisory team will access the pseudonymised data- Dr Don O'Neill, Dr Helen Murphy, and Dr Suzanne Denieffe. The data is confidential and will be anonymised. The data will not be made available to any third parties. The researcher will decline any request regarding data access by third parties.

What will happen to the results from this study?

The research outputs produced will be published in the thesis, research publications, conferences and dissemination events, etc. The results so published will be anonymous, and no person or organisation will be identified. Findings will be based on the information provided by the participants and include their direct quotations without revealing their identity.

Once the research study is completed, any research/project related data will fall under the responsibility of the Chair of the Joint School (Humanities and Education) Postgrad Research Board at SETU, where it will be securely held until destroyed at the end of their 10-year data retention period. At the end of the research study, the PhD Thesis will be available in the SETU library. If you wish to access this, this can be done by accessing: <http://repository.wit.ie/>

If you agree to support this research, please sign and return the consent form below.

GATEKEEPER CONSENT FORM

Title of Project: Embedding a culture of 'Internationalisation at Home'- Preparing for the changing context of Higher Education in Ireland

Name of Researcher: Nidhi Piplani Kapur

Please tick to confirm your understanding of the study and that you are happy for your institution to take part.

You voluntarily agree to allow access to your staff and facilities (if needed) to execute the data collection process for this study.

Please tick the boxes and sign below:

1. I confirm that I have read and understood the information provided for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions, and have these answered satisfactorily.
2. I understand that the participation of our institution and staff in the research is voluntary and that the participants are free to withdraw at any time before or during the study without giving a reason.
3. I understand that in the circumstance that requires re-recruiting a participant for this study, I agree to re-distribute the information leaflet, topic guide, and consent form to the potential participants.
4. I agree that our institution and staff will participate in the above study.

Signature

Date

Signature

Date

Nidhi Piplani Kapur
Researcher

We will be grateful if you could return the signed Gatekeeper Consent Form to the researcher at nidhipiplani.kapur@postgrad.wit.ie

Project Funded by

Embedding a culture of 'Internationalisation at Home'
Preparing for the changing context of Higher Education in Ireland

We Want to Hear from you!!

The Interview

Approximately One hour in length

Will be held in-person at your institution's campus or online through
Zoom at your convenience

Get involved if you are

- Full-time employee in your current institution/organisation
- Have spent at least a year in your current role
- Irish/International
- Comfortable with keeping the Camera ON (in case of online interviews) and recording of interviews (in-person/online) for note-taking purposes

Contact details of the Researcher

nidhipiplani.kapur@postgrad.wit.ie

[LinkedIn](#)

[Twitter](#)

Participant Information Leaflet

Participant Informed Consent Form

Ethical Approval
Ref: SETU2022REC0003

Project Funded by

Appendix E: Participant Research Pack (Focus Groups)

Nidhi Piplani Kapur <nidhipiplani.kapur@postgrad.wit.ie>

Invitation for a focus group | PhD Study on Internationalisation at Home

Nidhi Piplani Kapur <nidhipiplani.kapur@postgrad.wit.ie>

29 January 2024 at 14:45

To: [REDACTED]

Dear [REDACTED],

Thank you for your willingness to participate in my PhD research project, titled "Embedding a culture of 'Internationalisation at Home' - Preparing for the changing context of Higher Education in Ireland," funded by the Irish Research Council. This research study has been approved by SETU's Research Ethics Committee (Reference No. SETU2022REC0003), as attached and has also the approval of [REDACTED] Research Ethics Committee and the registrar's office.

I am in organising two focus groups comprising students from various higher education institutions (HEIs) in Ireland. If you agree to take part, you will be one of eight members of the focus group. The focus group discussion is expected to last approximately one hour and fifteen minutes.

As a potential participant, you have the flexibility to participate in any of the focus group discussions:

February 9, 2024 (Friday) - 17:00-18:30

OR

February 16, 2024 (Friday) -17:00-18:30

Your participation in this research will provide a valuable student perspective, helping Irish HEIs enhance the internationalisation aspect of both campus life and the curriculum.

I kindly request you to thoroughly review the attached documents, which include the Participant Research Pack and Topic Guide.

Additionally, I would like to extend an invitation for a brief online meeting to further elaborate on the purpose of the research and clarify your role as a participant. Please note that attendance at this briefing meeting is **optional**.

If you decide to participate, I will be grateful if you could fill, sign, and return the attached participant research pack to nidhipiplani.kapur@postgrad.wit.ie at your earliest convenience or by January 30, 2024 (Tuesday).

Thank you for considering my request. I look forward to your response.

Kind Regards,

Nidhi Piplani Kapur

Nidhi Piplani Kapur (She/Her)
IRC PhD Scholar- Internationalisation at Home
South East Technological University (SETU)
Cork Road Campus - Waterford X91 KEOK - Ireland

PARTICIPANT RESEARCH PACK

FOCUS GROUPS

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION LEAFLET

Project Title	Embedding a culture of ‘Internationalisation at Home’- Preparing for the changing context of Higher Education in Ireland
Researcher	Ms Nidhi Piplani Kapur PhD Scholar-Internationalisation at Home Email Address: nidhipiplani.kapur@postgrad.wit.ie
Primary Supervisor	Dr Don O’Neill Head of Department of Humanities South East Technological University (SETU), Waterford, Ireland Email Address: Don.ONeill@setu.ie
Co-Supervisors	Dr Helen Murphy Head, School of Education and Lifelong Learning South East Technological University (SETU), Waterford, Ireland Email Address: Helen.Murphy@setu.ie Dr Suzanne Denieffe Head of School of Humanities South East Technological University (SETU), Waterford, Ireland Email Address: Suzanne.Denieffe@setu.ie
Funding	Irish Research Council
SETU Ethical Approval Reference	SETU2022REC0003
Data Controllers	South East Technological University (SETU)
Data Protection Officer	Data Protection Officer SETU Cork Road Waterford +353 51 302608 dataprotection@setu.ie

Project Funded by

Informed Consent

You have been asked to participate in **a focus group discussion** for a PhD project carried out by the South East Technological University (SETU), Waterford researcher – Nidhi Piplani Kapur. This information leaflet will enable you to decide whether or not to participate in this research.

Why is this research being conducted?

In Irish third-level education, traditionally, a small minority of students have benefited from an international mobility experience as part of their studies through international exchanges, Erasmus programmes etc. This project will explore ways to internationalise the student experience through ‘Internationalisation at Home’ (IaH).

IaH will seek to provide international and intercultural learning to all students, including those who cannot take advantage of the mobility opportunities due to socio-economic, physical, or personal circumstances or a lack of interest or awareness about IaH. This study aims to investigate the opportunities and challenges in developing a culture of ‘Internationalisation at Home’ in an Irish Higher Education context. It will help create a framework for IaH that will bridge skill deficits in Irish graduates and build multicultural competencies required by the industry.

Why am I being asked to participate?

Your insights and experience will help identify the challenges and pathway of creating a framework in IaH that will help develop and foster global competencies in students at Home through the curriculum.

Do I have to participate?

Taking part in this study will not confer any professional advantage or disadvantage on you. Participation in this research is voluntary, and you are not obligated to participate. If you decide to participate in this research, you will be asked to sign a consent form attached at the end of the document.

What does participation involve?

If you voluntarily agree to participate in this research after you have read this leaflet and taken time to consider it, your role in the study will involve:

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Please find the Student Support Services available at your institution below:

How will the data gathered be managed and used in the study?

The data in the form of focus groups will be collected by the researcher – Nidhi Piplani Kapur. The pseudonymised data will be accessed by her supervisory team- Dr Don O’Neill, Dr Helen Murphy and Dr Suzanne Denieffe.

The research outputs produced will be published in the thesis, research publications, conferences and dissemination events, etc. The results so published will be anonymous, and no person or organisation will be identified. Findings will be based on the information you have provided, may include your direct quotations without revealing your identity.

Once the research study is completed, any research/project related data will fall under the responsibility of the Chair of the Joint School (Humanities and Education) Postgraduate Research Board at SETU, where it will be securely held until destroyed at the end of their 10-year data retention period. At the end of the research study, the PhD Thesis will be available in the SETU library. If you wish to access this, this can be done by accessing: <http://repository.wit.ie/>.

How will privacy and confidentiality be maintained?

The researcher will comply with SETU's GDPR policy and take explicit steps to protect the participants' privacy. Confidentiality of the participant's identities will be ensured. Participants will be pseudonymised and linked to codes. Any data that exposes the identity of the participants or their institution will be adjusted accordingly.

What are the limitations to the researcher’s confidentiality?

Though very unlikely due to the non-contentious nature of the topic being discussed, but if the participant discloses something unexpected that raises concern about risk or harm to others because a participant discloses criminal behaviours, events or intentions they have engaged in or have knowledge of, the researcher will be under a legal and moral duty to report this incident.

Does the researcher have permission from my institution for this research?

The researcher has sought ethical approval from her home organisation South East Technological University, which has been presented to and approved by your HEI. This approval allows the researcher to conduct focus groups in your HEI.

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All information held by SETU's IT is subject to the terms of the Freedom of Information Act 2014 and the Data Protection Act 2018. You can find information about this on the Institute's website: https://www.wit.ie/about_wit/documents_and_policies/documents_policies/

https://www.wit.ie/about_wit/documents_and_policies/staff_data_protection

Thank you and Next Steps:

Thank you for taking the time to read this information leaflet. If you agree and are happy to take part in this research, please sign and return the consent form attached below to the researcher at nidhipiplani.kapur@postgrad.wit.ie. Please also retain a copy of this information leaflet and the original signed Consent Form for your own records. If you provide your consent to participate, the researcher will contact you to arrange a time to conduct the focus group. You will only be contacted to arrange your participation in the aspects of the study described, that you have consented to.

Should you have any queries about this research, you can contact the researcher Nidhi Piplani Kapur at nidhipiplani.kapur@postgrad.wit.ie

For any other questions or concerns regarding the study which you do not wish to discuss with Nidhi Piplani Kapur, you can reach out to her supervisor Dr Don O'Neill at Don.ONeill@setu.ie

PARTICIPANT INFORMED CONSENT FORM

FOCUS GROUPS

**Project: Embedding a culture of 'Internationalisation at Home'- Preparing for the
changing context of Higher**

Education in Ireland

Researcher: Nidhi Piplani Kapur

Please tick the box)

1. I confirm that I have read and understood the information leaflet for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have these answered satisfactorily.
2. I understand that my participation is voluntary. In addition, should I not wish to answer any particular question or questions, I am free to decline.
3. I understand I must not participate in this research if I encounter any risk.
4. I understand that I will keep my camera on during the online focus group and grant permission to record the focus group discussion for facilitating a meaningful discussion and the researcher's note-taking purposes.
5. I understand that I can withdraw from the research at any point before or during the focus group without giving any reason and without my rights being affected.
6. I understand that I can withdraw or amend the transcripts from the focus group up to two months from the date of conducting the focus group.
7. I understand that my own and my institution's details will be anonymised.
8. I understand and respect that the privacy of other participants and the discussions in focus groups are strictly confidential and will not be identified or disclosed anywhere.
9. I understand that in any report on the results of this research the researcher will endeavour to keep my identity anonymous. This will be done by changing my name and disguising any details of my talk which is likely to reveal my identity.

Project Funded by

10. I grant my permission to use direct quotations from my discussion in publications, including PhD thesis, conference presentations, published papers, etc. Any quotations will be disguised extracts for anonymity.

11. I understand that efforts to ensure confidentiality and anonymity, however robust, cannot be absolutely guaranteed.

12. I understand that if I inform the researcher that I or someone else is at risk of harm or is engaging in misconduct, the researcher is under a legal and moral obligation to report this to the relevant authorities with or without my permission.

13. I understand that signed consent forms and original audio recordings will be securely retained for a period of 10 years.

14. I have been informed about the purpose of the study and my role and rights as a participant and in signing this form I am voluntarily giving my informed consent to participate. I agree to take part in the above study.

Participant's Institution _____

Gender _____

***Participant's Programme Level
in their Institution***

Full-time Undergraduate Degree

Full-time Postgraduate Degree

Participant's Programme Stage

First Year

More than one year

Participant's Nationality Status

Irish

Other EU/EEA

Campus

Project Funded by

International

Please select the tentative date that will best suit you:

February 9, 2024 (Friday) – 17:00-18:30

OR

February 16, 2024 (Friday)- 17:00-18:30

Participant's Name

Date

Signature

Nidhi Piplani Kapur

Researcher's Name

Date

Signature

We will be grateful if you could return the signed Participant Informed Consent Form to the researcher at nidhipiplani.kapur@postgrad.wit.ie

Project Funded by

Appendix F: Participant Research Pack (Semi-Structured Interviews)

Nidhi Piplani Kapur <nidhipiplani.kapur@postgrad.wit.ie>

Invitation to the PhD Study- Internationalisation at Home

Nidhi Piplani Kapur <nidhipiplani.kapur@postgrad.wit.ie>

29 May 2023 at 14:44

To: [REDACTED]

Dear [REDACTED],

My name is Nidhi Piplani Kapur, and I am working on a PhD project at the South East Technological University (SETU), Waterford, funded by the Irish Research Council. The project is titled, 'Embedding a culture of "Internationalisation at Home"- Preparing for the changing context of Higher Education in Ireland'. I am writing to seek your engagement in this research as a participant in this study.

This PhD project has been approved by SETU's Research Ethics Committee (Reference No. SETU2022REC0003). This approval has been accepted by [REDACTED] Research Ethics Committee.

The main aim of this research is to explore the opportunities and challenges in fostering a culture of internationalisation within Irish higher education institutions, based on the perspectives of the participants.

I would be very grateful if you could consider your participation in this research after carefully going through the attached documents (Participant information leaflet; topic guide and informed consent form).

I'll be happy to schedule a very brief online meeting with you to explain the purpose of the research and your role as a participant. This briefing meeting is optional.

Participation in this study involves a one-to-one semi-structured interview and will last about an hour. The interview will be conducted in person at your institution's campus or online through Zoom, at your convenience. I hope to schedule the interview between September- October 2023.

I would greatly appreciate it if you could let me know if you have any questions before deciding your participation in this research. If you agree to participate in the research, please fill, sign, and return the consent form attached at nidhipiplani.kapur@postgrad.wit.ie

I look forward to hearing from you.

Kind Regards,

Nidhi Piplani Kapur

Nidhi Piplani Kapur (She/Her)
IRC PhD Scholar- Internationalisation at Home
South East Technological University (SETU)
Cork Road Campus - Waterford X91 KEOK - Ireland

PARTICIPANT RESEARCH PACK

SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEWS

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION LEAFLET

Project Title	Embedding a culture 'Internationalisation at Home'- Preparing for the changing context of Higher Education in Ireland
Researcher	Ms Nidhi Piplani Kapur PhD Scholar-Internationalisation at Home Email Address: nidhipiplani.kapur@postgrad.wit.ie
Primary Supervisor	Dr Don O'Neill Head of Department of Humanities South East Technological University (SETU), Waterford, Ireland Email Address: Don.ONeill@setu.ie
Co-Supervisors	Dr Helen Murphy Head, School of Education and Lifelong Learning South East Technological University (SETU), Waterford, Ireland Email Address: Helen.Murphy@setu.ie Dr Suzanne Denieffe Head of School of Humanities South East Technological University (SETU), Waterford, Ireland Email Address: Suzanne.Denieffe@setu.ie
Funding	Irish Research Council
SETU Ethical Approval Reference	SETU2022REC0003
Data Controllers	South East Technological University (SETU)
Data Protection Officer	Data Protection Officer SETU Cork Road Waterford +353 51 302608 dataprotection@setu.ie

Informed Consent

You have been asked to participate in **a semi-structured** for a PhD project carried out by the South East Technological University (SETU), Waterford researcher – Nidhi Piplani Kapur. This information leaflet will enable you to decide whether or not to participate in this research.

Why is this research being conducted?

In Irish third-level education, traditionally, a small minority of students have benefited from an international mobility experience as part of their studies through international exchanges, Erasmus programmes etc. This project will explore ways to internationalise the student experience through 'Internationalisation at Home' (IaH). IaH will seek to provide international and intercultural learning to most students who cannot take advantage of the mobility opportunities due to socio-economic, physical, or personal circumstances or a lack of interest or awareness about IaH. This study aims to investigate the opportunities and challenges in developing a culture of 'Internationalisation at Home' in an Irish Higher Education context. It will help create a framework for IaH that will bridge skill deficits in Irish graduates and build multicultural competencies required by the industry.

Why am I being asked to participate?

Your insights and experience will help identify the challenges and pathway of creating a framework in IaH that will help develop and foster global competencies in students at Home through the curriculum.

Do I have to participate?

Taking part in this study will not confer any professional advantage or disadvantage on you.

Participation in this research is voluntary, and you are not obligated to participate. If you decide to participate in this research, you will be asked to sign a [consent form](#) as attached below.

What does participation involve?

If you voluntarily agree to participate in this research after you have read this leaflet and taken time to consider it, your role in the study will involve:

- Attend an **optional** briefing meeting with the researcher for about 10 minutes through Zoom at your convenience. This will allow you the researcher to explain the purpose of this study, participant burden and answer any questions you may have.
- Return the signed consent form attached at the end of the document (atleast two weeks prior to the conduct of the interview).
- Consider reading the interview questions (topic guide) as attached in advance, if possible.
- Participate in the interview online (through Zoom) or in-person at your institution's campus at your convenience. Participation in this study will entail engaging in an one-to-one in-depth interview. You will be amongst fifteen participants being interviewed in the study across different HEIs and organisations in Ireland. The interview will last about an hour.
- In case of an online interview, you will be requested to keep your camera ON for a meaningful discussion. Online/ in-person interviews will be recorded for note-taking purposes.
- If you are uncomfortable at any stage, you can withdraw before or during the interview without any consequence.
- If you have already taken part, you can request the researcher to amend or withdraw the transcript upto two months after the interview. After this time, the data will be consolidated and anonymised.

Are there any Expenses and/or Payments involved?

There are no expenses or payments expected from your participation in the interviews.

What are the benefits of participating?

The insight and knowledge produced from the findings of this study will contribute to shaping the higher education policy in Ireland. The stakeholders, such as you, participating in this research will benefit through improving IaH offerings in Irish HEIs. Your experiences and insights will help suggest a framework that will improve the internationalised outcomes for higher education.

What are the risks associated with participating?

Even though highly unlikely, the interviews may pressure the participants to reveal any private or sensitive information that can cause stress or harm. There are no issues of a personal or sensitive nature being discussed, and therefore the researcher does not anticipate the process being distressing for participants. The privacy and confidentiality of the participants and data collected will be maintained. Should the participants from the interviews experience discomfort, they can refer to the Employee Assistance Programmes at their institution. They can also inform the researcher- Nidhi Piplani Kapur and withdraw from the study without being affected. You can refer to the Employee Assistance Programmes available at your institution.

Please find the Employee Assistance Programme available at your institution below:

How will the data gathered be managed and used in the study?

The data in the form of interviews will be collected by the researcher – Nidhi Piplani Kapur. The pseudonymised data will be accessed by her supervisory team- Dr Don O’Neill, Dr Helen Murphy and Dr Suzanne Denieffe.

The research outputs produced will be published in the thesis, research publications, conferences and dissemination events, etc. The results so published will be anonymous, and no person or organisation will be identified. Findings will be based on the information you have provided, may include your direct quotations without revealing your identity.

Once the research study is completed, any research/project related data will fall under the responsibility of the Chair of the Joint School (Humanities and Education) Postgrad Research Board at SETU, where it will be securely held until destroyed at the end of their 10-year data retention period. At the end of the research study, the PhD Thesis will be available in the SETU library. If you wish to access this, this can be done by accessing: <http://repository.wit.ie/>.

How will privacy and confidentiality be maintained?

The researcher will comply with SETU's GDPR policy and take explicit steps to protect the participants' privacy. Confidentiality of the participant's identities will be ensured. Participants will be pseudonymised and linked to codes. Any data that exposes the identity of the participants or their institution will be adjusted accordingly.

What are the limitations to the researcher's confidentiality?

Though very unlikely due to the non-contentious nature of the topic being discussed, but if the participant discloses something unexpected that raises concern about risk or harm to others because a participant discloses criminal behaviours, events, or intentions they have engaged in or have knowledge of, the researcher will be under a legal and moral duty to report this incident.

Does the researcher have permission from my institution for this research?

The researcher has sought ethical approval from her home organisation South East Technological University, which has been presented to and approved by your institution. This approval allows the researcher to conduct interviews from your institution.

All information held by SETU's IT is subject to the terms of the Freedom of Information Act 2014 and the Data Protection Act 2018. You can find information about this on the Institute's website: https://www.wit.ie/about_wit/documents_and_policies/documents_policies/

https://www.wit.ie/about_wit/documents_and_policies/staff_data_protection

Thank you and Next Steps:

Thank you for taking the time to read this information leaflet. If you agree and are happy to take part in this research, please return the attached signed consent form to the researcher at nidhipiplani.kapur@postgrad.wit.ie. Please also retain a copy of this information leaflet and the original signed Consent Form for your own records. If you provide your consent to participate, the researcher will contact you to arrange a time to conduct the interview. You will only be contacted to arrange your participation in the aspects of the study described, that you have consented to.

Should you have any queries about this research, you can contact the researcher Nidhi Piplani Kapur at nidhipiplani.kapur@postgrad.wit.ie

For any other questions or concerns regarding the study which you do not wish to discuss with Nidhi Piplani Kapur, you can reach out to her supervisor Dr Don O'Neill at Don.ONeill@setu.ie

PARTICIPANT INFORMED CONSENT FORM
SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEWS

**Project: Embedding a culture of
'Internationalisation at Home'- Preparing for the changing context of Higher
Education in Ireland**

Researcher: Nidhi Piplani Kapur

(Please tick the box)

1. I confirm that I have read and understood the information leaflet for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have these answered satisfactorily.

2. I understand that my participation is voluntary. In addition, should I not wish to answer any particular question or questions, I am free to decline.

3. I understand I must not participate in this research if I encounter any risk.

4. I understand that I will keep my camera on (in case I opt for an online interview) and grant permission to record the interview to facilitate a meaningful discussion and the researcher's note-taking purposes. In either case, I grant permission to record my interview in person or online.

5. I understand that I can withdraw from the research at any point before or during the interviews without giving any reason and without my rights being affected.

6. I understand that I can withdraw or amend the transcript from the interview up to two months from the date of conducting the interview.

7. I understand that my own and my institution's details will be anonymised.

8. I understand and respect that the interviews are strictly confidential and the discussions will not be disclosed anywhere.

9. I understand that in any report on the results of this research the researcher will endeavour to keep my identity anonymous. This will be done by changing my name and disguising any details of my talk which is likely to reveal my identity.

10. I grant my permission to use direct quotations from my discussion in publications, including PhD thesis, conference presentations, published papers, etc. Any quotations will be disguised extracts for anonymity.

11. I understand that efforts to ensure confidentiality and anonymity, however robust, cannot be absolutely guaranteed.

12. I understand that if I inform the researcher that I or someone else is at risk of harm or is engaging in misconduct, the researcher is under a legal and moral obligation to report this to the relevant authorities with or without my permission.

13. I understand that signed consent forms and original audio recordings will be securely retained for a period of 10 years.

14. I have been informed about the purpose of the study and my role and rights as a participant and in signing this form I am voluntarily giving my informed consent to participate. I agree to take part in the above study.

Participant's Institution _____

Gender _____

Programme Level Taught

Year of employment in your current role

Full-time Undergraduate Degree

First Year

Full-time Postgraduate Degree

More than one year

Not Applicable

Participant's Nationality Status

Irish

Other EU/EEA

International

Please highlight the tentative dates that will suit you most in September/October 2023

September 2023

Dates Available _____

Time Available: _____

October 2023

Dates Available _____

Time Available _____

Please indicate your preferred mode of interview by selecting the option that best suits your convenience:

Online

In-Person

Participant's Name

Date

Signature

Nidhi Piplani Kapur

Researcher's Name

Date

Signature

We will be grateful if you could return the signed Participant Informed Consent Form to the researcher at nidhipiplani.kapur@postgrad.wit.ie

Appendix G: Topic Guides

TOPIC GUIDE

Embedding a culture of ‘Internationalisation at Home’- Preparing for the changing context of Higher Education in Ireland

The suggestive questions are based on the themes emerging from the literature review.

Context of the Study

In Irish third-level education, traditionally, a small minority of students have benefited from an international mobility experience as part of their studies. This project will explore ways to internationalise the student experience through ‘Internationalisation at Home’ (IaH).

The primary purpose of this research is to create a framework for IaH that helps HEIs in Ireland to foster the embedding of a culture of internationalisation in Irish HEIs. The study will draw on the findings that have investigated the challenges and opportunities presented by the participants in this study.

The below terminologies are explained and will be used frequently in the questions to draw on your experiences.

Internationalisation at Home (IaH)

The purposeful integration of international and intercultural dimensions into the formal and informal curriculum for all students within domestic learning environments (Beelen and Jones, 2015).

Internationalisation of the Curriculum (IoC)

Internationalisation of the Curriculum is the incorporation of international, intercultural and/or global dimensions into the content of the curriculum as well as the learning outcomes, assessment tasks, teaching methods and support services of a program of study (Leask, 2015).

Formal Curriculum

It includes pedagogy, i.e. teaching, learning and assessment (Beelen and Jones, 2015). It comprises the syllabus and all the associated planned schedule and activities that students must undertake as part of their degree program’ (Leask, 2015).

Informal Curriculum

The informal curriculum is not assessed but includes learning from the support services and activities such as formal mentoring programs, peer-assisted study sessions, volunteering programmes and organised social activities (Leask, 2015).

Hidden Curriculum

It is a part of both formal and informal curricula. It includes unintended, implicit and hidden messages sent to students—messages that HEIs may not even be aware they are sending (Leask, 2015).

Examples of IaH include (Leask, 2015; Bulnes and Louw, 2022):

Formal Curriculum

- Modules, assignments, projects etc. that focus on a global or international subject, such as SDGs, global health studies, or European/International Law.
- Modules, assignments, projects etc., that use international case studies, international videos, non-western sources in the literature or content, literature in different foreign languages to accommodate students' diversity, etc.
- Modules, assignments, projects, etc. that cover cross-cultural/ intercultural communication, skills or collaboration between mixed groups (domestic and international students).
- Modules, assignments, projects etc. that include shared supervision of students with lecturers from external institutions abroad, such as thesis supervision, online collaboration or supervision of international projects.
- A programme that has an online collaborative project whereby domestic students interact with students from and physically located in another country.
- Elements of a programme that focus on a particular country or region outside Ireland.
- Engagement programmes or activities with international companies and/or organisations, such as guest lectures, site visits etc.
- Opportunities for international work placements, Study trips, summer, and winter schools, semester abroad etc.
- Programme elements that include community outreach in the local environment, such as cultural others, underrepresented groups etc.
- Classroom settings that explicitly leverage on sharing of local knowledge and experience of students with different cultural backgrounds.
- Modules that are delivered by international lecturers, guest lecturers, live streaming, or recorded lectures from international faculty.
- Modules, assignments, projects etc. that have explicitly formulated international and/or intercultural learning outcomes.

Informal Curriculum

- Buddy programmes that connect domestic and international students (language, intercultural exchange, social integration etc.).
- Festivals that celebrate international languages, culture, food, religion etc.
- International weeks, conferences, volunteer programmes etc.
- Events and festivals aimed at involving the local community.
- Extracurricular activities with international companies and/or organisations.

Hidden Curriculum

- Unspoken or implicit values, behaviours, procedures, and norms that exist in the educational setting.
- Various unintended, implicit and hidden messages sent to students—messages we may not even be aware we are sending.
- The choice of selected textbooks sends a hidden message concerning whose knowledge counts in this curriculum and, by implication, whose does not.
- Hidden messages are also conveyed through the informal curriculum, for example, prescribing all international students to complete cross-cultural skills training prior to the commencement of classes. However, the same pre-requisite does not apply to domestic or home students.

Participants – Learners

Introduction Questions

1. What is your understanding of internationalisation at home in higher education?
2. Is there a need to include global perspectives and experiences through formal or informal curriculum during your study? Yes/No, why?
3. How has your institution created experiences (formal and informal) that promote/encourage internationalisation? Can you list some of these initiatives?
4. Have you participated in any activity that involved international and/or intercultural experiences or students? Please elaborate on the initiatives that you were a part of. Why did you choose the activity/activities?
5. Have you witnessed any improvement in your knowledge, skills and competencies after engaging in intercultural interactions/experiences and learning about the world through the curriculum offered in your home institution? Can you explain the knowledge, skills and competencies you believe you have developed?

Key Probe Questions

1. Where and how can we include students more purposefully and systematically in our IaH processes, and to what end?
2. What opportunities aid student participation in IaH initiatives?
3. What barriers prevent you and other students from participating in IaH initiatives?
4. How can your institution overcome the barriers associated with IaH and incentivise more students to participate in these activities?
5. How can IaH initiatives be made more visible in your institution and nationally?

Participants – Academic Staff/Academic Managers/Senior Managers

Introduction Questions

1. Is IaH a part of your institutional strategy? If yes, what does it state? Is it clearly defined? If not, what could be the possible reason?
2. Have you designed any purposeful interventions to promote IaH initiatives in your institution? Can you elaborate on some of those interventions?
3. Have you considered the role of the hidden curriculum in creating an inclusive campus?
4. What do you consider a good example of your programme or any other programmes in IaH?
5. Are there any publications/research or reports on IaH in any department/discipline in your institution? Please elaborate.
6. Are you aware of international best practices in IaH in the EU and international context? If yes, can you elaborate more on them?

Key Probe Questions

1. If IaH is part of your institutional strategy, how is it implemented across the institution? If not, why might this be the case?
2. What is needed for necessary conditions for the internationalisation of the home curriculum? Where do they need to be created?
3. How can we provide academic staff with the time, space, and expertise to develop purposeful
4. IaH activities for students?
5. Where and how can we include students more purposefully and systematically in our IaH processes, and to what end?
6. What are the challenges in implementing IaH activities in your HEI?
7. How can we overcome the barriers associated with IaH and incentivise more staff and students to participate in these activities?
8. How do we measure success through IaH?

9. How do we make IaH initiatives more visible in your institution and nationally?
10. How can national policies be used to influence and measure the implementation of internationalisation for all?

Participants – International Officers

Introduction Questions

1. Is IaH a part of your institutional strategy? If yes, what does it state? Is it clearly defined? If not, what could be the possible reason?
2. Have you designed any purposeful interventions to promote IaH initiatives in your institution? Can you elaborate on some of those interventions?
3. Have you considered the role of the hidden curriculum in creating an inclusive campus?
4. Do you use ICT and marketing tools to advance an international campus for your home students? If so, please provide some examples.
5. What do you consider a good example of IaH at your institution?
6. Are there any publications/research or reports on IaH in any department/discipline in your institution? Please elaborate.
7. Are you aware of international best practices in IaH in the EU and international context? If yes, can you elaborate more on them?

Key Probe Questions

1. If IaH is part of your institutional strategy, how is it implemented across the institution? If not, why might this be the case?
2. Where and what conditions must be created to successfully implement IaH through the informal curriculum?
3. How can we provide academic staff with the time, space, and expertise to develop purposeful IaH activities for students?
4. Where and how can we include students more purposefully and systematically in our IaH processes, and to what end?
5. What are the challenges in implementing IaH activities in your HEI?
6. How can we overcome the barriers associated with IaH and incentivise more staff and students to participate in these activities?
7. How do we measure success through IaH?
8. How do we make IaH initiatives more visible in your institution and nationally?
9. How can national policies be used to influence and measure the implementation of internationalisation for all?

Participants – External Stakeholder Organisations

Introduction Questions

1. Based on the work on the internationalisation of Irish HE, what have been the strengths, opportunities, and challenges with regard to improving the HE landscape from the lens of internationalisation and encouraging a better quality of experience for Irish and International students in Ireland?
2. What is your view on the positioning of IaH in Ireland and Europe?
3. IaH was referenced as important in furthering the internationalisation of Irish HEIs in the 2016-20 national strategy on internationalisation. Given this context, can your organisation do anything to promote a culture of IaH in Irish HE?
4. Are there any insights available on the impact of covid-19 on IaH in HE?

Key Probe Questions

1. What does IaH hold for future research, policymaking, and practice in Irish HEIs?
2. What are the challenges in implementing IaH activities in HEIs?
3. What structures must be set up to alleviate the challenges in implementing IaH in Irish HEIs?
4. How do we measure success through IaH?
5. How do we make IaH initiatives more visible in Irish HEIs and nationally?
6. How can national policies be used to influence and measure the implementation of internationalisation for all?

Appendix H: NVivo- Qualitative Data Analysis Software

Codes\\Phase 2: Initial Data Codes

Reflexive Thematic Analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2021)- Generating initial systematic codes: Begin coding the materials and give names or labels to the themes.

Linked with Heuristic Approach (Moustakas, 1990)- Immersion and early Incubation: The researcher's intuition guides early patterns of recognition and meanings begin to form.

Codes	Files	References
Change Management	16	210
Formal Curriculum	18	151
CPD	17	136
Academic Staff	18	133
Informal Curriculum	18	118
Assumptions	17	111
IoC	19	109
Communication	17	97
IaH Importance	17	92
Promotion	17	92
Incentives	16	77
Key Stakeholders	17	77
Funding	17	76
Systematic	15	76
Senior Leadership	16	73
Mobility	15	71
University Strategy	16	68
International student engagement	11	67
Cultural Awareness	18	66
Cultural Integration	15	64
International Office	19	64
Cultural Events	14	62
Diverse Classrooms	15	59
Comprehensive Approach	10	58
Cross cultural understanding	14	58
Inclusion	14	58
Curriculum Design	11	57
Intentional Integration	15	56
Virtual Internationalisation	13	56
Erasmus	14	55
Metrics	16	53
Working Group	10	53
International Students Presence	14	52
Teaching and Learning	11	51
Reward and Recognition	13	50
Top-Down Approach	14	50
Cultural Exchange	14	49
EDI	12	49
Irish student engagement	9	47

Codes	Files	References
Framework	9	37
Hidden Curricula	15	37
Single Department	10	36
Networks	12	35
Bottom-Up	13	34
Educating the university community	5	33
International student societies	11	33
Global Citizenship	11	31
IaH Champions	11	31
Intercultural Dimensions	9	31
Recruitment	12	31
Technological University	7	31
Embrace Perspectives	7	30
Interdisciplinarity	12	28
Staff Workload	10	28
Experience Sharing	7	27
International Exposure	5	27
International Staff	13	27
Student Experience	11	27
Academic Self	8	26
Community Engagement	9	26
International Projects	11	26
Irish Context	7	26
Partnerships	9	26
University Responsibility	9	26
Scheduling	11	25
Returning Mobile Students	9	24
Tokenism	6	24
Assessments	7	23
Impact of Internationalisation	8	23
Traditional University	4	23
Research Driven	5	22
Scoping Audit	6	22
Extra Work	9	21
Reference List	12	21
Skills	9	21
International Case Studies	8	20

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Codes	Files	References
Marginalisation	8	20
CoPs	7	19
Employers	9	19
Policy Perspective	3	19
Student Motivation	6	19
Sustainability	9	19
Co-designing curricula	10	18
Communication Skills	11	18
English Language Dominance	7	18
Inherent in Discipline	7	18
Internationalisation Strategic Plan	5	18
Social media	9	18
White Curricula	8	18
Competing Priorities	8	17
Positive Environment	10	17
Community Based Learning	8	16
COVID-19 pandemic	10	16
Electives	7	16
Graduate Attributes	9	16
ILOs	6	16
Polymakers	5	16
Students	5	16
Administrative Challenges	9	15
EUA	8	15
Group Work	10	15
International Conferences	8	15
Overcoming Stereotypes	5	15
Socialisation	6	15
Decolonise curricula	6	14
International Guest Speakers	9	14
Multicultural Societies	11	14
Research Group	2	14
Staff Motivation	5	14
Global South	6	13
Global University	5	13
Persistent Change Messages	5	13
Student Representation	6	13
Global South	6	13
Faculty Strategic Plans	5	12
Mergers	4	12
Reimagining Curricula	1	12

Codes	Files	References
School Level	5	12
Time Management Skills	5	12
Autonomy	5	11
Evidence Base	2	11
Irish Culture	5	11
Language Learning	5	11
Sustaining IaH	5	11
Languages Discipline	3	10
Module Level	6	10
Primary and Secondary Level	5	10
Bias	6	9
Cliques	5	9
Geopolitical Tensions	5	9
Programmatic Reviews	3	9
SDGs	6	9
Sub-culture	5	9
Academic Systems	4	8
Accommodation	6	8
Fear	5	8
International Business Programme	2	8
Reflections	2	8
Website	5	8
Diverse Domestic Population	4	7
Housemates	1	7
Joint campuses abroad	3	7
Reputation	1	7
Teacher Training	2	7
21st Century Skills	4	6
Definition	3	6
Globalisation	4	6
Level Playing Field	4	6
Library	3	6
Limitations	1	6
Peer-to-Peer Learning	5	6
Quality Assurance	2	6
Resistance	4	6
Study Abroad Experiences	4	6
Advocacy	4	5
International Outlook	1	5
Internships	1	5

Appendix H: NVivo- Qualitative Data Analysis Software

Codes\\Phase 2: Initial Data Codes

Reflexive Thematic Analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2021)- Generating initial systematic codes: Begin coding the materials and give names or labels to the themes.

Linked with Heuristic Approach (Moustakas, 1990)- Immersion and early Incubation: The researcher's intuition guides early patterns of recognition and meanings begin to form.

Codes	Files	References
Joint Degrees	3	5
Peer Pressure	3	5
Personal Development	2	5
Revenge Engagement	3	5
T&L Lab	1	5
Teaching	3	5
Area Study Centres	2	4
Brand Building	1	4
Capacity Building	1	4
Education Discipline	1	4
Emergency Response	2	4
Positioning	2	4
Professional Bodies	2	4
Soft power of IaH	3	4
Student Led	3	4
Summer Schools	3	4
UDL	2	4
Academic Managers	1	3
BIPs	2	3
Computer Sciences	1	3
English language Provision	3	3
Hard Disciplines	2	3
Inadequate data	2	3
International Alumni	2	3
Lack of international perspectives	2	3
Lexicon	1	3
National Investment Fund	3	3
Nursing Discipline	2	3
Organisational Skills	1	3
Social Work Discipline	1	3
Benchmarking	1	2

Codes	Files	References
Business Discipline	2	2
Culture Shock	2	2
Disguised IaH	1	2
Dynamic and evolving	1	2
Global Solutions	2	2
Imposter Syndrome	1	2
Irish Language	1	2
Marketing Purpose	2	2
Medicine Discipline	2	2
Other commitments	1	2
Outsourced Training	1	2
Reluctance	1	2
Seek Out	1	2
Sociology	2	2
Standalone Module	1	2
Business Analytics	1	1
Crisis Management	1	1
Department Level	1	1
Experts	1	1
Gastronomy	1	1
Institutional Distinctiveness	1	1
Interest as a barrier	1	1
International Descent	1	1
International League Tables	1	1
National Priorities	1	1
Personal circumstances	1	1
Prior Experience	1	1
Professional Practice Requirements	1	1
Risk Assessment	1	1
Wellbeing	1	1

Appendix H: NVivo- Qualitative Data Analysis Software

Codes\\Phase 3: Generating Initial Themes

Reflexive Thematic Analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2021)- Generating initial themes from the coded and collated data and giving names or labels to the themes and their subthemes.

Linked with Heuristic Approach (Moustakas, 1990)- Illumination- In this stage, the insights begin to surface, and the researcher begins to see the connections and identify the core dimensions of the experiences with IaH.

Themes	Files	References
IaH Enablers	19	3584
IaH Blockers	19	2729
Overcoming Barriers	19	2531
Ideal State for IaH	19	1597
Current Practice	19	1512
Need for IaH	19	1092
Key Stakeholders	19	858
IaH Understandings	19	587
National Policy Making for IaH	19	184
Measuring Success	17	124
Suggestions	9	66

Codes\\Phase 4: Reviewing and Developing Themes

Reflexive Thematic Analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2021)- Defining and reviewing themes: The researcher reviews the initial themes generated and develops themes that capture meaningful patterns with respect to the coded data and the entire dataset, linking the story of each theme with the overall analytic story of the dataset.

Linked with the Heuristic Approach (Moustakas, 1990)- Illumination and early Explication – The process of illumination continues testing tentative meanings and further clarifying them.

Themes	Files	References
Challenges	19	1616
Enablers	19	1588
Overcoming Challenges	19	1321
Rationale	19	1034
Conceptual Constructions	19	560

Codes\\Phase 5: Refining, Defining and Naming Themes

Reflexive Thematic Analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2021)- Refining, Defining and Naming Themes: The researcher writes a short description of each theme and finalises the name of each theme based on its interpretive story.

Linked with Heuristic Approach (Moustakas, 1990)- Explication: The researcher's reflection and depth bring fully developed themes with clear descriptions to life.

Themes	Files	References
1. Conceptual Constructions	19	487
2. Rationale	19	1007
3. Enablers	19	1479
4. Challenges	19	1795
5. Overcoming Challenges	19	1369

Appendix H: NVivo- Qualitative Data Analysis Software

Codes\\Phase 6: Producing the Report

Reflexive Thematic Analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2021)- Final write-up: Weaving data extracts and the researcher's analytic commentary to present the story of each theme. These analytical stories are contextualised in relation to existing knowledge, including a reflexive description of the methodological processes followed.

Linked with Heuristic Approach (Moustakas, 1990)- Creative synthesis: Presenting a rich, coherent account with reflexivity emphasising meaning-making and researcher's voice.

Theme 1: Conceptual Constructions

Sub-Themes	Files	References
Cross-Cultural Engagement	19	145
International Learner Diversity	18	131
Mobility	16	103
Assumptions	13	52
Curriculum	11	31
Terminology	11	25

Theme 2: Rationale

Sub-Themes	Files	References
2.1 Development of Intercultural and Global Citizenship Skills and Competencies	19	570
2.2 EDI Considerations	19	126
2.3 Impact of Learner Diversity	19	123
2.4 Impact on Teaching and Learning	14	72
2.5 Employability prospects for Learners	16	69
2.6 Sustainability Considerations	17	47

Theme 3: Enablers

Sub-Themes	Files	References
3.1 IoC	19	966
3.2 Stakeholder Engagement	19	249
3.3 Collaborations, Alliances and Networks	15	112
3.4 Institutional Commitment	14	99
3.5 Mobility	15	53

Appendix H: NVivo- Qualitative Data Analysis Software

Codes\\Phase 6: Producing the Report

Reflexive Thematic Analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2021)- Final write-up: Weaving data extracts and the researcher's analytic commentary to present the story of each theme. These analytical stories are contextualised in relation to existing knowledge, including a reflexive description of the methodological processes followed.

Linked with Heuristic Approach (Moustakas, 1990)- Creative synthesis: Presenting a rich, coherent account with reflexivity emphasising meaning-making and researcher's voice.

Theme 4: Challenges

Sub-Themes	Files	References
4.1 Learner and Staff Engagement	19	955
4.2 Leadership Commitment and Support	19	516
4.3 Awareness and Visibility	19	161
4.4 National Policymaking	17	88
4.5 Fragmented Implementation	15	75

Theme 5: Overcoming Challenges

Sub-Themes	Files	References
5.1 Institutional	19	1286
5.1.1 Change Management	19	684
5.1.2 Stakeholder engagement	19	432
5.1.3 Curriculum Design	18	170
5.2 National	17	83
5.2.1 Policy Vs Strategy	17	83

Appendix I: Criteria for excellent qualitative research based on Tracy's Eight "big tent" (2010, p. 837)

Criterion	Various means, practices and methods through which achieved
<p>(1) Worthy Topic</p>	<p>The topic of the research is:</p>
	<p>Relevant</p>
	<p>All publicly funded Irish HEIs</p>
	<p>Multilayered impact- learners, academic staff, academic managers, administrative staff, leadership, policymakers and influencers</p>
	<p>Timely response to</p>
	<p>National talent and innovation strategy- Global Citizens 2030 (DFHERIS, 2024)</p>
	<p>Internationalisation trends surveys such as the European Association for International Education (EAIE) Barometer (2024) and the International Association of Universities (IAU) Global Survey (2024)</p>
	<p>Institutional strategic plans of Irish publicly funded HEIs</p>
	<p>Significant/Interesting</p>
	<p>Core concept in the field of international education</p>
<p>Equitable access to internationalisation for the benefit of all students and staff</p>	
<p>Global citizenship skills and intercultural competencies</p>	
<p>(2) Rich Rigor</p>	<p>The study uses a sufficient, abundant, appropriate, and complex:</p>
	<p>Theoretical Constructs</p>
	<p>Firmly grounded in the qualitative paradigm</p>
	<p>Theoretical plurality through theories of organisational design, curriculum design and change management</p>
	<p>Breadth, depth and criticality of approach to literature in the field</p>
	<p>Working definition and evidence-based guiding framework for embedding a culture of IaH in Irish HEIs- IaH CPR (Content, Positioning and Reflection) framework</p>
	<p>Data and Time in the Field</p>
	<p>Two focus groups and seventeen semi-structured interviews</p>
	<p>Immersion in data for about a year (2023-24)</p>
	<p>Samples</p>
<p>Eight HEIs/Organisations- Two Traditional and two Technological Universities and two external stakeholder organisations in Ireland; one best practice HEI each in Europe and the UK</p>	

**Appendix I: Criteria for excellent qualitative research
based on Tracy's Eight "big-tent" (2010, p. 837)**

Criterion	Various means, practices and methods through which achieved
<p align="center">(2) Rich Rigor</p>	Nineteen students in two focus groups and semi-structured interviews with academic staff, academic managers, international officers, senior managers, policymakers, and influencers.
	Voices of Irish and international participants
	Equality, Diversity and Inclusion (EDI) considerations
	Context
	Varied experiences in understanding, implementing and supporting IaH across different types of institutions/organisations
	Data Collection and Analysis Processes
	Thoughtfully planned procedures and protocols approved by the Research Supervisors at SETU, Ireland (Waterford) and the SETU Research Ethics Committee and accepted by RECs of other HEIs
	Pilot focus group and interview for feedback and improvisation
	Informed by frameworks such as platform functional checklist for online data collection (Carter <i>et al.</i> , 2021); topic guides (Kallio <i>et al.</i> , 2016); reflexive thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2021) and heuristic approach (Moustakas, 1990) for data analysis
	Professional training received for using data analysis software NVivo 15
	Confirmation viva voce with an external examiner evaluating the research, including the literature review, research methodology, theoretical framework, and the IaH CPR conceptual framework.
<p align="center">(3) Sincerity</p>	The study is characterised by:
	Self-reflexivity about subjective values, biases, and inclinations of the researcher
	Training and development through modules, discipline-specific and general training to develop reflexivity
	Reflective writing journal
	Transparency about Methods and Challenges
	Clear articulation of protocols and procedures adopted
	Challenges in Ethical approval and data collection outlined in the Methodology chapter
	Acknowledging limitations of the study
	Author order and acknowledgements to participants, funder, supervisors, confirmation VIVA external examiner, supportive and critical colleagues, family and friends

*Appendix I: Criteria for excellent qualitative research
based on Tracy's Eight "big-tent" (2010, p. 837)*

<i>Criterion</i>	<i>Various means, practices and methods through which achieved</i>
<p align="center">(4) Credibility</p>	<p>The research is marked by:</p>
	<p>Thick description, concrete detail, explication of tacit (non-textual) knowledge and showing rather than telling</p>
	<p>Verbatim transcription of data collected reflecting detailed accounts of experiences with IaH</p>
	<p>Participant quotes used to 'paint the picture' and bring findings to life</p>
	<p>Triangulation or crystallisation</p>
	<p>Triangulation utilising data gathered from focus groups and semi-structured interviews</p>
	<p>Theoretical triangulation utilising multiple theories and frameworks</p>
	<p>Multivocality</p>
	<p>Diverse voices- sixteen participants each from traditional and technological universities, two each from external stakeholder organisations in Ireland and best practice institutions in Europe and the UK</p>
	<p>Supplemented with IaH experiences and practices in Irish HEIs with best practice institutions in Europe and the UK</p>
<p align="center">(5) Resonance</p>	<p>The research influences, impacts, or moves particular readers or a variety of audiences through:</p>
	<p>Aesthetic, evocative representation</p>
	<p>Painting a picture through storytelling and rich narratives by mindfully selecting impactful quotes by the participants</p>
	<p>Adding 'color' as a creative expression in tables and figures to break the monotony and 'not be boring'</p>
	<p>Naturalistic generalisations</p>
	<p>Offering insights in the findings and discussions chapter that are relatable by individuals in their respective institutional contexts</p>
	<p>Transferable findings</p>
	<p>Identifying strategies and recommendations for embedding a culture of IaH that can be transferable to other institutional settings beyond Ireland</p>

*Appendix I: Criteria for excellent qualitative research
based on Tracy's Eight "big-tent" (2010, p. 837)*

Criterion	Various means, practices and methods through which achieved
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<p align="center">(6) Significant Contribution</p>	The research provides a significant contribution:
	Conceptually/theoretically
	First of its kind study on embedding a culture of IaH in Irish HEIs at the national level, funded by the Government of Ireland
	Extends existing theories on organisation and curriculum design and change management suited to the Irish context
	Practically
	Offers actionable recommendations at the institutional and national levels
	Provides an evidence-based guiding framework- IaH CPR (Content, Positioning and Reflection) to embed a culture of IaH in Irish HEIs
	Proposes a working definition for 'embedding a culture of IaH' suited to the Irish higher education setting and transferable to other national and institutional contexts
	Morally
	Advocates for equity and inclusion in internationalisation experiences for the benefit of all learners and staff
	Methodologically
	Demonstrates innovative ways to utilise qualitative methods and theoretical constructs to explore varied experiences with IaH
	Heuristically
Stimulates an intense desire within the researcher to engage in future research	
Influences diverse stakeholders to engage in discourses to embed IaH systemically	

<p align="center">(7) Ethics</p>	The research considers:
	Procedural ethics (such as human subjects)
	Informed consent, confidentiality and data protection for all participants, in alignment with the protocols approved by SETU's Research Ethics Committee (REC) and accepted by RECs of other institutions where the participants
	Training and development- accredited module, epigeum and external certifications on research integrity and ethics
	Situational and culturally specific ethics
	Self-reflexivity
	Equality, diversity and inclusion
	Anonymity of participants and institutions through pseudonymisation to safeguard their identity

Appendix I: Criteria for excellent qualitative research based on Tracy's Eight "big-tent" (2010, p. 837)

Criterion	Various means, practices and methods through which achieved
<p>(7) Ethics</p>	<p>Relational ethics</p>
	<p>Respect and empathy informed by 'connectivity, humanness and empathy' principles (Brown and Danaher, 2019)</p>
	<p>Optional pre-research briefings for gatekeepers and participants</p>
	<p>Informed consent</p>
	<p>Building trust and rapport with the participants</p>
	<p>Reflecting and summarising participant perspectives to check for accuracy</p>
	<p>Exiting ethics (leaving the scene and sharing the research)</p>
	<p>Research findings will be shared with all participants</p>
	<p>Dissemination and publications</p>
	<p>(8) Meaningful Coherence</p>
<p>Achieves what it purports to be about</p>	
<p>Achieves purpose, research aims, and objectives and addresses the central research questions</p>	
<p>Uses methods and procedures that fit its stated goals</p>	
<p>Employs constructivist-interpretivist methodology and qualitative methods that align with the aim of the study</p>	
<p>Meaningfully interconnects literature, research questions/foci, findings, and interpretations with each other</p>	
<p>Synthesises literature, theoretical and conceptual constructs, researcher's reflections, methodology and methods with research questions to establish findings and interpretation that presents an interwoven and cohesive narrative about IaH</p>	

Appendix J: Confirmation VIVA presentation

EMBEDDING A CULTURE OF
'INTERNATIONALISATION AT HOME (IaH)'
PREPARING FOR THE CHANGING CONTEXT OF HIGHER
EDUCATION IN IRELAND

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PROJECT FUNDED BY Taighde Éireann
Research Ireland

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Overview

WHAT IS INTERNATIONALISATION at HOME (IaH)?

'The purposeful integration of international and intercultural dimensions into the formal and informal curriculum for all students within domestic learning environments'

(Beelen and Jones, 2015, p.69)

Appendix J: Confirmation VIVA presentation

My Research

EMBEDDING A CULTURE OF INTERNATIONALISATION AT HOME (IaH)

PREPARING FOR THE CHANGING CONTEXT OF HIGHER EDUCATION IN IRELAND

PRIMARY PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

Critique how IaH is interpreted in the Irish context considering its development globally.

Draw on findings related to the challenges and opportunities in implementing IaH at Irish HEIs, as presented by participants in this study.

Develop a guiding framework that can assist in embedding a culture of IaH within Irish HEIs.

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Progress To Date

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Relevance of the Study

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Appendix J: Confirmation VIVA presentation

Literature Review

Literature Review

Existing Frameworks in laH globally

Developing Innovative Approaches and Tools for laH-ATIAH by Newcastle University (UK), the University of Bologna (Italy) and KU Leuven (Belgium)

The Hague Internationalisation at Home-THIAH by the Hague University of Applied Sciences (Netherlands)

THE GAP

Sparse literature on laH in the Irish context

Lack of a guiding framework to support embedding laH within Irish HEIs

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Research Methodology

This study has been conducted in the interpretive paradigm based on the transferability and generalisation of new knowledge created

Reflexive Thematic Analysis (RTA) by Braun and Clarke (2021) and Moustakas' heuristic approach (1990)

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Appendix J: Confirmation VIVA presentation

Participants in the Study

IaH Theoretical Framework

Conceptual Framework in Development

IaH CPR- A dynamic framework for embedding a culture of 'Internationalisation at Home (IaH)' in Irish higher education institutions

Appendix J: Confirmation VIVA presentation

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THANK YOU FOR YOUR ATTENTION

Should you have any ideas or feedback, please feel free to get in touch with me at nidhipiplani.kapur@postgrad.wit.ie

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